

**Student Employment in the Higher Education Sector:
An investigation of the nature, extent and psychological
impact of combining work and study**

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Declaration

I declare that, except where explicit reference is made to the contribution of others, that this thesis is the result of my own work and has not been submitted for any other degree at the University of the West of Scotland or any other institution.

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Wish you a good life in heaven.

ABSTRACT

Since the 1990s researchers in the UK have focused attention on students in Higher Education (HE) who combine part-time employment with their full-time academic study. Previous research has suggested that work had an impact on HE students' academic achievement, physical fatigue, and psychological distress and anxiety. This thesis aims to establish contemporary information on the nature and extent of part-time employment. By focusing on one HE institution (HEI) in Scotland the thesis is able to consider potential changes in part-time employment over time. An additional aim is to investigate impact of employment on a number of psychological factors including stress, coping and self-efficacy. A mixed methods design was implemented, consisting of a systematic review (Study 1), two quantitative studies (Studies 2 and 3 as the short-term longitudinal design) and a subsequent qualitative study (Study 4).

In Study 1, a systematic review, 36 articles were identified for review. Scrutiny of these articles showed that few studies paid specific attention to the psychological impact of working whilst studying at university. Those studies which had paid attention tended to treat psychological consequences as a secondary or supplementary factor in their investigation of either the nature or extent of employment or the association between work and academic achievement. The review identified key psychological variables that should be considered in the context of student employment, namely, stress, coping strategies and self-efficacy.

Two quantitative surveys formed a short-term longitudinal design to explore the nature and extent of student employment and the potential association between employment status and key psychological outcomes. An online quantitative survey of 827 HE students was conducted in 2019 (Study 2), and in 2021 (Study 3) a second online survey was completed with 456 HE students.

Study 2 showed that working while studying in HE is the norm for students in 2019. Approximately, 70% of current students were currently working or had worked. A comparison between a 1998 data set and the 2019 study provided evidence of an increasing trend in paid term-time employment and increased weekly working hours. The dominant job types were also found to have changed over the two decades between the studies. Study 2 also found that employment status was associated with coping strategy, including problem solving, social contact and cognitive restructuring strategy. Type of job was associated with interpersonal relationship stress, total stress and self-efficacy. Furthermore, Study 2 found

that for current workers weekly work hours was positively correlated with total stress, physical stress, academic stress, express emotions, social contact, emotion focused engagement and overall engagement coping. Specifically, higher total stress was predicted by higher working hours along with lower levels of self-efficacy and more wishful thinking, social withdrawal and problem solving, but less problem avoidance.

Study 3 explored the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on student employment during the period of January 2020 through to April 2021. The results showed that the proportion of students involved in employment dropped from 67% to just over half with approximately 10% of students stopping work during the pandemic. The findings from Study 3 also showed that during the pandemic students weekly working hours increased and employment levels in the various job sectors changed with social care jobs increasing. Employment patterns (consistent workers, interrupted workers, who lost jobs, job finders, and no work groups) during this time were found to be related to coping strategies but not to stress or self-efficacy. Consistent workers used significantly more emotion expression and social contact coping than those students who did not work. Those students who lost their jobs used significantly more social contact coping than students who did not work. Additionally, consistent worker utilised significantly more emotion focused engagement than non-workers.

Study 4 adopted a qualitative approach consisting of an online semi-structured interview. Twelve participants were sampled from consistent workers, intermittent workers and the no workers group. Template Analysis explored the relationship between changes in employment, psychological impact and coping processes. Students indicated that they had experienced disruptions and modification to their employment due to COVID-19 pandemic restrictions. Such changes impacted students stress, well-being and sense of control. In reacting to these negative outcomes, students adopted both preventative and reactive coping. By using preventative coping students sought to avoid future stress by having well-being awareness and setting their priorities. In using reactive coping students took active actions and behaviours which included problem-solving and time management to deal with stress from employment changes and managing time between work and study. They also managed personal impact via rationalising and releasing emotions in supportive social circles. Sense of control underpinned such coping processes and this was identified as an area for future study. Overall, from their stories, employment was considered to be a way of coping within HE both financially and psychologically.

Based on the above four studies, it is clear student employment is a highly dynamic phenomenon. Part-time employment can be considered to be part of the normative experience of students within HE and employment is associated with a number of psychological outcomes such as stress. However, the findings also suggest that part-time employment is a way for undergraduates to cope with their financial and psychological needs whilst in HE. This thesis contributes to the existing empirical, theoretical and methodological knowledge. Based on the overall findings, practical implications are suggested for the specific HEI and other stakeholders.

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List of Abbreviations

Administration (Admin)

Analysis of variance (ANOVA)

British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC)

British Psychological Society (BPS)

Coping Strategies Inventory short form 32 (CSI-32)

Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19 or COVID)

Critical realism (CR)

Crowe critical appraisal tool (CCAT)

Dependent variable (DV)

Dialectical pluralism (DP)

Duplicate (DUP)

Effect Size (η^2)

European Union (EU)

Exclusion (EX)

For the specific purpose (Ad hoc)

General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

General practice (GP)

Grade point average (GPA)

Higher Education (HE)

Higher Education Institution (HEI)

Inclusion (IN)

Independent variable (IV)

Information Technology and Digital Services (ITDS)

Least significant difference (LSD)

Mean (M)

National Health Service (NHS)

National minimum wage (NMW)

National living wage (NLW)

Pay-As-You-Earn (PAYE)

Population, intervention, comparison, outcomes and context (PICOC)

Positive Affectivity (PA)

Reflexive Thematic Analysis (RTA)

Scottish Credit and Qualifications Framework (SCQF)
Standard Deviation (SD)
Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS)
Student Self-efficacy Scale (SSE)
Student Stress Inventory (SSI)
Study-work-life (SWL)
Thematic Analysis (TA)
Theory of planned behaviour (TPB)
Total number of observations or population size (N)
Tukey Honestly Significant Difference (Tukey HSD)
United Kingdom (UK)
United States (US)
University (Uni)
University of the West of Scotland (UWS)
Work-life (WL)
Work school conflict (WSC)
Work school enrichment (WSE)
Work-school facilitation (WSF)
Work-study (WS)

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CHAPTER 1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter focuses on introducing the phenomenon of students' participation in paid part-time employment in the Higher Education (HE) sector. It provides an overview of student employment in the United Kingdom (UK) and addresses three main aspects within the previous published literature regarding the nature and extent of employment, the motivation or reasons for working and the impact of student employment on academic achievement as well as psychological consequences. The latter has been neglected by researchers. Furthermore, this chapter provides an overview of the primary theories that have emerged from the psychology and education literature regarding *HE student part-time employment* (its short version *student employment* is used in the thesis). The chapter concludes by outlining the rationale for the present project and its key aims.

1.1 Background

Before considering the existing literature in detail, it is advisable to consider a wider perspective by placing student employment within a longer-term view. In the UK, student participation in paid, part-time employment is considered natural due to certain historical policies. During the 1980s the labour market highlighted the need for higher-wage jobs (Lewis, 2002) and the Robinson report (1997) reported that workers with Level 4 vocational qualifications earned less than those with a university degree. Consequently, this raised demands for higher qualifications and resulted in an increased demand for entrance into HE, especially in the early 1990s (Lewis, 2002; Robinson, 1997). To meet the need for a more qualified labour force, the UK government “proposed to expand student numbers so that 50 per cent of the relevant age cohort were in higher education” (Keating, 2005, p.430). This was referred to as “widening participants in HE” (Lewis, 2002, p.204). Widening participation created an opportunity for under-represented groups to take advantage of a university education and gain a valuable qualification. This included students from a wider socio-economic range than had previously featured in HE. In particular, widening participation witnessed increasing numbers of students from lower socioeconomic groups enrolling in undergraduate courses.

Widening participation however, created concerns over how a wider diversity of students could pay tuition fees. The UK government provided a solution by creating the framework

for Student Loans in the Education Acts of 1990, 1996, 1998 (Education in England, 2020a, 2020b, 2020c). These however, shifted “financing of higher education from the state to higher education beneficiaries”, namely, the undergraduates themselves (Pennell & West, 2005, p.133). The consequence of these changes was to raise student awareness of the costs associated with HE. Students reacted primarily in two ways to address financial problems associated with participation in HE (Pennell & West, 2005). One was to take on debt; the other was to participate in paid employment during vacation periods and term-time. Pennell and West (2005) noted that compelling students to work during term-time risks academic attainment.

It is also worth noting that in Scotland the economic and cultural environment is slightly different from the other countries that comprise the UK due to its status since the Treaty of Union (Smout, 1964; Spence, 2010) and the impact of devolution¹ in separating responsibility for HE from the rest of the UK (Mitchell et al., 1998; Riddell et al., 2013; Scottish parliament, 2020). Specifically, all areas regarding education and training were devolved in 1998 under the Scotland Act 1998, making Scotland unique in having devolved rights over HE and economic development (Scottish parliament, 2016, 2020).

As widening participation resulted in increasing numbers of students from lower socioeconomic groups entering HE, a particular problem regarding tuition fees and student financing emerged (Van Dyke et al., 2005). Empirical studies demonstrated the primary drive of student part-time employment while in full-time HE was due to financial necessity (Van Dyke et al., 2005) driven by a variety of factors including the need to purchase textbooks, food and to meet the cost of commuting to and from university campuses due to the lack of financial support from other sources (Watts, 2001). For some, the pressure to sustain themselves in HE meant more students combined work and study during term-time, moving away from the traditional model where students had typically only sought employment during vacation periods (Barr & Crawford, 2004; Bowl, 2001; Leathwood & O'Connell, 2003; McKechnie et al., 1998; McKechnie et al., 2005; Pennell & West, 2005). The reasons for working during term-time were to minimise the accumulation of student loan debt and taking

¹ Devolution, “as a management system of government”, “allows decisions to be made at a more local level” (Scottish parliament, 2020). The devolved matters included health, education, training, local government, many aspects of transport, social work, housing, economic development, the legal system, law and order, the environment, agriculture, fisheries and forestry, sport, and the arts (Mitchell et al., 1998, p.171). Opposite to the fact of devolved right of education and training belong to Scotland, Westminster reserves the power of the constitution of the United Kingdom including fiscal, economic and monetary system, common markets for goods and services, employment law and others (Scottish parliament, 2016; Scottish parliament, 2020).

part in “term-time work as a strategy” (Brennan et al., 2005, p.124) because “students used term-time work to reduce the amount of money they borrowed from the Student Loan Company, or to avoid taking out a student loan” (p.124).

Student employment is not a new topic. As early as the 1920s in the United States (US), the *Journal of Education* reported large numbers of students joining the labour force during their college education (After-School Work Held Bad Practice, 1929; College Students at Work, 1929; Multitude of Wage-Earning Students, 1927; New York University Students Earn Millions, 1927; Third of Students Work Way in College, 1929; To Use Budget Before Starting Part-Time Work, 1927). This burgeoning phenomenon in the US was linked to concerns around academic ability (Student With "Strong Back And Weak Mind" Seeks Jobs, 1932) and academic concerns due to study and work conflict (How part-time work affects academic performance, 1969; Sample Jobs: Part Time Work Acquaints Pupils, 1935).

Other studies nevertheless, found that work could benefit academic achievement. For example, Newman and Mooney (1940) defined student employment as a self-support activity – students supporting themselves to manage budgets through college (Colorado College & Albright, 1916, as cited in Newman & Mooney, 1940). Based on a review of the studies conducted in US in the 1920s and 1930s, one article by Millis (1925, as cited in Newman & Mooney, 1940) reported that higher academic achievement for those students working moderate hours compared to non-workers or those working an excessive number of hours. In contrast, another study indicated the time spent in part-time employment acted as a non-reliable predictor for scholarship (Kurtz, 1930, as cited in Newman & Mooney, 1940). These contradictory findings continued to emerge across a wide range of studies in the US as similar reports continue to appear in the UK.

In the UK, research focusing on the combining of full-time education with part-time employment included studies that reported students in a range of education settings ranging from secondary schools through to students in HE. Many UK studies focused on children or younger students and their involvement in the workforce (Banks & Roker, 1993; Hobbs et al., 1996; McKechnie et al., 1993; Mizen, 1992; Rikowski & Neary, 1997). School children can be viewed as vulnerable workers and, as such, they are protected by legislation. Research however, suggested this was not effective and that young workers were at risk as they lacked employment protection (Hobbs et al., 2009; McKechnie et al., 2009; McKechnie et al., 2013). Some studies nevertheless, identified social and psychological benefits especially related to children’s development that were linked to employment (Howieson et al., 2012; Simpson,

2014). The literature also contained a number of primary theories of student employment (Simpson, 2014) that were largely framed based on research using young participants (See Section 1.3).

Children and school students, however, are only part of the student employment picture. There are additionally studies focusing on older student groups, aged 16-19 years (Canny, 2002; Hodgson & Spours, 2001). These students typically are in the transition from school to work or to HE.

In considering participants of student employment, this thesis specifically focuses on students in HE. In the HE sector, many students combine work with full-time study. In previous decades students worked mostly during vacations (Bailey & Mallier, 1999; McKechnie et al., 1998) but this has gradually changed as outlined above so that it is now common, for students to work in both term-time and/or vacation time (Barke et al., 2000; Liddell & Rae, 2002; McKechnie et al., 1998). HE students from traditional and non-traditional backgrounds were found to be engaged in employment (Barke et al., 2000; Bowl, 2001; Jackson & Jamieson, 2009). In some cases, students worked full-time but the majority were full-time students with part-time jobs (Davies, 2008). The change in full-time students' behaviour with respect to paid employment has resulted in relevant studies exploring the nature and extent of this phenomenon and the potential impact of this behaviour.

1.2 Student Part-time Employment in HE

1.2.1 The Nature and Extent in Decades

Since the middle of the 20th Century, researchers have described university students combining part-time employment with full-time education in the UK (Broadbridge & Swanson, 2005; Hall, 2010) especially after the Robbins Report resulted in increasing numbers of students entering HE (Education in England, 2020d; Morris, 1964). Combining these activities has several social, economic and psychological implications (Hobbs & McKechnie, 1997; Van Dyke et al., 2005). In this thesis it is argued that the existing literature regarding this phenomenon in the UK can be categorised into three, chronological phases: pre-1990, 1990-2010 and post-2010.

In 20th Century prior to 1990 there was little research conducted because HE was accessible only to 'traditional students'² who seldom sought part-time employment during their time in

² Traditional student is a phase opposite to non-traditional student. "Non-traditional students are defined as first generation university attendees from working class or minority backgrounds" whereas traditional students are

HE. In the late 1990s changes in funding for HE (Barr & Crawford, 2004) and the expansion of HE created a new HE landscape. One policy change was that student loans replaced grants in 1990-1991 in the UK (Bailey, 2003). The other historical change was that new universities in Scotland emerged in the wake of Widening Participation (Universities Scotland, 2020). Consequently, the funding changes after 1990 resulted in students in HE being financially compromised, forcing students into paid employment.

Between 1990 and 2010, studies focused primarily on the nature and extent of part-time employment and its impact on students' academic attainment (McKechnie et al., 1998). This was a peak period for student employment research when a considerable amount of relevant literature was published.

From 1990 to 2000, researchers endeavoured to profile the nature and extent of student employment. Since Ford et al.'s 1995 study of student employment, the portion of working students has been constantly updated through individual studies carried out in various Higher Education Institutions (HEI). However, most such studies were not comparative despite being conducted in England, Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland. Existing studies were largely survey based, describing the nature and extent of student employment and utilised a quantitative approach. A few studies combined a survey approach with qualitative methods such as interviews (e.g. Ford et al., 1995 and Lucas & Lammont, 1998) or used a purely qualitative methodology (e.g. Lucas & Ralston, 1996).

The years from 1990 to 2000 also witnessed a new trend in student employment with students shifting from vacation time jobs to term-time employment. This was most notable in the final few years of this period (Broadbridge & Swanson, 2006). For example, a study in 1995 (Ford et al.) found more than half (57%) of students in one HEI in Scotland had only experienced vacation work. In contrast, just less than one third (29%) worked or currently worked during term-time. The study noted that only 14% of students did not work. Vacation work dominated the area of student employment, although this pattern changed at the onset of the 21 century with term-time employment emerging as the dominant experience.

Researchers claimed "term-time working has been identified as a growing phenomenon, which has replaced the more traditional pattern of vacation only work" (Brennan et al., 2005, p.51). By 2000, nearly half (47%) of undergraduate students worked in term-time (Callender & Kemp, 2000; Metcalf, 2001, as cited in Brennan et al., 2005). However, the situation

those from the middle-class background and follow the expected "pathways through HE that are bolstered by familial legacies" directly after high school (Holton, 2018, p.5).

appears more complex as ‘vacation employment’ featured mostly in students who combined term-time employment and vacation employment.

During this period, few studies noted the impact of student employment on their academic attainment in HE in the UK. The earliest published article was a study reporting both A-level results of students from schools and colleges in the North-east of England (Tymms & Fitz-Gibbon, 1992) which showed that nearly “half of all A-level students reported being engaged in part-time work and they tended to get slightly lower A-level grades” than those who did not have part-time work (p.193).

Since 2000, studies have focused on term-time employment. On rare occasions, articles reported term-time employment, distinguishing it from vacation employment. As Brennan et al. (2005) found, during 2000-2001, 44% of students worked during term-time and vacation periods, compared with vacation only workers (26%) and term-time only workers (4%). During 2001-2002, the figures for term-time and vacation work was reported as 38%, compared with vacation-only workers being 15% and term-time only workers being 4%. These researchers (Brennan et al., 2005) however did not explore reasons why the portion of term-time only workers remained unchanged, while the other two categories declined over the two terms. This article showed that the dominant employment pattern was a combination of term-time and vacation working although the phrase “term-time employment” dominated published research papers in future decades.

Studies into the nature and extent of employment continued to be reported over the next 10 years and nearly all considered only term-time employment. Attention focused on increased term-time employment amongst full-time students in the HE sector (Barr & Crawford, 2004; Bowl, 2001; Leathwood & O’Connell, 2003). For example, studies conducted in one Scottish university found about half of students were currently employed or had worked during term-time (Carney et al., 2005; Curtis & Williams, 2002; Woodward, 2003). The extent of student employment in the UK was lower than that reported in the US where 80% of full-time undergraduates work and, of those, 30% work more than 20 hours per week (Baffoe-Bonnie & Golden, 2007).

While these studies focused on term-time employment, in the decade they did consider the impact of work on students’ academic attainment (Broadbridge & Swanson, 2005; Hall, 2010). More importantly, the studies in that decade extended the idea of the impact of working from academic progression and attainment alone to other aspects of students’ lives

including their well-being and behaviour. A new trend emerged around the end of that decade; small-scale research studies began to link student employment with other psychological factors. A series of studies were conducted by researchers in Scotland based in Scottish HEIs (Barron & Anastasiadou, 2009; Broadbridge et al., 2007; Carney et al., 2005; McKechnie et al., 2005; Swanson et al., 2006). In these, students' well-being was explored in relation to paid employment (Broadbridge & Swanson, 2006; Carney et al., 2005). For example, psychological well-being has been reported in two studies (Broadbridge & Swanson, 2006; Carney et al., 2005). Broadbridge and Swanson (2006) investigated the relationship between work, social integration, and academic performance. Stress was one of the indicators associated with working students' adjustment to their academic environment (Swanson et al., 2006). This group of researchers also proposed the potential mediating role of psychological traits (such as "positive affectivity" and "stress") between "role congruence and adjustment" (Swanson et al., 2006, p.895). Moreover, Lowe and Gayle (2007) investigated students' support systems (e.g. family) and undergraduates' coping strategy alongside the nature and extent of part-time employment. These studies unfortunately were based on only one or two institutions (Broadbridge et al., 2007), limiting the generalisability of their findings. Additionally, almost all the above-mentioned studies, being quantitative investigations, utilised questionnaire surveys. An in-depth, exploration of students' lived experiences has yet to be published.

From 2010 to 2017, researchers still endeavoured to investigate the nature and extent of term-time employment and the impact of working on students' academic achievement. Researchers in Wales, reporting undergraduates' experiences, argued – "It seems reasonable to say that term-time employment is becoming a social norm for many students in the contemporary landscape of HE" (Mercer et al., 2016, p.182). However, the initial interest in considering psychological issues appears to have slowed down recently. Between 2010 and 2017, only one article that focused on psychological aspects of employment had been published in Scotland (see systematic review of this thesis, Chapter 3). While this may reflect the search strategy being limited to the year 2017 and the databases accessed nonetheless, it illustrates a potential gap in research of student employment in Scottish HE.

The study conducted in Scotland by McGregor (2015) reported the effect of work on several psychological variables including confidence, mental health and social activities. The primary aim of McGregor's (2015) study was to investigate the adverse impact of students' employment on their academic study with a secondary aim to explore students' self-

confidence, mental health and social activities. The study used a short questionnaire of 24 items to investigate academic achievement and two related, academic-relevant variables. One item measured confidence and two measured mental health and social activities. As such, the study relied upon a limited number of *ad hoc* items resulting in low validity for the quantification of psychological factors. Thus, it could be argued that the study failed to operationalise the key psychological variables in sufficient depth for its declared aim. Nevertheless, McGregor (2015) suggested that some psychological variables may function as mediators helping undergraduates cope with the dilemma of concurrent working and studying.

In summary, this review of several decades of research with respect to student employment, indicates that there is a risk of failing to fully understand student employment levels in Scotland. This review also shows that few studies have focus on the psychological consequences of student employment. Such a gap in knowledge offers researchers an opportunity to make a significant contribution to the literature.

1.2.2 Motivation to Work

One focus of the previous literature investigated why students want to work during their undergraduate degree as it was suggested that this would help explain the extent of student employment (Brennan et al., 2005). For many students, one obvious reason is linked to an extrinsic drive (e.g. money) as a financial reward. Money is what students seek from their part-time job to pay for tuition fees and support other expenses (Brownlow et al., 2004; Crockford et al., 2015; Smith & Wilson, 2002).

Previous studies also indicate that financial motivation is not the sole drive for full-time student's preference for part-time work. Students also work to enhance their career development. For example, Barron and Anastasiadou (2009) explored the work motivations of 150 full-time hospitality and tourism students at a university in Scotland. They found that nearly 40% of students worked for career development and 60% for financial gain.

Developmental reasons for working included gaining experience, developing personal and practical skills, and establishing career contacts (Barron & Anastasiadou, 2009). McGregor (2015) further argued that while students stated that money was a primary reason for working, they indicated other benefits such as work providing a break from their studies. Additional benefits included offering independence, motivation time management, social aspects and making contacts. McGregor's (2015) study further suggested that the benefits of

student employment could also be related to psychological factors such as socialisation, management, autonomy and motivation.

Identifying the reasons for students working was mainly explored through close-ended questions; respondents were provided with a list of choices from which they chose the most appropriate response (Dundes & Marx, 2006; Maguire, 2013; Moore & Rago, 2009; Robotham, 2012). For example, students were provided with a choice of options such as “personal money”, “financial need”, “financial independence”, “save for items”, “enjoy work”, “work experience”, “socialising”, “fund education”, and “independence” (Lucas & Lammont, 1998, p.50). In some cases, reasons for working were assessed by Likert scale responses (Carney et al., 2005; Davies & Marx, 1999; Moore & Rago, 2009). For example, Moore and Rago (2009, p.92) used a six-point Likert scale to measure reasons for work including “to pay for tuition”, “to pay for living expenses”, “to pay for transportation expenses”, “to gain experience” to name but a few. These items were designed largely as part of *ad hoc* surveys. In some studies, there were also attempts to explore reasons for not working (Lucas & Lammont, 1998; Purcell & Elias, 2010).

These studies therefore used close-ended questions, such as multiple-choice questions or Likert scale response questions that were pre-designed. This may have produced a methodological bias where the options provided reflected the researchers’ expectations rather than students’ experiences. Thus, it is suggested that at least one open-ended choice or one flexible choice such as “other reason(s) for work” should be added to avoid forced or limited answers.

Compared with survey based quantitative studies where responses may be limited by the survey design, qualitative approaches offer more flexibility. Open-ended questions have been adopted in qualitative studies (Wimshurst, 1987), interviews (Winkler, 2009), focus groups (Broadbridge & Swanson, 2006; Ang, 2008) and mixed methods studies. The type of questions used include: “Describe your motivations... of your work experiences” (Cheng & Alcántara, 2007, p.304); “What are your (main) reasons for working?” in interviews (Ang, 2008, p.104) and “Think back to when you first started working and studying. What were the main reasons for this?” (Ang, 2008, p.102); “What motivates you to work part-time while studying for a degree?” (Evans et al., 2014, p.89) in focus groups. Such open-ended questions are useful in terms of more fully exploring students’ lived experiences.

Compared with most published studies that report the nature and extent of students' employment, students' reasons for working may be better served by a different approach. Likert scale plus open-ended questions or other qualitative approaches for example, could be an alternative way to explore complex or changeable variables that have both quantitative and narrative characteristics. In these circumstances, quantitative scales can provide measurable and comparable data and so justify generalisation to other populations. Open-ended questions or other qualitative approaches can provide narrated accounts from individual views.

1.2.3 Impact of Student Employment

Another feature of the published empirical studies is that they have tended to focus and report on the impact of part-time employment on students' academic progression. Several studies have investigated both positive and negative impacts of term-time employment, drawing on samples from university and secondary school students (McKechnie et al., 2014; Robotham, 2013; Watts, 2001; Watts & Pickering, 2000). A primary concern of this body of work has been to consider the potential impact of employment on a number of factors.

1.2.3.1 Academic Achievement

A number of previous studies have addressed the adverse impact of student employment on academic achievement (Brennan et al., 2005; Liddell & Rae, 2002; Paul, 1982; Richards, 2003) and engagement, including decreased time for study (Curtis & Shani, 2002), fatigue (Curtis, 2003; Curtis & Shani, 2002), increased absences from formal teaching (Lucas & Ralston, 1997), and dropout rates (Bennett, 2003; King, 2002). In contrast, other studies suggest that in some cases working was associated with either positive or no effect on factors such as academic engagement (Tymms & Fitz-Gibbon, 1992), better academic outcomes (Hammes & Haller, 1983; Schill et al., 1985) or comparable outcomes to non-working students (Fjortoft, 1994). Tymms and Fitz-Gibbon (1992) for instance, found no direct link between work hours and studying hours.

Within this body of work it was argued that what mattered was not 'work status' (i.e. whether someone worked or not) but *how many* hours students worked (Curtis, 2003; Hay, 1969; Ma & Wooster, 1979; Liddell & Rae, 2002). Some studies suggested that a negative impact of employment emerged when students worked more than 15 hours per week. However, less than 15 hours work did not appear to make an appreciable difference to students' academic performance (Hay, 1969; Ma & Wooster, 1979). Hay (1969) for example, claimed there was no difference in academic performance between students who did not work and those who worked less than 15 hours and Ma and Wooster (1979) found that working less than 15 hours

per week did not affect students' academic achievement. Students working in white collar jobs scored better grades than blue collar workers (Ma & Wooster, 1979). This result partially aligned with Barke et al.'s (2000) results which found that more than half of participants perceived no adverse impact from term-time employment on their academic achievement, while less than half indicated "a deleterious effect" (p.3). This study however, reported percentage values without the benefit of a more sophisticated statistical analyses. This weakens the conclusion of the study. Research by Barke et al. (2000) also reported non-significant difference in terms of academic achievement and weekly working hours of 12 hours. However, a degree of caution is required as the statistics used median values rather than mean. Technically this was determined by the statistical requirement for abnormal distribution of grade point average (GPA) scores: the researcher had to use non-parametric statistics, but the median still may not be a best statistic indicator as it varies with number of participants.

A few studies have found an inverse relationship between working and students' academic scores. For instance, when answering the question, "Are your academic studies affected by working?", the response fell into three groups: one third chose employment "helps academic work", one third indicated a "bad effect" and one third claimed "no effect" (Curtis & Shani, 2002, p.135). A more recent study conducted in Scotland (McGregor, 2015) found that 53% of students self-reported their marks had not been affected by working during term-time with 5% reporting that they felt their marks had improved.

The impact of employment on academic achievement is not consistent as indicated above. The debate in this respect continues. Furthermore, these studies have identified other consequences of working on academic attainment and it is therefore possible that these findings may be explained by the interaction of different outcomes rather than focusing on a single factor such as hours worked.

1.2.3.2 Psychological Impact

While much research has focused on the impact of work on student academic achievement, some studies have examined the psychological consequences of student employment. While there are relatively few such studies, the psychological outcomes they have reported are varied. Part-time employment has been linked to the development of skills, confidence, and career prospects (Curtis & Shani, 2002). For example, when investigating the impact of part-time employment on academic performance, Curtis and Shani (2002) noted that 20-33% of

subjects reported benefits as a result of employment. These benefits include social skills, relieving stress regarding personal finances, improved self-confidence and time management (Curtis & Shani, 2002; Curtis & William, 2002).

On the other hand, some studies have identified negative psychological outcomes associated with working. These include an adverse impact on well-being and substance abuse behaviour (Curtis, 2003). Stress is a primary negative outcome of combining work and HE study. Based on several empirical studies in UK, Swanson et al. (2006) described a working student's life as follow:

“Student life has been described as increasingly characterized by reduced well-being, stress, a spiral of debt and failures in academic achievement.” (p.896)

Previously, Lee et al. (1999) found that the impact of part-time employment was partly positive and partly negative with reference to students' personal and social lives. They sampled 120 students majoring in Nursing in England in 1997. They defined “paid part-time work” as “any extracurricular activity, identified by students, which resulted in payment” themselves (Lee et al., 1999, p.443). This study investigated the nature and extent of student employment including hours worked, categories of jobs, reason for students working and its impact on students' academic performance. Nearly all students (96%) indicated a half-positive, half-negative outcome. Positive effects included financial benefits, increased social life and development of “confidence, social and communication skills and time management” (Lee et al., 1999, p.448). The negative effects included time deprivation and “physical and mental stress” (Lee et al., 1999, p.448). Stress was experienced as “tiredness, irritability, being stressed”, and “feeling fed up” (Lee et al., 1999, p.448). In this study, stress was clearly one of the negative effects of combining work and study.

A few studies have assessed the relationship between students' employment and stress (Butler et al 2010; Jogaratnam & Buchanan, 2004; Vaughn et al., 2016). Based on a sample in one HEI in England, one study found one in four working students felt stressed and more than half mentioned that physical tiredness undermined their studying (Curtis & Shani, 2002). A more recent study conducted in Scotland also identified 17% of participants being stressed as a consequence of working (McGregor, 2015).

Other researchers have found that part-time employment is associated with several potentially negative behaviours such as binge drinking (Bono et al., 2017; Butler et al., 2010), smoking

(Bono et al., 2017) and drug abuse (Miller et al., 2008). Some studies suggest that part-time employment during HE may expand social relationships or increase social activities beyond university (Gbadamosi et al., 2016; Lee et al., 1999). Expanded social circles and increased social activities may contribute to increasing drinking or smoking. Social drinking or smoking may not only be a consequence of employment but may be a form of coping strategy. It could be argued that changes in behaviour and social life represent adjustment to stress. Humphrey and McCarthy's (1998) study endorsed this notion finding that stress levels were reduced by good management of workload and units of alcohol consumed in a multi-variate model. Broadbridge and Swanson (2005) also linked stress with role management. Moreover, specific management of time along with general management were highlighted in studies focusing on working student's stress. Some researchers found that undergraduates adopted time management strategies to cope with time conflict between work and study. For example, students utilised time organisation or reorganising activity times to manage time (Cheng & Alcántara, 2007; Greene & Maggs, 2015).

One core element that should not be neglected is the concept of self. According to Bandura, "general beliefs of efficacy" of oneself is related to stress coping "as a personal resource or vulnerability factor" (1995, p.178). In the HE sector, a number of studies have demonstrated a strong relationship between stress, coping and self-efficacy (Saleem & Shah, 2011; Alqurashi, 2016). In terms of student employment, some studies related students' part-time employment to aspects of the self, including self-efficacy, malleable self-theory, self-confidence and self-clarity. Studies from Gbadamosi et al. (2015, 2016) suggested that self-efficacy could be one psychological factor that was embedded in part-time employment. They found "individual self-efficacy in the value attached to part-time working among students" in HE (Gbadamosi et al., 2015, p.3). A positive but non-significant regression using self-efficacy to predict part-time work was indicated. They interpreted that "the higher a students' self-efficacy in HE, the more positive they associate with their career aspiration but not necessarily part-time work" (Gbadamosi et al., 2015, p.11).

In addition, this study (Gbadamosi et al., 2015) discussed one aspect of self-theory (i.e. malleable self as an opposite of fixed self) associated with part-time work. Specifically, 'malleable self-theories' significantly and positively predicted part-time employment, meaning that "students who hold strong views that things are malleable, and people make a difference, are more likely to maximise the opportunities and value added provided by part time work" (Gbadamosi et al., 2015, p.11). Such a significant association between self-

efficacy and part-time work was further supported by a second study by Gbadamosi et al. (2016). Together these studies suggest that there may be a strong connection between self-efficacy and student employment which should not be neglected. If self-efficacy is significantly associated with career aspiration, could it also be related to other aspects of employment? This question requires further study.

In contrast, Sekiguchi (2012) found a significant negative association between time spent in part-time work and self-efficacy in team-member proficiency suggesting that working more is related to lower self-efficacy in that context. This supports the notion that self-efficacy could be related to quantitative aspects of employment and requires further investigation with a focus on general efficacy.

In these two sets of studies, the association between self-efficacy and part-time employment differed. The first study indicated that self-efficacy was associated with proactive attitudes and behaviours in employment whereas the latter indicated a negative association. An added complication is the comparability of the studies as the measurement of self-efficacy differed in these two studies as did the type of employment.

Other studies have shown a diverse range of sometimes conflicting findings. Students with part-time jobs or casual jobs had a significantly higher mean score on self-clarity (Earl & Bright, 2003). Moreover, one study established that “work experience helps enhance students’ self-confidence in working with people” (Cheng & Alcántara, 2007, p.307). Another study concluded that money earned from part-time working contributes to students’ self-concept as well as social well-being (Hammes & Haller, 1983). Employment further indirectly contributes to the academic performance of undergraduates (Hammes & Haller, 1983). However, another study found a non-significant association between self-awareness and perceived employability (Jackson & Wilton, 2017). The diversity of findings suggests that further research is required to investigate the potential links between part-time work experience and aspects of the self.

In summary, a number of benefits and psychological consequences associated with student employment have been investigated in previous studies. These however, tended to be by-products of research whose primary focus was on the nature and extent and or the relationship between part-time work and academic achievement. Among these psychological factors, stress stands out as a primary concern for students when coping with roles or the balance between work and study. It is possible that previous studies have identified the tip of

an iceberg regarding the psychological impact associated with student employment, suggesting that it would be of value to explore this issue more fully.

1.3 Primary Theory in Student Employment

Within the literature on student employment, several theoretical models have emerged that attempt to explain the potential benefits and costs that are associated with student employment. These theories are based on research findings drawn from studies involving children and adolescents who combine study with part-time work in secondary schools and the HE sector (Greenhaus & Beutell, 1985; Holmes, 2008; Parasuraman & Simmers, 2001). For example, the balance model (Richardson et al., 2014), role theory (Swanson et al., 2006) and the zero-sum theory (Greene & Maggs, 2015) draw on research from both school children and HE students. Others such as developmental theory (Nagengast et al., 2014) and primary orientation theory (Warren, 2002) draw on research which involved school students only.

Some models have used the notion of ‘balance’ to understand the impact of employment on students. Some focus on the balance between work and life in adult workers (Clutterbuck, 2003; Emslie & Hunt, 2009; Guest, 2002; White et al., 2003). Others focus on the work-study or work/school balance for student workers (Richardson et al., 2014) and some focus on the balance between costs and benefits of employment for child employees and/or child labourers (Hobbs & McKechnie, 1997; McKechnie & Hobbs, 2002).

Work-life (WL) balance has frequently been studied in full-time workers, especially female workers from middle- and working-class backgrounds (Guest, 2002; White et al., 2003). Later, the WL model was used in graduate participants (Puryer & Patel, 2016). Ong and Ramia (2009) used an expanded WL balance model in the study-work-life (SWL) balance in international students. However, the majority of researchers change the idea of WL balance to work-study (WS) balance (Hammes & Haller, 1983) when considering students’ part-time employment (Richardson et al., 2014). For student term-time workers, this model focuses on balancing the time for jobs resulting from the conflict between study and work. In doing so they neglect the complex and multi-dimensional nature of students’ well-being (Creed et al., 2015).

Moreover, the focus of balance model discussed in various studies, is more divergent than congruent. Researchers disagreed on what should be the focus in such models. Some considered the focus to be time balance. Richardson et al. (2014) for example, discussed the

balance model as “balancing the demands on time” and mentioned “Personal Coping Mechanisms” as a means of balancing time (p.306). Students used priority setting and “good time management” “to balance the two activities effectively” (Richardson et al., 2014, pp.304-305).

In the above, the balance model is interpreted in two different ways. On the one hand, balance is understood as balancing between certain aspects of life, including life and work. From this perspective, for student workers, the balance is either study and work balance or the balance between study, work and life. However, this can be difficult to interpret as the model did not specify what aspects of study, work or life should be included. On the other hand, the balance model represents a coping approach according to Richardson et al. (2014). As such, the emphasis is on balancing time although it could be argued that time cannot be the only factor in balancing work and study, or work, study and life. Based on this deficiency of the balance model, some researchers have proposed their own theory such as balancing different roles representing work, study or life. Thus, the balance model developed into role theory.

An alternative approach replaced concerns over balancing time with potential conflicts between the multiple roles that individuals carried out. For example, Swanson et al. (2006) drew attention to the different roles that students have such as learner and worker. Swanson et al. (2006) referred to the idea of a few role concepts including role balance, role conflict and role enhancement as three categories of role congruence. As such, their work contributed to the shaping of a new framework as role theory of student employment.

Role theory mainly addresses two opposite concepts: role conflict (Cheung & Tang, 2012; Creed et al., 2015; Dakas, 2011; Park & Sprung, 2015) and role facilitation (Butler et al., 2010; Creed et al., 2015). Some authors also used role congruence (Butler, 2007; Swanson et al., 2006) or work-school enrichment (Dakas, 2011) as alternative names for role facilitation. For adult workers, roles as worker as well as a family member conflicted: the time demands and behaviours required by one role conflicted with those required by the other (Greenhaus & Beutell, 1985; Parasuraman & Simmers, 2001). By investigating family roles and relationship status, some studies indicated that the different roles that students adopted influenced their education-work relationship. However, role theory acknowledges that the relationship between working and studying during term-time can be complementary and beneficial. Thus, term-time employment may have both positive and negative effects (Broadbridge & Swanson, 2002, 2005, 2006).

Role theory moves beyond the concern that balance theory has by considering the nature of the multiple roles that an individual has. These multiple roles could either conflict with each other or complement or facilitate each other. In the case of student employment, the dual roles are those of worker and HE student. In addition, the wider context and the students' role as a family member must be considered. Role theory was specifically interpreted under the cognitive appraisal assumption of Lazarus and Folkman (1984). Broadbridge and Swanson (2005) defined role theory from "a student employment perspective" to "understand the appraisal of combinations of the demands of work, university life and home life" (p.240). Broadbridge and Swanson (2005, 2006) also connected role theory with adjustment (or coping) as well as stress and well-being. They found psychological factors, especially "positive affectivity and stress were important mediators of the relationship between role congruence and adjustment" (Swanson et al., 2006, p.895). In addition, they stated role enhancement should be viewed as a positive impact that can result from employment.

Based on role theory, Hodgson and Spours (2001) created five role categories amongst full-time 16-19 years old students in six schools and one further education college in England, who are in transition either to working life or to further or higher education. The categories were: balancers, risk takers, connectors, outsiders and deliberate non-workers. This classification covered all students who either worked or did not. The first three types are students who participate in employment. According to Hodgson and Spours (2001), balancers take comfort in two roles as a student and an employee while risk takers spend too much time in employment and may risk academic study consequently. Connectors try to build on "active connections between their part-time employment and full-time course" (Hodgson & Spours, 2001, p.383). The other two categories focus on non-workers. The outsiders are who are seeking job experience but are currently not able to do so. The deliberate non-workers are the ones who consciously choose not to engage with work.

However, this classification system appears to lack clear definitions and criteria. For example, balancers were described as those who worked less than ten hours per week, were aiming to enter HE and used "paid employment both to earn money and to sharpen their ability to get organised, manage time and develop social skills" (Hodgson & Spours, 2001, p.382). However, it could be argued that balancers may be balancing a number of different factors such as time spent on academic workload or coping well. Such lack of clarity potentially undermines the utility of this classification. Therefore, hardly any studies used this classification of roles.

It can also be argued that there are other limitations within role theory. Role theory emphasises the multiple roles that a student may have such as being a worker in employment, a learner in university or a member of a family. During term-time, students can find themselves struggling to manage the conflict arising from two different, simultaneous roles as a learner and a worker. However, the problem may extend beyond the challenge of managing different roles to include the time and effort that is required to function in the roles. As such the issue may be one of time management rather than role conflict. It should, however, be acknowledged that role theory also raises the issue of the association of role conflict or facilitation with adjustment or coping and stress on students' sense of well-being (Broadbridge & Swanson 2005, 2006). This highlights a common point between balance model and role theory, namely, psychological stress and the adjustment and coping mechanisms required in an employment context.

The issue of time is a central focus of the zero-sum model which focuses on the trade-off between employment and education. The model suggests that the amount of time available to the student is finite. Hammes and Haller (1983) found participants believed "the heavier the course load, the less I could justify working" (pp.531-532). Students have a fixed amount of time (Greene & Maggs, 2015; Nonis & Hudson, 2006; Nonis et al., 2006) and time spent on work is time lost to study. Greene and Maggs (2015) found that when employment took more time, the time spent on study reduced accordingly. The zero-sum model therefore suggests a simple trade-off between work and study. However, critics of this approach argue that it neglects other activities in which students are involved such as social and leisure undertakings. To address this shortcoming, Nonis et al. (2006) used a diary approach to ascertain how US college students spent their time by investigating the amount of time spent on study, "paid work", entertainment, and sleeping (p.124). They found students are in fact "spending more time in entertainment activities and working than studying" (Nonis et al., 2006, p.124). As the researchers noted, participants' diaries only covered one week which may not be a typical college week for each student and may not capture the actual time demands that arise from their personal life and specific situations. However, including such variables was challenging and it would be difficult to ascertain which one was supposed to be responsible for students' time usage (Nonis et al., 2006). A positive aspect of this study is that it sought to separate students into two 'centred' groupings: life-centred and campus-centred. This classification links time spent to orientation theory.

It is evident that each of the models considered have various strengths and weaknesses. While they differ in terms of the key issues that explain the benefits or costs of combining full-time study with part-time work, they may share some common features. For example, they all, explicitly or implicitly, consider an approach that places an emphasis on the individual coping in terms of how they manage balance, role and time. Thus, understanding students' approaches to coping may be a fruitful line of investigation.

The developmental model essentially takes a positive view of student employment (Simpson, 2014). From this perspective part-time employment provides essential experience that helps students in their personal and professional development. This model identifies several positive aspects of employment including autonomy, confidence (Heptinstall, 1998), self-concept, personal responsibility (Marsh, 1991) and transition to adulthood (Green, 1990). It is argued that attaining these outcomes can have a positive impact on students' development. Traditionally, developmental theory was applied to populations of school students and child labourers (Simpson, 2014). However, with the notion of life-span theory (Baltes, 1987; Baltes et al., 1998), positive development is presently emphasised in the HE domain.

According to this model, any positive impact can be viewed as part of a process of development. In the study by Cheng and Alcántara (2007) it was found that students were of the view that part-time work brought reciprocal benefits including job-searching, social skills, time management, and enhancement of self-confidence and could shape students' academic and career interests.

The final model is the primary orientation model (Warren, 2002) which criticised the focus on quantitative factors such as 'time allocation' when investigating the relationship between work and study. In contrast, this approach argues that 'social psychological factors' represent "a primary orientation" (p.371). High school students in Warren's (2002, pp.384-388) study were regarded as either "school-oriented" or "work-oriented". Such orientation explains their engagement (not necessarily in terms of time dimension) in either school or employment. Warren (2002) explains that "students' social psychological orientation toward work (vs orientation toward school) is what affects their schooling outcomes" (p.371). Following this assumption, "employment intensity only matters if it is accompanied by disinterest in or disengagement from school" (Warren, 2002, p.371). While Warren (2002) proposed a model based on psychological factors (i.e. social psychological orientation) it could be argued that the concept of "social psychological orientation" (p.371) is rather vague. For example, there is little explanation as to what factors influence or underpin each orientation. Simpson (2014)

interpreted these orientations as reflecting the meaning or value that students ascribe to these domains: which is more important for a student, work or school? “Those who are less orientated towards school or who are primarily orientated towards work will perform poorly as school is of lesser importance to them” (Simpson, 2014, p.36).

However, Warren et al. (2000) also describes a process of the conscious monitoring of work and study by high school students who work: when their academic grades decrease, work may be reduced and when grades recover, hours of work may be increased. It is thus easy to see that the primary orientation model emphasises cognitive attitude or metacognitive monitoring and claims that that is the command centre of human behaviour.

This approach could be explained under the framework of theory of planned behaviour (TPB) (Ajzen, 1985). In this approach a student’s work decisions is a planned behaviour involving monitoring and relevant adjustment e.g. engage in more work or study behaviours. However, Warren (2002) did not link his theory with TPB which articulated the internal cognitive beliefs and control to external behaviours. In addition, Warren (2002) proposed that the focus should not solely be on the quantity of engagement but must include some acknowledgement of the quality of the engagement. As such he criticises the zero-sum model and its focus on time as the key factor as it neglects the quality of the work experience and the student’s engagement or interest in the job.

Warren’s (2002) primary orientation model was based on high school student workers. A similar pattern, however, may apply to undergraduates’ employment. For example, Cheng and Alcántara (2007) found most students said that they always opted to reduce work hours or stop working when academic pressure was mounting illustrating the function of conscious monitoring on the dynamic flow between work and study. Cheng and Alcántara (2007) were not seeking to apply primary orientation theory and argued that their findings demonstrated students’ coping strategies, although there are parallels with Warren’s (2002) approach.

Both theories are normally applied to discussions of employment of children and school students; to date, to my knowledge they have not been applied to HE students. This may be because HE students are thought of as older and have moved beyond the major developmental goals of school students. This provides a limited view of development and has resulted in a situation where planned employment by students is either entirely not framed by any theoretical models or is explained as a way of balance or role management.

Consequently, the crucial psychological elements of employment orientation as a planned

behaviour, involving decision-making, conscious monitoring, maintaining behaviour and goal guidance, are completely displaced by balance, roles, and time focused models.

It can be argued that, except for developmental theory, the other four theories place an emphasis on students' conscious monitoring of either their different roles or the balance between activities, and the management of their time. This emphasises the psychological processes that underpin these decisions and the consequences they have for students. This provides one of the central concerns of this thesis and suggests a need to better understand the psychological factors involved in student employment.

1.4 Rationale of this Thesis

Based on the above review it is possible to identify four main areas where there are gaps in knowledge with respect to HE and student employment. First, it can be argued that the previous literature in this area has tended to ignore or place little emphasis on the psychological impact of student employment. A few researchers have included some psychological factors in their research, but this tends to be of secondary interest as they focus on other issues (e.g. nature and extent of employment). This *ad hoc* approach means that there is a need for a systematic review of the literature to establish what psychological factors have been included in student employment research and to establish gaps in current knowledge.

Secondly, the review of current literature has also revealed a lack of research in post-2010 Scotland and as such it is lack of understanding of contemporary student employment experience. Therefore, an investigation of the nature and extent of HE student employment within the Scottish HE sector is likely to provide important insights.

Thirdly, from an overview of the literature, it appears that some research focused on stress and highlighted approaches to coping strategies that students deploy. At least two studies also reported self-efficacy in this context (Gbadamosi et al., 2015, 2016; Sekiguchi, 2012).

However, it is not possible to draw any clear conclusions due to the variability in measurement of these psychological concepts in previous studies. This would justify a more rigorous investigation of the psychological impact of student employment.

Finally, while some researchers suggested that there is a need for longitudinal research (e.g. Broadbridge & Swanson 2005; Swanson et al., 2006) in this area, few studies did so. There were some notable exceptions. For example, one study focused on social work students and adopted a short-term longitudinal design (Redmond et al., 2008). The project followed

students from Year 1 to Year 2 focusing on their attitudes to stress and job satisfaction. It found that social workers specifically working in child protection and welfare perceived higher stress and lower job satisfaction and that this pattern persisted over the two-year time. However, the majority of studies in this field adopted cross-sectional designs.

There are practical reasons for this. Longitudinal designs are time consuming in nature and have inherent advantages and disadvantages. Longitudinal design collecting “panel data entails following a cohort of individuals with the purpose of monitoring changes over a period of time” (Yee & Niemeier, 1996, p.1). Some issues associated with this design relate to the sample within the study. This drawback demonstrates the fixed sample cannot represent any changes within the population. The other limitation is that “there is invariably a fair amount of attrition” (Yee & Niemeier, 1996, p.4). To retain the inherent advantages of this approach an alternative is suggested – a short-term longitudinal design composed of repeated cross-sectional studies. The repeated cross-sectional data used an independent sample at each time which dissolved the issue of attrition of participants (Yee & Niemeier, 1996).

This approach has rarely been adopted in this research area. The current thesis employs the ‘repeated cross sectional’ studies forming a short-term longitudinal design and therefore contributes a new approach to the current subject. Utilising this approach will additionally allow an investigation of the dynamic nature of employment.

In summary, this PhD project’s primary aim is to investigate the nature and extent of student employment in Scotland and their related psychological outcomes within student employment in the HE sector in a Scottish university. The psychological outcomes are stress, the consequences of juggling work and study either according to balance model or role theory; coping strategies including management of time according to zero-sum model and self-efficacy as some studies have noted the role that students’ consciously made decisions of engaging in work or not.

1.5 Research Aims

The current research project aims to provide contemporary data on student employment in HE in a Scottish undergraduate context. An initial starting point is to collect contemporary information regarding the nature and extent of part-time employment of undergraduates in Scotland. This information will include the percentage of students participating in employment, work hours per week, type of job and rate of pay. However, the primary focus

of the research is to investigate the psychological elements underpinning students' decision to undertake part-time employment. As illustrated in the previous section, stress, self-efficacy and coping mechanisms are highlighted to confirm or challenge previously published studies, review articles and theoretical models.

The aims of this project are to:

- Aim 1: provide a systematic literature review of the psychological variables that have been linked to HE student employment and consider the potential relationship between psychological variables and student employment.
- Aim 2: establish contemporary information on the nature and extent to part-time employment amongst HE students. The thesis adds to knowledge in this area by considering potential changes in paid part-time employment in terms of quantitative and qualitative aspect of employment in a short-term longitudinal timeline.
- Aim 3: investigate the internal psychological factors that are related to part-time employment including the potential consequences (i.e. stress) and related psychological factors (i.e. coping and self-efficacy).
- Aim 4: evaluate the dynamic process adopted by HE students to manage their education and work roles.

It is worth noticed that this thesis is based on a case study of one specific HEI (a sample of post-92 universities) in the central and western Scotland.

1.6 Thesis Structure

The overall structure of this thesis is summarised below.

Chapter 1 presents an overview of student employment research and argues that there are identifiable phases of research within this area. The chapter also focuses on three main topic areas within the related literature – the nature and extent of employment, the reasons for and the impact of working. In addition, this chapter provides an exploration of the literature that has focused on the psychological impact of student employment prior to considering the dominant theories in this area. The rationale for this thesis is summarised along with the overall aims of the thesis.

Chapter 2 outlines the research methodology and methods which underpin this thesis by outlining the philosophy behind the adopted research design i.e. mixed methods. The chapter

describes various aspects of the current project including a review of the related, relevant literature, two quantitative surveys in a short-term timeline and a qualitative semi-structured interview. The ontology, epistemology and methodology are outlined in this chapter.

Chapter 3 provides a systematic review of the literature (Study 1), focusing on psychological factors as they related to working undergraduate students. The review identified stress, self-efficacy and coping and the associated relationships within student employment in previous studies. However, it was noted that the psychological aspects were a by-product rather than the primary focus of previous research. The review highlights implications regarding the research methods in the next steps of the study and these are discussed in detail.

Chapter 4 presents the findings from Study 2, the first of three empirical studies. This quantitative investigation was conducted in 2019. The chapter provides the study methods, results, discussion, and chapter conclusion.

Chapter 5 presents the findings from Study 3, the second empirical study. This second quantitative investigation was carried out in 2021, against a background of the Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19 or COVID) pandemic. As such the research project had to be adapted in the light of the disruption caused by lockdown conditions. The study reports the nature and extent of student employment and its associated psychological factors.

Chapter 6 presents the findings from Study 4, a third empirical study. This qualitative study employed semi-structured interviews. This chapter presents students' experiences of the impact of COVID-19 on their employment and how they adapted and coped.

Chapter 7 presents an overall discussion of all three empirical studies, combining the outcomes of all four studies. An overarching explanation underpinning this thesis' results and findings is also provided. The chapter concludes by discussing the implications of the findings along with reflections on the strengths and limitations of the research.

CHAPTER 2 METHODOLOGY and METHODS

2.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the methods, methodology and philosophic considerations that underpin the research presented in this thesis. In Section 2.2, for the purpose of achieving the research aims, a mixed methods approach was adopted as an overall design for the whole thesis.

Following the justification for adopting this design, four studies are outlined including one systematic review and three empirical studies. The contribution of each study is summarised, and the type of research design is explained. In Section 2.3, the author reflects on the issues associated with the use of a mixed methods approach. This section also explains the projects underlining epistemology (i.e. pragmatism) and indicates how this epistemology is reflected in each individual study. Section 2.4 considers ethical issues regarding the recruitment of participants and data collection. This section also explains the single institution sample strategy. In the last section of this chapter (2.5), the classification of terminology used for the whole thesis is outlined. Finally, Section 2.6 provides a concise chapter conclusion.

2.2 Mixed Methods

This section considers the aims of this project and how such aims could be achieved via mixed methods and why mixed methods is appropriate for this project.

2.2.1 Research Aims

The research in this thesis presents contemporary information regarding the nature and extent of part-time employment of undergraduate students within a Scottish context and to investigate the psychological elements underpinning this phenomenon (also see Section 1.5, Chapter 1). The research aims identified from the previous chapter are to:

- Aim 1: provide a systematic literature review of the psychological variables that have been linked to HE student employment and consider the potential relationship between psychological variables and student employment.
- Aim 2: establish contemporary information on the nature and extent of part-time employment amongst HE students. This thesis adds to knowledge in this area by considering potential changes in paid, part-time employment in terms of

quantitative and qualitative aspect of employment in a short-term longitudinal timeline.

- Aim 3: investigate the internal psychological factors that are related to part-time employment including the potential consequences (i.e. stress) and related psychological factors (i.e. coping and self-efficacy).
- Aim 4: evaluate the dynamic process adopted by HE students to manage their education and work roles.

The above aims were explored through one review of the literature (Chapter 3), three empirical studies (Chapters 4-6) and an overall discussion and conclusion chapter (Chapter 7). In the final Chapter, the author considers how each study individually and collectively achieved the aims of the current project and discusses related implications before reaching an overall conclusion.

2.2.2 Why Use Mixed Methods to Achieve the Aims of the Current Research?

In this section the author outlines why mixed methods was appropriate compared with a single method (i.e. quantitative or qualitative) in terms of serving the aims of the current research through its advantages and the legitimacy of methodological triangulation.

One primary argument for choosing a mixed methods design concerns the function of this design to serve the project's research aims. Aim 1 focuses on the provision of an appropriate literature review to outline the psychological variables linked to HE student employment. This review also aims to discover any evidenced potential relationship between psychological variables and student employment. Such a review may require a systematic approach which could involve both quantitative and qualitative synthesis. From this point of view, a mixed-methods design would be appropriate in dealing with the reality of potential mixed synthesis procedures. Aims 2 and 3 focus on addressing the nature and extent of part-time employment and related internal psychological factors. These two aims mainly require a quantitative approach of investigation with potential usage of supplementary qualitative approach. In contrast Aim 4 emphasises the evaluation of the dynamic process adopted by HE students to manage their education and work roles. This aim requires an approach that will explore students experience of employment and study. Hence, for this purpose, a qualitative approach is required. In summary, the three empirical studies adopted a combination of quantitative and qualitative approaches which reflects a mixed methodology.

Some consideration has been given to adopting a single approach either via quantitative or qualitative methods. However, it is felt that this would limit the potential contribution of the project to add new knowledge in this area. This research focuses on undergraduates who work part-time whilst studying in HE. Exploring the experiences of participating in paid employment during HE is complex and challenging when only one approach of investigation is utilised. When looking at the wider literature in this area it could be argued that studies that utilised a purely quantitative methodology limited the depth of the information that could be gathered at an individual level about employment experiences. For instance, McNall and Michel (2011) argued that using quantitative methods alone was likely to result in a lack of information regarding the ‘broader context’ of working students. In contrast, qualitative studies provide in-depth information, but the researchers identified the difficulty of generalisation based on qualitative designs (Hayes, 2000). In this thesis, to accomplish the second research aim, quantitative methods are sufficient to investigate and establish contemporary information on the nature and extent of part-time employment amongst HE students and provide information on the ‘quantity’ of work (such as hours worked). However, it is obvious that the amount of time worked does not capture all the potential changes within employment. Hence, the nature and extent of student employment cannot be sufficiently explored by either quantitative or qualitative approaches alone.

When considering the third aim of this thesis, a quantitative approach such as a survey or questionnaire could provide information on how stress and employment might be related from a statistical point of view. However, it could be diverse exploring students’ feelings and how they cope with subjective stress. Alternatively, a qualitative approach might better disclose information about the source of the stress, what students feel and how they cope.

A qualitative approach was deemed essential to address Aim 4 of this project which was to evaluate the dynamic process adopted by HE students in managing or balancing their education and work. In short, to sufficiently serve the multiple aims of this research, both quantitative and qualitative approaches are required. These approaches should not be separated but rather be integrated in terms of analysing and interpreting students’ experiences of employment. Adopting a mixed methods approach naturally inherits the merits of both approaches and has the potential to overcome the shortcomings of any one approach. In short, a qualitative approach compensates the inadequacy of quantitative method, and *vice versa* (Lund, 2012). For example, qualitative approaches help to compensate for a lack of understanding in the micro context and help capture details within a specific phenomenon

supporting “abstract and general” results for contextual and direct implication (Johnson & Onwuegbuzie, 2004, p.19). At a methodological level, a mixed methods approach offers the optimal chance of a sound understanding of certain research objectives. As Risjord et al. (2002) argue, although in the area of nursing research, that using both methods in a design collaboratively confirms and strengthens theories more sufficiently than using “either method alone” (p.269). In the context of this project, mixed methods design offers both statistical data regarding the nature and extent of student employment and qualitative narratives from individual students. In this way, using mixed methods is beneficial to facilitate theoretical considerations as well as draw practical implications. As such, the mixed methods approach is the appropriate choice to address the aims of research in this thesis. The legitimacy of combining both qualitative and quantitative methods at the level of methodology and philosophy is discussed further in Sections 2.3.1 and 2.3.2.

An additional reason for adopting a mixed methods design is that this design allows for the triangulation of information at the methodological level. Methodological triangulation (McEvoy & Richards, 2006; Mertens & Hesse-Biber, 2012) is a “combination of methodologies” in one or a series of studies which address the same phenomenon (Denzin, 1978, p.291, as cited in Jick, 1979, p.602). This approach was widely used before the legitimization of mixed methods. Triangulation could be a within or between method(s). The former provides “internal consistency” and “reliability” via cross-checking (Jick, 1979, p.602) while the latter provides “external validity” via integrating various data and methods (p.602). Mixed methods approach is therefore a triangulation between methods, allowing for cross-checking and validation by combining two distinct methods (i.e. qualitative or quantitative ones) and such combination enabled yielding the final congruent and comparable content (Jick, 1979). Thus, triangulation legitimates combining both qualitative and quantitative methods in one design under mixed methods.

In summary, by considering the fitness to achieve the aims of this thesis, and being supported by methodological justification, it is argued that mixed methods is the appropriate choice at both the study level and methodology level.

2.2.3 Overview of Four Studies in the Mixed Methods Design

This section outlines the four studies with respect to the mixed method design and how they address the research questions.

According to Leech and Onwuegbuzie (2009) any mixed methods design can be categorised according to three dimensions. The three dimensions are whether the mixed methods are partial or full at the 'level of mixing'; mixing is concurrent or in sequence; the research emphasises one method equally or dominantly as "emphasis of approaches" (Leech & Onwuegbuzie, 2009, pp.267-268). A more specific typology is suggested by Teddlie and Tashakkori (2006). Their typology consists of four categories including (i) sequential (either in exploratory sequential or explanatory sequential design) (Tashakkori et al., 2012), (ii) concurrent or parallel mixed methods design, (iii) conversion design, and (iv) fully integrated mixed methods design.

The choice of the specific design in one specific project is largely dependent on the research aims and the time resources available. When exploring an area or when the existing knowledge regarding a particular topic is lacking, an exploratory sequential design is deemed to be more suitable. This usually starts with a qualitative exploration which is then followed by specific studies (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). If the aim is to explore findings that are not explained in previous studies, an explanatory sequential design is appropriate. Usually, this type of design would initially investigate aspects via quantitative methods and then this would be developed with a qualitative study to explain the more nuanced issues at the individual cases level (Doyle et al., 2016; Plano Clark & Ivankova, 2016). In practice, researchers could utilise a multiple stage design (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011) which combines a variety of the above-mentioned research designs at different stages within one research project. Multiple stage design combines qualitative and quantitative methods to different degrees within the research process and exemplify the strength of each type of mixed methods design in a co-operative way.

To address the aims of this research, this thesis adopted the most flexible design, i.e. multiple stage mixed methods design. As a single design is not suitable for addressing the multiple purposes of this thesis, the four studies were integrated as a multiple stage mixed method design which is a practical choice to ultimately address the research aims. The systematic review (Study 1) utilised both narrative synthesis and qualitative synthesis. The outcomes of the review inform the psychological investigations in Studies 2 and 3. These two studies adopted an exploratory sequential design for the psychological component of the investigation. Study 2 was a quantitative study using an online survey (survey 1) to investigate both the nature and extent of employment within undergraduates and related psychological variables. Study 3 was a modified study using an adapted version of survey 1.

This adapted survey (survey 2) was introduced to adapt to the circumstances of COVID-19 and the interruption to the research process that COVID created. Studies 2 and 3 both were a quantitative study, when combined, comprised a short-term longitudinal design. Study 4 (interview) adopted a qualitative approach to explore, in depth and at individual level, unanswered questions that emerged from Study 3. This study was an explanatory sequential design (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011) based on study 3.

To be specific, the four studies are as follows:

2.2.3.1 Study One - Systematic Review

Up until 2017 there has been no systematic review published in the UK regarding the psychological impact of part-time employment on undergraduate students. It is therefore considered necessary to carry out such a review instead of a traditional literature search.

The reason for using a systematic review is to enhance the rigor of the search. Traditional narrative reviews can be flawed by bias from different sources (Tranfield et al., 2003), whereas a systematic review utilises steps that can be scrutinised, uses well-documented procedures and peer review to minimise bias (Torgerson, 2003). In the domain of health, social sciences and education, growingly literature reviews were conducted using this approach (Petticrew & Roberts, 2008). In addition, a systematic review allows for the integration of both quantitative and qualitative studies by careful involvement of a search strategy (Petticrew & Roberts, 2008).

The aim of this thesis' systematic review is to clarify the psychological factors associated with student employment that have been identified in the literature. This review utilised a specific protocol which includes a search strategy, screening, quality appraisal, data extraction and synthesis (Khan et al., 2003). The synthesis stage involved both narrative synthesis and content analysis as a qualitative synthesis approach to identify methodical issues, summarise research aims and to identify psychological variables studied in previous literature. The results from the systematic review informed the psychological part³ of subsequent studies in the current project.

³ Study 2 investigated the nature and extent of student employment and students' psychological factors in 2019. The part of nature and extent in Study 1 was pre-designed based on 1998 survey study to repeat a quantitative survey. Thus, the part of student employment in the study 1 was not a result of being informed via the systematic review, but a pre-design.

2.2.3.2 Study Two - Survey 1

Following the systematic review, an e-survey was adopted to collect the first wave of data. This involved a partial replication of a 1998 study of student employment that was carried out at Paisley University (McKechnie et al., 1998). The original study (McKechnie et al., 1998) was survey based and focused on collecting data on the nature and extent of student employment. The current project has access to the original survey tool and data sets used by McKechnie et al. (1998). This establishes current employment amongst HE students and allows comparison with another period. The goal of Study 2 is twofold. One is to investigate the nature and extent in 2019 and consider potential changes in part-time work (1998 vs 2019). The existing published literature lacks such a comparison. The second goal is to explore the potential links between student employment and psychological outcomes. Study 2 explored three key psychological variables identified from the systematic review that might be associated with student employment. Quantitative analysis was utilised.

2.2.3.3 Study Three - Survey 2 – Interruption of COVID-19 Pandemic

As of March 2020 in Scotland, COVID-19 directly impacted on the original research plan for this research project. The main consideration was that the COVID pandemic disrupted the labour market sectors that students typically relied on for their part-time employment. However, this also created an opportunity to explore the impact of COVID-19 on student employment and the impact of such changes to students' psychological outcomes. This opportunity was a non-repeatable event which might provide insights into the changes within student employment under a powerful social-economic influence. Thus, the original research plan was amended, and a second e-survey was carried out using a revised version of Survey 1. Survey 2 specifically collected information from participants covering the period January 2020 to April 2021. It also has two goals similar to Study 2 but situated in a pandemic context. One is to discover changes in employment that students faced during the time. The second goal is to explore the links of employment changes to the key psychological outcomes. Quantitative analysis was utilised to address the above aims.

2.2.3.4 Study Four - Qualitative Interviews

Surveys provide results based on substantial quantitative evidence, however, generalisability of results based on statistics lacks the depth of insight that can be discovered by listening to individuals' experiences. Guided by the paradigm of pragmatism, this thesis seeks to gain access to the true stories from individuals who are at the center of student employment. Within qualitative methods, semi-structured interviews allow the privacy of a one-to-one

setting to talk about sensitive topics such as feelings and personal experiences (Oates, 2015). The approach also encourages deep conversations within a guaranteed timeframe and semi-structured design also allows flexibility of conversation (Dunn, 2005) and initiated talking from the participants. Furthermore, the approach accommodates the researcher's capacity and resource limitation (Barriball & While, 1993).

This specific study sought to discover the real-life experiences of students during COVID pandemic from January 2020 until July/ August 2021. The main areas of interest included aspects of term-time employment and psychological outcomes of students who might be working or not, at the time of interview. One type of codebook thematic analysis (TA) known as template analysis (King, 2004, 2012; King & Brooks, 2016) was utilised as it provides an appropriate approach to understand what happened to student employment against the background of COVID-19 pandemic and their associated psychological feelings and reactions.

Following this, the author reflects on the disadvantages of mixed methods and proceeds to discuss the research worldview underpinning the mixed methods design used in this thesis.

2.3 Author's Reflections

2.3.1 Reflections of Mixed Methods

In this section, the author provides a definition of mixed methods, and reflects on the advantages of this approach as well as the challenges of using it in this research.

Based on a review of 19 definitions, Johnson et al. provided a general definition (2007, p.123) of mixed methods research:

Mixed methods research is the type of research in which a researcher or team of researchers combines elements of qualitative and quantitative research approaches (e.g. use of qualitative and quantitative viewpoints, data collection, analysis, inference techniques) for the broad purposes of breadth and depth of understanding and corroboration.

Tashakkori et al. (2012) claimed that mixed methods can be considered to be a pragmatic approach as it allows for combinations of research tools to collect multilayered answers to multifaceted questions. As a popular research design as well as method, mixed methods approach also has its disadvantages. The disadvantages of this design are associated with its power. Mixed methods design requires high quality in both quantitative and qualitative studies to achieve "multiple validities legitimation" (Johnson, 2012, p.753). This places high

expectations on the academic requirements regarding the researchers' ability, capacity of time and resource, and how to provide appropriate interpretation of the results. Specifically, mixed methods design requires the integration of both types of data analysis (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018) and conducting an integrated understanding of both quantitative and qualitative results. To face this challenge, the researcher used each study to inform the next study regarding either research methods or research content, then integrated all results and discussed them in the overall discussion in Chapter 7. Such a disadvantage raises concerns regarding how to appropriately operationalise the design in the context of this research. This concern is addressed in the methods and or discussion sections in chapters 3-6.

The other disadvantage concerns the legitimization of research methods at the philosophical level i.e. what kind of worldview underpins a mixed methods design? In the following section, the author discusses the epistemology of the chosen design at both the overall level and at the level of each study.

2.3.2 Overall Worldview of this Thesis

This section reviews and critiques different paradigms that can underpin mixed methods including transformative paradigm, critical realism, dialectical pluralism, and pragmatism. For this thesis, the author selected pragmatism as the appropriate paradigm. A justification for choosing pragmatism is outlined.

In the previous literature, there are mainly four paradigms⁴ legitimately underpinning mixed methods research. These are transformative paradigm (Mertens, 2007, 2010), critical realism (Maxwell & Mittapalli, 2010), dialectical pluralism (Shan, 2022) and pragmatism (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018; Morgan, 2014). Each of the first two paradigms holds its own assumptions in terms of ontology and epistemology (Maxwell & Mittapalli, 2010; Mertens, 2007, 2010). The transformative paradigm holds the worldview of prioritisation of social justice and the advance of human rights (Mertens, 2010). Transformative researchers emphasise ethical issues to achieve change and equity of representing diverse and disadvantaged populations from lower economic communities and cultures (Mertens, 2012a). They are driven by social change and aim to change social injustice and improve the equality of social practice. The UK has a long history of treating children and student workers

⁴ Paradigm is widely accepted as a phrase referring to “a superordinate framework or worldview accepted by a group of researchers, which shapes both theories and evidence” (Glassman, 2000, p.402)

differently (Hobbs et al., 1996, 2009, 2016) and this paradigm could be considered as appropriate.

However, it is not clear that the current project, with its specific aims, would identify any social injustice within student workers who may come from certain economic-social class or somehow are unfairly treated. Secondly, transforming society is not the primary and core concern of this research. The primary and core concerns of this research are to empirically update our knowledge and to identify any psychological factors which might be related to student employment. Such primary aims are more empirical than transformative.

Finally, based on one project focusing on one institution, the author doubts that the findings could empower sufficient endorsement regarding the changes to the injustice within wider society. The main suggestions would be valid only within the sampled HEI and may have limited generalisability beyond that particular population. Hence, the transformative paradigm seems not only to be out of step with the primary aims of this project but could be considered too ambitious and over-promising for this project.

At a methodological level, a transformative paradigm also advocates mixed methods research. However, as Mertens et al. (2010) indicate, researchers who have a transformative worldview should not adopt a mixed methods approach. Transformative paradigm has been criticised as offering suggestions rather than a justification for using mixed methods (Shan, 2022). Hall (2013) also criticised transformative paradigm as it legitimates only a few research methods (including mixed methods) within social research because the primary and dominant aims of this paradigm targets changing injustice within a society or a culture. Thus, it is an inadequate rationale for using mixed methods.

Critical realism, in common with the transformative paradigm, has limitations regarding an established worldview. This approach emphasises a critical reflection on reality and knowledge. Though reality is real and has its own structures, it exists independently of knowledge and human perception (Archer et al., 1998; Bhaskar, 2008, as cited in Zachariadis et al., 2013). When applied to social sciences, critical realism advocates that structures and mechanisms shaped by human actions are difficult to observe and measure directly. It also advocates the need to identify the cause of any phenomenon (Vincent & O'Mahoney, 2018). At a methodological level, the critical realist's worldview claims any method, including mixed methods, seeks to discover the deep mechanisms rooted in events (Volkoff et al., 2007, as cited in Zachariadis et al., 2013). This thesis' research project aims to update the nature

and extent of student employment first and then explore the psychological factors related to it. Such psychological aspects could be either the impact of, or the drive for, student employment. The relationship could be either causal or non-causal. Overall, this project aims to find more descriptive results (or findings) rather than to discover causal mechanisms. As such, the research aims of this project might not be entirely in accordance with critical realism.

As demonstrated above, the shared shortcomings of both transformative paradigm and critical realism limit their application to the current project.

In contrast, dialectical pluralism (DP) and pragmatism offer greater flexibility (Johnson, 2012; Shan, 2022). A dialectical position emphasises the social complexity of the human world (Shan, 2022) and researchers should be looking at it from multiple angles (Greene & Hall, 2010). This paradigm has its roots in Socrates' questioning and helping others see errors in reasoning and Plato's interactive dialogs (Johnson, 2017). Aristotle's reasoning including deduction and induction is also labelled "dialectical reasoning" (Johnson, 2017, p.157). With years of development by philosophers and researchers, a dialectic view comes to emphasise discovering what is true by considering opposing theories (Johnson, 2012).

Within this stance, DP has a strong worldview of multiple understanding and discovery from various times and sources (Johnson, 2012). In application, pluralism emphasises using more than one approach, channel, resource, or even multiple cultures to discover what is true.

Hence DP emphasises integrating multiple methods to discover dynamic complexity as a whole truth (Shan, 2022; Stefurak et al., 2016). It takes the stance that the truth lies in dialectical dialogs and a hermeneutical approach (Onwuegbuzie et al., 2009). To do this, it fundamentally requires mixed and integrated methods from both quantitative and qualitative approaches (Shan, 2022). Certain researchers even regard it as a metaparadigm which incorporates multiple paradigms (Johnson, 2012).

However, as a recently developed paradigm, DP remains under-defined. It has been interpreted as a highly clustered concept with limited application. Many researchers find its definition overly ambitious and hard to clarify. Additionally, it is unsuitable and inapplicable for a research project with limited resources.

For this project, DP potentially informs a project of multiple sources, channels, and stakeholders such as employers and associated industry, HEI staff and administration, working societies, and even government. Such a variety of sources may not be accessible

within the project's timeframe and resources. Hence, though it is a promising paradigm, it is not practical to adopt it in a PhD project.

The final paradigm that is considered is that of pragmatism. This paradigm⁵ seeks to resolve practical problems by focusing on being useful. It advocates the use of any appropriate philosophical frameworks which facilitate practical problem-solving. It is oriented towards practical commitments and problem-solving (Johnson & Onwuegbuzie, 2004; Feilzer, 2010) and provides maximum flexibility to not only allow researchers to choose what methods fit their research questions but offers the feasibility to compare across different praxeological studies (Sommer Harrits, 2011).

According to Hall (2013) and Shan (2022), numerous researchers support pragmatism as the paradigm appropriate for mixed methods (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018; Feilzer, 2010; Maxcy, 2003; Morgan, 2007). One representative example is Morgan (2007). He justifies pragmatism as a bridge connecting qualitative and quantitative methods in three respects. First, pragmatism adopts abductive connection of theory and data. Second, the relationship between researcher and the research process is rather intersubjective. Third, pragmatists adopt a transferable way of interpreting both qualitative and quantitative data (Morgan, 2007).

The first two paradigms are limited in their usage due to the fixed philosophical stance and the third paradigm, DP, is similarly limited in its application due to its complexity. By way of contrast, pragmatism is primarily used within the social sciences and psychological studies because of its flexibility to fit specific aims of a research (Johnson & Onwuegbuzie, 2004). In this project, pragmatism offers a useful stance owing to its flexibility and feasibility to combine both qualitative and quantitative methods in one design. It aligns with the aims of this thesis, and it facilitates the operational definition of each study as practical procedures which are required to fulfil the aims of the research (see Section 2.3.3).

This thesis ultimately is designed according to practical considerations and procedures that facilitate achievement of its research aims. Holding a pragmatists' worldview, the author is empowered by its flexibility to adopt whatever methods and related appropriate philosophical frameworks suited to achieve the aims of the research. In essence, the overall worldview reflected in a mixed methods design is a pragmatic choice in this thesis.

However, pragmatism has also been criticised because of its flexibility. For example, Shan (2022) critiqued pragmatism as lacking a specific, justified rationale for integration of both

⁵ The pragmatic paradigm originates from the pragmatic philosophy advocated by several philosophers including Peirce, Dewey, James and Rorty (Hall, 2013).

quantitative and qualitative methods. Others, including Greene and Hall (2010), Biesta (2010), and Denzin (2012) have also criticised the over-simplification of pragmatism (as cited in Mertens, 2012b). Some have argued that pragmatism should be challenged as it proposes that one approach is capable of fitting all types of studies (Johnson & Onwuegbuzie, 2004). In the opinion of the author, the flexibility and feasibility of pragmatism outweighs the above shortcomings. In the context of this thesis, the procedures, data collection and analysis of each study benefited from the guidance of this practical epistemology. Hence in a way, it compensates for a lack of rationale and over-simplification.

2.3.3 Interpretation of Epistemology within Each Study

Under the guidance of the overall epistemology of pragmatism, four studies were designed as a mixed methods design to fulfil the research aims (see Section 2.2.3). Pragmatism holds no preset assumption of ontology or epistemology (Morgan, 2014) and so accommodates each individual study in a series of one research project. As a first step, completing a systematic review (Study 1) was a practical choice. Concisely speaking, it aims to find out what is to be studied and what is not, when reviewing the literature (for full aims see Section 3.1, Chapter 3). The advantages of a systematic review, compared with a traditional narrative review, provide reliable procedures and robust synthesis (Boland et al., 2013). Moreover, it offers solutions regarding what to study and what methods to use in the next study. Studies 2 and 3 adopted a survey method for the quantitative investigations. Questionnaire based surveys were a practical choice to provide timely access to large scale data collection (Fricker & Schonlau, 2002).

In both survey-based studies, e-surveys were conducted via the internet which extended their reach and solved the limitation of time and location (Fricker & Schonlau, 2002). The two main components of each are rooted in pragmatism. One part of each survey addressed employment. Study 2 is an updated version of McKechnie et al.'s 1998 study with the aim of updating student employment profiles. The ability to update the 'old' 1998 version of the survey addressed the aim of understanding student employment by providing a temporal, comparative base.

Study 3 adapted Study 2 to explore changes in student employment during COVID-19 pandemic, lockdown conditions. In addition to exploring employment changes the survey also considers a range of psychological factors using standard psychometric tools which were appropriate and accessible. The same psychometric tools were utilised in Studies 2 and 3.

In contrast to the previous two studies, Study 4 used an interview method. For this study, pragmatism guided the choice of interview, how they were conducted and the composition of the interview questions. The decision to carry out interviews rather than focus groups was, in part, to protect students' privacy whilst discussing sensitive topics and to encourage more thoughtful expression from the participants (Dunn, 2005). In addition, it is a practical choice for the researcher who as a second language English speaker and would find focus groups difficult to understand and analyse. The interviews, due to the constraints imposed by COVID, had to be conducted online and this may not have been a useful approach for focus groups. However, the key drive in the choice of interviews is that semi-structured interviews could provide interviewees with a degree of comfort in terms of time and freedom to address the questions sufficiently (Barriball & While, 1993).

For the researcher, interviews allow the flexibility to follow-up meaningful answers and allow for the pursuit of related questions within the time frame of the event. More structured analysis (using one subtype of codebook TA, i.e. template analysis (King, 2012)) was chosen to facilitate handling large volumes of information in a short time frame. This analysis allows setting priori themes based on the three research questions to reduce the workload of sorting the voluminous information (King, 2012).

The choice of using reflective TA (Braun & Clarke, 2021) was rejected due to considerations of avoiding over-interpretation and cultural bias. A researcher from an oriental culture, limited in her understanding of the local culture might misinterpret primary data. To be concise, each study was designed, carried out and analysed by considering rigour as well as practical reasons under the epistemological framework of pragmatism.

2.4 Ethical Reflections

2.4.1 Ethic Considerations

This section details the author's consideration of the ethical issues associated with the systematic review and three empirical studies including data protection, the participation recruitment, data collection, storage and procession of data, and results/findings reporting.

The full text of the articles in the systematic review were accessed, stored, used, and cited in compliance with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Ethical approval for Studies 2, 3 and 4 were obtained from Ethics Committees of the School of Media, Culture and Society and later of the School of Education and Social Sciences, at the base institution where the research was conducted i.e. University of the West of Scotland (UWS). The recruitment of

participants for the survey studies (Studies 2 and 3) was supported by internal professionals of the Information Technology and Digital Services (ITDS) of UWS– who advertised the project via university wide email system- and this was carried out in line with GDPR. The advertisement for the two surveys covered the four Scottish campuses of UWS, i.e. Ayr, Dumfries, Lanarkshire and Paisley campuses. For Study 4, participants were recruited via student emails, volunteers and word-of-mouth by students who participated in Study 3. Students' information was anonymised and participants were able to withdraw from all studies during or after data collection. The process of collecting, analysing and reporting of both survey and interview data was in line with the British Psychological Society (BPS) Code of Ethics (British Psychological Society [BPS], 2014, 2021). In addition, specific ethical considerations of each of the empirical studies are outlined in the methods sections of the corresponding chapters.

2.4.2 Is One HEI Sample Appropriate for this Project?

This research was carried out in one Scottish HEI and there is a need to reflect on the decision to use a single case of institution. In contemporary Scotland, there is a diversity of HEIs and each has its own history, culture, population and location. This thesis focused on one post-92 HEI in central and west Scotland which represents an example of a 'new' university (i.e. post-92 university) in Scotland. The rationale of using one sampled post-92 HEI as a case for this thesis was based on following arguments.

First, average figures based on all Scottish HEIs may not reflect the characteristics of the nature and extent of student employment and its related psychological factors in the context of this specific HEI. This notion is endorsed by a few previous studies which argue that single case studies at HEI level have their own merits in and of themselves. For instance, McKechnie et al. (1998) who rationalise the value of study in one HEI methodologically and practically. They argue, “census and national data may not necessarily reflect accurately the picture within any specific institution” (McKechnie et al., 1998, p.29). Another example is Brennan et al. (2005) found poorer academic attainment of one HEI actually related to the specific population within such HEI which may have its own “propensity to work” (p.129). Hence it could be argued that psychological impact within one HEI could be valuable and could not be replaced by overall data from all Scotland HEIs.

Second, this decision is rooted in pragmatism worldview. From a practical point of view, on one hand, the implication of the research for policies or improvement strategies would be specifically fitted its own context. This would make such implications benefit its own

students directly. On the other hand, it is practical to compare student employment at two time points in this HEI. Since this project aims to find changes across decades by comparing the current study with previous findings (McKechnie et al., 1998), sampling within one specific HEI was necessary. Especially, for methodological necessity, to compare the results, the samples should be as homogeneous as possible and using the same institution facilitates this goal. Using the same HEI provides continuity. The studies in this thesis will contribute to the body of existing knowledge by providing updated, contemporaneous results and findings.

2.5 Terminology Used in this Thesis

This section addresses the definition of terminology used in this thesis.

2.5.1 Employment Variables

The prevalence of student employment is represented by a percentage indicating how many students work in a given time period. This indicates the prevalence or portion of student employment.

The term ‘quantity of employment’ refers to the hours worked per week by the student. This is sometimes referred to as contracted weekly hours in Studies 2 and 3. At other times it refers to the actual weekly working hours worked at the time of interview in Study 4.

The quality of employment is indicated by the proxy measure of job type. In this thesis there are six categories of student jobs. They are ‘shop work and sales’, ‘bar work’, ‘hotel and catering’, ‘admin and finance’, ‘social care’ and ‘other’. These job types were identified in the 1998 study conducted in the same HEI (McKechnie et al., 1998).

Pay rate or rate of pay represents how much student workers were paid per hour in term-time employment.

Employment status was used as a variable in Chapter 4 (Study 2) and refers to students work status (e.g. current, former worker or never worked) and their quantity of work. This means that current workers were categories in terms of the number of hours they worked (high, medium and low).

The term employment pattern describes the dynamic change of work status over time. This variable was only used in Chapter 5 (Study 3) when the employment during the COVID-19 pandemic was investigated.

2.5.2 Psychological Variables

This section outlines the definition, measurement and indicators of each psychological variable that is used within the project i.e. stress, self-efficacy and coping strategies⁶.

The choice of measurements for key psychological variables depends on firstly, the measurement instrument being a standardised psychometric tool with acceptable validity and reliability. Secondly, due to the fact this thesis focuses on HE students, each measurement tool should be specifically designed for a HE context or have been used in HE previously. This means that any measurement used would have a profile of norms within HE students or a similar student population. Based on the above criteria and considerations, three appropriate measurements were specifically adopted.

Stress could be measured by a variety of psychometric tools, many of which have been used in previous research. In Studies 2 and 3, stress was operationalised as the scores on the Student Stress Inventory (SSI) (Arip et al., 2015). The scale has five indicators for stress. In Study 4, stress was described as one of the negative feeling themes such as stress.

In Studies 2 and 3 self-efficacy was represented by the total score of Student Self-Efficacy Scale (SSE) (Rowbotham & Schmitz, 2013). The total SSE score represents the total level of self-efficacy.

Coping was generally defined as the “psychological response to stress” (Mathew, 2017, p.41). In Studies 2 and 3, coping was operationalised as the scores from the Coping Strategy Inventory (short form 32) (CSI-32) (Tobin et al., 1984a). Within this scale there are 14 indicators and three levels representing coping strategies. In Study 4, the various coping themes adopted by interviewees represent how they cope with employment changes and their impact.

2.6 Conclusion

Chapter 2 provides the rationale for the decision to adopt a mixed methods design for this project. This design is justified as appropriate at the methodological and epistemological levels. Guided by this overall design, one systematic review and three empirical studies are outlined to achieve the aims of this thesis. These studies are presented in the subsequent chapters in the following order: Study 1 (systematic review) is presented in Chapter 3, Study 2 (online survey 1) is presented in Chapter 4, Study 3 (online survey 2) is presented in

⁶ The justification of focusing on these three factors can be found in Chapter 3, the systematic review.

Chapter 5, and Study 4 (semi-structured interview) is presented in Chapter 6. Following this, by integrating the overall results/findings, a final discussion and conclusions chapter (Chapter 7) is given. Additionally, Chapter 7 also attempts to articulate its own contribution to existing knowledge and suggests practical implications for policymakers.

CHAPTER 3 SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

This chapter presents Study 1 of the thesis, the systematic review, which addresses the first aim of the thesis. This aim is to explore the existing literature on student employment and its association with psychological outcomes. This study informs the psychological component in the subsequent studies in the project.

In this chapter, following a short introduction (Section 3.1), the rationale of this study is discussed based on the critique of three representative articles that addressed psychological variables within student employment (Section 3.2). It consequently justified the necessity of focusing on psychological factors within student employment. It also demonstrated the need for a systematic approach rather than a traditional narrative literature review. Following this, the aims of this study are introduced. Section 3.3 describes the methods and methodology of this study and explains that this review was designed under the PICOC⁷ framework and followed the ‘typical’ procedure of a systematic review. Section 3.4 presents the results of the review followed by a discussion (Section 3.5) and conclusion (Section 3.6).

3.1 Rationale and Research Aims

Student employment in the UK has produced a significant mass of literature. Researchers have studied its nature and extent, the reasons for working and the associated academic impact (see Section 1.2, Chapter 1). However, within the research literature, there is a lack of research that explores the psychological elements within student employment. In the US where studies regarding student employment were first published, a few articles addressed part-time employment and how it impacts academic performance, whilst at the same time making some mention of psychological factors. For example, one representative article by Astin (1984) that focused on student engagement, addressed part-time employment located either on campus or off campus and how this impacted student retention. In this work, Astin implicitly described two psychological factors related to student employment: time spent on and off campus and social contact with students and staff on campus. However, how these psychological variables functioned in relation to student employment was not addressed as

⁷ PICOC is short for population, intervention, comparison or comparator, outcomes and context. It refers as a specific framework of defining the scope of literature review (Booth et al., 2012).

the research did not intend to explore psychological aspects in relation to student employment.

Perozzi et al. (2003) reviewed the effects of student employment on academic achievement but did not mention any psychological elements. Later, Riggert et al. (2006) reviewed the empirical research literature on student employment in HE and attempted to build a theoretical model of the key factors involved including psychological aspects. Their model recognised psychological elements underpinning working students' decision-making, regarding their ability to remain in HE or not. This model provided a link between student employment and psychological factors including personal characteristics of students, dissatisfaction and stress. These aspects had generally been neglected in other literature reviews (e.g. Astin, 1984). It should also be noted that the research that has so far been discussed in this section, all involves students in the US and as such the findings may not be directly transferable to the UK HE sector.

In the UK, there were no literature reviews or systematic reviews published before this project commenced in 2017. Any existing literature reviews were scattered and embedded within published empirical studies. Some researchers broadened the area by examining non-traditional students in HE (Bean & Metzner, 1985; Hughes, 1983) and mature students (Ozga & Sukhnandan, 1998; Richardson, 1994). Others, such as Broadbridge and Swanson, started a series of studies (Broadbridge et al., 2000; Broadbridge & Swanson, 2002, 2006) which included some overview of term-time employment and summarised a theoretical model of the relevant factors within one article (Broadbridge & Swanson, 2005).

In the literature review component of their article, Broadbridge and Swanson (2005) provided a transactional framework guided by role theory based on the combinations of the demands of work, university life and home life. In this framework, the first factor was “environmental sources of pressure (stressors, demands)” for an individual and the mediators/moderators were “individual characteristics” including personality variables (positive and negative affectivity and self-esteem) (p.239). The outcome variable was “adjustment to university” and this was defined by three aspects including psychological well-being, academic related aspects and “social integration” (p.239, p.242). Psychological well-being was viewed as a multi-component concept, composed of positive aspects such as “satisfaction”, “quality of Student Life”, “happiness”, and “coherence”, and negative aspects such as “stress, anxiety” and “depression” (p.239).

This framework was similar to Riggert et al.'s model (2006). Broadbridge and Swanson's model (2005) however, whilst being simpler, was largely based on a small number of empirical studies and was not exhaustive. Their first factor, sources of pressure, represented sources of stress, the mediators being personal characters of the individual experiencing the stress. The outcomes reflected coping with stress⁸: if the outcome was successful, it would be reflected positively in psychological, academic and social domains and if it was unsuccessful, these same domains were negatively affected. This framework posited a link between a specific psychological outcome (stress) and personal characteristics (e.g. self-esteem) and coping strategies within the context of student employment. Nevertheless, they explicitly addressed a particular knowledge gap that is relevant to this thesis. They argued that few student employment studies considered or investigated students' coping strategies. This initially inspired the author to pay special attention to stress, self-aspects and coping strategies.

From the above review, it is noticeable that there has been no systematic review of student employment and of relevance to this thesis, there has been no systematic review focusing specifically on psychological factors in the context of student employment. This supports the need for a clearer overview of the previous literature to identify the psychological factors that might be associated with student employment. To ensure a comprehensive and rigorous search of the existing research literature, the decision was made to conduct a systematic review rather than a traditional literature review. In relation to HE student part-time employment, this systematic literature review aims to identify the psychological factors on which previous researchers had focused. More specifically, the questions that this review aimed to address are:

- (i) What methods did previous studies adopt?
- (ii) What were the aims of previous studies?
- (iii) What psychological factors were investigated in previous studies?

3.2 Methodology and Methods

3.2.1 Procedure

This systematic review used the PICOC framework to define the research question (see Appendix 1). In this review, the PICOC represented full-time undergraduates (P-population),

⁸ This was the interpretation by the author. Broadbridge and Swanson (2005) stated "adjustment to university life" (p.240). They claimed, "the interrelationship of employment and university role demands on adjustment to university life need to be considered in terms of the following outcomes, as noted in Figure 1." (p.241)

work part-time (I-intervention) or never worked (C-comparison optional) have any psychological outcomes (O-outcomes) in Scotland (C-context). This study followed the typical procedures of a systematic literature review i.e. search strategy, screening, quality assessment, data extraction and synthesis (Boland et al., 2013; Khan et al., 2003). The flow of this systematic review is visually presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Flow Chat of Systematic Review⁹

3.2.1.1 Search Strategy

To conduct an exhaustive search of the relevant literature, this study adopted multiple search strategies (see Table 1) applied to 17 databases. Search strategy I was generally applied to each database. After that, the subsequent searches using strategies one by one (II, III, IV and

⁹ This flow was adapted from the PRISMA Flow Diagram (Moher et al., 2009). De-duplicate I and exclusion I were conducted online before merged data into Endnote.

V) added newfound literature into the pool. At this stage, this review did not limit time of publication, country and language¹⁰.

Table 1 Multiple Searching Strategy

Strategy Number	Details
Strategy I	"Part time employment" OR "term-time" work AND "higher education" OR undergraduate* OR universit* OR college* OR tertiary education NOT faculty or teach* or placement or train* or staff
Strategy II	part-time employment AND higher education OR term time work NOT faculty or teacher* or placement or training or staff
Strategy III	"part time employment" AND students
Strategy IV	"term time work" AND students
Strategy V	"part time work" AND students

3.2.1.2 Screens

To reduce the large number of items and focus on only relevant literature, a preview of title and abstract of articles (Screen I) was carried out online after running each search. With the automatic functions of de-duplicate provided in the database (Deduplicate I), 1125 items were imported into Endnote version X8. Afterwards, an auto-deduplication (Deduplication II) was carried out using a function within Endnote. 884 items remained (see Appendix 2). A review of title and abstract (Screen II) was applied according to the exclusion criteria II (see Table 2) and manual deduplication (Deduplicate III) was then conducted.

Table 2 Exclusion Criteria II (Screen II)

Exclusion Type	Code	Exclusion Criteria
Any irrelevant or partial relevant literature	EX0	Any literature is irrelevant. Any literature concerns background information of students or employment. Any literature does not contain both study and part time work, including general children, adolescences (age 11-18), Youth (young adult) (age 18-21) and adults/ staff/ part time workers, who are not students. Any literature only concerns work only. Any literature addresses the various aspects of students except for part time working. This criterion is set for any literature missed filtering out at stage of Screen I.

¹⁰ None-English articles were excluded at Screen stage III.

Exclusion Type	Code	Exclusion Criteria
Young children ages 5 to 10	EX1	Any literature concerns who are young children between age 5 to 10.
Part-time students	EX2	Any literature concerns certain students who study part-time in higher education, including mature students, or mother (maternal) students and adult students.
Organised training or placement /instruction /intervention	EX3	Any literature concerns project or programmes conducted by institution or staff as a purpose for intervention, work-study training (placement), and other kinds of educational procedures.
Graduates, postgraduates	EX4	Any literature concerns relevant theme of students who have graduated or study in postgraduate level including PhD or Doctorate.

The reason for manual deduplication was that Endnote cannot detect identical articles due to the varied formats of references automatically input by different data platforms. After Screen II and deduplication III, 541 items remained. As a reliability check, the supervisory team conducted a review of the title and abstract of 10% of the 884 articles from Screen II (n=88)¹¹, using the same inclusion and exclusion criteria. Then the percentage of agreement among the four viewers (three experts plus the researcher) was calculated as a reliability estimate. The reliability rate among the four reviewers of Screen II was 78%. At this point, Screen III by a full review of the full text was applied based on the exclusion/inclusion criteria III (see Table 3) and the process of deduplication (IV) was conducted again.

Table 3 Exclusion Criteria III (Screen III)

Code of Screen III	Code	Description
Exclusion of Screen III	EX NA	Exclusion for not being an article
	EX NE	Exclusion for not being written in English
	EX NF	Exclusion for not being available of full text
	EX NR	Exclusion for not being research
	EX PR	Exclusion for only part of it (less than 1/3) being relevant
	EXS2 EX*	Exclusion under conditions of Screen II criteria

After this, a total of 451 items remained which were reviewed against eight categories (see Table 4). All the papers that focused on young adults/children above ten years of age were

¹¹ Three academic experts of the supervisor team (two males and one female; one Professor, one Reader, one Lecturer) reviewed 10% samples. Expert reviewer 1 reviewed 30 articles. Expert reviewer 2 reviewed 29 articles. Expert reviewer 3 reviewed 29 articles. The number of articles reviewed was generated randomly via online random generation system (<https://www.random.org/integer-sets/>).

excluded as they are not considered HE students. Following this, each paper was reviewed in terms of its relevance to psychological factors. Articles were considered as highly or not highly relevant according to whether more than or less than one third of the specific article addressed psychological factors. After this screening (Screen IV), 361 items were excluded leaving 90 articles which were appraised by the quality assessment tool.

Table 4 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria IV (Screen IV)

Category	Criteria
Drives- general	Articles with less than one third addressed psychological elements were excluded.
Drives- internal/ psychology	Highly relevant to psychological factors, all were included.
Impacts- general	Articles with less than one third addressed psychological elements were excluded.
Impacts- internal/ psychology	Highly relevant to psychological factors, all were included.
Young/ children research (aged 10 above but not in HE)	Using non-university participants, all excluded.
Drives- External drives (Economy; Politics; Society; Family; Environment)	Not highly relevant to psychological factors, all excluded.
Nature and extent	Articles with less than one third addressed psychological elements were excluded.
Impacts- Academic achievement /Drop out/retention	Articles with less than one third addressed psychological elements were excluded.

The reason for adopting multiple screens was to ensure inclusion of the most relevant literature and avoid excluding the same at an early stage. Overall, Screens I and II aimed to filter out entirely irrelevant literature. Screen III then assessed the availability by filtering out inaccessible articles. Screen IV then focused on whether at least a third of each article addressed psychological factors. In this way, the large number of articles was reduced from 1125 to 90, all of which included relevant psychological factors which could be assessed for their methodical rigour.

However, there is a need to consider the adoption of a multiple screening approach and the decision-making process regarding inclusion and exclusion. For example, for articles which focused on young adults/child participants, two stages of screening took place. During Screen II, the articles dealing with young children (i.e. less than 10 years old) were excluded, as at this age participants cannot enter HE. However, research involving older children (i.e. more than 10 years old) was retained in the screening process as some studies included young people who were of HE age. Screen IV reviewed each article to identify whether the

participants were involved in HE and if not, then the article was excluded. This strategy was adopted to avoid potentially excluding relevant articles at too early a stage in the screening process.

The screening process also had to address research that included part-time and full-time students. This research project focuses on full-time students. Full-time and part-time students have differing commitments in terms of their financial situation, time usage, family duties, social networks, and other aspects. Previous studies indicate that full-time student workers face more challenges including finance, academic studies, health, time management and social relationships compared to part-time student workers (Darolia, 2014; Holmes, 2008; Hall, 2010; Lucas & Lammont, 1998; McCoy & Smyth, 2007). To ensure this review focused on full-time students EX2 targeted part-time students that in some cases were referred to as mature students, mother students and mature adults. However, the exclusion criteria for this study were based on the part-time study status of students and not the characteristics mentioned above (i.e. age and life characteristics of the students). Thus, part-time students instead of mature students was used as the label.

Finally, this research project is interested in the naturally occurring paid part-time employment which took place at the same time as studying in HE. This criterion does not include employment opportunities created by educators and or HEIs. Thus, EX3 filtered out the training programmes designed by HEI including education intervention, work-study training (placement), and other kinds of educational procedures such as internships.

3.2.1.3 Quality Assessment

Quality appraisal is a key stage of a systematic literature review as it can establish the quality of the literature upon which the review is based. A review based on high quality articles suggests robust information. For this thesis a quality assessment was conducted on the 90 items that remained after Screen IV. The decision was made to use the adapted Crowe critical appraisal tool (CCAT) (see Appendix 3) as this is a widely used appraisal tool to assess the quality of articles within the discipline of psychology (Crowe & Sheppard, 2011a). The CCAT allows for a consistent appraisal of different types of articles using different designs (Crowe et al., 2012). For these reasons, the CCAT with its unified scoring system was chosen as the quality assessment tool for this study (Crowe & Sheppard, 2011b).

Crowe indicated that the cut-off score within the CCAT system should be considered to be 75% (Crowe & Sheppard, 2011b) and other empirical studies that have used CCAT have

adopted this as standard (e.g. Catalano, 2013; Sexton et al., 2019). Therefore, this study also adopted a 75% cut-off point. Within the 90 articles¹² included in the penultimate stage, 36 articles (40%) qualified as high quality (\geq than 75%), 50 articles (55.6%) were classified as medium high quality (\geq 50% but $<$ 75%), and four articles (4.4%) were categorised as medium quality (\geq 25% and $<$ 50%). There were no articles with a CCAT score of less than 25% (see Table 5).

Table 5 Result of Quality Assessment by CCAT

Quality results	Code	Score	Frequency	Percentage (n=90)
High quality	H	75%-98%	36	40.00%
Medium High quality	MH	50%-73%	50	55.56%
Medium quality	M	25%-48%	4	4.44%
Low quality	L	0%-23%	0	0.00%
Total	4	--	90	100%

The final 36 items that scored above 75% (scaled as high quality) were included in the next stage of synthesis. These are displayed in Table 6 along with a summary of the title, year of publication and publication journal.

The descriptive statistics from the CCAT relating to the final set of articles (see Table 7), indicates the overall quality of the inclusion was 80.56 with a standard deviation of 4.98. Ethics matters was the lowest rated quality aspect of all the articles that were reviewed.

¹² Scores of CCAT of 90 items can be seen in Appendix 4.

Table 6 The Final Inclusions (N=36)

Short Title (Author and Year)	Article No.	CCAT Score	Long Title	Published Journal	Year
Nonis & Hudson, 2006	016	78%	<i>Academic performance of college students: Influence of time spent studying and working</i>	Journal of Education for Business, 81 (3): p. 151-159.	2006
Cheng & Alcántara, 2007	049	80%	<i>Assessing working students' college experiences: a grounded theory approach.</i>	Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education, 32 (3): p. 301-311.	2007
Josiam et al., 2010	052	78%	<i>Attitudes to Work of Generation Y Students in Hospitality Management: a comparative analysis of students in England, Scotland and Northern Ireland.</i>	Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Education, 22 (1): p. 44-53.	2010
Jogaratnam & Buchanan, 2004	059	83%	<i>Balancing the demands of school and work: stress and employed hospitality students.</i>	International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management, 16 (4): p. 237-245.	2004
Jackson & Wilton, 2016	081	80%	<i>Career management attitudes among business undergraduates.</i>	Australian Journal of Career Development, 25 (1): p. 7-22.	2016
Cheung & Tang, 2012	098	88%	<i>Chinese Undergraduate Students' Work Values: The Role of Parental Work Experience and Part-Time Work Quality.</i>	Journal of Career Development (Sage Publications Inc.), 39 (3): p. 231-247.	2012
Butler et al., 2010	102	78%	<i>College Student Employment and Drinking: A Daily Study of Work Stressors, Alcohol Expectancies, and Alcohol Consumption.</i>	Journal of Occupational Health Psychology, 15 (3): p. 291-303.	2010
Vaughn et al., 2016	104	85%	<i>College student mental health and quality of workplace relationships.</i>	Journal of American College Health, 64 (1): p. 26-37.	2016
Bouchard & Nauta, 2017	107	85%	<i>College Students' Health and Short-Term Career Outcomes.</i>	Journal of Career Development, 45 (4): p. 393-406.	2017
Tessema et al., 2014	157	78%	<i>Does Part-Time Job Affect College Students' Satisfaction and Academic Performance (GPA)? The Case of a Mid-Sized Public University.</i>	International Journal of Business Administration, 5 (2): p. 50.	2014
Pascarella et al., 1998	161	88%	<i>Does work inhibit cognitive development during college?</i>	Educational Evaluation & Policy Analysis, 20 (2): p. 75-93.	1998
Bono et al., 2017	164	90%	<i>Drinking, cigarette smoking, and employment among American college freshmen at a four-year university.</i>	Substance Use & Misuse, 52 (2): p. 182-193.	2017
Swanson et al., 2006	171	90%	<i>Earning and learning: Role congruence, state/trait factors and adjustment to university life.</i>	British Journal of Educational Psychology, 76 : p. 895-914.	2006

Short Title (Author and Year)	Article No.	CCAT Score	Long Title	Published Journal	Year
Ho & Huang, 2013	173	80%	<i>Earning while Learning: Part-Time Work during Term-Time.</i>	Asia Pacific Journal of Educational Development, 2 (1): p. 59-66.	2013
Manthei & Gilmore, 2005	186	85%	<i>The effect of paid employment on university students' lives.</i>	Education + Training, 47 (3): p. 202-215.	2005
Bednarska & Olszewski, 2016	197	78%	<i>Effect of Work Experience on Students' Attitudes Toward Hospitality Careers.</i>	Tourism and Hospitality Management, 12 :p. 235-249.	2016
Teng, 2008	216	90%	<i>The effects of personality traits and attitudes on student uptake in hospitality employment.</i>	International Journal of Hospitality Management, 27 (1): p. 76-86.	2008
Hall et al., 2015	224	80%	<i>Empathy in UK pharmacy students: Assessing differences by gender, level in the degree programme, part-time employment and medical status.</i>	Pharmacy Education: An International Journal of Pharmaceutical Education, 15 (1): p. 241-247.	2015
Gbadamosi et al., 2015	228	80%	<i>Employability and students' part-time work in the UK: does self-efficacy and career aspiration matter? Examining the link between adult attachment style, employment and academic achievement in first semester higher education.</i>	British Educational Research Journal, 41 (6): p. 1086-1107.	2015
Beauchamp et al., 2016	257	80%	<i>How does Term-time Paid Work Affect Higher Education Students' Studies, and What can be Done to Minimise any Negative Effects?</i>	Social Psychology of Education, 19 (2): p. 367-384.	2016
McGregor, 2015	331	75%	<i>Impact of Ethical and Affective Variables on Cheating: Comparison of Undergraduate Students with and without Jobs.</i>	Journal of Perspectives in Applied Academic Practice, 3(2): p.3-14	2015
Hsiao, 2015	348	75%	<i>The impact of part time employment on students' health and academic performance: a Scottish perspective.</i>	Higher Education, 69 (1): p.55-77	2015
Carney et al., 2005	354	75%	<i>Job characteristics and college performance and attitudes: A model of work-school conflict and facilitation.</i>	Journal of Further and Higher Education, 29 (4): p. 307-319.	2005
Butler, 2007	391	90%	<i>Making ends meet: some of the consequences of part-time work for college students.</i>	Journal of Applied Psychology, 92 (2): p. 500-510.	2007
Hammes & Haller, 1983	435	83%	<i>Multitasking, but for what benefit? The dilemma facing Nigerian university students regarding part-time working.</i>	Journal of College Student Personnel, 24 : p. 529-535.	1983
Gbadamosi et al., 2016	461	75%		Journal of Education and Work, 29 (8): p. 956-979.	2016

Short Title (Author and Year)	Article No.	CCAT Score	Long Title	Published Journal	Year
Sekiguchi, 2012	534	75%	<i>Part-Time Work Experience of University Students and Their Career Development.</i>	Japan Labor Review, 9 (3): p. 5-29.	2012
Jackson & Wilton, 2017	554	75%	<i>Perceived employability among undergraduates and the importance of career self-management, work experience and individual characteristics.</i>	Higher Education Research & Development, 36 (4): p. 747-762.	2017
Greene & Maggs, 2015	622	83%	<i>Revisiting the time trade-off hypothesis: Work, organized activities, and academics during college.</i>	Journal of youth and adolescence, 44 (8): p. 1623-1637.	2015
Winkler, 2008	713	76%	<i>Students as non-standard employees. Exploring work related issues in students' perceptions on their term-time job.</i>	Management Revue, p. 179-199.	2008
Lee et al., 1999	732	75%	<i>Students' part-time work: towards an understanding of the implications for nurse education.</i>	Nurse Education Today, 19 (6): p. 443-451.	1999
Earl & Bright, 2003	790	80%	<i>Undergraduate level, age, volume and pattern of work as predictors of career decision status.</i>	Australian Journal of Psychology, 55 (2): p. 83-88.	2003
Park & Sprung, 2015	805	75%	<i>Weekly work-school conflict, sleep quality, and fatigue: Recovery self-efficacy as a cross-level moderator.</i>	Journal of Organizational Behavior, 36 (1): p. 112-127.	2015
Koeske & Koeske, 1989	843	78%	<i>Working and non-working students: roles, support and wellbeing.</i>	Journal of Social Work Education, 25 : p. 244-256.	1989
Creed et al., 2015	862	78%	<i>Working while studying at university: The relationship between work benefits and demands and engagement and wellbeing.</i>	Journal of Vocational Behavior, 86 : p. 48-57.	2015
Dakas, 2011	867	78%	<i>Work-School Conflict and Work School Enrichment: A Student's Perspective on Taking on Multiple Roles Through On-campus and Off-campus Employment.</i>	Honors Scholar Theses. 205.	2011

Table 7 Descriptive Statistics of CCAT Scores of Final Inclusion

CCAT	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Preliminaries	36	2.00	4.00	3.50	0.56
Introduction	36	3.00	4.00	3.81	0.40
Design	36	4.00	8.00	6.69	0.96
Sampling	36	1.00	5.00	3.19	1.12
Data collection	36	.00	4.00	3.19	1.12
Ethic matters	36	.00	2.00	0.94	0.95
Results	36	3.00	6.00	5.14	0.96
Discussion	36	2.00	7.00	5.58	1.25
Total score	36	28.00	36.00	32.06	2.12
Percentage score	36	75.00	90.00	80.56	4.98

3.2.1.4 Data Extraction and Transfer

Following the procedure detailed above, the key information relating to the methods and results was extracted from the original articles and manually copied into data extraction forms. The extracted information consisted of study characteristics (title, short title, article number, design, details of tool, sample method and size, aim of study, and analysis methods), participant characteristics and results of outcomes. Numerical data (numbers of programme¹³, initial number of samplings, valid number of samplings, and return rate) and nominal data (type of research method and sampling) were also extracted. An example of data extraction can be seen in the form in Appendix 5.

Two sets of data were transferred into Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) v25. One dataset consisted of the quality score assessed by CCAT for each article. The CCAT quality score included percentage score, total score, and the scores for the eight sections. The eight section scores represented the quality of an article with respect to preliminaries, introduction, design, sampling, data collection, ethical matters, results and discussion (Crowe & Sheppard, 2011a).

The second dataset consisted of information on the methods used and this was extracted from the data extraction form. This dataset included 14 dimensions (see Appendix 6). Five dimensions related to research design, data level (primary/secondary data), type of

¹³ For example, if one study sampled social science programme/subjects, the number of the sampled programme was one. If one study sampled computer, engineer and psychology programme/subjects, the number of the sampled programme was counted as three.

questionnaire (*ad hoc*/psychometric), question type (open-ended/close-ended/mixed both) and reliability and validity (partially provide/completely provide). Another five dimensions related to the sampling method (sampling method, sample country, programme limit, sample institution types, and sample size), while the remaining four dimensions related to the procedure (conductor, initial number of samplings, valid number of samplings, and return rate).

3.2.2 Synthesis

Synthesis is the final stage of the systematic review (Pollock & Berge, 2018). In this review, narrative synthesis and qualitative synthesis were both utilised to the final included 36 articles. Narrative synthesis focused on methodical information. It was used to identify gaps in the methods, detect the main study aims and to highlight main psychological factors. The qualitative synthesis utilised qualitative content analysis and was conducted on aims of study and the psychological variables in final included articles. The process of synthesis used in this review is listed in Table 8.

Further detail on the qualitative conceptual content analysis for assessing the psychological variables (the third aim of this review) is provided here. First, any mention of psychological variables that appeared in the results section of the final 36 articles were highlighted with green background. Then within this section, the frequency of word occurrence was counted with an automatic word search function within each article. The result of this automatic word searching was then marked in brackets after the highlighted phrases. One example of an analysed article can be seen in Appendix 7. This process created a list of psychological variables identified in the final 36 articles. The top level of categories of psychological variables were reported in the section of Findings (Section 3.3.3) combined with narration of specific variables.

Table 8 Synthesis Adopted

Review aims	Targeted content	Type of synthesis	Applied area in the articles	Procedures	Indicators
(i) What methods did previous studies adopt?	Methods and methodology	Narrative synthesis	Abstract and Methods	Based on extraction form. To classify first, then input SPSS analysis. To summarise the results/output of SPSS.	Statistical frequency and percentage Narration
(ii) What were the aims of previous studies?	Study aims	Qualitative conceptual content analysis	Whole article	Based on extraction form. To review first and create initial categories. Base on original article, to search word occurrence, confirm or change classification.	Categories developed, word occurrence and or content coverage rate.
		And narrative synthesis	--	To summarise the categories of content analysis.	Narration
(iii) What psychological factors were investigated in previous studies?	Psychological variables	Qualitative conceptual content analysis	Results or Findings	Based on extraction form. To identify variables first, then code and search word occurrence and finally classify.	Categories developed, word occurrence and or content coverage rate
		And Narrative synthesis	Whole article	Based on original article. To highlight key psychological variables.	Narration

3.2.3 Reflections of Choices of Synthesis

This section presents the rationale for the adoption of both a narrative synthesis and a content analysis.

Generally, there are two types of synthesis that have either a quantitative or qualitative orientation (Sandelowski et al., 2006). Quantitative synthesis utilises statistics to compare quantitative characters of at least two empirical studies (Sandelowski et al., 2006) and it is effective for analysing the results from studies with the same design. Quantitative synthesis includes meta-analysis, meta-regression, and diagnostic meta-analysis (Sandelowski et al., 2006). Qualitative synthesis in contrast, is particularly powerful for synthesising qualitative findings as well as quantitative results (Bearman & Dawson, 2013). Qualitative synthesis includes meta-ethnography, thematic synthesis, realist synthesis, framework synthesis, content analysis, meta-aggregation, and other newly developed sub-types (Barnett-Page & Thomas, 2009).

In the current review, both narrative synthesis and qualitative synthesis using content analysis were used. First, the narrative synthesis, which is commonly included in any systematic analysis (Popay et al., 2006), was used as it provided “transparent heterogeneity between studies” and was utilised as a pre-setting procedure leading to deeper analysis such as meta-analysis or qualitative synthesis (Barnett-Page & Thomas, 2009, p.3). In this project, to serve the review aim (i), a narrative synthesis was the appropriate choice, because narrative synthesis can combine both narration and basic descriptive analysis to provide a holistic picture of the basic information and provide the setting of further synthesis. However, further and deeper synthesis was also needed to provide synthesis regarding the aims of studies in the final set of articles (review aim ii) and identifying what psychological factors within student employment were investigated in these articles (review aim iii). This necessity of deeper synthesis focusing on aims and psychological variables highlighted the need for choosing an appropriate method of this further synthesis.

Since the final set of articles indicated high level of heterogeneity, the variability in the results, participants profiles and the study designs (which consisted of both quantitative and/or qualitative designs) presented a challenge as to what synthesis approach could be used. It would have been problematic to conduct quantitative synthesis such as meta-analysis as this usually requires high level of homogenisation of research methods or designs (Littell et al., 2008). This left the author to consider the narrative synthesis and possible qualitative synthesis as an alternative. As the author was aware of the variety of potential synthesis

within the qualitative synthesis family, several considerations were considered that influenced the choice of qualitative content analysis.

In general, the variety of qualitative synthesis differs in terms of the framework guidance. Each individual type of synthesis reflects a segment within the spectrum of philosophical frameworks, which varies from relativism (being more interpretative) to positivism (being more descriptive) (Barnett-Page & Thomas, 2009). Since the purpose of the synthesis is to address the review aims i.e. a description of what the aims of the studies were, and to identify the psychological variables that had been studied, interpretative synthesis was inappropriate. The author as a pragmatist, chose what was appropriate regardless of the frameworks of the synthesis approaches. Since the practical reason to serve the review aims, the author again as a pragmatist, primarily considered the descriptive and objective approach. Therefore, content analysis and meta-aggregation were both considered.

Content analysis and meta-aggregation have the strength of transparent synthesis and are based on accurate and reliable original findings. The process of employing both also avoids any bias rooted from the re-interpretation and over interpretation that can often appear within other qualitative synthesis (Lockwood et al., 2015). The former, content analysis, has the advantage of preserving the benefits of quantitative counting as well as interpretation based on the original qualitative text (Mayring, 2004). Content analysis is flexible to be used upon either qualitative or quantitative evidence achieved from either quantitative and or qualitative research. The later, meta-aggregation relies only on aggregating evidence by extracting the findings from the text then grouping them under the shared meanings (Grover et al., 2023). Moreover, it is normally used to provide qualitative evidence through qualitative research only.

For this project, the author first believed that content analysis would provide the required synthesis to answer the review aims in the previous literature since it integrated both quantitative frequencies and the categorisation of findings. Secondly, the sources of the systematic review in this chapter combined qualitative, quantitative, and mixed-methods research articles. Thus, from a practical perspective, content analysis would be more appropriate than meta-aggregation. However, both have been criticised as being aggregated and simplifying “rich descriptions” in qualitative studies into “thin abstractions” (Bergdahl, 2019, p.1). In addition, content analysis has been criticised for focusing on occurrence frequency, location and coverage percentage (Krippendorff, 2004, 2018). To compensate for this, the narration provided by narrative synthesis may provide rich description rather than

narrow categories. This further justifies combining narrative synthesis along with qualitative synthesis as a useful compensatory strategy. In this chapter, the indicator of frequency count of words occurrence was adopted and reported to articulate the findings of synthesis. Coverage rate was only reported when occurrence frequency was not sufficient to evidence the categories.

3.3 Findings

The author first lists relevant information of final included articles including aims of studies, methods, variables and key findings in a table (see Appendix 8) before synthesis started. Then the author uses this section to present the findings of the synthesis on the methods, followed by the aims of studies, and finally the psychological variables that had been identified.

3.3.1 Methods of the Final Articles

To identify potential gaps within the adopted methods a narrative synthesis was carried out. The results including research design, sample method and other aspects were narrated and combined with reference to the quantitative analysis results (see Table 9).

Table 9 Design and Method of Final Inclusions (N=36)

Design and Method	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Survey by questionnaire (cross section)	29	80.56	80.56	80.56
Mixed methods	2	5.56	5.56	86.12
Survey by interview /focus group (cross section)	2	5.56	5.56	91.67
Survey and diary record (possible cross section)	1	2.78	2.78	94.45
Diary record (longitudinal design)	1	2.78	2.78	97.22
Survey by questionnaire (longitudinal design)	1	2.78	2.78	100.00
Total	36	100.00	100.00	

Consideration of the research design is important in assessing an empirical study and this analysis found that only two studies used mixed methods combining a survey with interviews (Hammes & Haller, 1983; McGregor, 2015) and two used qualitative method by conducting a focus group (Cheng & Alcántara, 2007) or a semi-structured interview (Winkler, 2008). Two studies adopted a longitudinal design by collecting daily diary data where participants reported information on work patterns or time spent on employment. Greene and Maggs (2015) collected these 14-days diaries for seven semesters and investigated the “time trade-

off perspective” (p.4). Similarly, Park and Sprung (2015) also used diary data collection. They initially collected data on demographic information and self-efficacy by an initial survey and then followed this with weekly diary data. This rarely used longitudinal design was beneficial in terms of comparing results across time periods.

The review process also showed that previous research used questionnaires that consisted either of *ad hoc* items or a psychometric scale (see Table 10). Nearly 75% of studies used *ad hoc* questionnaires with less than 20% using a combination of *ad hoc* and psychometric scales. Less than 10% of studies relied only on psychometric scales. Psychometric scales can be argued to provide accurate measurement due to their construction which enhances their validity and reliability. However, since psychological factors were often not the focus of these studies, *ad hoc* questionnaires were widely used. Overall, previous studies were limited in their use of psychometric scales.

Table 10 Type of Measurement to Psychological Factors

Type of measurement	Frequency	Percent
Ad hoc	26	72.22
Psychometric	3	8.33
Ad hoc and Psychometric	7	19.45
Total	36	100.00

It is worth noting the countries of origin of the final set of review articles. As indicated in the Table 11, approximately 42% of the articles were based on research carried out in the US, approximately 14% were conducted in the UK (excluding Scotland), whereas only 8% were based on research conducted in Scotland. These three studies were Carney et al. (2005), Swanson et al. (2006) and McGregor (2015).

One of the main issues that was identified from this review, was that psychometric scales were rarely employed. In the current project it was necessary to use *ad hoc* questionnaire for the aim to update the data on the nature and extent of student employment. However, psychometric scales were appropriate for the investigation of psychological outcomes. Therefore, this review indicated that it was appropriate to conduct *ad hoc* surveys along with psychometric scales. It also justified the value of such a survey in Scotland to provide a baseline for student employment and contemporary information on the nature and extent of student employment. It was also of value to identify key psychological variables to understand the complex relationships among work, study, and psychological outcomes. This

review suggested that from a methodical point of view, it was important for future research to use: (i) a longitudinal design (ii) a Scottish sample, and (iii) psychometric scales to ensure validity and reliability of findings relating to psychological factors.

Table 11 Type of Sampling Country

Sampling Country	Frequency	Percent
US	15	41.7
UK (excluding Scotland)	5	13.9
China	4	11.1
Scotland	3	8.3
England and Australia ¹⁴	2	5.6
European Union (EU)	2	5.6
Japan	1	2.8
Australia	1	2.8
Canada	1	2.8
New Zealand	1	2.8
South Africa	1	2.8
Total	36	100.0

3.3.2 The Aims of the Final Articles

This synthesis confirmed that the main aims in the final 36 articles focused on three aspects (see Table 12). For the first aspect, 36% focused on the impact of employment (n=13) including psychological impact (n=4), academic achievement (n=4), and both (n=5). For the second aspect, 36% focused on career-related outcomes (n=13), which included career aspiration (n=3), career attitudes (n=3), and career ability (n=3) and other career related aspects (career decision, job satisfaction and clustered career outcomes). For the third aspect, 33% focused on employment per se including nature and extent and quality of employment (n=12).

Based on this synthesis, it was evident that the items identified by CCAT as ‘high quality articles’ mainly focused on the impact of academic achievement, career aspects, and nature and extent of employment. As psychological variables were always embedded in studies focusing on non-psychological factors, this also indicated that there was lack of focus on psychological outcomes of student employment.

Despite this lack of focus on psychological factors, they were still explored however, this was rarely done in relation to the primary aim of the studies. Whilst the synthesis of aims of these

¹⁴ Because these two articles investigated two countries in one design, so they were listed and not counted in UK (excluding Scotland) category.

studies disclosed psychological factors that were embedded within other research interests, it is valuable to highlight what these psychological factors were. In total 33% of the articles (n=12) addressed motivation to work and physical and mental health (see Table 13). A further 14% of the articles investigated other psychological factors including self-related aspects (n=5), social aspects (n=5), school satisfaction (n=4), personality (n=3), cognition (n=3), stress (n=3) and coping/adjustment (n=3). It is apparent that even within such a small number of articles a variety of psychological factors were identified.

Table 12 Aims of Studies under Classification

Categories of aims	Sub-categories	Short title and Item No.	Word Frequency	Coverage rate
Impact of employment (N=13, 36.11%)	Impact to academic achievement alone	Nonis & Hudson, 2006 (No. 016)	Academic performance 53 GPA 27	GPA coverage rate 3.67%.
		Tessema et al., 2014 (No. 157)	Academic performance 8 GPA 90	-
		Butler, 2007 (No. 391)	Academic performance 4 School performance 26	-
		Beauchamp et al., 2016 (No. 257)	Academic performance 49	-
	Impact to both (academic achievement and psychology)	Cheng & Alcántara, 2007 (No. 049)	-	Impact of work on college life coverage rate 5.0%.
		McGregor, 2015 (No. 331)	Confidence 7 Health 14	Confidence, physical and mental health coverage rate 6.33%; Impact to study coverage rate 15.13%; How to improve study (study B) coverage rate 13.39%.
		Carney et al., 2005 (No. 354)	-	Physical and mental wellbeing coverage rate 6.96%; Academic performance coverage rate 2.53%.
	Impact to psychological aspects alone	Hammes & Haller, 1983 (No. 435)	GPA 6	-
		Lee et al., 1999 (No. 752)	Performance 15 Course performance 3 Positive and negative effects 4 Negative effect 7 Effect 23	-
		Jogarathnam & Buchanan, 2004 (No. 059)	Stress 72 Stressor 38	-
Career related profile (N=13, 36.11%)	Career aspiration	Pascarella et al., 1998 (No. 161)	Cognitive development 112	-
		Swanson et al., 2006 (No. 171)	Adjustment 59 Stress 76 PA (positive affectivity) 33 NA (negative affectivity) 36	-
		Manthei & Gilmore, 2005 (No. 186)	Activities 35	Balancing activities, social life and study time a coverage rate 6.90%.
		Teng, 2008 (No. 216)	Attitude 64 Aspiration 54	-
		Gbadamosi et al. 2015 (No. 228)	Career aspiration 72	-
		Gbadamosi et al., 2016 (No. 461)	Career aspirations 24	-

Categories of aims	Sub-categories	Short title and Item No.	Word Frequency	Coverage rate
	Career attitudes	Josiam et al., 2010 (No. 052)	Career prospect 4 Attitude 172 Work attitude 44 Positive attitude 21 Negative attitude 17 Work value 30 Work ethic 15	-
		Jackson & Wilton, 2016 (No. 081)	Attitude 12 Career attitude 7 Protean career attitudes 14 Boundaryless career attitudes 23 Self-direction 36 Values-driven 31 Boundaryless mindset 36	-
		Cheung & Tang, 2012 (No. 098)	Attitude 19 Work attitude 4 Motivation to do good work 28 Work cynicism 29	-
	Career decision and pursuing	Bednarska & Olszewski, 2016 (No. 197)	Career attractiveness 9	-
	Career outcomes	Earl & Bright, 2003 (No. 790)	Career decision 99	-
		Bouchard & Nauta, 2017 (No. 107)	Aspiration 38 Work volition 78 Career 149 Career aspiration 14	-
	Career ability	Dakas, 2011 (No. 867)	Job satisfaction 32	-
		Sekiguchi, 2012 (No. 534)	Skill 62 Job autonomy 24 Job crafting 28	-
		Jackson & Wilton, 2017 (No. 554)	Perceived employability 18 PE (perceived employability) 72	-
		Winkler, 2008 (No. 713)	Work task 15 Training opportunities 12	-
Employment per se	Nature and extent	Cheng & Alcántara, 2007 (No. 049)	Work experience 9 Type of job 2 Type of work 2	Work experiences coverage rate 1.75%.

Categories of aims	Sub-categories	Short title and Item No.	Word Frequency	Coverage rate
(N=12, 33.33%)		Swanson et al., 2006 (No. 171)	-	Work characteristics coverage rate 0.82%.
		Ho & Huang, 2013 (No. 173)	-	Work type and work hours coverage rate 1.38%.
		Manthei & Gilmore, 2005 (No. 186)	-	Paid employment coverage rate 6.30%.
		McGregor, 2015 (No. 331)	-	Nature and extent coverage rate 5.67%.
		Carney et al., 2005 (No. 354)	-	Level of student employment a coverage rate 2.72%.
		Gbadamosi et al., 2016 (No. 461)	-	Extent of work coverage rate 2.91%.
		Greene & Maggs, 2015 (No. 622)	-	Working minutes and hours coverage rate 0.60%.
	Lee et al., 1999 (No. 752)	Incidence and nature 3	Nature and extent of work coverage rate 4.61%.	
	Quality of work	Cheung & Tang, 2012 (No. 098)	Work quality 13	Work experience coverage rate 0.54%.
		Winkler, 2008 (No. 713)	Work task 15 Working hours 7	Work task (low-skills job) and working hours/schedules a coverage rate 7.74%.
Both quality and quantity of work	Sekiguchi, 2012 (No. 534)	-	Quality and quantitative aspects of work coverage rate 9.17%.	

Table 13 Psychological Factors Studied to Serve Main Aims

Categories	Short title and item No.	Word frequency	Coverage rate
Motivation	Nonis & Hudson, 2006 (No. 016)	Motivation 36	-
	Cheng & Alcántara, 2007 (No. 049)	Motivation 5	Motivation to work 0.93% coverage.
	Josiam et al., 2010 (No. 052)	Motivation 36	-
	Cheung & Tang, 2012 (No. 098)	Motivation to do good work 28	-
	Beauchamp et al., 2016 (No. 257) Lee et al., 1999 (No. 752)	Amotivation 23 -	Motivation to work 4.04% coverage.
Health	Creed et al., 2015 (No. 862)	Well-being 51	-
	McGregor, 2015 (No. 331)	Physical health 5 Mental health 7	Physical health and mental health 3.72% coverage; Tiredness and stress 0.80% coverage.
	Carney et al., 2005 (No. 354)	Physical health 8 Mental health 16	-
	Bouchard & Nauta, 2017 (No. 107)	Unhealthy days 18	-
	Park & Sprung, 2015 (No. 805) Vaughn et al., 2016 (No. 104)	Fatigue 89 Mental health 70	- -
	Butler, 2007 (No. 391)	School satisfaction 26	-
School satisfaction	Tessema et al., 2014 (No. 157)	Satisfaction 110	-
	Swanson et al., 2006 (No. 171)	Satisfaction 53	-
	Bouchard & Nauta, 2017 (No. 107)	Major satisfaction 15	-
	Gbadamosi, 2015 (No. 228)	Self-efficacy 68	-
Self-related factor	Gbadamosi et al., 2016 (No. 461) Sekiguchi, 2012 (No. 534)	Self-efficacy 28 Self-efficacy 30	- -
	Jackson & Wilton, 2017 (No. 554) Park & Sprung, 2015 (No. 805)	Self-awareness 11 Self-efficacy 74	- -
	Koeske & Koeske, 1989 (No. 843) Swanson et al., 2006 (No. 171)	Symptom 40 Stress 76	- -
Stress	Butler et al., 2010 (No. 102) Jogaratham & Buchanan, 2004 (No. 059)	Work stressor 25 Stress 48 Stressor 36	- - -
	Hammes & Haller 1983 (No. 435) Lee et al., 1999 (No. 752)	Strategies 6; Adjustment 3 Adaptation	Coping 29.28% coverage. Why students work 3.56% coverage.
	Swanson et al, 2006 (No. 171) Koeske & Koeske, 1989 (No. 843)	Adaptation 14 Social support 33	- -
	Winkler, 2008 (No. 713)	Social integration 10	-
Social relationship	Vaughn et al., 2016 (No. 104)	Workplace relationships 35	-
	McGregor, 2015 (No. 331)	Social activities 3 Social life 3	Impact on social life 0.98% coverage.
	Cheng & Alcántara, 2007 (No. 049)	-	Impact on social life and self-confidence 2.87% coverage.
	Pascarella et al., 1998 (No. 161)	Cognitive development 112	-
Cognitive outcomes			

Categories	Short title and item No.	Word frequency	Coverage rate
Personality	Cheng & Alcántara, 2007 (No. 049)	Perception /perceive 9	Perception on work 2.02% coverage.
	Jackson & Wilton, 2017 (No. 081)	Attitudes 108	-
	Bono et al., 2017 (No. 164)	Personality 26	-
Time spending	Swanson et al., 2006 (No. 171)	PA (i.e. positive affect) 32	-
	Teng, 2008 (No. 216)	Personality traits 43	-
	Nonis & Hudson, 2006 (No. 016)	Time spent 27	-
Substance usage	Greene & Maggs, 2015 (No. 622)	Time spent 34	-
	Butler et al., 2010 (No. 102)	Alcohol consumption 67 Alcohol expectancies 26	-
	Bono et al., 2017 (No. 164)	Alcohol use 22 Tobacco use 10	-
Other aspects	Hsiao, 2015 (No. 348)	Cheating behaviour 12	-
	Hall et al., 2015 (No. 224)	Cheating intention 45 Empathy 102	-
	Beauchamp et al., 2016 (No. 257)	Attachment style 84	-
	Bouchard & Nauta, 2017 (No. 107)	Work volition 74	-

3.3.3 Key Psychological Variables

3.3.3.1 Findings Based on Content Analysis

To further address the psychological content, a qualitative content analysis was conducted on the psychological variables that were mentioned in the final 36 articles. It focused on manifest content of various psychological variables studied in the articles. Overall, the findings indicate that there were a broad range of psychological factors involved in student employment. The analysis resulted in nine secondary categories based on more than 50 primary subcategories (see Table 14) and the detailed results of the content analysis on each article can be seen in Appendix 9.

In summary, the information in Table 14 shows that ‘emotion’ or the emotional consequences associated with student employment, was the mostly frequently addressed category within psychological factors. Within the category of emotion, seven sub-categories were identified and these were (in order of frequency): well-being and physical and mental health, satisfaction, stress, other positive emotions, other negative emotions, pressure/tension, and anxiety/depression. Considering the main aim of this thesis was to find the primary consequences of student employment as a negative impact, the negative emotions needed to be further reviewed in narrative synthesis (see 3.3.3.2). The second most frequently addressed category was ‘behaviour’ or behaviours of working students. Within this category, there were eight sub-categories and the most common ones were time spent on work, drinks/tobacco use,

and other activities. Within which, time spent occupied more than one third coding and absence usage took another two fifth. Time spent as a way of how students behaved also could be a way to tackle time. The third most frequently addressed category was ‘development’ of aspects. This included six sub-categories of which the most common was career aspirations, learning skills, and work experience. As a positive outcome, this category is not the primary interest of this project. Fourth highest category was social aspects including both social as majority aspect and self as minority aspect. With large codes supported research interest on social aspect, self may not be studied enough. Other categories included cognition, theory, and management/coping. Motivation was the least addressed. This could be due to lots of motivation studies combined with nature and extent investigation and may have been excluded in screen procedure.

This analysis highlights that psychological variables were important and salient enough to be studied further within student employment.

Table 14 Categories of Psychological Factors Addressed in Result Section

Sub-categories	Sub-category codes	Frequency coded	Percent in its category	Categories	Sub-total of Coding frequency	Sub-total percent in total coding			
Perception	PC1	67	35.64	Cognition	188	8.80			
Expectation	PC2	24	12.77						
Intention	PC3	32	17.02						
Decision making	PC4	45	23.94						
Judgement	PC5	14	7.45						
Other senses/cognitions	PC6	6	3.19						
Stress	PE1	73	16.70	Emotion	437	20.45			
Satisfaction	PE2	81	18.54						
Other positive emotions ¹⁵	PE3	62	14.19						
Well-being/Mental health	PE4a	45	10.30						
/Burnout									
Well-being/Physical health	PE4b	59	13.50						
Anxiety/Depression	PE5	29	6.64						
Pressure/ Tension	PE6	36	8.24						
Other Negative	PE7	41	9.38	Motivation	58	2.71			
Affection	PE8	11	2.52						
Motivation as drive	PM1	47	81.03	Behaviour	347	16.24			
Motivation as impact	PM2	11	18.97						
Drinks/tobacco	PB1	85	24.50						
Time spend	PB2	120	34.58						
Social/Cultural activities	PB3	15	4.32						
Expenditure	PB4	11	3.17						
Cheating	PB5	20	5.76						
Involvement in Work	PB6a	6	1.73						
Involvement in Study	PB6b	10	2.88						
Other activities	PB7	68	19.60						
Work/study related activities	PB8	12	3.46						
Social perception	PS1	20	7.55				Social aspects	265	12.40
Self-efficacy	PS2	47	17.74						
Self-theory/self	PS3	36	13.58						
Interpersonal relationships	PS4	94	35.47						
Socialization/ social life	PS5	36	13.58						
Social support	PS6	32	12.08						
Personality	PI1	65	26.32	Individual difference	247	11.56			
Attachment	PI2	59	23.89						
Attitude	PI3	77	31.17						
Value/Belief	PI4	32	12.96						
Ethic	PI5	10	4.05						
Ability	PI6	4	1.62						
Career /career aspiration	PD1	118	39.07	Development	302	14.13			
Skills learning	PD2	59	19.54						
Experience	PD3	58	19.21						
Cognition	PD4	47	15.56						
Challenge/Opportunity	PD5	5	1.66						
Academic achievement/knowledge	PD6	15	4.97						
General Management	MMC1	29	20.28	Management/coping	143	6.67			
Time management	MMC2	11	7.69						

¹⁵ Other emotions included Empathy, enjoyment, efficiency, confidence and others.

Sub-categories	Sub-category codes	Frequency coded	Percent in its category	Categories	Sub-total of Coding frequency	Sub-total percent in total coding
Coping	MMC3	10	6.99			
Control	MMC4	45	31.47			
Adjustment/ adaption	MMC5	34	23.78			
Strategy	MMC6	14	9.79			
Balance theory	TH1	16	10.67	Theory	150	7.02
Role theory	TH2	127	84.67			
Zero sum theory	TH3	6	4.00			
Other theory	TH4	1	0.67			

3.3.3.2 Narrative Synthesis of Key Psychological Factors

The above findings indicate that although psychological factors were often not the main aim of the 36 articles, they were still important considerations. However, because this conceptual content analysis can result in the loss of individual details from each article, narrative synthesis may function as a supplementary approach to provide more ecological information about how these psychological factors were discussed in the original articles. Therefore, in the following sections, the author presents a narrative of three important categories of psychological factors that were identified in the content analysis (stress and well-being, management and coping strategies, and self-aspect).

The reason for focusing on these three factors is to target the aims of the project (relating to Aim 3 of the whole thesis). The thesis set to find out the most salient psychological consequence within student employment and its related psychological factors. As the introduction of this chapter (see 3.1) indicates that stress and the related factors of self-aspect and coping strategies were argued of needing attention within student employment. Considering such argument and the synthesis of psychological factors in this chapter so far, it is wise to proceed a narrowed narrative synthesis on the specific three aspects. Reviewing the research evidence relating to these categories will provide a justification for whether it is appropriate to further investigate on these psychological factors in the next stage of the thesis.

3.3.3.2.1 Stress and Well-being

Within the emotion category, stress, well-being along with other negative emotions (such as anxiety/depression and pressure/tension) were frequently studied. Stress was studied under various variables headings including stress, stressors, and symptoms. At the level of the individual articles, this was supported by evidence of perceived stress (Swanson et al., 2006), symptoms (Koeske & Koeske, 1989), stressor (Jogaratham & Buchanan, 2004), and general mental health or well-being (Carney et al., 2005; Gbadamosi et al., 2016; Vaughn et al.,

2016). For example, Swanson et al. (2006) defined perceived stress using the popular Perceived Stress Scale (short version) and found that the number of hours that students worked were associated with psychological factors such as social role congruence, adjustment to university, psychological stress and personality traits. Comparisons between working and non-working students found that those “in employment reported more perceived stress than those not in employment” (p.9).

Prior to 2000, researchers had found that social support was an important factor that influenced how stress was perceived (Koeske & Koeske, 1989). Students with lower social support suffered more from somatic symptoms (e.g. headaches and upset stomach). The researchers also suggested that full time students with part-time jobs who had lower support, experienced a higher intensity of greater symptoms (Koeske & Koeske, 1989). Social support appears to act as a buffer, helping this group of students cope with distress. Jogaratnam and Buchanan (2004, p.241) identified that important stressors within student employment included: “time pressure”, “general social mistreatment”, “friendship problems”, “developmental challenge”, “academic alienation”, “romantic problems”, and “assorted annoyance”. The researchers also considered the impact of gender, year of study and full/part-time students, but failed to link this with any other psychological variables. What this discussion indicates is that there is still a lack of understanding of how students cope with the stress associated with student employment. As a result, this gap in knowledge will be addressed later in this thesis.

3.3.3.2.2 Coping and Management

The global category of management/coping was investigated under various labels including general management, time management, coping, control, strategies and adaption/adjustment (Bouchard & Nauta, 2017; Butler et al., 2010; Carney et al., 2005; Cheng & Alcántara, 2007; Hammes & Haller, 1983; Hsiao, 2015; Jackson & Wilton, 2016; Lee et al., 1999; Manthei & Gilmore, 2005; Sekiguchi, 2012; Swanson et al., 2006; Winkler, 2008). Within these articles the approach to coping may not be the most relevant in terms of everyday coping with employment (Jackson & Wilton, 2016) or in some cases the concept was not specifically studied (Winkler, 2008) or it was dealt with as a by-product of other main research interests such as career aspect or role theory (Swanson et al. 2006).

The more relevant studies investigated time management but did not necessarily approach this from a coping perspective. For instance, Manthei and Gilmore (2005) using regression

investigated time spent on three activities, study, work and leisure¹⁶. However, the numbers of hours per week spent on these three activities showed no statistical difference. This suggested that working students somehow managed to balance time for each of these activities. This result was in line with other studies which focused on how school students coped with employment by managing time commitments. Hammes and Haller (1983) used a mixed methods approach (questionnaire and interview) and found that to work, approximately 70% of students admitted reducing their leisure time, approximately 50% reduced their time spent socialising, and about 25% reduced their study time and re-directed this to work. They also found other strategies that students used to balance work with study. One common strategy was “to choose carefully the semesters in which to take employment” (p.531); this suggests that students regulated their scheduled work according to the course demands or workload. Another common strategy was to reduce the number of hours worked or to leave their jobs during times of high academic stress (e.g. exam, start/end of semester) to satisfy study demands.

Other studies also found working students sacrificed their “free time, sleep time, and time for socializing with friends” (Cheng & Alcántara, 2007, p.306), reorganised activity times (Greene & Maggs, 2015), and rescheduled their work (Hammes & Haller, 1983). In this study, however, such strategies only centred round time management which was only one coping aspect that working students adopted. These studies highlight the fact that students made strategic decisions about managing their time and utilised time management as a coping strategy. However, these studies also highlight the need to consider a wider set of strategies rather than focus solely on time management.

Several researchers also argued that working students used a variety of coping strategies to manage work and study (Sekiguchi, 2012; Swanson et al., 2006) as part of an overall strategy. Swanson et al. (2006) investigated adaption and adjustment but found no statistical difference “between students in employment or not in employment in terms of adaptation to university” (p.9). However, other researchers did find evidence for a link between employment and the coping strategy that was adopted. For example, Sekiguchi (2012) found ‘crafting’ (task crafting, relational crafting, and cognitive crafting) was used by students as a coping or management strategy. The term ‘crafting’ was defined by Wrzesniewski and Dutton (2001, p.179) as “the physical and cognitive changes individuals make in the task or

¹⁶ Leisure activity included “sport, recreational and cultural activities” (Manthei & Gilmore, 2005, p.205).

relational boundaries of their work” and by doing so students demonstrate how they proactively design their work. The research found that the length of part-time work (i.e. the number of months worked) significantly and positively impacted on job autonomy and job crafting. Given the lack of agreement in the research literature about the utility of different coping strategies, it would be beneficial for future research to explore strategies such as adjustment/adaptation and coping in more detail. In addition, since previous studies also neglected the association between stress-centred negative emotions and overall coping strategies which otherwise endorsed in adult workers (e.g. Saleem & Shah, 2011; Alqurashi, 2016), it would be useful to explore this within the context of part-time employment within an undergraduate population.

3.3.3.2.3 Self-aspects

Within the social aspects category in Table 14, the sub-categories included both social and self-characteristics. Researchers, such as Sekiguchi (2012), Gbadamosi et al. (2015), and Gbadamosi et al. (2016), investigated self-theory and self-efficacy in relation to student employment. Self-aspect was studied as self-efficacy in recovery, job searching, and team building. For example, Sekiguchi (2012) studied work experience and how this related to work-related variables and self-efficacy in career planning. He found that school grades positively correlated with career exploration and “self-efficacy in team-member proficiency” (p.15). They also found higher skill variety was associated with a stronger focus on career exploration and higher job search self-efficacy. These findings demonstrate that academic achievement and skills learning within employment, contribute to career self-efficacy and supports the function of self-efficacy and its close relationship to both work and study.

Furthermore, Gbadamosi et al. (2015) used self-theory to investigate work variables (beneficial work and career aspiration) and their relationship with self-efficacy in HE. Self-theory in this study was measured by two dimensions of fixed and malleable self-theories. They found self-efficacy positively predicted career aspiration and that higher malleable self-theories were associated with beneficial work and career aspiration (p.1086). These results indicate the value of using self-efficacy and self-theory when considering students work experience in HE.

In a related study (Gbadamosi et al., 2016) found self-efficacy significantly predicted beneficial work and along with gender, it also significantly predicted career aspiration. This study offered evidence of the role of self-efficacy in student work in HE in the context of Nigeria. Research has also shown significant associations between self-efficacy, perceived stress and coping

approaches however, this research was not conducted within the context of student employment (Anand, 2019; Delahaij & Van Dam, 2017; Gibbons, 2010; Glazer & Liu, 2017). This may be explained by the tendency of researchers to focus on the areas of nature and extent of employment or the impact of student employment on academic performance. Alternatively, it may reflect the desire to focus on the practical implications of student employment for careers. Whatever the explanation is, future studies are needed to discover the relationship between self-efficacy, perceived stress and coping approaches in the context of student employment.

3.4 Chapter Discussion

3.4.1 Summary of Findings and Contributions

This review provides an overview of psychological factors related to student employment. A systematic literature review was conducted to identify the psychological factors that have been highlighted within student employment research; these were then screened and appraised based on the research quality. This process identified 36 articles which were then reviewed using both narrative synthesis and qualitative conceptual content analysis. This review identified a number of important methodical issues within the published research including a lack of ecological designs such as longitudinal and mixed methods designs, a lack of psychometric scales for measuring psychological variables, and a lack of studies that specifically sampled populations within Scottish HEIs. The review also highlights that the main aims of previous studies were the impact of employment, career aspects and the nature and extent of student employment. Within the theme of the impact of employment, psychological factors were rarely studied and overall, there appeared to be a varied and scattered interest in psychological variables. These psychological variables were then identified under nine primary categories and over 50 sub-categories. Subsequent narrative synthesis identified three key psychological variables that seemed to be related and which would benefit from future research, namely stress, self-efficacy, and coping strategies.

To the author's knowledge, this systematic review is the first to focus solely on undergraduate employment and the potential psychological outcomes. It provides not only suggestions for the next stage of this thesis (see Section 3.4.3) but contributes to the existing knowledge of reviews in this area. This review has identified methodical issues in this area such as the over-dependence on *ad hoc* scales necessitating the use of established psychometric scales to assess psychological variables in future studies. It also found that the

relationship between student employment and important psychological variables needs further research within Scotland's HE sectors.

3.4.2 Strength and Limitation

3.4.2.1 Strengths

One of the strengths of this review was its systematic approach. Each step was clearly defined and documented and the review was executed rigorously and transparently reported. The researcher also considered the risks of bias and was cautious of quality control. The risk of bias and quality control ought to be considered using any approach of synthesis within a systematic review (Drucker et al., 2016). The risk of bias in this review was minimised through using multiple search strategies. Searches were conducted across 17 data sources that covered academic data bases and the grey literature. Moreover, the review did not limit language and year of publication at the initial search stage. These strategies minimised publication bias. Secondly, this review used a quality appraisal tool (CCAT) to filter the final set of research articles based on research quality. This procedure minimised the potential bias of including low quality research literature. Thirdly, this review carefully adopted appropriate synthesis methods, both narrative synthesis and qualitative synthesis using content analysis. This dual synthesis approach facilitated the generalisability of the information and key highlights within the content of the studies.

3.4.2.2 Limitations

However, it is important to note several limitations regarding this review when interpreting its findings. Firstly, the review was limited to articles available on the searched databases before May 2017 and therefore articles published after this date were not included. Secondly, during the screening process some articles were excluded as these were not available in English and some full texts could not be accessed. The screening process itself reflected the current interest in psychological variables within student employment meaning that many articles regarding nature and extent, or academic impact of working were excluded. It is possible that some of these articles could have included useful information on psychological variables. This could also be the case for those articles that failed to meet the CCAT quality threshold of $\geq 75\%$ quality scores.

Thirdly, although the research took a cautious approach with respect to quality control, there is nevertheless a risk of bias within content analysis during the process of classification (Cho & Lee, 2014). During this process it is possible that different researchers might classify the

same evidence differently. Inevitably, this researcher's own "subjectivities, personalities, and predispositions" (Sipe, 2004, p.483) might influence how content analysis is conducted. Additionally, as a PhD project, the quality check can only be executed within the supervisor team. Despite conducting a reliability analysis process with all members of the supervisory team and achieving a reliability rate of 78%, this was based on a review of only 10% of all the articles at this stage rather than the entire body of articles.

3.4.3 Next Steps

Firstly, the section of the narrative synthesis that focused on methods and methodology in final articles revealed that few published studies have adopted a mixed methods approach, longitudinal studies nor ecological designs. These issues should be addressed in future research. Secondly, few studies utilised established psychometric scales that are appropriate to operationally define psychological variables. This suggests the need for employing appropriate measures of psychological variables in future research. Thirdly, very few studies were conducted within Scotland; this is an important knowledge gap especially considering research suggests that Scottish students may have different attitudes to work compared with other parts of the UK (Josiam et al., 2010). It would therefore be valuable to conduct future research within a Scottish HE student population given the differences that exist within the HE environment (e.g. financing of HE, education policy) in Scotland compared to the rest of the UK.

In summary, this review found that the primary aims of studies identified in the literature review focused on the impact of student employment (including academic achievement), career related outcomes associated with student employment and identifying the nature and extent of student employment.

In terms of the psychological variables that were highlighted in the narrative synthesis, this review found that the most frequently mentioned category was 'emotions'. This included sub-categories such as stress and well-being. These studies covered aspects including stressors, health symptoms, sleep quality, fatigue, well-being (including mental health) and other negative emotions. This review found an association between stress-centred negative emotions and work characteristics. However, at the same time, a few studies focused on important psychological factors such as coping strategies and self-efficacy. Studies that focused on the amount of time spent working and studying suggested that students deployed coping strategies such as time management. These studies however, failed to link coping strategies to stress-centred negative emotions. The final category of psychological variables

was the self-aspect and studies here highlighted the involvement of self-efficacy and possible broad self-theory in student employment. Therefore, this review suggests that the psychological variables (stress, coping/management and self-efficacy) appear to be related. This possible relationship would be explored in this thesis.

3.5 Chapter Conclusion

This systematic review has identified 36 high quality research articles. Subsequent analyses of these articles have focused on the methods employed, the primary aims as well as relevant psychological variables related to student work. Overall, the review highlights the need for a study based on a Scottish sample of students along with certain methodical recommendations for next stage of this project. The methodical recommendations include (i) a focus on three key psychological factors (stress, self-efficacy and coping strategies), (ii) the use of a longitudinal design and mixed methods design and (iii) a reliable and valid measurement of psychological variables through the use of psychometric scales.

CHAPTER 4 STUDENT EMPLOYMENT SURVEY 2019

This chapter presents the findings from the first student survey (Survey 1) as Study 2. Study 2 was based on one case of the specific HEI in central and western Scotland as designed. The findings from this survey address Aims 2, 3 and 4 of the thesis and more specifically will: (i) provide information on the nature and extent of student employment in 2019; (ii) explore changes in the nature and extent of student employment; (iii) investigate the link between student employment and internal psychological factors. Additionally, Study 2 provides snapshots of the dynamic copings adopted by HE students to manage their education and work roles.

The chapter initially explains the need for a quantitative survey. The study material, procedure and analysis method are outlined along with the results from Study 2. The final section of the chapter discusses the implications of Study 2 and provides a chapter conclusion.

4.1 Introduction

The rationale for this quantitative investigation of student employment is based on the findings from the systematic review (Chapter 3). The systematic review identified three reasons to support the need for a quantitative study.

First, based on a review of the 36 empirical studies, it was argued that there was a need for contemporary information on the nature and extent of student employment. The review found that most previous studies in this area were conducted in the US or in the UK. In contrast, studies in Scotland accounted for less than one tenth (8.33%). As this project emphasised that Scotland has its own specific economic, cultural and educational atmosphere and context (Chapter 1), a new study conducted in Scotland will contribute to existing knowledge of student employment by providing a sample in one post-92 Scottish HEI. Additionally, the systematic review found that few studies were able to focus on changes in the nature and extent of employment over time. This project seeks to address this gap by comparing its result to a 1998 study (McKechnie et al.) conducted in the same post-92 HEI as the present study. The 1998 study sampled more than 1000 participants across five faculties. While the current project is taking place in the same HEI it must be noted that the HEI context has changed over the last 20 years. The present study was conducted 12 years after the HEI was

granted university status and the faculty/school structure has since changed. Despite these changes the current study argues that there is value in comparing the findings between the year 1998 and 2019.

Second, the systematic review revealed the relationship between work variables (including quantity and quality of employment) to broad but scattered and poorly operationalised psychological outcomes. The review found that the association between employment and psychological outcomes was relatively neglected and/or reported as a by-product of the main studies concern (e.g. nature and extent of employment, career aspects or impact to academic achievement). This finding formed the second aim of the survey which was to focus on the association of employment with psychological outcomes. The systematic review also identified which psychological variables should be considered. The review highlighted several key psychological aspects including self-aspect, time coping/management and stress (Dakas, 2011; Jogaratnam & Buchanan, 2004; Koeske & Koeske, 1989), symptoms (Koeske & Koeske, 1989) and well-being (Carney et al., 2005; Park & Sprung, 2015; Vaughn et al., 2016). Combined with inspiration from the dominant theories and discussion in Chapter 3, the review identified three primary factors of stress, self-efficacy and coping as having underpinned various theories in this area and that had been repeatedly studied. However, previous studies had not always used robust psychometric tools to assess these concepts, and this would be addressed within the present study.

Third, the systematic review clarified the methodology for this stage in the project, namely, to use a longitudinal design or mixed methods design. The systematic review showed that longitudinal designs were seldom used in previous studies due to the drawbacks of time commitment and the loss of participants. An accelerated longitudinal design (Bell, 1954; Farrington, 1991) in a short time may overcome such shortcomings. Additionally, the review indicated that previous research benefited from the use of a combination of *ad hoc* and psychometric scales and this study will adopt this approach.

In summary, a new study of student employment will provide contemporary data on the nature and extent of student employment within a Scottish context. This will also provide comparative data to consider changes in employment between two time periods.

Additionally, the neglected relationship between work and psychological elements (stress, self-efficacy and coping) could also be robustly investigated by using appropriate robust assessment tools.

This study aims to address three research questions:

- (i) What is the nature and extent of student employment in 2019?
- (ii) How does the nature and extent of contemporary student employment compare with previous studies?
- (iii) What is the relationship between employment (namely employment status and type of job) and psychological outcomes?

4.2 Methods

This section outlines research design, participants, survey material and assessment tools, procedures, operational definitions, analysis method and ethical considerations of Study 2.

4.2.1 Design

This study adopted a cross-section survey design, but it is also the first survey in a short-term longitudinal design (in 2019 Chapter 4 and 2021 Chapter 5 separately) and serves as quantitative part of the mixed methods design. The study used an online questionnaire survey and sought to gather information on the nature and extent of student employment in 2019 and three psychological outcomes.

4.2.2 Participants

The sample was sourced from the five academic Schools within a Scottish, post-92 HEI, situated in central and western Scotland. In total there were 991 initial participants who accessed the e-survey. Within them, 164 participants were excluded as they did not meet the participant criteria. This included 9 participants (0.9%) who indicated they did not want to participate, 106 participants who withdrew (10.6%) and 30 participants were excluded as they were postgraduate students (3.0%). Additionally, 19 participants (1.9%) were excluded since they were registered as part-time students.

Responses from 83.45% (N=827) of the participants were thus included finally. They were all full-time undergraduates with an average age of 25.88 years with a standard deviation of 8.19. The age of participants ranged from 17 to 58 years old. Nearly three-quarters of participants were females (n=615, 74.37%) and one-quarter males (n=204, 24.77%). Other gender participants were less than 1% (n=8, 0.86%). The distribution of participants was not equally distributed across schools due to convenient sampling based on volunteers. The distribution of participants across schools is detailed in Table 15. Slightly less than one third (31.56%) of participants came from the School of Media Culture and Society and this was

matched by participants from Health Life (30.71%). More than 10% of participants came from the School of Business and the School of Computing Enterprise and Physical Science. The School of Education was the least represented with 7.98% of participants¹⁷.

Table 15 also summarised the percentage of students from each academic year with approximately one third from either Year 2 (n=240, 29.02%) or Year 3 (n=278, 33.62%). Slightly more than one fifth were in Year 4 (n=185, 22.37%) but only 15% were from Year 1 (n= 124, 14.99%). The majority of students were home students (n=757, 91.54%) with 5% from the EU (n=52, 6.29%). Approximately 1% were from other parts of UK or from overseas as international students.

Table 15 Profiles of Participants (Study 2)

Academic variable	Sub-type	Frequency	Percent
School of course	Media Culture and Society	261	31.56
	Health Life	254	30.71
	Business	138	16.69
	Computing Enterprise Physical science	106	12.82
	Education	66	7.98
	Not sure	2	.24
Year of study	Year 1	124	14.99
	Year 2	240	29.02
	Year 3	278	33.62
	Year 4	185	22.37
Student status	Home student (Scotland)	757	91.54
	EU student	52	6.29
	Student from other parts of UK (England, Wales and Northern Ireland)	10	1.21
	Non-EU/International Student	8	.97
	Total	827	100.0

4.2.3 Measures

The online survey (Appendix 10) consisted of five sections. Section one focuses on the nature and extent of undergraduates' part-time employment. The 1998 survey by McKechnie et al. (1998) was adapted to allow for the collection of comparable information across two decades. The adaptations involved updating terminology relating to funding to reflect the current funding systems. This section also included questions relating to student demographic information, funding and family situation, work situation, reason for work, and impact on study. Information was also collected about students' typical work pattern over seven days. Section two focuses on the assessment of stress and the Student Stress Inventory (SSI) (Arip et al., 2015) consisting of 40 items was used. Cronbach's alpha for all the scales was greater

¹⁷ There was also a category of Not sure (n=2, 0.24%) due to the obscurity information provided by two participants.

than 0.7. The SSI were tested in university environments in Peninsular Malaysia (Abdullah & Dan, 2011; Arip et al., 2015) and other cultures as well. It was reported as having a high content validity of .805 and an overall reliability coefficient of .857 (Arip et al., 2015). The scale consisted of four subscales, each consisting of 10 items. These were physical factor, interpersonal relationship factor, academic factor and environmental factor (Arip et al., 2015). Each subscale score ranged from 10-40. Combining the scores from each subscale produced the total stress score. The total score of SSI ranged from 40-160. Total scores were divided into three categories: mild (40-80), moderate (81-121) and severe stress (122-160).

Section three of the survey assesses self-efficacy. The Student Self-Efficacy Scale (SSE) was used to assess this variable. The SSE consisted of 10 items with each item scored by a four-point Likert scale ('*Not at all true*', '*hardly true*', '*moderately true*', and '*Exactly true*'). The initial Cronbach Alpha was identified as .84 (Rowbotham & Schmitz, 2013) and in another applied study it was .81 (Rowbotham & Owen, 2015).

Section four focuses on the assessment of coping strategies. The Coping Strategies Inventory short form (32 Item) (CSI-32) (Tobin et al., 1984a) was used for this project. Each item in this scale was scored on a five-point Likert scale ('*Not at all*', '*A little*', '*Somewhat*', '*Much*', and '*Very much*'). This inventory used norms from college students, and it merges self-reporting and other measurements of stress (Tobin et al., 1989). That scale consisted of eight primary subscales each comprising four items. The subscales were: 'problem-solving', 'cognitive restructuring', 'express emotions', 'social contact', 'problem avoidance', 'wishful thinking', 'self-criticism' and 'social withdrawal' (Tobin et al., 1984b; Tobin et al., 1989). The Cronbach alpha average score of the eight primary subscales was .70.

The primary subscales when combined in pairs produce four secondary subscales that were: problem-focused engagement, emotion-focused engagement, problem-focused disengagement and emotion-focused disengagement. The Cronbach alpha average of these four secondary subscales was .80. Speyer et al. (2016) reported a high internal consistency ($\alpha=0.56-0.80$) 'for three scales' in various language (p.12). Consistency for the fourth scale was not ideal, however, the factor structure consistent was good in all four scales (Speyer et al., 2016).

Combining the secondary subscales in pairs produced two tertiary subscales: the engagement tertiary subscale and the disengagement tertiary subscale. The α average of these two tertiary subscales was .90. The use and reporting of these scales varied across studies that had used

this psychometric tool¹⁸. In this study, to focus on the coping strategies as far as possible, the primary subscales were prioritised. However, in some instances secondary and tertiary level subscales were used.

The final section of the survey informed participants the survey was about to end and to recruit volunteers for potential future research.

4.2.4 Procedures

4.2.4.1 *Distribution of Recruitment and Advertisement*

The e-survey advertisement was circulated by professional staff from the ITDS team using the student banner system. The use of a third party to distribute the survey advertisement was in line with GDPR. The advertisement was sent to 15,103 undergraduates at three time points, namely, 13th March 2019, 27th March 2019 and 16th April 2019. The survey was distributed across the four Scottish campuses of this HEI. The total number of students contacted on each campus was 8081, 4142, 2492 and 388. The same advertisement was also posted on social media (Facebook) by sharing in the closed group for research participants within the HEI. The survey was displayed using the online platform ‘eSurvey Creator’ (eSurvey Creator, 2019). It was opened at 23:00, 12th March 2019 and closed at 23:00, 26th April 2019.

4.2.4.2 *Data Preparation: Cleaning Process, Scoring and Transfer*

The raw data, especially that relating to ‘course title’ and ‘job title’, was cleaned. This was carried out according to clearly stated criteria. Each stage in the process was documented. Total score and sub-scores, if applicable, were calculated for the three standardised measures of SSI, SSE and CSI-32. The final, cleaned data was transferred from excel to IBM SPSS v25.0 after defining the data value as one key procedure of SPSS.

4.2.5 Operational Definition

4.2.5.1 *Time Period*

The ‘current time’ refers to the time that the survey was conducted (18th March to 26th April 2019). Correspondingly, ‘term 1’ refers to the term before that is 3rd September to 15th

¹⁸ Previous studies either used combination of both secondary and tertiary scales in the analysis (Addison et al., 2007) or combination of primary and secondary scales (Poudel-Tandukar et al., 2020). Or they only used one level scales such as tertiary scales (Asturias et al., 2021), secondary scales (Hooberman et al., 2010) and primary scales (Pidgeon et al., 2015; Anuar et al., 2019).

December 2018. 'Summer 2018' refers to June, July and August 2018. '2017/2018' means from term one of 2017/2018 to term three, i.e. September 2017-August 2018.

4.2.5.2 Student

In this thesis, the term 'student' refers to full-time undergraduate students. Undergraduate also defines the level of study from Level 7 to 10 in the Scottish Credit and Qualifications Framework (SCQF) or from 1st to 4th year. This means that students studying at pre-university and postgraduate level were excluded from the survey as were undergraduates who were registered as part-time students.

4.2.5.3 Employment Variables

Based on previous literature, this study focuses on considering the quantity and quality of employment. Traditionally, work status has been classified as current workers, former workers and never worked. In this study, to capture the quantity of work the weekly working hours of current workers was taken into account. Employment status therefore consisted of five categories- current workers (low, medium and high hours worked), former workers and never worked.

According to previous literature, hours worked per week has been classified into low/medium/high hours according to the most used cut off points: 10 hours and 20 hours. Low hours equate with working less than or equal to 10 hours per week. Medium hours is considered to be more than 10 hours but less than 20 hours per week. High hours is defined as working 20 or more hours per week. The term 'former worker' applies to students who had worked in the past but did not work at the time of the study, while 'never worked' refers to those students who had never worked at any time point of the time period this study investigated.

In this study the quality of employment was indicated by use of a proxy, namely job type. Studies have varied in their categorisation of 'job type'. However, to compare the current findings with McKechnie et al.'s 1998 study, this project adopted the same definition used in that 1998 study. Hence 'type of job' was classified into six categories: 'hotel and catering', 'bar work', 'shop work and sale', 'admin and finance', 'social care', and 'other'.

4.2.5.4 Key Psychological Variables

Stress - In total there are five indicators representing stress at two levels. At the overall level, one indicator was the total score of the Student Stress Inventory (SSI) (Arip et al., 2015). At the sub-scale level four indicators, representing the four subscales of the SSI, were used and

they were: physical stress, interpersonal relationship stress, academic stress and environmental stress.

Self-efficacy - There is one indicator of self-efficacy and that is the participants total score on the Student Self-Efficacy Scale (SSE) (Rowbotham & Schmitz, 2013). Scores can range from 10-40.

Coping Strategy - In total there are 14 indicators for coping strategy. Seven (score from four primary, two secondary, and one tertiary subscales) each for engagement and disengagement strategy respectively (Tobin et al., 1984a). Engagement indicators include scores of four primary subscale (problem-solving, cognitive restructuring, express emotions and social contact), scores of two secondary subscales (problem-focused engagement and emotion-focused engagement, and score of engagement tertiary subscale. Similarly, disengagement indicators include scores of four primary subscales (problem avoidance, wishful thinking, self-criticism and social withdrawal), scores of two secondary subscales (problem-focused disengagement and emotion-focused disengagement), and score of disengagement tertiary subscale. The eight primary subscales score from 4-20. Four secondary subscales score 8-40. Two tertiary subscales score 16-80.

4.2.6 Analysis

Analysis was undertaken using IBM SPSS Statistics v25. Basic analysis of frequency, percentage and descriptive statistics were conducted. Inferential statistics were also generated on the work variables (i.e. work status, weekly hours worked and type of job) and psychological variables (i.e. score of SSI, SSE and CSI-32). This included ANOVA¹⁹ or other alternative robust tests (i.e. Welsh and Brown-Forsythe test) and general linear regression model using either univariate or multivariate approaches.

4.2.7 Ethics

An ethics application was submitted and proved by MCS²⁰ Ethics Committee in March 2019 (Ethic approval letter see Appendix 11 and Appendices 12-14).

¹⁹ Analysis of variance (ANOVA) provided the statistical significance of a psychological variable across various employment patterns. A significant result of ANOVA demonstrated a difference between groups is larger enough than the individual difference statistically. A significant result represents that “at least one of the population means” of several “groups is different” (Kim, 2017, p.23).

²⁰ MCS represents School of Media, Culture and Society.

4.3 Result One: Nature and Extent of Undergraduates' Employment in 2019

The results in this section provide empirical information regarding the nature and extent of student employment. This section addresses the first aim of this study, namely, what is the nature and extent of student employment in 2019?

4.3.1 Prevalence of Student Employment

Based on the survey results approximately 70% of current students have worked. This was based on the four time periods covered within the data collection (see Table 16), i.e. currently, in term 1, during summer 2018 and 2017/2018. As Table 16 shows at the time of the survey the majority of students currently work (n=609; 73.7%) while by way of contrast, there were just more than a quarter of students (n=217; 26.3%) who did not work at the time of the study.

Table 16 Percentage of Undergraduates' Employment in Scotland (Study 2)

Employment	Current Time		Term One		Summer 2018		2017/2018		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Working	609	73.7	451	70.1	479	74.6	410	69.3	1949	72.1
Not Working	217	26.3	192	29.9	163	25.4	182	30.7	754	27.9
Total	826	100	643	100	642	100	592	100	2703	100

Note: One participant could report work during any point of the four time periods.

The findings from the survey also show that during the current time and summer-time periods a higher proportion of students worked. During the summer period there is less pressure on students to study or to engage in coursework. It is at this time that the highest percentage of students worked. Current time (March to April 2019) is term 2 in the academic calendar which was less busy than term 1 in terms of study demand. During the current time, students work 3.7% more than term 1. The percentage of students reporting that they worked in 2017/2018 dropped slightly compared to the current time.

4.3.2 Number of Hours Worked

In their current job, students worked on average 17.53 hours with a standard deviation of 7.74. The mean is the lowest across the four time periods in this study. The minimum hours worked was reported as 2 hours per week, with the maximum figure being 40 hours per week. The average weekly working hours were calculated at four time periods: currently, in term 1, summer 2018 and 2017/2018. Across the four time periods undergraduates worked on

average 19.54 hours weekly with a standard deviation of 8.88 and a range from 2 to 55 (see Table 17, average based on data of all four time periods). Students worked more than 20 hours weekly during summer 2018 (M=24.70, SD=11.10) which is the highest weekly working hours amongst the four data collection periods. During Term 1 and 2017/2018, they worked 17.86 or 18.05 hours per week, this is six hours less than summer 2018. Students' weekly hours of work are greater in summertime.

Summer 2018 job had the largest standard deviation which was more than 11 hours with a wide range from 3 hours to 55 hours. For the 2017/2018 period the standard deviation was more than 8.5 with a range of 2 hours to 48 hours. Current and term 1 time periods were similar in that both had a standard deviation which was roughly 8 with a similar range of 2 hours to 40 hours. This pattern suggests that during the summer period students seek to maximise working hours, alternatively it could be that employers make greater use of student employees during the summertime. The median hours worked for summer 2018 is the highest with more than 20 hours and during the other three time periods the median is 8 hours lower. The mode for summer 2018 job was 30 hours the highest. During the other three time periods the median was 14 hours less. This demonstrated that most frequently students work for 16 hours per week during current time, term 1 and 2017/2018. During the summertime period, the figure was 30 hours weekly.

Table 17 Descriptive Statistics of Weekly Hours Worked (Study 2)

Employment	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Median	Mode
Current job	437	2.00	40.00	17.53	7.74	16	16
Term 1 job	338	2.00	40.00	17.86	7.97	16	16
Summer 2018 Job	375	3.00	55.00	24.70	11.10	24	30
2017/2018 Job	309	2.00	48.00	18.05	8.70	16	16
Summary	365	2.00	55.00	19.54*	8.88*	--	--

Note: * = average

4.3.3 Type of Job

In this section the type of jobs that students worked currently, in term 1, summer 2018 and 2017/2018 is considered.

Table 18 summarises the findings and shows that 'shop work and sales' was the most popular type of job with just under one third of participants working in this category. 'Social care' follows this with slightly less than one third of students employed in this type of job. One fifth of participants work in the category 'Other' work. The latter category was used to

capture the wide range of jobs that students reported but which employed a small number of students in each type of job. The ‘other’ work category includes a wide range of jobs including security jobs such as ‘Security Steward’, sports job including sport ‘coach’ and ‘Trainer’, events and leisure industry jobs such as ‘Leisure attendant’ and ‘Cinema Host’, hair and beauty advisor or assistant, lab jobs such as ‘Laboratory Analyst’, factory workers such as ‘Kennel worker’, cleaner and sessional worker. More than one tenth of participants worked in ‘Hotel and catering’ jobs while under one tenth worked in ‘Admin and finance’. ‘Bar work’ was the least popular category with just over 5% of students employed in this type of job.

Across all four time periods, the same distribution of job categories was found (See Table 18). ‘Shop work and sale’, ‘social care’ and ‘other’ work were the top three work sectors, in contrast, ‘bar work’, ‘Admin and finance’ and ‘Hotel and catering’ were the three lowest work sectors. ‘Shop work and sales’ was the most popular and ‘bar work’ was the least popular.

Table 18 Frequency and percentage of Current, Term 1, Summer 2018 and 2017/2018 Job

Type of Job	Current Job		Term 1 Job		Summer 2018		2017/2018		Average
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	%
Bar work	23	5.07	24	6.67	19	4.77	18	5.36	5.47
Admin and finance	33	7.27	24	6.67	36	9.05	22	6.55	7.39
Hotel and catering	47	10.35	37	10.28	49	12.31	51	15.18	12.03
Other	91	20.04	73	20.28	91	22.86	71	21.13	21.08
Social care	128	28.19	88	24.44	85	21.36	70	20.83	23.71
Shop work and sales	132	29.08	114	31.67	118	29.65	104	30.95	30.34
Total	454	100	360	100	398	100	336	100	100

Across the four time periods it is noticeable that the percentage of employment is relatively stable in several job categories e.g. bar work, admin and finance, shop work. However, in the two categories there was some evidence of variation in employment levels. In the case of ‘social care’ comparing 2017/18 levels of employment with the ‘current time’ period a higher percentage of students were found to be employed in this sector. In contrast ‘hotel and catering’ tended to decline in terms of the percentage of students employed.

4.3.4 Pay Rate

Based on the information provided by undergraduates who reported that they were currently the average rate of pay was £8.94 per hour. The minimum pay reported was £5.00 per hour,

whereas the maximum pay was £27.50 per hour. The standard deviation of pay rate was £2.83. The average pay rate is slightly higher than the National Minimum Wage (NMW)²¹, with the minimum pay being nearly £1 lower than NMW for 18 to 20 years old, while the maximum pay rate reported was considerably higher than NMW.

The data indicate that the hourly rate of pay increased over time from 2017/18 and this probably reflects changes in the NMW. Pay rates increased by approximately 20 pence per time period (see Table 19). As Table 19 shows the mean hourly rate of pay varied across the different time periods and the greatest degree of variation is to be found in the minimum rates of pay, with the lowest reported hourly rate found in the Summer 2018 period.

The standard deviation of hourly pay rate for each period are comparable which means that during each period the difference of individual pay rate varied little. However, at around £2.50 this variation equates with approximately one quarter of the hourly pay which is not small suggesting that within one period individuals' earnings could vary quite a lot.

Table 19 Descriptive Statistics of Rate of Pay (Unit £) (Study 2)

Employment	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Median	Mode
Current job	439	5.00	27.50	8.94	2.83	8.50	8.75
Term 1	340	5.50	26.93	8.71	2.73	8.31	8.00
Summer 2018	372	2.70	27.50	8.52	2.73	8.10	8.00
2017/2018 Job	311	4.05	27.50	8.31	2.60	8.00	7.50
Average	366	4.31	27.36	8.62	2.72	--	--

4.3.5 Summary of Nature and Extent of Student Employment

In summary, the prevalence of student employment in Scotland (70%) is similar to England and other countries. Student employment can be considered to be the norm for students in 2019. The findings demonstrate that Scottish students work up to nearly 20 hours per week and are employed in a range of job types. Across the four time periods, one-third worked in 'shop work and sales', while 20% or more students worked in 'social care' and 'other' jobs. Approximately, 10% of students were found to work in the 'hotel and catering' sector. A smaller number of students, less than 10%, worked in 'admin and finance' or 'bar work'. There is some indication of changing patterns of employment across the time periods.

²¹ The national minimum wage (NMW) for those aged 25 or over was £7.83 from Apr. 2018 till Mar. 2019 and raised to £8.21 since Apr. 2019 to Mar. 2020. For those aged 18 to 20, the NMW was £5.90 from Apr. 2018 till Mar. 2019 and raised to £6.15 since Apr. 2019 to Mar. 2020 (UK government, 2022).

On average, student workers' hourly pay rates were £8.62 with a £2.70 standard deviation. There is a great degree of variation in the maximum and minimum rates of £2.70 to £27.50 per hour. The latter case can be an outlier as it represents a student working in a specialised role involving safeguarding children.

4.4 Result Two: Comparison of Nature and Extent of Employment between 1998 and 2019

The results from the present survey were compared with those from a 1998 study which took place in the same HEI (McKechnie et al., 1998). This comparison allows us to consider the second research question namely, (ii) how does the nature and extent of contemporary student employment compare with previous studies? This additionally will address the latter part of Aim 2 of the whole thesis and in doing so add to our understanding of potential changes to employment over time.

4.4.1 Prevalence of Employment

The results from the present study indicate that the number of students currently working was approximately 70%. The 1998 study by McKechnie et al. (1998, p.31) reported that “just under half” of participants were employed. The same study reported that more than half (54%) of Year 1 were employed, which was “higher than other year group” (p.31). This suggests that contemporary undergraduates are more likely to work while studying full-time in HE compared to 20 years ago. From a longitudinal perspective, the proportion of students participating in term-time employment would appear to have increased over time and can be considered to be the norm for HE students.

McKechnie et al. (1998) found that 23% of participants (n=397) never worked, 34% (n=591) were consistent workers and 22% (n=377) were intermittent workers. There were also 21% students (n=352) who only worked during the summer vacation period. Table 20 provides a summary of the comparison between 2019 and 1998.

The comparison reveals several changes in employment. First, as previously noted, a higher percentage of students now work during term-time whilst attending HE. When the patterns of employment are considered, the percentage of students who never worked whilst studying has declined (15.33% vs 23%) and a higher percentage of students consistently work across the year (40.75% vs 34%). The greatest change would appear to be in the categories of intermittent and summer/vacation workers. In the former case a higher percentage of students were classified as intermittent workers compared to 1998 (41.73% vs 22%) whilst the

percentage of students who restricted their employment experiences to the summer vacation period showed decreased (2.19% vs 21%).

Table 20 Percentage of Work History 2019 vs 1998*

Work History	2019 (N=822)		1998 (N=1717)		Percentage Difference
	n	%	n	%	%
Intermittent worker	343	41.73	377	22	19.73
Consistent worker	335	40.75	591	34	6.75
Summer worker	18	2.19	352	21	-18.81
Never worked	126	15.33	397	23	-7.67

Note: * 2019 is this the current study; 1998 refers to McKechnie et al.'s. (1998) study.

4.4.2 Working Hours

In 1998 (McKechnie et al.), students from Year 2 to Year 5 worked for an average of 14.30 hours per week, however the study also showed that a minority of students worked in excess of 20 hours per week (p.34). The present study found that amongst those currently working the average weekly hours were 17.53. This would suggest a degree of comparability in average work hours between the two studies or a modest increase at best.

4.4.3 Type of Job

The results from the present study, one-third of students working in shop and sale work and 10% work in bar work, are slightly lower than that found in 1998 study. Table 21 summarises the comparisons between the studies. Employment in the social care sector job increased by nearly 18% and those working in the 'Other' category increased by 6%. While there is a slight increase in those working in the 'admin and finance' category there appears to have been a decline in both 'shop work/sales' and 'bar work'.

Table 21 Percentage of Sectors as Type of Job 2019 vs 1998*

Type of Job	2019 Average %	1998 %	Percentage Difference
Bar work	5.50	18	-12.5
Admin and finance	7.38	5	2.38
Hotel and catering	12.05	13	-0.95
Other	21.08	15	6.08
Social care	23.70	6	17.7
Shop work and sales	30.35	43	-12.65

Note: *1998 study refers to study of McKechnie et al. (1998).

4.4.4 Pay Rate

In 1998 McKechnie et al. (1998) reported that the hourly pay rate for students was £3.72. At the time of that study the NMW had not been introduced²². However, considering the impact of inflation over this period, the variation in pay levels between the two studies is relatively small.

4.4.5 Summary of Comparison between 2019 and 1998

In summary, the comparison between the two studies which were carried out in the same institution 20 years apart indicates that the level of participation in employment amongst HE students has increased over time. The work patterns indicate that there has been a decline in the number of students who opt to work during vacation time in the summer and this is replaced with an increase in consistent and intermittent workers. It is worth noting that the rise in the latter is considerable. This is in line with the argument that term-time employment is now the norm for HE students (Broadbridge & Swanson, 2006; Robotham, 2009)²³.

The other notable finding from this comparison is linked to the types of work that students undertake. The data suggests that while ‘shop work and sales’ is still the dominant sector other areas are declining e.g. ‘bar work’. In addition, there is considerable growth in some sectors most notably ‘social care’. This might reflect changes in the labour market and this will be explored more fully in the discussion.

4.5 Results Three: Difference of Psychological Factors Accounted by Quantity and Quality of Employment

A key focus for this project is to explore the relationship between part-time work and a range of psychological variables. The results in this section address research question (iii) what is the relationship between employment (namely employment status and type of job) and psychological outcomes? In the context of the whole thesis, this section serves to Aim 3 by providing insight into the link between psychological factors and part-time employment. Additionally, findings of coping strategies also provide snapshots information of coping

²² The National Minimum Wage Act 1998 was published on 31st July 1998. It legislated the basic pay for the working workers. It specified those who “has ceased to be of compulsory school age” (Open government, 2011) should be paid NMW.

²³ The citations followed demonstrated the trend of term-time employment is dominant norm: “Term-time employment is becoming the norm for students in higher education in the UK, a pattern following the US.” (Broadbridge & Swanson, 2006) “working part-time is increasingly becoming the norm among higher education students”. (Robotham, 2009, p.325)

strategies for Aim 4. This section provides an overview of working students' level of stress, coping strategy and self-efficacy within the context of quantity and quality of employment, i.e. employment status and type of job. This is followed by the presentation of the inferential analyses to consider the potential association between the quantity and quality of employment and the psychological outcomes. The employment status was designed to include quantity of employment by categorizing students as: current worker - high hours, medium hours, low hours; former worker and never worked. The type of job was utilised as a proxy of quality of employment.

4.5.1 Stress

4.5.1.1 Employment Status with Stress

Table 22 provides a summary of the descriptive statistics for the stress scores. The average total stress score is 79.66 with a standard deviation of 17.62 and a range from 40 to 134. This indicates a mild stress level for the participating students (Arip et al., 2015), however, it is at the upper end of scale and close to meeting the criteria to be classed as moderate levels of stress.

Table 22 Descriptive Statistics of Stress across Employment Status

Psychological Outcomes	Employment Status	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Physical stress (SSI subscale score 1)	Low hours	61	19.87	5.11	10.00	31.00
	Medium hours	209	20.55	5.33	10.00	35.00
	High hours	162	21.31	5.32	10.00	36.00
	Former worker	88	20.56	5.07	10.00	34.00
	Never worked	96	19.92	5.90	10.00	32.00
	Total	616	20.58	5.37	10.00	36.00
Interpersonal relationship stress (SSI subscale score 2)	Low hours	60	15.12	3.76	10.00	27.00
	Medium hours	209	15.93	4.20	10.00	30.00
	High hours	162	16.02	4.12	10.00	30.00
	Former worker	88	16.44	4.14	10.00	31.00
	Never worked	96	17.06	5.36	10.00	34.00
	Total	615	16.13	4.35	10.00	34.00
Academic stress (SSI subscale score 3)	Low hours	60	24.47	6.82	10.00	38.00
	Medium hours	209	25.05	6.39	10.00	39.00
	High hours	162	26.12	6.22	10.00	38.00
	Former worker	88	24.48	6.27	10.00	37.00
	Never worked	96	24.09	7.45	10.00	39.00
	Total	615	25.05	6.56	10.00	39.00
Environment stress (SSI subscale score 4)	Low hours	60	16.98	4.78	10.00	29.00
	Medium hours	209	17.45	5.42	10.00	34.00
	High hours	162	17.80	5.26	10.00	33.00
	Former worker	88	18.38	5.67	10.00	31.00
	Never worked	96	19.20	6.86	10.00	36.00
	Total	615	17.90	5.63	10.00	36.00

Psychological Outcomes	Employment Status	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Total stress (Total score of SSI)	Low hours	60	76.47	17.21	42.00	116.00
	Medium hours	209	78.98	16.93	40.00	124.00
	High hours	162	81.26	16.33	42.00	127.00
	Former worker	88	79.85	16.74	40.00	116.00
	Never worked	96	80.27	21.78	43.00	134.00
	Total	615	79.66	17.62	40.00	134.00

The highest average stress score appeared in academic stress (25.05). The standard deviation score of academic stress (SD=6.56) was a little larger than the other subscales. The mean physical stress score is 20.58 with a standard deviation of 5.37. The average score for environmental stress was 17.90 with a standard deviation of 5.63. The lowest average stress score was found in interpersonal relationship stress (M=16.13) with the smallest standard deviation of 4.35.

An ANOVA was conducted using employment status as the independent variable (IV) and stress as the dependent variables (DVs). Levene's test indicated a violation of Homogeneity of Variance except for physical stress and academic stress where Welch statistics were used instead. The results show that there are no significant findings across the employment status groups regarding any level of stress (see Table 23 and 24).

Table 23 ANOVA Results of Stress across Employment Status

Stress		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p	Partial η^2
Physical stress (SSI subscale score 1)	Between Groups	159.39	4	39.85	1.38	.238	.009
	Within Groups	17586.39	611	28.78			
	Total	17745.78	615				
Academic stress (SSI subscale score 3)	Between Groups	323.73	4	80.93	1.89	.111	.012
	Within Groups	26129.00	610	42.83			
	Total	26452.73	614				

Table 24 Robust Tests of Equality of Means of Stress across Employment Status

Stress	Robust Test	Statistic ^a	df ₁	df ₂	p	Partial η^2
Interpersonal relationship stress (SSI subscale score 2)	Welch	2.01	4	227.74	.095	.014
	Brown-Forsythe	2.16	4	440.55	.072	
Environment stress (SSI subscale score 4)	Welch	1.86	4	227.36	.119	.014
	Brown-Forsythe	2.15	4	441.42	.073	
Total Stress (Total score of SSI)	Welch	1.00	4	224.32	.407	.006
	Brown-Forsythe	0.90	4	421.07	.465	

a. Asymptotically F distributed.

4.5.1.2 Job Type and Stress

The descriptive statistics for stress scores by job type can be found in Table 25. Among the four subscales, the highest mean was found for academic stress (M=5.41, SD=6.40). The second highest mean was physical stress with a slightly lower standard deviation (M=20.74, SD=5.34). Environment stress indicated a lower mean with a further lower deviation (M=17.49, SD=5.26). Interpersonal stress was the lowest by mean score with the smallest deviation (M=15.84, SD=4.11).

Table 25 Descriptive Statistics of Stress under Type of Job

Psychological Outcomes	Type of Job	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Physical stress (SSI subscale score 1)	Hotel and catering	46	21.09	5.32	10.00	31.00
	Bar work	23	22.96	5.45	14.00	32.00
	Shopwork and sales	129	20.57	5.54	10.00	34.00
	Admin and finance	32	21.22	5.10	10.00	32.00
	Social care	127	20.72	5.21	10.00	36.00
	Other	88	20.22	5.29	10.00	34.00
	Total	445	20.76	5.34	10.00	36.00
Interpersonal relationship stress (SSI subscale score 2)	Hotel and catering	46	16.20	4.36	10.00	29.00
	Bar work	22	17.68	5.34	11.00	28.00
	Shopwork and sales	129	16.17	3.98	10.00	29.00
	Admin and finance	32	16.41	4.59	11.00	30.00
	Social care	127	14.91	3.76	10.00	30.00
	Other	88	15.84	3.95	10.00	27.00
Total	444	15.84	4.11	10.00	30.00	
Academic stress (SSI Subscale score 3)	Hotel and catering	46	26.41	5.62	13.00	38.00
	Bar work	22	28.00	5.87	13.00	36.00
	Shopwork and sales	129	25.62	6.87	10.00	39.00
	Admin and finance	32	25.34	5.22	15.00	34.00
	Social care	127	25.12	6.17	10.00	38.00
	Other	88	24.40	6.77	10.00	38.00
Total	444	25.41	6.40	10.00	39.00	
Environment stress (SSI subscale score 4)	Hotel and catering	46	17.93	5.33	10.00	32.00
	Bar work	22	19.82	5.83	11.00	34.00
	Shopwork and sales	129	18.07	5.51	10.00	33.00
	Admin and finance	32	17.81	5.30	10.00	30.00
	Social care	127	16.65	4.76	10.00	29.00
	Other	88	16.93	5.23	10.00	31.00
Total	444	17.49	5.26	10.00	34.00	
Total stress (Total score of SSI)	Hotel and catering	46	81.63	15.83	45.00	119.00
	Bar work	22	88.68	17.66	53.00	119.00
	Shopwork and sales	129	80.43	17.58	40.00	127.00
	Admin and finance	32	80.78	15.78	52.00	122.00
	Social care	127	77.39	15.57	42.00	116.00
	Other	88	77.39	17.68	42.00	119.00
Total	444	79.52	16.87	40.00	127.00	

Consideration of each stress subscale shows that the stress scores in 'bar work' had the highest mean scores. There was greater variation in stress scores across all the subscales for all the other job types to the extent that no other patterns were obvious. More specifically, for physical stress, the mean in order of descent was bar work (M=22.96, SD=5.45), admin and finance (M=21.22, SD=5.10), hotel and catering (M=21.09, SD=5.32), social care (M=20.72, SD=5.21), shop work and sales (M=20.57, SD=5.54) and other work (M=20.22, SD=5.29). For interpersonal relationship stress, the mean in descending order is type of bar work (M=17.68, SD=5.34), admin and finance (M=16.41, SD=4.59), hotel and catering (M=16.20, SD=4.36), shop work and sale (M=16.17, SD=3.98), other work (M=15.84, SD=3.95), and social care (M=14.91, SD=3.76).

For academic stress, the means in descending order are type of bar work (M=28.00, SD=5.87), hotel and catering (M=26.41, SD=5.62), shop work and sale (M=25.62, SD=6.87), admin and finance (M=25.34, SD=5.22), social care (M=25.12, SD=6.17) and other work (M=24.40, SD=6.77). For environment stress, the mean in order of descend was type of bar work (M=19.82, SD=5.83), shop work and sale (M=18.07, SD=5.51), hotel and catering (M=17.93, SD=5.33), admin and finance (M=17.81, SD=5.30), other work (M=16.93, SD=5.23) and social care (M=16.65, SD=4.76).

The highest mean for total stress score was found in bar work with a slightly larger standard deviation (M=88.68, SD=17.66). The second highest mean of total stress was in 'hotel and catering' (M=81.63, SD=15.83). 'Shop work and sales' (M=80.47, SD=17.58) and 'admin and finance' (M=80.78, SD=15.78) shared a similar mean of total stress but the former had a larger standard deviation and the latter a smaller deviation. 'Social care' (M=77.39, SD=15.57) and 'other' (M=77.39, SD=17.68) type of job shared a similar low mean of total stress but the former has a smaller deviation and the latter a larger deviation.

An ANOVA was conducted using type of current job as the independent variable (IV) and stress as the dependent variables (DVs). Levene's test indicated a violation of Homogeneity of Variance. The results show that stress of interpersonal relationship subscale ($F_{(5, 438)} = 2.58, p < .05$) and total stress ($F_{(5, 438)} = 2.27, p < .05$) was significant different overall across current job type (see Table 26).

Table 26 ANOVA Results of Stress across Type of Current Job

Psychological Outcomes		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p	Partial η^2
Physical stress (SSI subscale score 1)	Between Groups	153.76	5	30.75	1.08	.372	.014
	Within Groups	12524.46	439	28.53			
	Total	12678.23	444				
Interpersonal relationship stress (SSI subscale score 2)	Between Groups	213.85	5	42.77	2.58	.026*	.029
	Within Groups	7275.80	438	16.61			
	Total	7489.65	443				
Academic stress (SSI subscale score 3)	Between Groups	300.68	5	60.14	1.48	.196	.017
	Within Groups	17823.07	438	40.69			
	Total	18123.75	443				
Environment stress (SSI subscale score 4)	Between Groups	292.99	5	58.60	2.14	.060	.024
	Within Groups	11983.97	438	27.36			
	Total	12276.96	443				
Total stress (Total score of SSI)	Between Groups	3183.20	5	636.64	2.27	.047*	.025
	Within Groups	122863.69	438	280.51			
	Total	126046.89	443				

Note: * it is significant at the level of 0.05.

Bonferroni *post hoc* tests indicate that there is no significant difference in total stress between particular types of current jobs. However, a Tukey honestly significant difference (HSD) *post hoc* test indicates that bar work has a significantly higher stress score from interpersonal relationship than social care workers (Mean difference=2.77, $p=.04<.05$). Similarly, Tukey HSD also indicates that bar work had significantly higher total stress than social care workers (Mean difference=11.29, $p=.043<.05$). This result indicates that students felt a significantly higher level of interpersonal stress from social relationships or overall stress when working involved in bar work. In contrast, students working in the social care sector felt significantly less stress from interpersonal relationships and overall stress compared to bar workers.

4.5.2 Self-efficacy

4.5.2.1 Employment Status with Self-efficacy

The descriptive statistics for self-efficacy under the five employment categories are summarised in Table 27. The average of the total self-efficacy score is shown to be 30.48 with a standard deviation of 5.71. The total score of SSE ranges from 10 to 40. The mean score of total self-efficacy is around 30 under the five employment categories. However, for those who are in the never worked group the mean of total self-efficacy was the highest with a standard deviation was slight bigger than those who worked ($M=30.88$, $SD=7.10$). Students who worked for either low ($M=30.79$, $SD=6.07$) or high hours ($M=30.73$, $SD=5.36$) have the second or third highest self-efficacy. In contrast, former workers have the second lowest self-efficacy scores ($M=30.31$, $SD=5.35$) and students who work medium hours produced the lowest self-efficacy ($M=30.08$, $SD=5.32$). The standard deviation of those who work low

hours is slightly larger than those who work medium hours or high hours and who worked previously. The standard deviation for these three employment categories is around 5.30.

Table 27 Descriptive Statistics of Self-efficacy across Employment Status

Psychological Outcomes	Employment Status	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Total self-efficacy (Total score of SSE)	Low hours	57	30.79	6.07	18.00	40.00
	Medium hours	199	30.08	5.32	10.00	40.00
	High hours	156	30.73	5.36	14.00	40.00
	Former worker	85	30.31	5.35	17.00	40.00
	Never worked	92	30.88	7.10	10.00	40.00
	Total	589	30.48	5.71	10.00	40.00

An ANOVA was conducted using employment status as the IV and total score of self-efficacy as DV. Levene's test indicates a violation of Homogeneity of Variances and the Welch statistic was used instead. The results indicate that there are no significant differences between the employment status groups regarding the total score of self-efficacy (see Table 28).

Table 28 Robust Tests of Equality of Means of Self-efficacy across Employment Status

Total Score of SSE	Statistic ^a	<i>df</i> ₁	<i>df</i> ₂	<i>p</i>	Partial η^2
Welch	.49	4	212.32	.746	.003
Brown-Forsythe	.46	4	382.02	.766	

a. Asymptotically F distributed.

4.5.2.2 Type of Job on Self-efficacy

The descriptive statistics for self-efficacy based on job type can be found in Table 29. Students currently working in admin and finance jobs had the highest level of self-efficacy along with those working in social care, the other category and hotel and catering reported higher levels of self-efficacy. In contrast shop and sales workers produced a lower level of self-efficacy with those working in bar work returning the lowest mean score for self-efficacy.

Table 29 Descriptive Statistics of Self-efficacy under Type of Job

Psychological Outcomes	Type of Job	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Total self-efficacy (Total score of SSE)	Hotel and catering	44	30.52	4.00	23.00	39.00
	Bar work	22	28.50	4.92	17.00	36.00
	Shopwork and sales	121	29.23	5.84	10.00	40.00
	Admin and finance	31	31.77	4.02	24.00	40.00
	Social care	121	31.57	5.21	18.00	40.00
	Other	86	30.60	5.88	14.00	40.00
	Total	425	30.46	5.42	10.00	40.00

General linear modelling using univariate and One-way ANOVA was conducted in order to examine if there is any relationship between job type (IV) and self-efficacy. The DV is self-efficacy which is indicated by the total score of SSE. Levene's test of equality of error variances indicated the violation of homogeneity assumption when using total score of SSE ($p < .05$). The Welch robust test (see Table 30) was used as an alternative indicating that there was a significant difference of total self-efficacy between the different type of jobs ($F_{(5, 114.35)} = 3.421, p < .01$). Bonferroni *post hoc* test indicated that social care workers ($M = 31.57, SD = 5.21$) had a significantly higher self-efficacy than shop /sales workers ($M = 29.23, SD = 5.84$) (Mean difference = 2.34, $p < .05$).

Table 30 Robust Tests of Equality of Means of Overall Self-efficacy across Type of Job (N=425)

Total Score of SSE	Statistic	df_1	df_2	p	Partial η^2
Welch	3.42	5	114.35	.006**	.038
Brown-Forsythe	3.82	5	281.36	.002**	

a. Asymptotically F distributed. **Significant at level of 0.01.

This result indicates that students' perceptions of their capability and efficiency varied between the job categories. Students working in the social care sector reported higher levels of self-efficacy compared to those working in the shop and sale sector.

4.5.3 Coping Strategy

4.5.3.1 Employment Status and Coping Strategies

Table 31 provides an overview of the descriptive statistics for the coping strategy scale. The average of both engagement (M=49.92, SD=12.77) and disengagement (M=45.08, SD=12.82) coping strategies was approximately 50. For the four secondary subscales, the mean was around 20. Problem-focused engagement (M=26.26, SD=6.36) provided the highest mean with the smallest deviation. This was followed by emotion-focused engagement (M=23.66, SD=8.61) while emotion-focused disengagement had a lower mean (M=22.87, SD=7.86). The lowest mean score was for problem-focused disengagement (M=22.21, SD=6.94). This shows that at the secondary subscale level, engagement strategies, either focused on emotions or problems, had higher mean scores than disengagement strategies. At primary subscale level, problem-solving appeared a highest mean with the smallest standard deviation (M=13.27, SD=3.38), followed by cognitive restructuring (M=12.99, SD=3.67) and social contact (M=12.26, SD=4.75). The mean scores for other strategies were around 11 with a standard deviation falling between 4 or 5. The lowest mean score was found for problem avoidance (M=10.46, SD=3.52).

From the descriptive data students working in the low hours category had the highest problem-solving score. This is in turn followed by former workers and those students who never worked. Those students who currently worked medium hours had the lowest problem-solving coping scores.

Table 31 Descriptive Statistics of Coping Strategy by Employment Status

Psychological Outcomes	Employment Status	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Problem-solving (CSI-32 primary subscale 1)	Low hours	52	13.79	3.40	7.00	20.00
	Medium hours	188	12.80	3.05	5.00	20.00
	High hours	143	13.10	3.43	4.00	20.00
	Former worker	81	13.16	3.48	4.00	20.00
	Never worked	86	14.36	3.69	5.00	20.00
	Total	550	13.27	3.38	4.00	20.00
Cognitive restructuring (CSI-32 primary subscale 2)	Low hours	52	14.12	3.57	6.00	20.00
	Medium hours	188	12.90	3.46	4.00	20.00
	High hours	143	13.38	3.48	5.00	20.00
	Former worker	81	12.49	3.51	4.00	20.00
	Never worked	86	12.34	4.40	4.00	20.00
	Total	550	12.99	3.67	4.00	20.00
Express emotions (CSI-32 primary subscale 3)	Low hours	52	12.52	4.88	4.00	20.00
	Medium hours	188	11.35	4.33	4.00	20.00
	High hours	143	11.11	4.40	4.00	20.00

Psychological Outcomes	Employment Status	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
	Former worker	81	11.20	4.68	4.00	20.00
	Never worked	86	11.55	4.96	4.00	20.00
	Total	550	11.41	4.56	4.00	20.00
Social contact (CSI-32 primary subscale 4)	Low hours	52	14.38	4.25	5.00	20.00
	Medium hours	188	12.17	4.60	4.00	20.00
	High hours	143	11.73	4.88	4.00	20.00
	Former worker	81	12.17	4.51	4.00	20.00
	Never worked	86	12.12	5.11	4.00	20.00
	Total	550	12.26	4.75	4.00	20.00
Problem avoidance (CSI-32 primary subscale 5)	Low hours	52	10.46	3.30	5.00	18.00
	Medium hours	188	10.63	3.67	4.00	20.00
	High hours	143	10.64	3.42	4.00	18.00
	Former worker	81	10.72	3.29	4.00	20.00
	Never worked	86	9.57	3.66	4.00	20.00
	Total	550	10.46	3.52	4.00	20.00
Wishful thinking (CSI-32 primary subscale 6)	Low hours	52	12.02	4.11	4.00	20.00
	Medium hours	188	12.03	4.28	4.00	20.00
	High hours	143	11.42	4.24	4.00	20.00
	Former worker	81	11.99	4.38	4.00	20.00
	Never worked	86	11.28	4.66	4.00	20.00
	Total	550	11.75	4.33	4.00	20.00
Self-criticism (CSI-32 primary subscale 7)	Low hours	52	11.29	3.92	4.00	19.00
	Medium hours	188	11.43	4.37	4.00	20.00
	High hours	143	11.41	4.70	4.00	20.00
	Former worker	81	11.74	4.53	4.00	20.00
	Never worked	86	11.53	5.01	4.00	20.00
	Total	550	11.47	4.53	4.00	20.00
Social withdrawal (CSI-32 primary subscale 8)	Low hours	52	10.63	3.98	4.00	19.00
	Medium hours	188	11.04	4.28	4.00	20.00
	High hours	143	11.20	4.25	4.00	20.00
	Former worker	81	12.15	4.36	4.00	20.00
	Never worked	86	12.26	5.24	4.00	20.00
	Total	550	11.40	4.44	4.00	20.00
Problem-focused engagement (CSI-32 secondary subscale 1)	Low hours	52	27.90	6.56	14.00	38.00
	Medium hours	188	25.70	5.90	11.00	40.00
	High hours	143	26.48	6.32	9.00	40.00
	Former worker	81	25.65	6.23	8.00	38.00
	Never worked	86	26.70	7.26	9.00	40.00
	Total	550	26.26	6.36	8.00	40.00
Emotion-focused engagement (CSI-32 secondary subscale 2)	Low hours	52	26.90	8.46	9.00	40.00
	Medium hours	188	23.52	8.42	8.00	40.00
	High hours	143	22.84	8.35	8.00	40.00
	Former worker	81	23.37	8.49	8.00	40.00
	Never worked	86	23.66	9.38	8.00	40.00
	Total	550	23.66	8.61	8.00	40.00
Problem-focused disengagement (CSI-32 secondary subscale 3)	Low hours	52	22.48	6.40	11.00	38.00
	Medium hours	188	22.66	7.16	8.00	40.00
	High hours	143	22.06	6.78	8.00	38.00
	Former worker	81	22.70	6.77	8.00	36.00
	Never worked	86	20.85	7.16	8.00	40.00
	Total	550	22.21	6.94	8.00	40.00
Emotion-focused disengagement (CSI-32 secondary subscale 4)	Low hours	52	21.92	6.62	8.00	35.00
	Medium hours	188	22.47	7.55	8.00	40.00
	High hours	143	22.61	7.75	8.00	39.00
	Former worker	81	23.89	7.70	10.00	40.00
	Never worked	86	23.79	9.39	8.00	40.00
	Total	550	22.87	7.86	8.00	40.00
Engagement	Low hours	52	54.81	13.12	24.00	78.00

Psychological Outcomes	Employment Status	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
(CSI-32 Tertiary subscale 1)	Medium hours	188	49.21	12.70	19.00	80.00
	High hours	143	49.31	11.67	25.00	80.00
	Former worker	81	49.02	12.60	16.00	76.00
	Never worked	86	50.36	14.15	21.00	80.00
	Total	550	49.92	12.77	16.00	80.00
Disengagement (CSI-32 Tertiary subscale 2)	Low hours	52	44.40	10.88	26.00	70.00
	Medium hours	188	45.13	13.07	20.00	80.00
	High hours	143	44.66	12.57	16.00	74.00
	Former worker	81	46.59	12.01	23.00	72.00
	Never worked	86	44.64	14.54	16.00	80.00
	Total	550	45.08	12.82	16.00	80.00

When considering cognitive restructuring scores, those students who worked low hours indicated the highest cognitive restructuring coping. This was followed by those who worked for high or medium hours. In contrast to these scores former workers had lower cognitive restructuring scores and students who never worked had the lowest scores for coping strategy.

In the case of emotions those students who were working low hours expressed the highest level of this coping strategy. The pattern for descending scores for this strategy indicated that never worked and those who worked medium hours had the next highest scores, while former workers expressed lower level of emotions. Students who worked for high hours expressed lowest scores for this coping strategy.

When considering social contact those students who worked low hours had the highest scores for this coping strategy, followed by former workers and those who worked medium hours. In contrast students who never worked had lower scores for social contact and those students who worked the highest number of hours had the lowest scores for social contact coping.

In the case of problem avoidance former workers had the highest scores for this strategy, followed by those who worked for medium hours or high hours. Students who worked low hours had the next lowest level for problem avoidance followed by students who never worked. With respect to the coping strategy of wishful thinking, students who worked medium or low hours had the highest scores, followed by former workers. Students who worked high hours had lower scores for this strategy and those students who never worked used wishful thinking the least.

The mean scores for the coping strategy of self-criticism were similar across all employment status groups. However, some variation in mean scores was noted for the final strategy, social withdrawal. For this strategy students in the never worked category had the highest scores, followed by former workers. Those students who worked high or medium hours had lower

scores for social withdrawal, while students who worked low hours had the lowest mean score for this strategy.

Applying Levens's Test of Homogeneity of Variances found that there was no violation of the homogeneity assumption except for cognitive restructuring, social withdrawal and emotion-focused disengagement scales. For these three scales, Welch's test was used as an alternative. The ANOVA results (see Table 32) indicate that there was a significant difference for coping strategies of problem-solving ($F_{(4, 545)} = 3.64, p < .01$) and social contact ($F_{(4, 545)} = 3.14, p < .05$) between employment categories. Using the Welch test a significant difference was found for cognitive restructuring ($F_{(4, 198.88)} = 2.60, p < .05$) between employment categories (see Table 33).

Table 32 ANOVA Results of Coping Strategies across Employment Status

Coping Strategies		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p	Partial η^2
Problem-solving (CSI-32 primary subscale 1)	Between Groups	163.35	4	40.84	3.64	.006**	.026
	Within Groups	6122.36	545	11.23			
	Total	6285.71	549				
Express emotions (CSI-32 primary subscale 3)	Between Groups	82.71	4	20.68	.996	.409	.007
	Within Groups	11315.87	545	20.76			
	Total	11398.58	549				
Social contact (CSI-32 primary subscale 4)	Between Groups	279.21	4	69.80	3.14	.014*	.023
	Within Groups	12101.64	545	22.21			
	Total	12380.85	549				
Problem avoidance (CSI-32 primary subscale 5)	Between Groups	83.20	4	20.80	1.68	.153	.012
	Within Groups	6737.50	545	12.36			
	Total	6820.70	549				
Wishful thinking (CSI-32 primary subscale 6)	Between Groups	57.97	4	14.49	.77	.544	.006
	Within Groups	10231.90	545	18.77			
	Total	10289.87	549				
Self-criticism (CSI-32 primary subscale 7)	Between Groups	8.85	4	2.21	.11	.980	.001
	Within Groups	11270.24	545	20.68			
	Total	11279.09	549				
Problem-focused engagement (CSI-32 secondary subscale 1)	Between Groups	252.98	4	63.24	1.57	.181	.011
	Within Groups	21956.36	545	40.29			
	Total	22209.34	549				
Emotion-focused engagement (CSI-32 secondary subscale 2)	Between Groups	654.216	4	163.554	2.225	.065	.016
	Within Groups	40052.882	545	73.492			
	Total	40707.098	549				
Problem-focused disengagement (CSI-32 secondary subscale 3)	Between Groups	224.29	4	56.07	1.17	.325	.008
	Within Groups	26220.67	545	48.11			
	Total	26444.96	549				
Engagement (CSI-32 Tertiary subscale 1)	Between Groups	1470.30	4	367.58	2.28	.060	.016
	Within Groups	88026.18	545	161.52			
	Total	89496.48	549				
Disengagement (CSI-32 Tertiary subscale 2)	Between Groups	250.91	4	62.73	.38	.823	.003
	Within Groups	89928.73	545	165.01			
	Total	90179.64	549				

Notes: ** It is significant at the level of 0.01; * it is significant at the level of 0.05.

Initially Bonferroni *post hoc* tests were carried out and this showed that students who never worked used significantly more problem-solving than those students who worked for medium hours (Mean difference=1.56, $p=.004 <.01$). Following this a Tukey HDS *post hoc* test showed that students who never worked relied less on cognitive restructuring than those students who worked for low hours (Mean difference=-1.78, $p=.045 <.05$), in contrast the Bonferroni test for this comparison only indicated a marginal effect ($p=.057 >.05$). In addition, students who worked low hours had significantly higher social contact scores than those who working medium hours and high hours (Mean difference=2.21, $p=.028 <.05$; Mean difference=2.66, $p=.005 <.01$).

Table 33 Robust Tests of Equality of Means of Coping Strategy across Employment Status

Coping Strategies	Robust Test	Statistic ^a	df_1	df_2	p	Partial η^2
Cognitive restructuring (CSI-32 primary subscale 2)	Welch	2.60	4	198.88	.037*	.020
	Brown-Forsythe	2.63	4	379.81	.034*	
Social withdrawal (CSI-32 primary subscale 8)	Welch	2.01	4	201.24	.095	.016
	Brown-Forsythe	2.13	4	399.94	.076	
Emotion-focused disengagement (CSI-32 secondary subscale 4)	Welch	0.98	4	202.90	.422	.007
	Brown-Forsythe	0.99	4	406.84	.414	

Notes: a. Asymptotically F distributed. * It is significant at the level of 0.05.

4.5.3.2 Job Type and Coping Strategy

A summary of the descriptive statistics for coping strategy by job type can be found in Table 34. At the tertiary subscale level, overall engagement coping was higher than for disengagement strategies. Within engagement coping those working in ‘admin and finance’ had the highest mean (M=52.62, SD=11.19). Students who worked in ‘social care’ had slightly lower mean scores (M=52.28, SD=12.29). The three job categories of ‘other’, ‘shopwork and sales’ and ‘hotel and catering’ followed with a mean score of less than 50. Those working in ‘bar work’ produced the lowest mean score. The mean scores for all six job categories for disengagement coping were very similar and fell within the range of 40-50. ‘Social care’ has the lowest mean, while ‘hotel and catering’ has the highest.

Table 34 Descriptive Statistics of Coping Strategies under Type of Job

Coping Strategies	Type of Job	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Problem-solving (CSI-32 primary subscale 1)	Hotel and catering	39	12.08	3.31	7.00	20.00
	Bar work	21	11.95	3.89	5.00	18.00
	Shopwork and sales	115	12.77	3.00	7.00	20.00
	Admin and finance	29	13.69	3.13	7.00	20.00
	Social care	112	13.13	2.95	7.00	20.00
	Other	79	13.81	3.66	4.00	20.00
	Total	395	13.04	3.25	4.00	20.00
Cognitive restructuring (CSI-32 primary subscale 2)	Hotel and catering	39	13.31	3.62	6.00	20.00
	Bar work	21	11.62	3.56	6.00	20.00
	Shopwork and sales	115	12.82	3.35	4.00	20.00
	Admin and finance	29	13.72	3.32	7.00	20.00
	Social care	112	13.73	3.16	6.00	20.00
	Other	79	13.54	4.02	4.00	20.00
	Total	395	13.27	3.50	4.00	20.00
Express emotions (CSI-32 primary subscale 3)	Hotel and catering	39	10.67	4.40	4.00	20.00
	Bar work	21	9.71	4.36	4.00	18.00
	Shopwork and sales	115	11.35	4.24	4.00	20.00
	Admin and finance	29	12.10	4.49	4.00	20.00
	Social care	112	12.34	4.37	4.00	20.00
	Other	79	10.94	4.70	4.00	20.00
	Total	395	11.45	4.44	4.00	20.00
Social contact (CSI-32 primary subscale 4)	Hotel and catering	39	12.64	4.73	4.00	20.00
	Bar work	21	10.57	4.84	4.00	20.00
	Shopwork and sales	115	12.29	4.91	4.00	20.00
	Admin and finance	29	13.10	4.13	5.00	20.00
	Social care	112	13.08	4.43	4.00	20.00
	Other	79	11.47	4.85	4.00	20.00
	Total	395	12.35	4.72	4.00	20.00
Problem avoidance (CSI-32 primary subscale 5)	Hotel and catering	39	11.41	3.77	6.00	20.00
	Bar work	21	10.81	3.96	4.00	18.00
	Shopwork and sales	115	10.96	3.40	4.00	18.00
	Admin and finance	29	10.83	3.04	5.00	18.00
	Social care	112	9.59	3.44	4.00	20.00
	Other	79	11.14	3.57	4.00	20.00
	Total	395	10.63	3.53	4.00	20.00
Wishful thinking (CSI-32 primary subscale 6)	Hotel and catering	39	12.69	4.45	4.00	20.00
	Bar work	21	12.95	4.93	4.00	20.00
	Shopwork and sales	115	12.31	3.81	4.00	20.00
	Admin and finance	29	12.10	4.34	4.00	20.00
	Social care	112	10.95	4.35	4.00	20.00
	Other	79	11.42	4.28	4.00	20.00
	Total	395	11.80	4.26	4.00	20.00
Self-criticism (CSI-32 primary subscale 7)	Hotel and catering	39	12.36	4.49	4.00	20.00
	Bar work	21	11.67	4.90	5.00	20.00
	Shopwork and sales	115	11.37	4.01	4.00	20.00
	Admin and finance	29	12.62	4.24	4.00	20.00
	Social care	112	10.79	4.38	4.00	20.00
	Other	79	11.32	4.91	4.00	20.00
	Total	395	11.40	4.42	4.00	20.00
Social withdrawal (CSI-32 primary subscale 8)	Hotel and catering	39	11.31	3.64	4.00	19.00
	Bar work	21	12.24	4.56	4.00	20.00
	Shopwork and sales	115	11.54	4.16	4.00	20.00
	Admin and finance	29	11.62	4.75	4.00	20.00
	Social care	112	10.54	4.25	4.00	20.00
	Other	79	10.72	4.43	4.00	20.00

Coping Strategies	Type of Job	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
	Total	395	11.11	4.27	4.00	20.00
Problem-focused engagement (CSI-32 secondary subscale 1)	Hotel and catering	39	25.38	6.27	15.00	39.00
	Bar work	21	23.57	6.98	11.00	36.00
	Shopwork and sales	115	25.59	5.69	14.00	39.00
	Admin and finance	29	27.41	5.98	16.00	38.00
	Social care	112	26.86	5.71	15.00	40.00
	Other	79	27.35	7.00	9.00	40.00
	Total	395	26.31	6.17	9.00	40.00
Emotion-focused engagement (CSI-32 secondary subscale 2)	Hotel and catering	39	23.31	8.35	8.00	40.00
	Bar work	21	20.29	8.68	8.00	35.00
	Shopwork and sales	115	23.63	8.40	8.00	40.00
	Admin and finance	29	25.21	7.78	12.00	40.00
	Social care	112	25.42	8.18	9.00	40.00
	Other	79	22.41	8.85	8.00	40.00
	Total	395	23.80	8.46	8.00	40.00
Problem-focused disengagement (CSI-32 secondary subscale 3)	Hotel and catering	39	24.10	7.45	10.00	38.00
	Bar work	21	23.76	8.60	10.00	38.00
	Shopwork and sales	115	23.27	6.46	9.00	38.00
	Admin and finance	29	22.93	6.71	10.00	36.00
	Social care	112	20.54	6.90	8.00	39.00
	Other	79	22.56	6.59	11.00	40.00
	Total	395	22.44	6.93	8.00	40.00
Emotion-focused disengagement (CSI-32 secondary subscale 4)	Hotel and catering	39	23.67	6.80	11.00	34.00
	Bar work	21	23.90	8.44	9.00	40.00
	Shopwork and sales	115	22.90	6.85	8.00	38.00
	Admin and finance	29	24.24	8.18	9.00	40.00
	Social care	112	21.32	7.66	8.00	40.00
	Other	79	22.04	8.11	8.00	40.00
	Total	395	22.51	7.54	8.00	40.00
Engagement (CSI-32 Tertiary subscale 1)	Hotel and catering	39	48.69	11.81	30.00	73.00
	Bar work	21	43.86	13.93	19.00	68.00
	Shopwork and sales	115	49.23	12.14	23.00	78.00
	Admin and finance	29	52.62	11.19	31.00	75.00
	Social care	112	52.28	12.29	24.00	80.00
	Other	79	49.76	13.14	25.00	80.00
	Total	395	50.11	12.49	19.00	80.00
Disengagement (CSI-32 Tertiary subscale 2)	Hotel and catering	39	47.77	11.61	23.00	68.00
	Bar work	21	47.67	14.94	19.00	76.00
	Shopwork and sales	115	46.17	11.78	22.00	73.00
	Admin and finance	29	47.17	13.53	23.00	74.00
	Social care	112	41.86	12.78	16.00	76.00
	Other	79	44.59	12.62	22.00	80.00
	Total	395	44.94	12.64	16.00	80.00

At the secondary subscale level, the highest mean score was for problem-focused engagement (M=26) while emotion-focused engagement had a slightly lower mean of 23. Problem and emotion-focused disengagement both had a mean around 22. For problem-focused engagement, ‘admin and finance’ workers had the highest mean. This is followed by ‘other’ and ‘social care’. ‘Shopwork and sales’ and ‘hotel and catering’ have lower means with ‘bar work’ having the lowest mean. When looking at emotion-focused engagement, ‘social care’ workers had the highest mean, followed by ‘admin and finance’ and ‘shopwork and sales’.

'Hotel and catering' and 'other' type have lower mean scores, with 'bar work' having the lowest mean of all job categories. For problem-focused disengagement, the mean score was highest for 'hotel and catering' followed by 'bar work', 'shopwork and sales', 'admin and finance' and 'other' workers with those working in 'social care' having the lowest mean score. For emotion-focused disengagement the order of highest to lowest mean was 'admin and finance', 'bar work', 'hotel and catering', 'shopwork and sales' and 'other', with 'social care' workers providing the lowest mean.

At the primary subscale level, the mean scores ranged from 11 to 13 with the highest mean appearing under cognitive restructuring ($M=13.27$, $SD=3.50$), followed by problem-solving ($M=13.04$, $SD=3.25$) and social contact coping ($M=12.35$, $SD=4.72$). The lowest mean appearing under problem avoidance ($M=10.63$, $SD=3.53$). For the coping strategy of problem-solving, the 'other' job type produced the highest mean just under 14 while 'admin and finance' and 'social care' had slightly lower means. This was followed by 'shopwork and sales' and 'hotel and catering' while 'bar work' had the lowest mean. For the coping strategy of cognitive restructuring the job categories of 'social care' and 'admin and finance' had the two highest mean scores. 'Other' and 'hotel and catering' had slightly lower means and these were followed by 'shopwork and sales' while 'bar work' had the lowest mean score for this strategy.

The pattern of means (highest to lowest) for the coping strategy labelled express emotions was 'social care', 'admin and finance', 'shopwork and sales', 'other' and 'hotel and catering' while 'bar work' employees had the lowest mean score. For the coping strategy of social contact the pattern was 'admin and finance', 'social care', 'hotel and catering', 'shopwork and sales' and 'other' with 'bar work' having the lowest mean score. With the problem avoidance strategy 'hotel catering' workers had the highest mean score with those employed in 'social care' producing the lowest mean score for problem avoidance. The pattern of means for the strategy of wishful thinking showed that those in the 'bar work' category had the highest mean, followed by those students in 'hotel catering', 'shopwork and sales', and 'admin and finance' and 'other' type while 'social care' workers had the lowest mean score for this strategy.

For the strategy of self-criticism those working in 'admin and finance' had the highest mean while those employed in 'social care' had the lowest mean score. The pattern of mean scores within the final coping strategy, social withdrawal, showed that those working in 'bar work' had the highest mean score and the lowest mean for this strategy was found for those students working in the 'other' job category.

Three levels of subscales from the coping strategy inventory (CSI-32) were used as DVs and the type of current job was used as the IV. A general linear model and ANOVA was conducted on the data. Levene's Test of Homogeneity of Variances indicated no violation of homogeneity assumptions. The results can be seen in Tables 35-37.

Table 35 ANOVA Results of Coping Strategies of Primary Subscales across Type of Job

Primary Level Coping		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p	Partial η^2
Problem-solving (CSI-32 primary subscale 1)	Between Groups	129.05	5	25.81	2.49	.03*	.031
	Within Groups	4028.45	389	10.36			
	Total	4157.50	394				
Cognitive restructuring (CSI-32 primary subscale 2)	Between Groups	116.69	5	23.34	1.93	.09	.024
	Within Groups	4703.78	389	12.09			
	Total	4820.47	394				
Express emotions (CSI-32 primary subscale 3)	Between Groups	210.17	5	42.03	2.16	.06	.027
	Within Groups	7573.52	389	19.47			
	Total	7783.69	394				
Social contact (CSI-32 primary subscale 4)	Between Groups	207.80	5	41.56	1.89	.10	.024
	Within Groups	8554.29	389	21.99			
	Total	8762.09	394				
Problem avoidance (CSI-32 primary subscale 5)	Between Groups	179.60	5	35.92	2.95	.01**	.036
	Within Groups	4742.17	389	12.19			
	Total	4921.77	394				
Wishful thinking (CSI-32 primary subscale 6)	Between Groups	185.02	5	37.01	2.07	.07	.026
	Within Groups	6951.57	389	17.87			
	Total	7136.60	394				
Self-criticism (CSI-32 primary subscale 7)	Between Groups	123.52	5	24.70	1.27	.28	.016
	Within Groups	7587.08	389	19.50			
	Total	7710.60	394				
Social withdrawal (CSI-32 primary subscale 8)	Between Groups	105.85	5	21.17	1.17	.33	.015
	Within Groups	7067.25	389	18.17			
	Total	7173.10	394				

Notes: *It is significant at the level of 0.05. **It is significant at the level of 0.01.

The results indicated that there were significant differences for the strategies of problem-solving ($F_{(5, 389)} = 2.49, p < .05$), problem avoidance ($F_{(5, 389)} = 2.95, p < .05$), problem-focused disengagement ($F_{(5, 389)} = 2.72, p < .05$) and disengagement ($F_{(5, 389)} = 2.37, p < .05$) between job

categories. The analysis found that emotion-focused engagement ($F_{(5, 389)} = 2.20, p = .053 > .05$) and engagement coping ($F_{(5, 389)} = 2.23, p = .051 > .05$) had marginal effects, but the p values were higher than .05.

Table 36 ANOVA Results of Coping Strategies of Secondary Subscales across Type of Job

Secondary Level Coping		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p	Partial η^2
Problem-focused engagement (CSI-32 secondary subscale 1)	Between Groups	405.33	5	81.07	2.16	.06	.027
	Within Groups	14606.99	389	37.55			
	Total	15012.32	394				
Emotion-focused engagement (CSI-32 secondary subscale 2)	Between Groups	776.87	5	155.37	2.20	.053	.028
	Within Groups	27422.33	389	70.49			
	Total	28199.20	394				
Problem-focused disengagement (CSI-32 secondary subscale 3)	Between Groups	637.85	5	127.57	2.72	.02*	.034
	Within Groups	18269.26	389	46.97			
	Total	18907.10	394				
Emotion-focused disengagement (CSI-32 secondary subscale 4)	Between Groups	373.67	5	74.73	1.32	.26	.017
	Within Groups	22031.05	389	56.64			
	Total	22404.72	394				

Note: *It is significant at the level of 0.05.

Table 37 ANOVA Results of Coping Strategies of Tertiary Subscales across Type of Job

Tertiary Level Coping		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p	Partial η^2
Engagement (CSI-32 Tertiary subscale 1)	Between Groups	1707.64	5	341.53	2.23	.051	.028
	Within Groups	59714.68	389	153.51			
	Total	61422.32	394				
Disengagement (CSI-32 Tertiary subscale 2)	Between Groups	1861.77	5	372.36	2.37	.04*	.030
	Within Groups	61121.00	389	157.12			
	Total	62982.78	394				

Note: *It is significant at the level of 0.05.

Four *post hoc* tests were conducted using Bonferroni method. Firstly, Bonferroni *post hoc* test indicated non-significant difference of Problem-solving, coping strategy between particular one type of current job to another. Secondly, Bonferroni *post hoc* test indicated significant difference of problem avoidance coping strategy for social care (M=9.59, SD=3.44) type than ‘other’ type of job (M=11.14, SD=3.57) ($p = .04 < .05$) and shop work/sales (M=10.96, SD=3.40) ($p = .05 \leq .05$). Thirdly, Bonferroni *post hoc* test indicated a significant difference of problem-focused disengagement coping strategy between social care (M=20.54,

SD=6.90) and shop work/sales (M=23.27, SD=6.46) (Mean difference=2.74, $p=.042<.05$). Finally, Bonferroni *post hoc* test also indicated non-significant difference of disengagement coping strategy between particular one type of current job to another. Tukey HSD indicated a marginally value of engagement coping, with social worker marginally used more engagement than bar worker (Mean difference=8.42, $p=.051>.05$).

4.5.4 Summary of Relationship

The mean scores for stress varied between the five employment categories. However, the results found no significant differences between employment groups. In contrast, the results for stress when using job type as the IV found two significant findings for the stress subscale of interpersonal relationship stress and the total stress score. Tukey HSD *post hoc* tests indicated 'bar work' reported significantly higher levels of interpersonal relationship and total stress compared to 'social care' workers.

Across the five employment categories the mean score for self-efficacy showed some variation. Those students who had never worked reported the highest mean score for self-efficacy. However, the ANOVA results found no significant differences between the employment groups for self-efficacy. In contrast, the Welch robust test did indicate that there were significant differences for total self-efficacy scores between the different job categories. Bonferroni *post hoc* test indicated 'social care' workers had a significantly higher self-efficacy than 'shop /sales' workers.

The mean score for coping strategies for the five employment categories showed some degree of variation. The average for the tertiary subscales (i.e. both engagement and disengagement), was approximately 50. For the four secondary subscales, the mean was approximately 20 and at the primary subscale level, the mean was approximately 10. Comparisons between employment status groups found significant difference for problem-solving coping strategy, social contact coping strategy and cognitive restructuring. The Bonferroni *post hoc* test indicated that students who had never worked used significantly more problem-solving than those who worked for medium hours. A Tukey HSD *post hoc* test indicated students who had never worked used significantly less cognitive restructuring than those who worked for low hours. Students who worked for low hours used significantly more social contact than those who worked for medium hours and high hours.

In addition, the category of current job was significantly linked to problem-solving, and disengagement coping including problem avoidance, problem-focused disengagement and

disengagement. In the case of emotion-focused engagement and engagement coping a marginal effect emerged but the p values were slightly higher than .05. The *post hoc* tests using Bonferroni method indicated non-significant difference for problem-solving and disengagement coping strategy between one type of job to another. However, Bonferroni *post hoc* test indicated students who worked in social care jobs indicated significantly less problem avoidance coping strategy than those worked in 'other' and 'shop work/sales'. Similarly, students who were employed in social care jobs utilised significantly less problem-focused disengagement than those who worked in 'shop work/sales' jobs. However, using employment status as a categorical variable might obscure any linear relationships between quantity (i.e. weekly hours worked) of employment and the psychological measures. As this study only collected weekly working hours for the 'current workers', it would be beneficial to consider current worker group using hours worked as interval data and considering the relationship between weekly work hours and the psychological factors.

4.6 Linear Relationship of Employment and Psychological Outcomes

4.6.1 Correlation

Pearson correlation analysis was conducted to explore any associated relationships between work variable (current weekly working hours) and three psychological outcomes (stress, self-efficacy and coping strategy).

4.6.1.1 Weekly Working Hours of Current Job and Stress

Table 38 provides a summary of the Pearson correlation results for weekly hours worked and stress. The results indicate that hours worked was significantly positively correlated with three indicators of stress: total score of stress ($r=.106, p<.05$), physical stress ($r=.115, p<.05$), and academic stress ($r=.113, p<.05$). These results indicated that those students working longer weekly hours were likely to have higher levels of overall stress, particularly higher level of physical and academic stress. However, weekly working hours of current job was not significantly associated with interpersonal relationship stress and environmental stress. In other words, hours worked per week was not associated with stress levels from interpersonal relationship and environment.

Table 38 Correlation of Weekly Working Hours, Stress and Coping Strategy

Pearson Correlation	Physical Stress (N=430)	Academic Stress (N=429)	Total Stress (N=429)	Express Emotions (N=382)	Social Contact (N=382)	Emotion-focused Engagement (N=382)	Engagement (N=382)
Weekly working hours (N=437)	.115*	.113*	.106*	-.102*	-.144**	-.134**	-.104*

Notes: * Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). Only significant results were listed here.

4.6.1.2 Weekly Working Hours of Current Job and Self-efficacy

A two tailed Pearson correlation analysis indicated that there were no significant correlations between current weekly working hours and self-efficacy overall score as measured by the SSE. Hours worked per week was not found to be associated with a student's level of self-feeling regarding efficient and capability of accomplishment of tasks.

4.6.1.3 Weekly Working Hours of Current Job and Coping Strategy

With respect to coping strategies hours worked per week was shown to have a negative correlation with two of the primary subscales, one secondary and one tertiary subscales of CSI-32.

Firstly, weekly working hours was negatively correlated with expression of emotions (CSI-32 primary subscale 3, $r=-.102$, $p<.05$) and social contact (CSI-32 primary subscale 4, $r=-.144$, $p<.01$). There was no significant correlation between this work variable and the other six primary coping strategies. Secondly, hours worked per week was significantly negatively correlated with emotion-focused engagement (CSI-32 secondary subscale 2, $r=-.134$, $p<.01$). There were no significant correlations with respect to the other three secondary coping strategies. Thirdly, hours worked per week was significantly correlated with engagement coping strategy (CSI-32 tertiary subscale 1, $r=-.104$, $p<.05$). There were no significant correlations between this work variable and overall disengagement coping strategies.

These results indicate a negative association between hours worked per week and engagement coping strategy. The more hours worked per week the less the engagement strategy was utilised, especially engagement focusing on dealing with emotions including expressing emotion. Students working longer hours per week tended to have lower levels of expression of emotions. Engagement in social contact also decreased significantly with longer working hours per week.

As these associations were negative it means that working more hours per week results in less expression of emotion, less social contact and less emotion-focused engagement. Or conversely, it could be interpreted that more emotion express, more social contact and more emotion-focused engagement is associated with working fewer hours per week. However, overall the associations were weak ($r < .2$).

Weekly working hours were not significantly correlated with other aspects of coping strategy. Having found significant correlations for hours worked per week and total stress, physical stress and academic stress, along with express emotions (CSI-32 primary subscale 3), social contact (CSI-32 primary subscale 4), emotion-focused engagement (CSI-32 secondary subscale 2) and overall engagement coping strategies, a regression analysis was carried out to consider the relationship of weekly work hours and the above-mentioned psychological outcomes.

4.6.2 Regression

Based on the previous analysis indicating significant correlations between hours worked per week and total stress, physical stress and academic stress, three regression analysis were conducted. Three significant models emerged as can be seen in Table 39. Due to the space limitations, the model with the highest power (prediction model for total stress) is reported.

Table 39 Regression Models of Predictors of Stress

Regression Models	R^2
Total score of stress = $80.13 + 1.126$ Social withdrawal + 1.031 Wishful thinking - $.924$ SSE - $.862$ Problem avoidance + $.699$ Problem-solving + $.255$ Current job weekly working hours.	$R^2 = .369$
Physical stress = $17.07 + .377$ Social withdrawal + $.251$ Wishful thinking - $.234$ Problem avoidance + $.085$ Current job weekly working hours.	$R^2 = .233$
Academic stress = $30.28 + .460$ Wishful thinking - $.400$ SSE - $.393$ Problem avoidance + $.239$ Social withdrawal + $.108$ *Current job weekly working hours.	$R^2 = .339$

Using hours worked per week, self-efficacy and copings strategy to predict total stress, a significant model emerged: $F_{(10,381)} = 21.66, p < .001$. The model explains 36.9% of the variance in total score of stress ($R^2 = .369$). Table 40 provides the regression coefficients for the predictor variables entered into the model.

The final model was:

Total score of stress = $80.13 + 1.126$ Social withdrawal + 1.031 Wishful thinking - $.924$ SSE - $.862$ Problem avoidance + $.699$ Problem-solving + $.255$ Current job weekly working hours.

Table 40 Coefficients^a of Model One Variables

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
	<i>B</i>	Std. Error	<i>Beta</i>		
(Constant)	80.128	5.802		13.811	.000
Current weekly working hours	.255	.089	.121	2.874	.004*
Total self-efficacy (Total score of SSE)	-.924	.162	-.302	-5.707	.000*
Problem-solving (CSI-32 primary subscale 1)	.699	.308	.140	2.266	.024*
Cognitive restructuring (CSI-32 primary subscale 2)	-.110	.295	-.024	-.374	.709
Express emotions (CSI-32 primary subscale 3)	-.258	.227	-.070	-1.138	.256
Social contact (CSI-32 primary subscale 4)	-.071	.206	-.021	-.342	.732
Problem avoidance (CSI-32 primary subscale 5)	-.862	.252	-.187	-3.417	.001*
Wishful thinking (CSI-32 primary subscale 6)	1.031	.229	.269	4.508	.000*
Self-criticism (CSI-32 primary subscale 7)	.324	.187	.088	1.734	.084
Social withdrawal (CSI-32 primary subscale 8)	1.126	.201	.293	5.604	.000*

Note: a. Dependent Variable: Total score of SSI

The normal probability plot of the residuals and the plot of standardized residuals against fitted values are shown in Appendix 15 and this supports the argument that the model is a good fit.

This model indicates that higher total stress was predicted by higher weekly work hours, higher scores for problem-solving, wishful thinking, social withdrawal and lower levels of self-efficacy and problem avoidance.

4.6.3 Summary of Linear Relationships

At the correlation level, hours worked per week was positively associated with students' level of overall stress, physical stress and academic stress. Current workers weekly work hours had no specific association with working students' self-efficacy. In addition, this work variable was significantly and negatively correlated with overall engagement coping, especially with emotion-focused engagement including emotion expression and social contact engagement but not with problem-focused engagement. Working hours was not significantly associated with overall disengagement strategy, neither with emotion-focused nor problem-focused disengagement.

Regression analysis produced three significant regression models. In the analysis with the strongest power, weekly hours predicted students total stress score along with self-efficacy and some particular forms of coping strategy. Higher levels of stress were predicted by greater weekly hours, higher levels of the coping strategies of social withdrawal and wishful thinking, lower levels of self-efficacy, less problem avoidance and more problem-solving. In addition, weekly hours were also found to predict physical stress (with low power) and academic stress (with medium power) along with self-efficacy and some aspects of coping strategies.

4.7 Chapter Discussion

This section first discussed results of nature and extent, comparison with 1998 study, difference and relationship of employment with psychological outcomes one by one by interpretation related to previous studies. Finally, this section addressed the limitation of this study and the further direction and insights for the next step.

4.7.1 Nature and Extent of Contemporary Student Employment

4.7.1.1 *How Many Students Work?*

This study found that 70% of students were employed during term-time and that they combined this activity with studying full-time in the HE sector. The percentage of working students found in this study is supported by evidence from previous studies conducted in Scotland²⁴. Recently, McGregor (2015) in a Scottish study reported that 62% of students from a Creative Computing subject in a post-92 university were working. However, it ought to be noted that this study drew its sample from the top post-92 university, while the current study was carried out in a different post-92 HEI. This illustrates that the prevalence of employment may vary between HEI's and suggests that other aspects including location, courses and so forth need to be considered when looking at employment levels (Neves & Hillman, 2017a). Another study conducted in 2010 demonstrated the extent of variation in employment levels reporting 71.4% of students working in Scotland which was lower than that found in Northern Ireland (86.2%) but higher than England (42.7%) (Josiam et al., 2010).

Two national investigations (National Archives Website, 2020; National Union of Students, 2008) indicate that the prevalence of undergraduate employment in Scotland may be slightly

²⁴ The discussion related with relevant studies in Scotland and or in UK were referred. The comparison with the relevant previous studies ordered from closer year to farer year approximately.

lower than the average for the whole UK. However, one study (Neves & Hillman, 2017a) suggests a different perspective. The researchers using the Pay-As-You-Earn system (PAYE) reported that 73% of undergraduate students in England and Wales were identified as being in employment during the tax years ending 2015 and 2016 (National Archives Website, 2020). Similarly, a national study conducted by the National Union of Students (2008) found that 75% of students undertake paid employment while at university, either during term-time (35%) or during the holidays (51 %). In England alone, 68% of students engaged in term-time employment (Robotham, 2009). “Hours spent in paid employment unrelated to” students’ course was 33%-36% (figure found in related data set of 2012-2017) (Neves & Hillman, 2017a, p.31; 2017b). In this study the portion of employed students was only half of the previous study. The reason for this could be that it filtered out course-related jobs, and only counted course-unrelated jobs. This result indicates that half of student work may relate to student’s study and might be ‘non-interfering work’.

4.7.1.2 How Many Hours do Students Work per Week?

This study found that the average working hours of 19.54 hours was higher than any previous study and the results suggest that over time the average weekly hours have increased.

McGregor (2015) found that the median for hours worked was 16 with a range from 3 to 68, and 25% of participants worked less than 11 hours per week, while 75% worked more than 10 hours per week. This contrasts with the current study where 19% of students worked less than 11 hours per week, while 81% worked more than 10 hours per week. This means that in 2019 just under one-fifth of students worked less than 10 hours weekly compared to one-fourth in 2015. Accordingly, in 2019 just over four-fifths of students worked more than 11 hours weekly compared with three-quarters in 2015. It can be argued that the proportion of students working longer hours (more than 10 hours) has increased between 2015 and 2019. Carney et al. (2005) reported an average of 14.2 hours per week while McKechnie et al. (1998) found the average number of hours worked was 14.2 hours in their study. In the present study the range of weekly hours was from 2 hours to 55 hours. Previous research in Scotland found that the number of hours worked per week ranged from 8 to 40, the average working hours per week was 15 to 20 (Broadbridge & Swanson, 2006)²⁵. In England,

²⁵ The figures were introduced as the profile of participants in their qualitative study. But it did reflect the fact of a range of working hours of 84 participants of the focus group (Broadbridge & Swanson, 2006).

Swanson et al. (2006) found students worked 18.6 hours with a 9.9 standard deviation and a range from 0 to 76 hours.

If comparing students with full-time employees, who typically work 35 hours per week, undergraduates work more than half of the time (55.83%) that full-time employees do. This represents a significant commitment on top of the course hours expected by HEI's for full-time study. This could result in increased levels of stress arising from the demands of work and study and the results of the correlation analysis did indicate a positive association for weekly hours worked and stress (see 4.6.1). However, further qualitative investigation might help to clarify the nature of this relationship.

4.7.1.3 What Types of Jobs do Students Work in?

The present study found that one-third of students worked in the sector of 'shop work and sales', while one fifth or more students worked in the job categories of 'social care' and 'other' work. About one tenth of students worked in hotel and catering and less than one tenth of students worked in the sector of 'admin and finance' or 'bar work'. These findings were consistent with the results from other studies that had taken place in Scotland (Carney et al., 2005) and in England (Robotham, 2009). One study in Scotland found half²⁶ of students worked in the retail sector, with nearly 40% working in the food and drink sector and more than 10% working in the 'other' sector (Carney et al., 2005). In that study the retail sector included shop work, supermarket, department store, retail other and petrol station. The level of employment in the retail is nearly 20% higher than the findings from the current study (Study 2)²⁷ where 30.35% worked in shop work and sales. In addition, Carney et al.'s (2005) results for the food and drink sector accounted for 40% of workers, though it should be noted this combines bar and pub work, restaurant, catering hotel, fast food and club. However, it is still 20% plus higher than the result in the current study where bar work plus hotel and catering accounted for less than 18% of current jobs. Carney et al.'s (2005) 'other' category included call centre, health caring and university employment. Among this health care accounted for 3% of employees which is more than 20% less than the finding from the current study. In contrasting the results between the previous study and the present one the 'other' and 'social care' categories of employment shows an increase in number of students working in these sectors.

²⁶ This was calculated by data provided in the original article: 371 divided by 756 (Carney et al., 2005, p.310).

²⁷ When compares with other studies, current Study 1 refers to this study.

In England, one study found that students were “employed in retailing (41%), catering (13%), bars (15%) and other service work (27%)” (Robotham, 2009, p.327). The retail sector in this study was 10% higher than that found in the current research. Bar work in Robotham’s study was similar to Carney et al.’s (2005) 14% figure. Both studies figures were approximately 9% higher than for the present study. The results from previous studies indicate that HE students continue to be employed in similar sectors across the UK and the differences in percentages employed in various sectors may be explained by variations in regional labour market demands. However, it is necessary that we acknowledge the time gap between these studies and the present survey data and consider other reasons for the variations.

First, the sample of students within a study may influence the most popular work sectors. In the present study, the sampled HEI has degrees majoring in social care, admin and finance and there is a strong presence of nursing studies. This might contribute to the portion of workers identified in these two sectors. From this perspective the percentages found in the different job types may reflect the degree course offered by any HEI. This may also explain why the ‘other’ job category had more than one fifth of student workers. The types of jobs included in this category displayed a strong pattern congruent with the main subjects of the HEI sampled. Alternatively, adopting a role theory perspective some jobs may be “non-interfering work” (Neves & Hillman, 2017a; 2017b). This argument could be supported by Lee et al. (1999) who sampled a student population who were studying branches of nursing studies, adult branch and mental health. Lee et al. (1999) reported that the majority of working students were employed in work involving taking care of people (68%). In contrast a minority (18%) worked in bar/waitress work and shop/sales assistant and other work (only 7%) (Lee et al., 1999).

Second, the findings may be the result of potential bias in data collection which may be a shortcoming of the online survey method. The online survey may only attract the attention of certain participants who have similar attitudes or personalities. This result might reflect the social needs of different working sectors.

Third, the results may reflect the economic and commercial changes of the last decade that in turn are reflected in the labour market and the demand for employees in various sectors. Alternatively, it could be a strategy that undergraduates deliberately avoid catering or bar work to avoid tiredness and to help balance study and work. Bar and restaurant work could be more beneficial to social aspects because the work itself overlaps with social life (Lashley, 2013). Some students might deliberately avoid these sectors because too much social

interactions results in over-stretching their energy and creates strain. However, this explanation would require further investigation.

4.7.1.4 Student Pay

In this study the average rate of hourly pay was found to be £8.62, a figure which is close to the NMW rate of £8.72 (from 1 April 2020) for age 25 or over. The average age of the present sample is around 25. Two decades ago, McKechnie et al. (1998) found student workers in the same post-92 University as the present study were paid on average £3.72 per hour. Several years ago, 52.4% of students were employed in hospitality and tourism organizations in Nottingham England and reported pay rates at the legal minimum wage (at that time) between £4.85 per hour and £5.00 per hour (Lashley, 2013). Considering the impact of inflation there is little evidence that real term pay has increased.

Because the minimum pay rate is based on age (Dickens et al., 2010), it is worth considering the age distribution of our participants. Half of the participants were younger than 23 and a quarter of participants were younger than 20 years of age. Some participants (0.6%) were as young as 17. Considering the age of participants, the slow increase of pay could be related to students' age profiles. The age based minimum wage came into effect from 1 April 1999 and has been criticised as a form of age discrimination especially for those under the age of 22 years who are paid "a development rate, rather than the full adult rate" (Sargeant, 2010, p.351). Because of their age and current pay rate system, student workers may need more protection and the slow increase in pay across these studies may be a consequence of the lack of protection of student workers' rights. The only protection for student workers is the national minimum wage (Lang & Kahn, 1998) and some have argued that more specific regulations for protecting student workers are needed even in this modern era. Laws or regulations regarding student workers have been studied and questioned for a few years. For example, legislation to protect child employees (Hobbs et al., 2016; McKechnie et al., 1994; Rikowski & Neary, 1997) and improve occupational health and safety has been suggested by certain researchers (Harpur & James, 2014).

In the context of the present research the current findings on the nature and extent of undergraduate employment address the first Aim of this thesis. In addition to providing contemporary data the findings show a degree of consistency with previous findings and suggest some level of change over time.

4.7.2 The Challenge in Discussing Change over Time

From a longitudinal perspective, there is some evidence to suggest that the prevalence of student employment during term-time has been increasing over time. However, it is difficult to support this claim definitively as comparing different studies is challenging. For example, the actual proportion of workers and weekly working hours are heavily dependent on the sample characteristics including location and HEI and other factors.

It is also worth noting that in comparing studies the sampling method (size, mother population, the level of involvement of participants) may be a variable which impacts on the percentage of working students reported in Scotland, UK or even globally. Some studies involve national students sampling (National Archives Website, 2020; National Union of Students, 2008), while some studies focus on sampling only one institution (e.g. the present study and McKechnie et al, 1998) or one specific subject area or degree program (e.g. Bednarska & Olszewski, 2016). In addition, students who volunteer to participate in these studies may vary between studies. The topic of the survey, student employment, may result in only those who are working, volunteering to participate and non-working students might tend to skip this kind of survey. Hence using more objective methods, for example, the PAYE system might be a more reliable approach than collecting self-report data.

The operational definition of variables between studies may also vary (e.g. definition of employment). For example, most studies including the present one, define students as full-time students and filtered out part-time students. Some studies such as Neves and Hillman (2017a; 2017b) filtered out any students who were involved in course related employment as they defined this as ‘non-interfering’ work. The National Union of Students (2008) and National Archives Website (2020) also limited age as 19-25 or 26-34 years and this might lead to under-representation of older non-traditional students.

Another factor to consider when comparing studies is the variation in methodology adopted. Different approaches to data collection may introduce variations in response rates, for example, in McKechnie et al.’s 1998 study the target sample and methodology were different compared to the present studies online survey approach. In this early 1998 study, hard copies of surveys were distributed and data collection involved the researchers in face to face contact with participants. Such variations complicate any comparisons between data sets.

4.7.3 Work and Psychological Outcomes

4.7.3.1 Stress

The results from this study found that employment/work status was not related to either stress or self-efficacy. This was an unexpected finding as the previous literature found weekly working hours (defined in terms of categories) impacted on stress. For example, Dundes and Marx (2006) who investigated American undergraduates' employment found 20% of working students (who working less than 10 hours) agreed with a single item question of "Work increased my stress level" (p.114) this figure increased to 70% and 80% for 10-19 hours workers and above 20 hours workers, respectively. However, the present study used a more robust and detailed indicator of stress and that may explain the lack of significant findings.

The present study found that job type was significantly related to the total stress score and stress of interpersonal relationship. Tukey HSD indicated that those employed in bar work had significantly higher total stress and interpersonal relationship stress than social care workers. This means that different job types influenced stress overall and stress sourced from interpersonal interaction and relationships.

Studies focusing on bar workers are rare, however, one good qualitative study summarised that bar workers suffered more interpersonal stress than social care workers. The bar environment has described as more intense, physically demanding (constant motion), busy, involving long work shifts and creating interpersonal tension and this results in "occupation-specific stress" (Conway & MacNeela, 2012, p.971). The focus group in the study described the physical stress and social stress for bar workers. Physical fatigue was a characteristic of this job with workers describing themselves as "exhausted" and "knackered" (p.979). Social tension was also worse. On the one hand, the bar work lifestyle characterised as working while others are socialising and the work "partly cut the participants off from" normal scheduled socialising especially with "family and friends" (p.977). One participant stated, "I started drifting away from my regular friends" (p.977). On the other hand, offensive interactions happened routinely to bar workers especially to females (Conway & MacNeela, 2012) with some customers threatening to hit staff, while others resort to verbal aggression. The level of risk was perceived as being out of the employees control due to the "unpredictable customers and fights breaking out" (p.981). Females were likely to be exposed to sexual verbal abuse and harassment. Working in bars meant that workers "don't have personal space" (p.981) and feel they are subjected to a loss of control. The following description gives a glimpse of this:

“People approach you whether you want to be having a conversation with them or not, they will sit at the bar and you have no choice but to be in that space ... for however long they decide.” (Conway & MacNeela, 2012, p.981)

With the development of no smoking legislation and limitations on serving alcohol to “intoxicated and underage customers” (Buvik, 2013; Buvik & Tutenges, 2018, p.230), the environment improved in bars. However, it is still not clear what causes students involved in bar work to indicate levels of interpersonal relationship stress. One possible explanation is considered in the next section.

Previous studies which focused on stress did not consider the issue of job type as a potential variable and interpersonal relationship stress has tended to be ignored. However, several studies have considered sexual harassment (Good & Cooper, 2016; Klein et al., 2020) and tobacco intake (Jones et al., 2001) when working in bars. Some have argued that such environmental hazard exists in all hospitality venues including restaurants, kitchens, and bars (Bates et al., 2002; Good & Cooper, 2016; Klein et al., 2020). Overall, previous studies suggest contradictory associations between social aspects of stress and employment experience. A minority of studies indicated that social relationships may be a strain for students. For instance, Jogaratnam and Buchanan (2004) identified several social strains including “mistreatment, friendship problems, romantic problems, and assorted annoyance” (p.241).

However, other studies have shown that social relationships in the work context are a benefit or at least not a burden. For instance, Ho and Huang (2013) found students had a relatively high mean score when asked if the workplace allowed them to expand relationships, indicating an advantage of work. Creed et al. (2015) also found workplace benefits and demands which explained 15% of well-being, 4% of positive feelings, and 4% of vigour. Recently, Vaughn et al. (2016) found student workers rank their supervisors and co-workers at their workplace as being “moderately or very helpful” when compared to their rating as being “slightly upsetting” (p.29).

Similarly, students agree with the statement “I feel like I have someone to talk to and discuss matters with when I find life difficult” and this group had significantly less chance of having major depression and depressive disorders (Youssef, 2016, p.72). Winkler (2008) studied the perceptions of relations with other employees. He found that most of the students reported that they actually “get along well with the direct supervisor” and other “fulltime employees” (p.192). As part-time workers, students experienced no hostile behaviour from fulltime staff.

In those instances where there was any tension, student workers tended to ascribe this to the individual traits of the other staff and student workers could develop relations with such staff “over time” (p.183). However, it important to note that, unlike the present study, the research mentioned above relied on *ad hoc* questions and did not assess social relationship stress via rigorous psychometric scales which have built in validity and reliability.

This study found the subscale with the highest score was academic stress, but no significant results were found when exploring differences between groups based on employment status or job type. However, previous studies have shown that academic stress is a main source of undergraduates’ stress, however, these studies did not consider work or employment status (Barker et al., 2018; Fisher, 1994; MacGeorge et al., 2005; Misra et al., 2000; Struthers et al., 2000; Zhang & Zheng, 2017). Academic stress refers to stress arising from academic sources including financial problem due to the expense of university, the need to juggle time between study and social activity, delivering presentations, submission deadlines, examinations, dealing with the challenge of learning a difficult subject and handling academic problems (Arip et al., 2015).

In the normal population of undergraduates, academic stress was thought to be related to time conflicts. For instance, Misra et al. (2000) found perceived academic stress was associated with time management including control of time. In the population of working students, stress was studied under the framework of the balance model, role theory and zero-sum theory. For example, Butler (2007) found “greater work hours, higher job demands, and lower levels of job control were related to higher levels of Work Study Conflict” (p.505). Hence, the result from the current study could be attributed to the possibility that working students did not feel the work-study conflict and thus working hours did not directly contribute to any academic stress. Alternatively, it could be that for the working students in this HEI, working more hours or working in specific job types did not affect academic stress at all. However, the current findings offer another option which the regression results may explain (section 4.6.2), namely that other factors such as self-efficacy and coping strategies somehow help to decrease some academic stress.

There were no significant results regarding physical stress between employment status or job type groups in this study. Physical stress refers to physical symptoms of stress including headaches, back pain, sleep problem, difficulty breathing, worry, tiredness/fatigue, sweating, and stomach pain, frequent cold or even drastic weight loss (Arip et al., 2015). It represents the bodies’ reaction to stress. Physical stress was investigated in previous studies under the

title of somatic symptoms associated with students combining work and study (Koeske & Koeske, 1989; Park & Sprung, 2015; Vaughn et al., 2016). For example, working students who had “enough time during the day for rest and relaxation” experienced less burnout, but those who were required to study and work long hours experienced more burnout (Youssef, 2016, p.70). Lee et al. (1999) identified negative aspects of work including time strain and “the physical and mental stress of combining both work and study” (p.448).

In Scotland, Carney et al. (2005) used the general linear model also found “indebtedness and part time working” to be a detrimental factor which slightly but significantly affected “both mental and physical health” (p.307). Park and Sprung (2015) investigated students’ end-of-week fatigue and its relationship with the work study conflict (WSC). They found greater fatigue was found during weeks of higher WSC. They also found higher weekly WSC was related with lower quality student experience. This study suggests that physical stress is associated with work study conflict, a fundamental concept within both balance model and role theory. In addition, Koeske and Koeske (1989) found full-time students with part-time jobs experienced the highest symptom score.

Based on the above previous studies have indicated that working student may have higher physical stress than non-working students. However, this study did not endorse previous findings. One possible explanation could be the links between stress and other variables such as coping and social support. For example, Koeske and Koeske (1989) also found that the association between symptoms and work experience was not simple and involved support: “the Low Support group reported more symptoms than did the High Support group, regardless of Student/Work Status” (p.251). Vaughn et al. also (2016) found social ties were associated with physical stress. They found the amount of “supportive ties” predicted decreased somatic symptoms along with other health indicators. In contrast, the amount of “ambivalent ties” predicted increased somatic symptoms (p.27).

There were no statistically significant findings regarding environment stress between employment status or job type categories in this study. Environmental stress refers to stress from the environment including transportation, noise, pollution, and weather, living conditions, campus facilities, crowding, waiting and security (Arip et al., 2015). Few studies have considered this type of stress for HE participants.

While it was possible to find previous studies that considered academic stress, physical stress, and social relationship stress they considered these aspects of stress independently. The

contribution that the present research makes is that it uses one psychometric validated tool to measure total stress as well as four subscales of stress. This made it easier to compare different types of stress in one study. In addition, previous studies did not consider different work status, some focused solely on hours worked. Other studies had operationalised employment as work Vs no work. In this study a more nuanced approach to operationalising employment was adopted which considered current employment and hours (low, medium and high work hours) and included categories of former and never worked students.

4.7.3.2 *Self-efficacy*

Comparing students' self-efficacy scores by employment status produced no significant differences, however, significant differences were found dependent on students' job type. Bonferroni *post hoc* test indicated social care workers had a significantly higher self-efficacy scores when compared to shop /sales workers.

Perceived self-efficacy refers to the "beliefs in one's capabilities to organize and execute the courses of action required to manage prospective situations" (Bandura, 1995, p.2). Previous studies have identified an association between self-efficacy and work or study. Gbadamosi et al. (2016) found self-efficacy and female gender was a significant predictor of part-time work and career aspirations. In contrast, Sekiguchi (2012) suggested that paid employment may influence self-efficacy by affecting self-efficacy of team building and job search. Other studies suggest that self-efficacy is related to physical stress. Park and Sprung (2015) investigated recovery self-efficacy and found that this was significantly associated with sleep quality and weekly fatigue.

However, it should be noted that all the above studies were conducted outside of the UK (e.g. Nigeria, Japan and US). Fortunately, Gbadamosi et al. (2015) has conducted research in two post-92 universities within the UK. Using regression, they found self-efficacy may have a positive impact on working (beneficial work), but this was not significant. They found that it was the malleable part of self-efficacy and not the fixed part that was significantly related to beneficial work. They interpreted this as "students who hold strong views that things are malleable, and people make a difference, are more likely to maximise the opportunities and value added provided by part-time work" (Gbadamosi et al., 2015, p.11).

A second concern is that previous studies have used different measures of self-efficacy and explored relationships with different psychological variables. Gbadamosi et al. (2016) used a self-efficacy questionnaire, consisting of six items, to check self-efficacy in HE and in the wider world. Using a six-item scale developed by Sonnentag and Krueger (2006) it was found

that there was a relationship between recovery self-efficacy and sleep quality and fatigue (Park & Sprung, 2015), it was suggested this was a result of work-school conflict and the physical symptoms of stress. Sekiguchi (2012) focused on self-efficacy in team-member proficiency-measured using a three-item scale developed by Griffin et al. (2007). However, a closer examination of the items (e.g. “Coordinate my work with co-workers.”) (Griffin et al., 2007, p.337), suggests that this merely tested self-efficacy of interpersonal relationship. All these measurements contain a relatively small number of items, and this might the validity of the measurement, though it must be acknowledged that the Cronbach’s alpha was relatively high for each scale.

However, referring to previous studies did not explain why students who worked in shop work and sales type of jobs feel less competitive than those students who work social care jobs. One possible reason could be the respect received from co-workers or team leaders in these different jobs varied and impacted students’ self-efficacy. Alternatively, jobs in the social care sector may require higher qualification which in turn makes it more meaningful for students once they have secured employment in this sector. However, future research will be required to explore this matter more fully.

4.7.3.3 Coping Strategy

The results in this study illustrated that employment status is only related to three coping strategies, problem-solving, social contact and cognitive restructuring. This study found that students who never worked used significantly more problem-solving strategies than those who worked for medium hours. Problem-solving refers to “both behavioral and cognitive strategies designed to eliminate the source of stress by changing the stressful situation” (Tobin et al., 1984a, p.2). This means that the never worked students used behavioral or cognitive methods to solve certain problems more than students who worked. These problem-solving strategies could vary and include focusing on the problem, increasing the time taken to solve the problem and improved planning to anticipate the problem (Tobin et al., 1984a). However, what problems could never-worked students face compared to their working counterparts? It is possible that never worked students face financial hardship as a result of entering HE without the extra income generated from part-time employment. Previous studies have endorsed the financial pressures faced by working and nonworking students (Barron & Anastasiadou, 2009). Moreover, a small semi-structured interview study of students in the UK indicated that “finances and employment” were the main reasons for freshmen’s stress (Denovan & Macaskill, 2013, p.2). However, to explore the problems that non-working

students may face will require additional research and may be best explored by adopting a qualitative approach.

Previous studies have demonstrated that working students use time management to solve problems between work and study. Due to term-time employment, students “had to make their life more focused and structured, and they learned how to manage time” (Cheng & Alcántara, 2007, p.307). Several studies have suggested that time management should be considered to be a benefit arising from employment (Lee et al., 1999; Manthei & Gilmore, 2005). For example, some students indicated that negotiating individual working times with employers was an important activity for them (Winkler, 2008).

Secondly, this study found students who never worked also used significantly less cognitive restructuring than those who worked for low hours. This cognitive strategy emphasises the restructuring process, i.e. “alter the meaning of the stressful transaction” to be “less threatening” or to focus on the “positive aspects” or to view the matter “from a new perspective” (Tobin et al., 1984a, p.2). This finding could be interpreted as working students needing to restructure their cognition or thinking. However, this only appears to apply for those working low hours.

The study also found that students who worked low hours were significantly more likely to use social contact strategy than those who worked for medium hours and high hours. Social contact strategy was defined as “seeking emotional support from people, one’s family, and one’s friends” (Tobin et al., 1984a, p.2), this emphasises the social function of relationships around the person to help them cope with a crisis or stress. The findings show that students working for less than 10 hours contacted others for social purposes more than those worked for 10-19 hours and more than 20 hours.

Finally, there was a main effect for the type of current job problem-solving, problem avoidance, problem-focused disengagement and disengagement. Bonferroni *post hoc* test showed that social care workers used less of the problem avoidance coping strategy than either other and shop work/sales. These workers also used less problem-focused disengagement coping than shop work/sales.

Previous studies have tended to focus on all working students or specific discipline groups of students (e.g. nursing students) without offering a direct comparison between types of jobs. The results from this study found that students who work in social care jobs were significantly more likely to use less negative coping such as avoiding problems or problem disengagement. There is some support for this finding, for example, Zhao et al. (2015) using

the Coping Behavior Inventory found the most common coping behavior amongst nursing students was transference, followed by staying optimistic and problem-solving. Avoidance was the least frequently used coping strategy. However, in another study, Hirsch et al. (2015) found nursing students used negative coping strategies, especially escaping. While these studies may offer some support it must be noted that employment status was not recorded for the students in these studies.

A limitation of both studies is that when considering variations in strategy, they relied upon comparison means without any statistical test to ascertain the significance of any differences. In addition, the mean differences that these studies found between the coping strategies were small. For example, in Zhao et al.'s study (2015), transference was only .01 higher than staying optimistic. In Hirsch et al.'s study (2015), the mean for the escape strategy was merely .24 higher than that for positive reappraisal. A positive aspect of Hirsch et al.'s (2015) study was that it did not make decisions merely on mean values but included regression analysis (regression beta of .34). Other problems in these studies relate to the label of measurement. In Zhao et al.'s study (2015), the definition of transference and avoidance was not sufficiently clarified to distinguish between the terms. For example, it defined the most common behavior of transference as students choosing to "relax via TV, movies, a shower, or physical exercises" (p.404). These responses could also be classified as avoidance or distraction. In Hirsch et al.'s study (2015), two items with high means of 2.11 and 2.22 do not appear to measure 'escape'. The two items in question were "c-51 I promised myself that things would be different next time" and "c-62 I went over in my mind what I would say or do" (p.504). In addition, most of the items for escape were similar to those used for the 'wishful thinking' category in the present study.

Another limitation is that both studies focus on nursing students who may not necessarily work in social care or nursing jobs. These two studies did not include any comparison with students in other discipline areas when they concluded the negative coping strategy for nursing students.

In summary, in terms of the quantity aspect of employment, this study found that employment status is only related to certain active coping strategies including problem-solving, social contact and cognitive restructuring but does not link to stress and self-efficacy. In terms of the quality of employment, this study found that job type is related to interpersonal relationship stress, total stress, self-efficacy and certain passive coping strategies. These passive strategies included problem-solving, problem avoidance, problem-

focused disengagement and overall disengagement. Within the seven job categories the findings show that the ‘social care sector’ and ‘shop/sale sector’ were highlighted showing frequent significant difference with others. Occasionally, the ‘Other’ sector and ‘Bar work’ sector was significant.

4.7.4 Linear Relationship

4.7.4.1 Correlation

Previous research has shown that attention should be paid to the hours that students commit to working. In this study it was possible to consider the hours of employment for those who are currently working and it was found that work hours was significantly associated with total stress, physical stress, and academic stress, but not with environmental or interpersonal relationship stress. In addition, work hours were significantly associated with engagement and some sub-types of engagement (i.e. express emotion, social contact and emotion-focused engagement) but this association was not found for disengagement.

The present findings are in line with those from some previous studies. For example, some studies found higher work school conflict resulted in greater fatigue and lower quality of sleep for working students (Cheng & Alcántara, 2007; Martin et al., 2012; Park & Sprung, 2015). The researchers also found a positive correlation between work hours and physical stress which is in line with the present study’s findings. This study extends the findings from previous results regarding the link between work and academic achievement (Butler, 2007; Nonis & Hudson, 2006) to include work and stress arising from academic activities.

The negative association between weekly work hours and some engagement coping suggests that work may decrease the chances of students’ proactively expressing emotions and contacting others. One explanation for this could be time management where students escape unnecessary social events to save time for work or study. This would be in line with some previous studies (Cheng & Alcántara, 2007; Hammes & Haller, 1983). Such strategies reduce students’ involvement in social events and activities where emotions could be expressed and social contacts could be made.

However, correlation results also indicated that working more hours resulted in higher stress and lower engagement coping, but work experience did not matter to students’ self-efficacy. This result suggests that the relationship between work hours and self-efficacy is either not direct or not instant. Gbadamosi et al. (2015, 2016) indicated the value of self-efficacy and

self-theory as a system involving students work experience in HE. The reason for this inconsistency with the present findings could be only explained by the factors included in different studies. In Gbadamosi et al.'s studies (2015, 2016) they did not investigate coping strategies which is a vital and direct 'action' to adjust stress (Bandura, 1995). Whereas self-efficacy is the belief or appraisal of one's own 'capabilities' of such actions organised and executed "to manage prospective situations" (Bandura, 1995, p.2). The failure to observe such actions limited the investigation between work, self-efficacy and stress. The co-multivariate relationships between work hours, stress, coping and self-efficacy (see section 4.6.2) could be one explanation for the inconsistency between findings.

The involvement of coping strategy may have weakened or obscured the strength of connection between work hours and self-efficacy. An alternative explanation could be that the association between work hours and self-efficacy requires a longer time period in order to appear. As a part of the core of our sense of self, self-efficacy may not be affected in a short time span. The final explanation could be that work is associated with self-efficacy not in terms of the quantity of work (i.e. weekly hours) but in the quality of work. As the results in 4.5.2.2 demonstrated, students working in different types of job felt significantly different to their capabilities and efficacy. However, because this study looked at employment in seven different sectors, when looking at the overall level of efficacy and specific working hours the association disappeared. This finding suggests that quality of work rather than quantity of work matters more in the context of self-efficacy.

4.7.4.2 Regression

This study found that some disengagement coping strategies such as social withdrawal, wishful thinking and problem avoidance were powerful predictors of stress, but that they acted in opposite directions. Social withdrawal and wishful thinking positively added to higher total stress, physical stress and academic stress. In contrast, problem avoidance as an inactive coping strategy decreased stress. The study also found that weekly working hours consistently predicted three types of stress, working more hours resulted in higher total stress, physical and academic stress. Only one engagement strategy, coping- problem-solving, significantly predicted total stress but did not predict physical or academic stress. This result might suggest that problem-solving as an active coping strategy may contribute to other aspects of stress (i.e. environmental stress and interpersonal relationship). The other inconsistent predictor was self-efficacy which successfully predicted total stress and academic stress but failed to predict physical stress. It is possible that physical stress as a

symptom of high stress might not be associated with self-feeling of efficacy or that the association is weak or unsteady.

These results were partially supported by the previous literature. First, the results expand existing knowledge regarding the relationship between work, stress and coping within the population of working students. In previous studies Dakas (2011) found the number of hours worked per week impacted work school conflict, with greater working hours associated with higher role conflict. Park and Sprung (2015) also found higher levels of weekly work–school conflict was associated with lower sleep quality, one aspect of physical, and higher end-of-week fatigue. In a normal student population (not only working students), Matheny et al. (2002) also found coping resources (including confidence, physical health, structuring, and social support) contributed more than half of variance in perceived stress of American university students. They also suggested that the students who thought that they had more coping resources were less likely to perceive situations as stressful (Matheny et al., 2002). Though it should be noted that in this study, different operational measurements were used: coping was measured by Coping Resources Inventory for Stress and stress was measured by Perceived Stress Scale (Matheny et al., 2002).

Second, the findings of a relationship between work, stress, self-efficacy and coping strategy were also in line with previous literature (Broadbridge & Swanson, 2005; Riggert et al., 2006). These researchers found that “environmental sources of pressure (stressors, demands)” of an individual (Broadbridge & Swanson, 2005, p.239) appeared as conflict between the roles of study, work and life. Such stressors or role conflicts were mediated/moderated by “individual characteristics” such as positive or negative affectivity and self-esteem along with some demographic factors (p.239). The stressors in turn affected “adjustment to university” which includes psychological well-being, academic related aspects, and social integration (p.239). Within these, psychological well-being is a multiple concept composed of positive aspects (satisfaction, quality of Student Life, happiness, and coherence) and negative aspects (stress, anxiety, and depression) (p.239). Riggert et al.’s theory (2006) also supports the association of work and psychological outcomes including stress: pre-existing characters, social interaction and academic outcomes together contribute to his/her psychological outcomes (i.e. utility, stress, satisfaction and goals attainment) (Riggert et al., 2006).

Third, in the above discussion, previous research has tended to focus more on stressors rather than stress. In a review article, Robotham (2008) identified stressors including studying stressors, being in a different country and financial stressors. Financial needs required and

drove students into “taking part-time paid employment during their studies” (Robotham, 2008, p.740). Such a combination of paid work and academic study caused students’ stress mainly because of time demands. Using a sample of full-time working nurses who studied part-time for a degree, Timmins and Nicholl (2005) found that the pressure of meeting work commitments was a main stressor in addition to study. However, it must also be noted that not all studies concur on this relationship, for example Jogaratnam & Buchanan (2004) failed to find any association between work hours with stressors (source of stress) including time pressure, general social mistreatment, friendship problems, developmental challenge, academic alienation, romantic problems, and assorted annoyance.

However, it appears that stress and coping form a mutual relationship. When facing stress, students naturally seek to use coping strategies and in return the use of coping strategies reduces stress (Folkman & Lazarus, 1980, 1986; Lazarus, 1974; Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). For instance, Kausar (2010) found that perceived stress negatively correlated with active practical coping (“proactive responses to the stressors” p.37), but positively correlated with avoidance coping as withdrawal, including “shifting away from stressors” and “distracting to other activities, excessive sleep, and turning to drugs” (p.37). In this study, the Coping Strategies Questionnaire (Kausar, 2001) was used (Kausar, 2010). Academic workload predicted one fifth of the variance of students perceived academic stress. Stressors were mainly from study workload including time spent in labs, at home, in projects and other activities (p.40). The results from Survey 1 found that stressors combined study and work together, but mainly manifested in academic and physical stress but not interpersonal relationship and environmental stress. Hence, the significant main effect of working hours on total stress could be contributed to by academic and physical stress.

In summary, this study based on the regression analysis found a specific link between stress, self-efficacy, coping strategies and work hours. This demonstrates that stress was the consequence of a combined effect from both work hours, feelings of self-efficacy and some coping strategies, but not any of them alone. Previous studies found an association either between work and stress (Koeske & Koeske, 1989; Jogaratnam & Buchanan, 2004; Swanson et al., 2006; Ryan et al., 2011) or between stress and coping alone (Viner, 1999; Yun et al., 2019) separately. The results of the present studies have expanded our understanding in this area.

4.7.5 Strengths and Limitations

In this study, all the *post hoc* tests used Bonferroni and occasionally when Bonferroni test was non-significant, Tukey HSD was used as an alternative. Both *post hoc* tests are less sensitive and conservative than Fisher's LSD²⁸. Thus, in this study there were a few marginal non-significant results which could have been significant when using a more sensitive *post hoc* test such as LSD. The decision to use specific *post hoc* tests was decided by the priority to control for Type I errors²⁹ (Sato, 1996). Tukey HSD is one of the most appropriate *post hoc* tests (Ruxton & Beauchamp, 2008), however, both Tukey HSD and Bonferroni procedures control for Type I errors (Ruxton & Beauchamp, 2008).

By using Bonferroni or Tukey HSD for *post hoc* tests meant that the study adopted a more rigorous statistical approach. However, Ruxton and Beauchamp (2008) did suggest using all three Tukey procedures and then selecting "the one with the lowest minimum significant difference" by comparing "the test statistic and the standard error" (p.692). Due to time constraints, it was not practical to conduct this procedure and as a result some of the *post hoc* test which were not significant by using Bonferroni was significant by Tukey HSD could be a false significance.

4.8 Chapter Conclusion

4.8.1 Nature and Extent of Undergraduates' Employment

The results from this study demonstrate that working while studying in Higher Education is a common experience for students in this particular Scottish HE institution with approximately 70% of students either currently working or having worked. On average students worked up to 20 hours per week but committed more time to work during the summer vacation period. This study therefore concludes that amongst HE students combining part-time work with full-time study is the normative experience. The job sectors that students work in remain consistent with previous research, however, the distribution of students across these job sectors shows signs of variation and this may reflect change in the economy and labour market.

²⁸ LSD means least significant difference (LSD) (Hayter, 1986). Tukey HSD was less conservative or less powerful than LSD. It was designed to control Type I error (Lane, 2010).

²⁹ Type I error means the statistic result falsely refuse the null hypothesis which is true in the population (Pollard & Richardson, 1987).

4.8.2 Changes in Student Employment

The comparison between the 1998 and the 2019 surveys highlights a number of changes. The overall percentage of students who work has increased, however, the number of hours worked remains fairly consistent. The comparison between these two studies suggests that there have been some major changes in student work patterns with fewer students limiting their work to vacation employment and more students working during term-time and at various times across the calendar year (i.e. intermittent workers). This pattern may reflect the increasing economic challenges that many students face. However, it is notable that the level of pay, while reflecting relevant NMW changes does not appear to have increased greatly over time. The two studies also draw attention to the change in the dominant job sectors that students work in. This may reflect changes in the local labour markets but may also represent changes in the wider economy. While the comparison between these two time points is of interest, it was noted that there are challenges in comparing findings between these two studies (e.g. variation in methodology) which may limit the interpretation of differences.

4.8.3 Work Variables: Employment Status and Type of Job

Across the employment status groups, there were no significant results regarding differences in level of stress or self-efficacy. However, job type did indicate that specific job sectors such as bar work had significantly higher stress scores in the areas of interpersonal relationship and total stress when compared to social care workers. Bonferroni *post hoc* test indicated social care workers had a significantly higher self-efficacy than shop /sales workers.

As for coping strategies, comparisons across employment status, found a significant difference in scores for problem-solving, social contact and cognitive restructuring coping strategy. Firstly, Bonferroni *post hoc* test indicated students who never worked used significantly more problem-solving than those who worked for medium hours. Secondly, Tukey HSD *post hoc* tests indicated students who never worked used significantly less cognitive restructuring than those who worked for low hours. Students who worked for low hours used significantly more social contact than those who worked for medium hours and high hours. Similarly, under job types there was a significant difference in terms of problem-solving, problem avoidance, problem-focused disengagement and disengagement coping strategies. Bonferroni *post hoc* test indicated students worked in the type of social care jobs indicated a significantly less problem avoidance coping strategy than those who worked in 'other' and 'shop work/sales' categories.

Likewise, students working in social care jobs utilised significantly less problem-focused disengagement than those worked in the type of 'shop work/sales' jobs.

In conclusion, bar work brought a significantly higher personal relationship stress than working in social care area. Social care workers felt a significantly higher sense of being effective and efficient regarding their capabilities to work than shop /sales workers. Social care workers also used significantly less problem avoidance than those who worked in the sectors of 'other' and 'shop work/sales'. The results in this study and previous literature highlighted outcomes associated with bar work, social care and shop/sales. Within the three types of jobs, bar workers reported more social stress, shop/sales workers felt less capable regarding work efficiency and tended to avoid solving problems and those working in social care felt less stress in terms of social relationships, higher sense of efficacy within work and used less avoidance of problems. However, such key psychological outcomes within these three types of jobs need further investigation.

4.8.4 Linear Relationships - Work and Psychological Outcomes

This study found that weekly hours were positively correlated with total stress, physical stress and academic stress, but that work hours were negatively associated with engagement coping including expression of emotions, social contact, emotion-focused engagement and overall engagement.

Weekly work hours predicted the total score of stress and academic stress along with self-efficacy and disengagement coping strategy, specifically wishful thinking, social withdrawal and problem avoidance. The higher the number of hours worked the more emotion-focused disengagement coping strategy and lower level of self-efficacy predicts higher level of total stress and academic stress separately.

Significantly hours worked per week predicted physical stress along with some aspects of coping strategies but not self-efficacy. Higher scores of physical stress were predicted by working more hours, more emotion-focused disengagement including social withdrawal, wishful thinking, and less problem avoidance.

CHAPTER 5 STUDENT EMPLOYMENT: THE IMPACT OF COVID

This chapter presents findings from Study 3, a second online survey of students (Survey 2). Study 3 attended the same case of the post-92 HEI institution that provided the sample for Study 2. The primary goal of Study 3 was to explore students experience of employment during 2021 against the background of COVID-19 and in doing so address the overall thesis aims 2 and 3. This chapter also provides a snapshot of students coping strategies and the association with other variables in the 2021 survey which partially addressed Aim 4.

This chapter provides a justification for another quantitative survey and outlines the study material, procedure, methods and analysis in section 5.2 Methodology. Following this the chapter presents the findings in sections 5.3 and 5.4. Section 5.5 provides chapter discussion and proposes the next research step. Section 5.6 provides chapter conclusion.

5.1 Introduction

This PhD project seeks to develop the understanding of student employment (nature and extent) and the potential association between employment and a number of psychological variables. As noted earlier, the emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic disrupted the planned research programme and resulted in a few amendments to the research plan. One consequence of this was the decision to conduct a second survey focusing on HE student employment during the time of the pandemic.

The first survey (Study 2) found that 70% of undergraduate students worked, and that there was an association between hours worked per week and perceived stress and some emotion-focused coping strategies. Work hours positively correlated with total stress, as well as physical and academic stress. However, work hours negatively correlated with some coping strategies including expression of emotions and social contact which also contributed to the negative correlation from weekly work hours to emotion focused engagement and general engagement coping strategies. Additionally, working hours positively predicted overall stress, academic stress and physical stress along with coping strategies. Social withdrawal, wishful thinking and problem-solving were predictors in a positive direction, whereas problem avoidance was found to be negative predictor of stress. Self-efficacy negatively predicted overall stress and academic stress but not physical stress.

The occurrence of the COVID-19 pandemic provided an opportunity to understand the impact of macro-economic-social change on student employment. This survey built on the previous survey to allow for an investigation of the changes in the nature and extent of employment and the impact that employment changes might have on HE students in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic.

5.1.1 COVID-19 Pandemic in Scotland

On Sunday 1st March 2020 Scotland had the first confirmed positive case of COVID-19 (Scottish government, 2020a) and on the 23rd of March, Scotland entered its first national lockdown (Scottish Parliament Information Centre [SPICe], 2020). From this initial lockdown through to the time of this survey, there were several waves (Macfarlane, 2021; SPICe, 2022) of lockdown (Scottish government, 2020b, 2020c, 2020e, 2021) and periods where restrictions were eased (SPICe, 2020). Table 41 provides an overview of this period.

The COVID-19 lockdown triggered the first economic recession within the UK since the 2008 global economic crisis. The British Broadcasting Cooperation (BBC) news (Chan & Plummer, 2020) reported that the coronavirus lockdown from April 2020 caused the economy to shrink by more than 20% compared with the first three months of that year. The two consecutive quarters of economic decline defined an economic recession (Chan & Plummer, 2020). The service sector, which accounts for four-fifths of the entire economy, was particularly badly hit and the decline resulted in the closure of shops, hotels, restaurants, schools, car repair shops etc. (Chan & Plummer, 2020). Household spending, factory and construction output all plunged (Chan & Plummer, 2020).

The economic recession had a dramatic effect on the job market. Official data indicated that, “the number of people in work fell by 220,000 between April and June” (Chan & Plummer, 2020). The consequences of the pandemic for those still working were reflected in employment changes such as “experiencing longer working hours, increased workload, irregular work shifts, and shortage of personal protective equipment (PPE)” (Moyo, 2020, p.323).

The Resolution Foundation surveyed people regarding their employment during the 6-11 May 2020. They found a higher proportion (one-third) of lower-paid employees had lost their jobs or had been furloughed, compared to higher-paid employees (Resolution Foundation, 2020). Young people (18 to 24-year-olds) were more likely (nearly 25%) to be furloughed (British Broadcasting Cooperation [BBC] News, 2020a; Resolution foundation, 2020).

Table 41 Lockdown and Ease off in Scotland during COVID-19 Pandemic

Lockdown/Ease phase	Time Period	Relevant restriction in Scotland
1 st Lockdown	23 rd Mar. 2020 -28 th May 202	People were asked to ‘stay at home’ (Scottish government, 2020b). People were only allowed ‘shopping for necessities’ and short daily exercises. Non-essential premises were closed including ‘non-essential retail’, ‘outdoor markets’, ‘entertainment premises and leisure facilities’, ‘playgrounds’, and ‘holiday accommodation’ (Scottish government, 2020b). There were ‘restriction of businesses selling food or drink’ (Scottish government, 2020b).
Phase 1 Ease off	29 th May 2020 – 18 th Jun. 2020	People were allowed only to travel broadly 5 miles within the local community. Gradually drive through food venues and garden or plant shops reopened. The outdoor leisure activities were permitted in the local areas (Scottish government, 2020b).
Phase 2 Ease off	19 th Jun. 2020 – 9 th Jul. 2020	‘All shops with street access’ reopened (Scottish government, 2020c).
Phase 3 Ease off	10 th Jul. 2020 – 3 rd Jan. 2021	The interior non-essential shops reopened with restriction of mandatory face coverings (Scottish government, 2020d). From 15 July, all hospitality venues re-open with strict physical distancing and ‘Test and Protect’ scheme (Scottish government, 2020e).
2 nd Lockdown	4 th Jan. 2021- 1 st Apr. 2021	Scotland ‘return for a period to a situation much closer to the lockdown of last March’: stay at home unless essential shopping, education, childcare or to support the vulnerable. Work from home wherever possible; all schools returned to remote learning until the end of January; The additional premises, service providers and retailers closed (Scottish government, 2021).

Against this background it could be anticipated that the area of student employment would also be affected. However, no specific data was collected regarding this group of employees and the potential impact COVID may have had on the nature and extent of their employment. It could be argued that COVID-19 provides an opportunity to examine changes in student employment and the associated psychological outcomes under a unique set of economic and social circumstances.

5.1.2 Potential Impact on Employment

5.1.2.1 COVID-19, Employment Variables, and Psychological Outcomes

While researchers may not have focused on the impact of COVID-19 on student employment, several studies did look at the wider population of workers. These studies suggest that the employment situation was directly associated with psychological consequences in the period following the start of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Using a sample of full-time working adults, Gómez-Salgado et al. (2020) found just less than three quarters of participants suffered psychological distress, with a higher percentage found in women and those in lower middle age. They also found that the ‘not working’ group (32.7%) and ‘working away from home’ group (48.5%) had a higher level of distress compared with the ‘work at home’ group (18.8%) (p.2). They additionally found that those who did not live with children (including under-16 youngsters) had a higher percentage of psychological distress than those who lived with youngsters (p.13). Unfortunately, this interpretation was based on the comparison of percentage differences rather than more robust analysis.

However, the researchers did use more robust analysis in the form of logistic regression to consider the predictors of stress. The primary predictors of psychological distress were sex and health-related factor (i.e. presence of symptoms and close contact with a positive case) (Gómez-Salgado et al., 2020). The secondary minor predictors were age, employment status, and self-rated health (p.11). It is noticeable that except for direct health factors and demographic factors (i.e. gender and age), employment status was one predictor of psychological distress.

5.1.2.2 COVID-19 and Potential Linkage to Students in University

While studies on student employment during COVID are absent, researchers did consider the link between COVID-19 and students’ psychological health.

Several studies noted that students in universities were affected by COVID-19 in terms of psychological outcomes such as anxiety and depression. In China, a study carried out during the COVID-19 period, found that students’ levels of anxiety were related to several key factors including the effects of COVID on their economic circumstances, daily life and delays in their academic activities (Cao et al., 2020). It was also noted that social support helped decrease anxiety levels (Cao et al., 2020).

Li et al. (2020) compared students' mood before and after confinement and symptoms of anxiety and depression. They found that a lower fear of infection to oneself along with a younger age significantly predicted higher positive affect. In contrast, "inadequate supplies of hand sanitizer" and higher year of study significantly predicted higher negative affect (Li et al., 2020, p.6). Higher "general fear of infection" along with higher score of "inadequate supplies of hand sanitizers" and higher year of study significantly predicted anxiety and depression (p.6). These results suggest that students general fear of infection, one's own infection, some maturity indicators (older age or higher year of study), and supplies of sanitizer were important for students' mood state, anxiety and depression during COVID-19 pandemic.

Against the background of studies of Gómez-Salgado et al. (2020) and Cao et al. (2020), it could be argued that there is a need to understand the impact of COVID on student part-time employment. Particularly, it is important to understand the dynamic of changes in employment created by COVID-19 pandemic amongst this group of workers. Such dynamic changes could be reflected in changes to work status across the different stages related to the imposition of COVID restrictions, lockdown and the easing of restrictions. This study therefore focused on the association of dynamic changes of employment with psychological outcomes. As such COVID-19 created the opportunity to explore the relationship between changing student employment experiences and the potential impact which this might have on psychological outcomes.

5.1.3 Research Objectives of Study 3

This study aims to investigate the impact of COVID on student employment from 23rd Mar. 2020, the first lockdown in Scotland, through to 2021. The study seeks to:

- (i) identify the impact of the COVID disruption on student employment.
- (ii) investigate the impact of employment changes on students' psychological outcomes including perceived levels of stress, self-efficacy and coping strategies.

5.2 Methodology

This section provides information on the research design, participants, survey material, measures, procedure, operational definitions, analysis method, and ethical considerations.

5.2.1 Design

This study adopted the same cross-section survey design as used in Study 2, the first online survey. This survey also forms the second part of the accelerated (short-term) longitudinal

design and quantitative part of the mixed methods design. The original online questionnaire from the first survey was modified to match the new objectives of this investigation and its focus on the impact of COVID.

5.2.2 Participants

The sample was sourced from four Scottish campuses of the same post-92 HEI that was used in Study 2. In total 791 participants clicked the link to the e-survey. Of these, 335 participants (42.4%) were excluded based on the following criteria: 5 participants (0.6%) declined to participate, 77 participants withdrew during the survey (9.7%) and 63 were excluded as they were postgraduate students (8.0%). Most exclusions (186 participants, 23.5%) were explained by the fact that participants could withdraw at any time point during the survey without giving any reasons, in effect they failed to complete the survey. In addition, four students (0.5%) were part-time students and were excluded on that basis.

A total of 456 participants, 57.6% of the original sample who clicked on the link, completed the survey and were included in the final analysis. This achieved the minimum sample size of 375 required based on a theoretical suggestion from an online sample calculator justified in ethical application.

Participant ages ranged from 18 to 58 years old, the average age was 26.21 with a standard deviation of 8.18. Nearly four-fifths of participants were females (n=360, 78.90%) and one-fifth males (n=89, 19.50%). A few participants (n=7, 1.50%) chose 'other' as their gender. Within the sample, nearly 9 in 10 students were home students i.e. from Scotland (n=401, 87.94%). A small number of students came from other parts of the UK (n=5, 1.10%), with just under one-tenth from the EU (n=44, 9.65%) and from international countries (n=6, 1.32%). Participants were evenly distributed across year 1 (n=128, 28.07%), year 2 (n=132, 28.95%) and year 3 (n=113, 24.78%) with a smaller percentage from year 4 (n=83, 18.20%).

5.2.3 Measures

The survey drew on the design of the previous survey used in study 2. The major revisions focused on the changes to employment experienced pre-COVID since January 2020 and during COVID - between March 2020 and the time of current survey's approval and administration February to April 2021.

The revised survey (see Appendix 16) consisted of five sections: part one investigated changes to student employment due to COVID-19 pandemic; parts two, three and four used standardised research tools to examine student perceived stress, self-efficacy and coping

strategy. The final section sought to recruit potential volunteers for the next step of the project.

Section one focused on the investigation of the nature and extent of student employment (do you work? job title, duties, employer, and pay rate) during different time periods (January 2020 to March 2020 and April 2020 to April 2021). This survey was adapted from study 1 which in turn had revised McKechnie et al.'s 1998 survey (McKechnie et al., 1998). The main modifications were made in part one in terms of capturing data from different time periods.

The adaptations involved the introduction of three time periods to the survey, pre-COVID-19 (January 2020 to March 2020); during the initial impact of COVID (April 2020 to September 2020) and the later period (Oct 2020 to April 2021). As in the first survey this section also included questions relating to students' demographic information, funding and family situation, work situation, and reasons for stopping work. Additional questions included changes or adaptations to work resulting from COVID-19 adaptations.

In line with the first survey, section two of the survey included a measure of stress, namely the Student Stress Inventory (SSI) (Arip et al., 2015). Section three was a measure of self-efficacy and used Student Self-Efficacy Scale (SSE) (Rowbotham & Schmitz, 2013; Rowbotham & Owen, 2015). Section four was a measure of coping using the Coping Strategies Inventory short form (32 Item) (CSI-32) (Tobin et al., 1984a; Tobin et al., 1989).

Section five asked students to indicate if they would volunteer for future research work as it was anticipated that the final study may rely upon a qualitative approach (Study 4).

5.2.4 Procedure

5.2.4.1 *Distribution of Recruitment and Advertisement*

The e-survey advertisement was distributed in the same way as the previous survey with professional staff from ITDS team using the HEI banner system, this approach was compliant with GDPR requirements. The advertisement for the online survey was sent to 15,103 undergraduates on two occasions 26th Feb. 2021 and 1st Apr. 2021. The same advertisement was also posted on social media (Facebook) by sharing within a closed group of several HEI student Facebook accounts such as the HEI student union. This was in line with the procedure in Study 2, however, due to the low rate of online engagement at the start of the data collection extra posts were also shared on Twitter (the researcher's account) and more Facebook accounts but still limited to the HEI in question.

The survey was displayed using the online platform Surveyhero (previous e-survey creator) (Surveyhero, 2021). The survey was pilot tested with PhD students and staff during 11th Jan. 2021 to 15th Jan. 2021. The formal survey was opened at 23:00 25th Feb. 2021 and closed at 23:00 25th Apr. 2021.

5.2.4.2 Data Preparation: Cleaning Process, Scoring and Transfer

As with Study 1, raw data especially ‘course title’ and ‘job title’ were cleaned. The whole process of cleaning was conducted according to certain criteria and well-documented. Total score and sub-scores (if applicable) were calculated for three standardised measures of SSI, SSE and CSI-32 and IBM SPSS v25.0 was used for data analysis.

5.2.5 Operational Definition

5.2.5.1 Job Time Period

The survey requested information from students about their employment from three time periods or phases, these were: Phase I ‘Jan. to Mar. 2020’ (1st January 2020 to 31st March 2020); Phase II ‘Apr. to Sept. 2020’ (1st April 2020 to 30th September 2020); Phase III ‘Oct. 2020 to current date’ (1st October 2020 to date of completion of the survey i.e. 26th February to 23rd April 2021).

5.2.5.2 Key Employment Factors

The primary focus was to collect information on students’ employment status during these the periods. To identify work patterns three questions were asked for each time phase. For phase I, participants were asked ‘Do you work during the entire period?’. For phase II, participants were asked whether they were working currently, or had had their work stopped³⁰ or whether they never worked during this period. For phase III, the question for Phase II was repeated. According to their answers, participants were placed into one of five categories (see Table 42). Those who did not work in all three phases (chose No to phase I, chose did not work for phases II and III) were defined as ‘no worker’. Those who worked at all three phases (chose Yes to phase I, chose currently work for phases II and III) were defined as ‘consistent worker’. Those had jobs but stopped at phase II/III were defined as ‘job interrupted’. Those who had jobs at phase I and/or II but lost their job at phase II and/or III,

³⁰ According to what students fill in the survey, furlough was treated as a temporary interruption of work but not an entire stopped work. But if after furlough, students lose the job or were made redundant, they would think their work was stopped. In this sense, stopped work means lose jobs. Whereas furlough is only a work arrangement due to the fact they were still paid by the employer. Thus, a consistent worker may also have a furlough experience. All working students could have an experience of furlough depends on the work arrangement from the employer, no matter which category they were in the current classification.

were defined as ‘who lose jobs’. Some students did not have jobs at phase I and /or II, but found jobs at phase II and /or III, but did not stop working or lose job were defined as ‘job finder’.

Table 42 Five types of Employment Pattern Defined by Employment across Phases

Employment Pattern	Phase I Jan. - Mar.2020		Phase II Apr. – Sept. 2020			Phase III Since Oct. 2020		
	Yes, I work.	No, I did not work.	Work currently.	Work stopped.	Did not work.	Work currentl y.	Work stopped.	Did not work.
No worker		x			x			x
Consistent worker	x		x			x		
Job interrupted	And/or x	And/or x		And/or x			And/or x	
Who lose jobs	x		And/or x		And/or x			And/or x
Job finder		x	And/or x			And/or x		

5.2.5.3 Key Psychological Factors

The key psychological variables in this study were the same as those in study 1 (See section 4.2.3 and 4.2.5.4). The same assessment tools were used for each variable.

5.2.6 Analysis

Analysis was conducted in IBM SPSS Statistics 25. The analysis focused on basic analysis of frequency and percentage, and descriptive analysis was conducted on the data from the sections on the nature and extent and the psychological outcomes. Further inferential statistics ANOVA was conducted on the work status changes (i.e. employment pattern as IV) and psychological variables (i.e. score of SSI, SSE and CSI-32 as DVs).

5.2.7 Ethics

An ethic application for the study was submitted and approved by ESS³¹ Ethics Committee in January 2021. The approval number³² was 2021-13934-12192. To ensure that the study targeted appropriate participants they were in the first instance given a participant information sheet. Participants were asked to provide consent prior to completion of the

³¹ School of Education and Social Science.

³² Ethic approval letter, Participant information sheet, Research informed consent form and Debriefing form can be seen also in Appendices 17-20.

survey and a debrief form was provided with further information and to direct participants to support if required.

5.3 Result One: Nature and Extent of Undergraduates’ Employment in COVID-19 Pandemic Background

This section presents the findings on several aspects of student employment in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic. The findings in this section provided empirical information regarding the nature, extent and the changes in student employment against the background of COVID-19 pandemic (Aim 2 of the thesis). This section also addresses the first research question for Study 3 (i) what was the impact of COVID disruption on student employment?

5.3.1 Prevalence of Student Employment in COVID-19 Pandemic

The percentage of students with part-time jobs from Jan. 2020 to Apr. 2021 is presented in Table 43. This table indicates that before the COVID-19 pandemic first lockdown (23rd Mar. 2020), the employment rate of undergraduates was 67.3% (n=307). By the time of the third time period the figure has dropped to 50.2%.

Table 43 Percentage of Employment during COVID-19 Pandemic (N=456)

Employment	Phases						Total	
	Jan. to Mar. 2020		Apr. to Sept. 2020		Oct. 2020 to Apr. 2021			
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Not working	149	32.7	148	32.5	171	37.5	468	34.2%
Working	307	67.3	242	53.1	229	50.2	778	56.9%
Stopped work	-		66	14.5	56	12.3	122	8.9%

As the table indicates the percentage of ‘not working’, ‘working’ and ‘stopped’ work fluctuated over this time period. The rate of ‘not working’ students remained steady at approximately 33% from Phase II and increased by 5% by the time of Phase III. The percentage of working students was 67.3%, dropping to 53% in Phase II, and decreased to approximately 50% in Phase III. In addition, since the national lockdown at the end of March 2020, more than 10% of all participants stopped work at both phase II and III. Overall, nearly 10% of students stopped work during COVID-19 pandemic.

5.3.2 Number of Hours Worked

The average number of hours worked per week was calculated for the three phases (see Table 44). Across all three phases, undergraduates worked for 21.53 hours with a standard deviation of 10.12 and a range from 0 to 59. More specifically they worked for more than 20 hours per week during Phase I (M=20.94, SD=10.58) and this increased in Phase II (M=23.79, SD=12.79). Phase II also provided the highest average working hours and the largest standard deviation across the three time periods. During Phase III, students worked for nearly 20 hours per week with a slightly smaller standard deviation (M=19.86, SD=9.66) which was the lowest among the three time periods.

Table 44 Descriptive Statistics of Weekly Hours Worked (Study 3)

Phase	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Median	Mode
Phase I	300	0.00	60.00	20.94	10.58	20	16
Phase II	246	0.00	63.00	23.79	12.79	24	30
Phase III	234	0.00	55.00	19.86	9.66	18	16
Average	260	0.00	59.33	21.53	10.12	-	-

5.3.3 Type of Job

This section summarises the results regarding the type of job that students worked in during the COVID-19 pandemic time (See Table 45).

During this period the percentage of students working in the sector of 'social care' increased from 27.55% during Phase I to 35.7% during Phase II and 40.7% during Phase III.

Employment within 'shop work and sale' increased slightly from 27.5 % during Phase I to 28.9% during Phase II and 28.2% during Phase III separately. Overall, the trend indicates a sharp increase in jobs in the social care sector and a slight increase in the shop and sales sector. In contrast the decrease in employment rates in the other four sectors ('hotel and catering', 'bar work', 'admin and finance' and 'other' work) is obvious when compared to the Phase I findings.

The percentage of students employed in 'social care' was the highest accounting for more than one third of employment. This was followed by 'shop work and sales' which accounted for over a quarter of student jobs. More than one in ten students worked in 'other' (14.37%)

type and ‘hotel and catering’ (12.03%) while less than one tenth of participants worked in ‘admin and finance’ (7.20%) and ‘bar work’ (3.57%).

Table 45 Descriptive Statistics of Type of job (Study 3)

Type of Job	Jan to Mar 2020 Phase I		Apr to Sept 2020 Phase II		Oct 2020 to Apr 2021 Phase III		Average	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Hotel and catering	46	15.0	27	10.2	27	10.9	33.33	12.03
Bar work	15	4.9	9	3.4	6	2.4	10.00	3.57
Shop work and sales	84	27.5	77	28.9	70	28.2	77.00	28.20
Admin and finance	26	8.5	19	7.1	15	6.0	20.00	7.20
Social care	84	27.5	95	35.7	101	40.7	93.33	34.63
Other	51	16.7	39	14.7	29	11.7	39.67	14.37
Total	306	100.0	266	100.0	248	100.0	273.33	100.0

5.3.4 Pay Rate

The mean of pay rate across the three time periods was £9.64 with a standard deviation of 4.91 (see Table 46). Pay rates in the pandemic year 2020 and 2021 show a very modest increase with mean of pay rates for each of the time periods being £9.64, £9.55 and £9.73. The respective standard deviations were 5.85, 4.45 and 4.44. The maximum pay rate reported was £70 per hour and minimum pay increased across the time periods from £4.50 in Phase I to £6.00 during Phase III. These results demonstrated a wider range and slightly increase of pay rate during COVID-19 pandemic time.

Table 46 Descriptive Statistics of Pay Rate (January 2020- April 2021) (Unit £) (Study 3)

Phase	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Rate of pay Phase I	291	4.50	70.00	9.64	5.85
Rate of pay Phase II	231	5.00	70.00	9.55	4.45
Rate of pay Phase III	232	6.00	70.00	9.73	4.44
Average in this study	251	5.17	70.00	9.64	4.91

5.3.5 Summary

In the pandemic year from Jan. 2020 to Apr. 2021, approximately 57% of students worked, however, there was evidence of a decline in employment from Phase I (67.3%) to 50.2% at Phase III. Overall, just under one tenth of students reported that their employment was

stopped during this period. For those students who were working their weekly hours varied across the three time periods. At Phase I, students worked for just over 20 hours weekly, increasing to nearly 24 hours at Phase II and dropping to just under 20 hours at Phase III. On average, just over one third of students worked in 'social care' jobs and less than 30% worked in 'shop work and sales'. More than one tenth of students worked in either 'other' and 'hotel and catering' type. The percentage in the former type is slightly higher than the latter. Around 7% worked in 'admin and finance'. In contrast, 'bar work' is the most unpopular type of employment with less than 4% employed in this sector. Across the three time phases, 'social care' showed a dramatic increase in students working in this sector from 27.5% during Phase I to 40.7% during Phase III. Similarly, 'shop work and sales' indicated a slight increase from nearly 28% during Phase I to 28.9% during Phase II and 28.2% during Phase III separately. In contrast the other four job types illustrated a decreasing trend in terms of the numbers working in these sectors: 'Hotel and catering' (dropped 5%), 'other' (dropped 4%), 'Admin and finance' (dropped 2.5%) and 'bar work' (dropped 2.5%).

While there was variation across the three time periods in terms of the types of jobs that students were working in when we look at rates of pay the picture is one of consistency. Across three phases the average hourly rates of pay were £9.64, £9.55 and £9.73.

5.4 Result Two: Impact of Employment Patterns to Psychological Outcomes during the COVID-19 Pandemic

This section addresses the changes to psychological outcomes associated with student employment in HE against the background of the COVID-19 pandemic. As such it answers the second research question of Study 3 (What was the impact of employment changes on students' psychological outcomes including perceived levels of stress, self-efficacy and coping strategies). The findings also address Aim 3 of the whole thesis by investigating the relationship between psychological factors and part-time employment. The findings additionally address Aim 4 of the thesis by providing a snapshot of coping strategies in the background of COVID-19.

The findings considered here focus on the students' employment pattern across the three time periods. During these three phases, student work status changed (see Table 47). Nearly two fifths of students worked consistently. More than one fifth were non-workers. More than one fifth had their jobs interrupted or stopped for some reason. Less than one tenth, either lost their jobs, or found a new job.

Table 47 Employment Patterns in Background of COVID-19 Pandemic

Employment Pattern	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
No worker	95	20.83	20.83	20.83
Consistent worker	179	39.25	39.25	60.08
Who lose jobs	43	9.43	9.43	69.51
Job finder	35	7.68	7.68	77.19
Job interrupted	104	22.81	22.81	100.0
Total	456	100.0	100.0	

Based on the above it is worth investigating the relationship between these employment patterns and the key psychological outcomes of stress, self-efficacy and coping strategies.

5.4.1 Stress

The descriptive statistics indicate the overall stress scores across the different employment patterns (see Table 48). The mean for total stress was 83.18 with a standard deviation of 18.48.

Across the whole sample those in the 'job finders' category had the highest stress score with a large standard deviation ($M=86.91$, $SD=19.69$). This was followed by those whose jobs were interrupted ($M=84.41$, $SD=18.05$) and No workers ($M=83.80$, $SD=19.84$). Those students who worked consistently had lower stress scores ($M=81.88$, $SD=18.08$) while those who lost their jobs during the time investigated had the lowest total stress score ($M=81.14$, $SD=17.10$).

For the four subscales, academic stress had the highest mean score ($M=25.91$) with a standard deviation of 7.18, followed by physical stress ($M=20.55$, $SD=4.96$). Environment stress ($M=19.54$, $SD=5.90$) and interpersonal relationship stress had mean scores of under 20 while interpersonal relationship stress was the lowest mean score with the smallest deviation ($M=17.18$, $SD=4.71$).

For the subscale of physical stress, those who found jobs during the pandemic reported the highest mean score of 21.68 with a standard deviation of 4.96. This was in turn followed by those whose jobs were stopped or interrupted ($M=21.04$, $SD=4.63$). Those students who lost their jobs ($M=20.62$, $SD=4.56$) and those who did not work ($M=20.24$, $SD=5.72$) during the pandemic had lower levels of physical stress. Finally, the lowest mean for this subscale was reported by consistent workers ($M=20.20$, $SD=4.79$).

In the case of the interpersonal relationship stress subscale, the mean scores showed that those students who did not work (i.e. no worker) had the highest score followed in

descending order by job finders, those whose job were interrupted, consistent worker and those students who lost their jobs.

Table 48 Descriptive Statistics of Stress across Employment Patterns

Psychological Outcomes	Employment Pattern	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Physical stress (SSI subscale score 1)	No worker	94	20.24	5.72
	Consistent worker	171	20.20	4.79
	Who lose jobs	42	20.62	4.56
	Job finder	34	21.68	4.96
	Job interrupted	100	21.04	4.63
	Total	441	20.55	4.96
Interpersonal relationship stress (SSI subscale score 2)	No worker	94	17.99	5.11
	Consistent worker	171	16.70	4.38
	Who lose jobs	42	16.19	4.16
	Job finder	34	17.94	4.38
	Job interrupted	100	17.40	5.10
	Total	441	17.18	4.71
Academic stress (SSI subscale score 3)	No worker	94	25.04	7.03
	Consistent worker	171	26.37	7.41
	Who lose jobs	42	24.86	6.62
	Job finder	34	27.24	7.83
	Job interrupted	100	25.92	6.89
	Total	441	25.91	7.18
Environment stress (SSI subscale score 4)	No worker	94	20.52	6.61
	Consistent worker	171	18.61	5.62
	Who lose jobs	42	19.48	5.63
	Job finder	34	20.06	6.74
	Job interrupted	100	20.05	5.31
	Total	441	19.54	5.90
Total of stress (Total score of SSI)	No worker	94	83.80	19.84
	Consistent worker	171	81.88	18.08
	Who lose jobs	42	81.14	17.10
	Job finder	34	86.91	19.69
	Job interrupted	100	84.41	18.05
	Total	441	83.18	18.48

Those students who found jobs reported the highest level of academic stress ($M=27.24$, $SD=7.83$), followed by consistent worker ($M=26.37$, $SD=7.41$). Those students who did not work during this time reported lower levels of academic stress ($M=25.04$, $SD=7.03$). However, those students who lost their jobs had the lowest academic stress ($M=24.86$, $SD=6.62$).

For environment stress, those who did not work reported the highest level of stress from the environment ($M=20.52$, $SD=6.61$) while those students who found jobs ($M=20.06$, $SD=6.74$) and had their jobs interrupted ($M=20.05$, $SD=5.31$) had marginally lower stress scores. Students who lost their jobs had lower levels of environmental stress ($M=19.48$, $SD=5.63$), however, those students who work consistently recorded the lowest stress scores for this subscale ($M=18.61$, $SD=5.62$).

To investigate whether the variations in stress are statistically different across the five employment patterns, an ANOVA was conducted using employment pattern as the IV and the five indicators of stress as the DVs. Levene's test indicated no violation of Homogeneity of Variances. The analysis indicated that there were no significant differences for total stress scores or for any of the subscales between the five employment patterns as can be seen in Table 49.

Table 49 ANOVA of Stress across Employment Patterns

Stress		Sum of Squares	<i>df</i>	Mean Square	<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>	Partial η^2
Physical stress	Between Groups	97.20	4	24.30	.99	.414	.009
	Within Groups	10729.80	436	24.61			
	Total	10827.00	440				
Interpersonal relationship stress	Between Groups	167.31	4	41.83	1.90	.110	.017
	Within Groups	9607.54	436	22.04			
	Total	9774.85	440				
Academic stress	Between Groups	213.88	4	53.47	1.04	.387	.009
	Within Groups	22454.50	436	51.50			
	Total	22668.37	440				
Environment stress	Between Groups	272.46	4	68.12	1.98	.097	.018
	Within Groups	15025.09	436	34.46			
	Total	15297.56	440				
Total stress	Between Groups	1122.60	4	280.65	.82	.513	.007
	Within Groups	149202.89	436	342.21			
	Total	150325.49	440				

5.4.2 Self-efficacy

The descriptive statistics for self-efficacy can be found in Table 50. The average score of self-efficacy was 29.38 and across the five employment patterns, students had similar levels of self-efficacy of approximately 29. Consistent workers indicated the highest mean of self-efficacy (M=29.75) with a standard deviation of 6.32, followed by non-workers who had the second highest mean. Those students whose jobs were interrupted during this time period and those who found a job indicated a lower level of self-efficacy. Those who lost their jobs had the lowest mean of self-efficacy (M=28.86) with a standard deviation of 5.40.

Table 50 Descriptive Statistics of Self-efficacy under Employment Patterns

Psychological outcomes	Employment pattern	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Total Self-efficacy (Total score of SSE)	No worker	94	29.41	6.95
	Consistent worker	164	29.75	6.32
	Who lose jobs	42	28.86	5.40
	Job finder	34	29.00	7.01
	Job interrupted	92	29.05	5.98
	Total	426	29.38	6.35

To consider if there are any significant differences between the five employment patterns in terms of self-efficacy an ANOVA was conducted using employment pattern as the IV and the total score of self-efficacy as the DV. Levene's test indicated no violation of Homogeneity of Variances. The analysis found that there were not significant differences between the five employment patterns (see in Table 51).

Table 51 ANOVA of Self-efficacy across Employment Patterns

Group	Sum of Squares	<i>df</i>	Mean Square	<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>	Partial η^2
Between Groups	48.71	4	12.18	.30	.88	.003
Within Groups	17065.44	421	40.54			
Total	17114.15	425				

5.4.3 Coping Strategies

Table 52 provides a summary of the descriptive statistics for coping strategies measure for each employment pattern. The average score for engagement coping strategies ($M=50.05$, $SD=13.13$) was higher than that for disengagement ($M=47.02$, $SD=13.90$) strategies. For engagement coping strategies, consistent workers indicated the highest mean ($M=51.59$, $SD=12.88$), followed by those students who lost jobs and those who found their jobs were interrupted. In contrast, students who found jobs indicated a lower level of engagement strategies. Those students classified as no workers ($M=46.67$, $SD=14.00$) appeared to use the engagement coping strategies the least. For disengagement coping strategies, students who found jobs indicated the highest mean score ($M=48.71$, $SD=13.41$), followed by those who found their jobs interrupted and consistent workers. Students who did not work (no worker) had the second lowest level of disengagement usage ($M=46.40$, $SD=14.98$) and those students who lost their jobs ($M=45.71$, $SD=12.63$) had the lowest scores for disengagement coping strategies.

Among the four secondary subscales, the mean scores ranged from 23 to 26. Problem focused engagement ($M=25.85$) had the highest mean with a standard deviation of 6.60 and this was followed by Emotion focused engagement ($M=24.20$, $SD=8.60$). Emotion focused disengagement had a lower mean score ($M=23.73$, $SD=8.16$) while the lowest mean was for Problem focused disengagement ($M=23.29$, $SD=7.37$). This pattern of results indicates that at the secondary subscale level, engagement strategies which were focused on emotions or problems had a higher mean score than those found for disengagement strategies.

The descriptive mean scores indicate that there are variations across the different employment patterns. The consistent workers ($M=26.31$, $SD=6.40$) utilised the problem focused engagement the most, followed by those who found jobs and those whose jobs were interrupted during the pandemic. In contrast, those who lost their jobs had lower levels of problem-focused engagement usage. However, it was the no worker group ($M=25.24$, $SD=7.20$) used this coping strategy the least.

Those students who lost their jobs ($M=25.79$, $SD=7.27$) utilised emotion focused engagement the most, followed by consistent workers and those whose jobs were interrupted. In contrast, students who found jobs indicated a lower level of emotion focused engagement usage. Those in the no worker group ($M=21.42$, $SD=8.88$) used this coping strategy the least.

Those students who found jobs during this period ($M=24.42$, $SD=6.85$) utilised problem

focused disengagement most, followed by those whose jobs were interrupted and the consistent worker group. In contrast, those students who lost their jobs indicated a lower level of problem focused disengagement usage. Based on the mean scores the no work group ($M=22.47$, $SD=8.51$) used this coping strategy the least.

Amongst those students who found jobs the descriptive data shows that they utilised emotion focused disengagement the most ($M=24.29$, $SD=8.26$), followed by those who had their jobs interrupted and non-workers. In contrast, consistent workers indicated a lower level of emotion focused disengagement usage. Students who lose their jobs ($M=23.17$, $SD=7.81$) used this coping strategy the least.

Table 52 Descriptive Statistics of Coping Strategies under Employment Patterns

Coping Strategies	Employment Pattern	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Problem-solving (CSI-32 primary subscale 1)	No worker	90	12.97	4.00
	Consistent worker	150	13.15	3.46
	Who lose jobs	42	12.52	2.97
	Job finder	31	12.94	3.19
	Job interrupted	90	12.94	3.56
	Total	403	12.98	3.53
Cognitive restructuring (CSI-32 primary subscale 2)	No worker	90	12.28	3.89
	Consistent worker	150	13.17	3.50
	Who lose jobs	42	12.83	3.22
	Job finder	31	13.00	3.60
	Job interrupted	90	12.93	3.77
	Total	403	12.87	3.63
Express emotions (CSI-32 primary subscale 3)	No worker	90	10.34	4.43
	Consistent worker	150	12.34	4.38
	Who lose jobs	42	11.98	3.79
	Job finder	31	11.29	4.54
	Job interrupted	90	11.78	4.85
	Total	403	11.65	4.50
Social contact (CSI-32 primary subscale 4)	No worker	90	11.08	5.24
	Consistent worker	150	12.94	4.54
	Who lose jobs	42	13.81	4.29
	Job finder	31	11.77	4.96
	Job interrupted	90	13.07	4.90
	Total	403	12.55	4.85
Problem avoidance (CSI-32 primary subscale 5)	No worker	90	10.57	4.10
	Consistent worker	150	10.91	3.58
	Who lose jobs	42	10.43	3.12
	Job finder	31	11.39	3.51
	Job interrupted	90	10.93	3.32
	Total	403	10.83	3.59
Wishful thinking (CSI-32 primary subscale 6)	No worker	90	11.90	5.01
	Consistent worker	150	12.53	4.57
	Who lose jobs	42	12.12	3.86
	Job finder	31	13.03	4.09
	Job interrupted	90	12.89	4.58
	Total	403	12.46	4.57

Coping Strategies	Employment Pattern	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Self-criticism (CSI-32 primary subscale 7)	No worker	90	11.54	4.77
	Consistent worker	150	11.47	4.19
	Who lose jobs	42	11.48	4.67
	Job finder	31	11.29	4.77
	Job interrupted	90	12.01	4.50
	Total	403	11.59	4.47
Social withdrawal (CSI-32 primary subscale 8)	No worker	90	12.39	4.56
	Consistent worker	150	12.00	4.66
	Who lose jobs	42	11.69	4.18
	Job finder	31	13.00	4.37
	Job interrupted	90	12.04	4.95
	Total	403	12.14	4.63
Problem focused engagement (CSI-32 secondary subscale 1)	No worker	90	25.24	7.20
	Consistent worker	150	26.31	6.40
	Who lose jobs	42	25.36	5.84
	Job finder	31	25.94	6.27
	Job interrupted	90	25.88	6.81
	Total	403	25.85	6.60
Emotion focused engagement (CSI-32 secondary subscale 2)	No worker	90	21.42	8.88
	Consistent worker	150	25.28	8.20
	Who lose jobs	42	25.79	7.27
	Job finder	31	23.06	8.54
	Job interrupted	90	24.84	9.06
	Total	403	24.20	8.60
Problem focused disengagement (CSI-32 secondary subscale 3)	No worker	90	22.47	8.51
	Consistent worker	150	23.44	7.31
	Who lose jobs	42	22.55	6.11
	Job finder	31	24.42	6.85
	Job interrupted	90	23.82	6.98
	Total	403	23.29	7.37
Emotion focused disengagement (CSI-32 secondary subscale 4)	No worker	90	23.93	8.48
	Consistent worker	150	23.47	7.98
	Who lose jobs	42	23.17	7.81
	Job finder	31	24.29	8.26
	Job interrupted	90	24.06	8.41
	Total	403	23.73	8.16
Engagement (CSI-32 tertiary subscale 1)	No worker	90	46.67	14.00
	Consistent worker	150	51.59	12.88
	Who lose jobs	42	51.14	10.00
	Job finder	31	49.00	12.55
	Job interrupted	90	50.72	13.75
	Total	403	50.05	13.13
Disengagement (CSI-32 tertiary subscale 2)	No worker	90	46.40	14.98
	Consistent worker	150	46.91	13.66
	Who lose jobs	42	45.71	12.63
	Job finder	31	48.71	13.41
	Job interrupted	90	47.88	14.08
	Total	403	47.02	13.90

At the primary subscale level, problem-solving appeared to be the highest mean with the smallest standard deviation ($M=12.98$, $SD=3.53$), followed by cognitive restructuring ($M=12.87$, $SD= 3.63$) and social contact ($M=12.55$, $SD= 4.85$). The means for wishful thinking ($M=12.46$, $SD=4.57$) and social withdrawal ($M=12.14$, $SD=4.63$) were comparable though marginally lower. Two strategies, self-criticism and express emotions, had lower

mean scores, however, the lowest mean score was found for problem avoidance which also had a smaller standard deviation ($M=10.83$, $SD=3.59$).

The descriptive mean scores show that there are variations between the different employment patterns. Students who worked consistently indicated the highest problem-solving usage ($M=13.15$, $SD=3.46$), followed by non-workers, those who found jobs and those whose jobs were interrupted. Students who lost their jobs indicated the lowest problem-solving mean score ($M=12.52$, $SD=2.97$). Those who worked consistently indicated the highest cognitive restructuring form of coping ($M=13.17$, $SD=3.50$), followed by those who found a and those students whose jobs were interrupted. Whereas students who lost their job used lower levels of cognitive restructuring. Those who never worked i.e. no worker had the lowest mean score indicating the lowest usage of this strategy ($M=12.28$, $SD=3.89$). Students who worked consistently expressed the highest level of emotions ($M=12.34$, $SD=4.38$), followed by those who lost their job and those students who had their jobs. Students who found a job expressed lower level of emotions, however, it was students who never worked that had the lowest mean score for this coping strategy ($M=10.34$, $SD=4.43$). Those students who lost their jobs had the highest level of social contact ($M=13.81$, $SD=4.29$), followed by those who had their job interrupted and those students classified as consistent workers. In contrast, those students who found a job had lower levels of social contact while those students who never worked had the lowest level of social contact ($M=11.08$, $SD=5.24$).

Those students who found work during this time indicated the highest level of problem avoidance ($M=11.39$, $SD=3.51$), followed by whose job was interrupted and those who worked consistently. Those students who never worked had a lower level of problem avoidance, whilst students who lost their job used problem avoidance the least ($M=10.43$, $SD=3.12$). Those students who found a job had the highest level of wishful thinking ($M=13.03$, $SD=4.09$), followed by students who had their jobs interrupted and those that worked consistently. Students who lost their job had a lower mean score for wishful thinking and those who never worked used the least wishful thinking ($M=11.90$, $SD=5.01$). When looking at self-criticism those students who had their jobs interrupted used this strategy the most compared to the other employment status groups ($M=12.01$, $SD=4.50$), while non-workers used slightly less of this strategy. Those students who found a job during this time had the lowest mean scores for self-criticism ($M=11.29$, $SD=4.77$). Finally, for social withdrawal those students who found work during this time had the highest scores for this coping strategy ($M=13.00$, $SD=4.37$). Following on from this group in descending order were

those who never worked, had their job interrupted, and those who worked consistently. Students who lost their jobs relied on this strategy the least ($M=11.69$, $SD=4.18$).

To explore the potential for finding significant differences in the use of coping strategies between the employment patterns identified earlier an ANOVA was conducted using the employment pattern as the IV and coping strategies as the DVs. Levene's test found no violation of Homogeneity of Variances. The results indicated significant difference for a number of strategies: express emotion coping ($F_{(4, 398)}=2.95$, $p<.05$, Partial $\eta^2 = .029$), social contact coping ($F_{(4, 398)}=3.56$, $p<.01$, Partial $\eta^2 = .035$) and emotion focused engagement coping ($F_{(4, 398)}=3.65$, $p<.01$, Partial $\eta^2 = .035$) between the five employment patterns (Table 53).

Table 53 ANOVA of Coping Strategies across Employment Patterns

Coping Strategies		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p	Partial η^2
Problem-solving (CSI-32 primary subscale 1)	Between Groups	13.10	4	3.28	.26	.903	.003
	Within Groups	4998.74	398	12.56			
	Total	5011.84	402				
Cognitive restructuring (CSI-32 primary subscale 2)	Between Groups	45.71	4	11.43	.87	.485	.009
	Within Groups	5254.32	398	13.20			
	Total	5300.03	402				
Express emotions (CSI-32 primary subscale 3)	Between Groups	234.77	4	58.69	2.95	.020*	.029
	Within Groups	7908.90	398	19.87			
	Total	8143.67	402				
Social contact (CSI-32 primary subscale 4)	Between Groups	327.19	4	81.80	3.56	.007**	.035
	Within Groups	9146.41	398	22.98			
	Total	9473.60	402				
Problem avoidance (CSI-32 primary subscale 5)	Between Groups	24.63	4	6.16	.48	.754	.005
	Within Groups	5161.21	398	12.97			
	Total	5185.84	402				
Wishful thinking (CSI-32 primary subscale 6)	Between Groups	60.47	4	15.12	.72	.577	.007
	Within Groups	8333.76	398	20.94			
	Total	8394.23	402				
Self-criticism (CSI-32 primary subscale 7)	Between Groups	21.75	4	5.44	.27	.897	.003
	Within Groups	8015.51	398	20.14			
	Total	8037.26	402				
Social withdraw (CSI-32 primary subscale 8)	Between Groups	40.75	4	10.19	.47	.755	.005
	Within Groups	8562.19	398	21.51			
	Total	8602.94	402				
Problem focused engagement (CSI-32 secondary subscale 1)	Between Groups	75.70	4	18.93	.43	.785	.004
	Within Groups	17428.07	398	43.79			
	Total	17503.77	402				
Emotion focused engagement (CSI-32 secondary subscale 2)	Between Groups	1052.36	4	263.09	3.65	.006**	.035
	Within Groups	28704.96	398	72.12			
	Total	29757.32	402				
Problem focused disengagement (CSI-32 secondary subscale 3)	Between Groups	152.56	4	38.14	.70	.593	.007
	Within Groups	21698.47	398	54.52			
	Total	21851.03	402				

Coping Strategies		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p	Partial η^2
Emotion focused disengagement (CSI-32 secondary subscale 4)	Between Groups	46.72	4	11.68	.17	.952	.002
	Within Groups	26729.88	398	67.16			
	Total	26776.59	402				
Engagement (CSI-32 tertiary subscale 1)	Between Groups	1512.51	4	378.13	2.22	.066	.022
	Within Groups	67811.39	398	170.38			
	Total	69323.91	402				
Disengagement (CSI-32 tertiary subscale 2)	Between Groups	262.84	4	65.71	.34	.852	.003
	Within Groups	77360.91	398	194.37			
	Total	77623.75	402				

Note: ** significant at the level of 0.01; * significant at the level of 0.05.

The three effect sizes indicated by Partial η^2 are all slightly higher than those necessary for a small effect size (i.e. .01) but lower than that required for a medium effect size (i.e. .06).

Bonferroni post hoc test indicated consistently working students used significantly more emotion expression (M=12.34, SD=4.38) than those who never work (M=10.34, SD=4.43) ($p=.009<.01$). Similarly, students who were consistent workers (M=12.94, SD=4.54) ($p=.038<.05$) and those who lost their job (M=13.81, SD=4.29) ($p=.024<.05$) used significantly more social contact than those who never work (M=11.08, SD=5.24). In addition, consistent workers (M=25.28, SD=8.20) used significantly more emotion focused engagement coping than those who never work (M=21.42, SD=8.88) ($p=.007<.01$).

5.4.4 Summary

The mean score for total stress was approximately 83 with a standard deviation of 18.48. Among the four subscales, academic stress had the highest mean at approximately 25, followed by physical stress (20). Both environment stress and interpersonal relationship stress had means that were less than that found for physical stress and the lowest mean stress score was found for interpersonal relationship stress. However, the ANOVA results found no significant variation in stress among the five employment patterns.

In terms of significant differences, a similar finding emerged for self-efficacy i.e. no significant differences between the employment patterns. In addition, the level of self-efficacy showed little variation across all five employment patterns.

For the coping strategies, the average of engagement (approximately 50) was higher than disengagement (approx. 47). At the secondary subscale level, both emotion and problem focused engagement strategies had higher mean scores than both disengagement strategies. The means of four secondary subscales range from 23 to 26. The highest mean was problem

focused engagement (nearly 26), followed by emotion focused engagement (approx. 24). The mean of emotion focused disengagement was lower (under 24) and the lowest mean was just more than 23 illustrated by problem focused disengagement. As for primary subscales, problem-solving was the highest (just under 13), followed by the four subscales, cognitive restructuring, social contact, wishful thinking and social withdrawal, which all had means between 12 and 13. Self-criticism and express emotions indicated a mean score from 11 to 12. The lowest mean score was for problem avoidance (just under 11).

Significant ANOVA results were found for two primary coping strategies - express emotion and social contact, and emotion focused engagement coping among employment patterns.

The difference was particularly noted between consistent workers and non-workers.

Bonferroni post hoc test indicated consistent workers adopted significantly more emotion expression than those who never worked. Similarly, both consistent workers and those who lost their jobs made more social contact than those who never worked. Moreover, consistent workers utilised more emotion focused engagement coping significantly than those who never worked.

5.5 Chapter Discussion

This section considers the main results relating to the nature and extent of student employment against the background of the COVID-19 pandemic by comparing the present findings with previous studies and the results from the first survey (see Chapter 4). The remainder of the discussion focuses on the psychological impact on students before considering the practical implications and the next steps.

5.5.1 Changes in the Nature and Extent of Student Employment during COVID-19

5.5.1.1 Numbers of Working HE Students

With respect to the first research question, the findings showed that for this survey, on average nearly 60% of students were working, and approximately 34% of students did not work. Across the time period being studied less than 10% of students stopped work in phase II and III. Across three time phases, the percentage of working students decreased from 67% at Phase I to 50% at Phase III. In contrast, the percentage of those not working increased about 5% from Phase I to III. This result indicated a clear reduction in the numbers working over the time period of this study.

The percentage of working students in Study 3 decreased by 10% compared to the results from the levels of employment found in Study 2. The percentage of those students who did

not work increased by 6% in Study 3 compared with Study 2. This result was in line with research focusing on the younger population in full-time employment during COVID which indicated job losses amongst young workers. The Resolution Foundation focused on 18 to 24-year-olds, but also surveyed all age groups regarding employment during 6-11 May 2020. They found a higher portion (one-third) of lower-paid employees had lost their jobs or been furloughed, compared to higher-paid ones (BBC News, 2020a, 2020b; Resolution foundation, 2020).

However, a degree of caution is needed when interpreting the percentage decrease in HE employment levels as it cannot be simply interpreted as a net loss in the number of working students. It is possible that the decline could be related to an overall disengagement from students during COVID. This suggestion was supported by the slightly lower score of overall disengagement in this study than Study 1 (Mean difference=-1.94). This suggests that overall students presented a trend of disengagement from everything, including participation in the survey. Alternatively, the results may reflect the fact that the percentage of students who work did drop as part of economic impact in background of COVID pandemic. The drop in student employment would be consistent with the overall impact of COVID on the UK economy. The economic recession negatively impacted the services sector (a key employment sector for students), the closure of service venues and dropped household consumption (BBC News, 2020a). In that sense the student employment labour market was impacted in the same way as the adult labour market.

5.5.1.2 Did Students Work Hours Change during COVID-19?

This study found undergraduates worked for an average of 21.53 hours per week, and this was two to three hours more per week than the average hours worked found in Study 2. For those students who were in work the demand for their time from employers increased. At the higher end, some students worked more than 60 hours per week which was greater than the maximum hours of 55 per week in Study 2. In contrast some students were furloughed which changed their weekly hours to zero.

The findings also suggest that working hours increased after the policies of furlough and COVID restrictions were lifted. There are a few explanations for this, first, it could be that those currently working were helping to cover for full-time staff off sick or on holiday leave. Second, it is possible that the opening times varied because of the COVID restrictions (SPICe, 2020; Scottish government, 2020b) and companies were seeking to maximise

turnover by staying open longer. As a flexible labor force, student workers may have been expected to cover these extra shifts and to adapt to a changeable work Rota.

It is also possible that the increase in work hours between survey 1 and 2 is part of a trend that was identified in the previous chapter of students' working hours increasing over time. Previous literature (see section 4.7.1) identified a trend of increasing weekly working hours over a number of decades though it was mild and slow. In these circumstances the increase in hours may not be related to COVID and the economic context.

5.5.1.3 Changes of Type of Job

The findings from this study found a sharp increase in jobs within social care and a slight increase of shop and sales along with a decrease in the other four types of work i.e. 'hotel and catering', 'bar work', 'admin and finance' and 'other' work. This trend would appear to reflect the impact of COVID on various employment sectors. During the three lockdowns in Scotland (Scottish government, 2020b, 2020c, and 2020d), only essential services (such as social care and groceries shop) were allowed to open, other non-essential industries (such as hotels, restaurants and bars) were closed. Thus, employment levels in some sectors such as hotels and bars were negatively impacted while others such as social care were boosted by the increased care needs and by the job vacancies associated with COVID-19 pandemic e.g. the need for additional staff to cover absences and existing staff having to isolate. This argument is supported by one interesting study which focused on the impact to the food industry (Nakat & Bou-Mitri, 2021). The researchers found that COVID-19 could impact "consumer purchasing behavior, transportation network disturbances, labor absenteeism, and the closure of various food manufacturing industries" (p.8). The 'income effects' and 'cost of time' (Cranfield, 2020, p.151) may shift the 'consumption patterns' from eating out in restaurants to 'meals prepared and consumed at home' (Nakat & Bou-Mitri, 2021, p.8). The latter notion was partially supported by reports of the "more than 22,000 had volunteered" in the NHS and social care (BBC News, 2020c) and students working in the in the health front line (BBC News, 2020d).

Another obvious reason is that the NHS experienced shortages of staff (BBC News, 2020e), which could create employment opportunities for students who were studying in the subject areas related to health and social care (e.g. nursing studies), allowing them to work "in the frontline" as nurses, radiographers, paramedics and other healthcare workers (BBC News, 2020c). Alternatively, the change in employment could arise from students moving to new job sectors as they need to work for financial reasons. For example, within the 'other'

category, the jobs that students did were mainly in the creative industries, sports or teaching. Such industries were impacted by COVID-19 restrictions (Comunian & England, 2020; Scottish government, 2020b, 2020c, and 2020d; Taylor et al., 2021; Wiltshire et al., 2022). As a result, the ‘other sector’ employment levels dropped in 2020-2021 and those students sought work in the sectors that were growing e.g. social care.

The findings from this study supported the notion that the nature and extent of student employment in COVID-19 background changed significantly.

5.5.2 What’s the Impact of Employment Changes to Students’ Psychological Outcomes?

5.5.2.1 *Stress*

The exploration of the relationship between work status, indicated by employment pattern, and stress found that there were no significant relationships. This finding is contrary to results from previous studies. Generally, studies focusing on the COVID pandemic demonstrated more stressful and negative feelings or emotions. For example, Li et al. (2020) found increased levels of anxiety and depression within the normal population during COVID. Similarly, Gómez-Salgado et al. (2020) found that a ‘not working’ group and those “working away from home” had a higher proportion of distress compared with the work at home group (p.6). Both of these studies were conducted at the very beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic and it is possible the results from both studies may not be comparable with the timeframe for the present study. Secondly, both studies drew conclusions based on adult populations and, as such, their results may not be applicable to a student population.

One study did use HE students, however, this research was carried out in a different country. Cao et al. (2020) found that about three-quarters of college students had no symptoms of anxiety contrasted with only a quarter that had anxiety which varied within mild, moderate, and severe levels during the COVID 19 period. This study utilised a large sample and used a reliable psychometric scale. Cao et al.’s study partially supports the argument that negative emotions or feelings did not necessarily happen to all students. Anxiety during COVID-19 was related with other factors such as economic circumstance, daily life and academic activities (Cao et al., 2020).

Other studies conducted in the pre-COVID period also indicated that stress was related with employment. For instance, a pre-COVID study (Vaughn et al., 2016) found workplace relationships were associated with college students’ mental health. A recent study conducted during COVID-19 pandemic sampled adult workers and demonstrated that two types of work

self-efficacy were associated with lower well-being (Fida et al., 2022). This study measured work self-efficacy in terms of empathic, assertive, task and emotional self-efficacy. Specifically, they found that those with “low self-efficacy but high empathic” and “high assertive and task self-efficacy but low emotional” (Fida et al., 2022, p.2) work self-efficacy were prone to a risk of lower well-being. However, it should be noted that the previous studies only described the situation of stress or used percentages as the indicator of being prone to risk but did not carry out more rigorous statistical comparison. One explanation based on the present results could be that stress was balanced out through students using coping strategies (see Section 5.5.2.3). Moreover, the comparison in the current study is innovative as previous studies have not compared students with varying employment patterns across three time periods. COVID created a unique opportunity to explore the dynamic aspect of employment and consequently trying to find comparable studies in literature was difficult. Combined with the results presented in 5.4.1 and the discussion here, this study supports the conclusion that student stress did not differ across the various employment patterns identified during the pandemic.

5.5.2.2 Self-efficacy

An exploration of the relationship between work status and self-efficacy failed to find any significant relationships. Students’ work patterns were not associated with their feelings of self-efficacy.

The lack of significant findings is not in line with previous research which used adult workers. Researchers had suggested that there was a decreased sense of how effective, capable or powerful a person felt during COVID. For example, Moyo (2020) found that most workers felt that they no longer ‘have strength’, ‘feel safe’ and no longer found the workplace to be ‘pleasant’ during the COVID-19 pandemic. However, the above factors in Moyo’s study were only measured by one question and while it provides some insight the measures lack validity and reliability.

One reason for the lack of significant difference in self-efficacy between the five employment patterns is that self-efficacy may be a core element in our sense of self and this was not affected by our experiences during the pandemic. If this assumption is correct, then students can show and draw upon strong coping processes as a function of self-monitoring and self-regulation. This argument is supported by an EU based study of adolescence during lockdown (Cattelino et al., 2021). The study found that self-efficacy has the function of

predicting positive coping. In this study self-efficacy was assessed by self-regulated learning and regulatory emotional self-efficacy. While Cattellino et al.'s study (2021) sampled younger students it showed that, in the context of the COVID pandemic, self-efficacy was associated with proactive coping strategies.

However, the findings from the present study indicate that students' self-efficacy does not significantly vary with employment status.

5.5.2.3 Coping Strategy

When considering students' coping strategies several significant findings were found. The findings show significant differences regarding express emotion coping, social contact coping and emotion focused engagement coping when compared between the five employment pattern groups. Bonferroni *post hoc* tests indicated that students who were consistent workers had significantly higher scores for emotion than students who never worked. Similarly, both consistent workers and those who lost their jobs adopted significantly more of the social contact strategy than those who never worked. Moreover, consistent workers utilised significantly more emotion focused engagement coping than those who never worked.

These results highlight the significant difference between students who are consistent workers and those students who never worked in terms of emotion expression and social contact which are both forms of emotion-focused coping. Given that significant results were found in emotion focused engagement coping, it could be argued that that the significant effect of emotion focused engagement at the secondary subscale level was mainly contributed to by emotion expression and social contact coping. One possible explanation for this could be that the social contact within a familiar and steady workplace helped student workers deal with their emotions by providing the opportunity for emotional expression and interacting more frequently with others. In previous studies, for example, Cao et al. did find social support helped decrease anxiety level (2020).

Such emotion-focused engagement could happen between co-workers given the social relationships in the workplace but may also emerge in interactions with clients or customers. Students who are consistently working may build up social contacts and feel a greater degree of safety and comfort in expressing their emotions in the context of colleagues working in a shared environment. However, this explanation would need further research to substantiate this argument. A key question for future study would be to explore why consistent workers use more emotional expression and social contact coping especially when their stress and self-efficacy did not differ?

The results from this study also found that those students who lost their jobs used significantly more social contact coping than those who never worked. One possible explanation is that students who lost their jobs seek to cope with this by using social contacts to support them or to help them find alternative work. Previous research conducted during COVID-19 (Cao et al., 2020) showed that social support helped to reduce anxiety. Cao et al.'s study was carried out in China and drew upon a sample for the general population. In contrast the present study focuses on a student population and their work status, however, the results confirmed that students who consistently worked during the pandemic students and students who lost their job had higher levels of social contact coping than non-workers.

However, the function of social contact, whether it is to find a new job or for social support or some other function, is not clear based on the present findings. Further exploration drawing on a more qualitative approach may clarify this.

The present results and discussions support the view that students who are consistent workers use significantly more emotional expression, social contact and emotion-focused engagement coping than non-workers. In addition, those students who lost their job during the pandemic adopted more social contact coping strategy than non-workers.

5.5.3 Direction for Further Studies

This study has raised a number of questions and identified three potential directions for further studies. First, the findings indicate that follow up studies are needed to explore why consistent workers are more likely to use emotion expression, social contact and emotion-focused engagement strategies? It could be argued that adopting a qualitative approach may shed some light on these questions. Second, it should be noted that the results in this study are based on generalised trends for either consistent workers or those students who had never worked. It is possible that the results could be over-generalised and should be supported or verified by individual examples. Further exploration using a qualitative methodology could provide this.

Finally, the results from this study highlight three particular groups of students: non-workers, consistent workers and those who lost their jobs. In the context of coping strategies non-workers expressed significantly less emotions and used less social contact than those who worked consistently. Overall, non-workers used significantly less engagement coping than consistent workers. Non-workers also used significantly less social contact than those who had worked but lost their jobs during the pandemic. The findings indicate the importance of

not simply considering those students who combine part-time work with their HE studies. This consideration informed the sampling strategy for the next step in this research project by justifying the need to include students who worked consistently during the pandemic along with those who lost their jobs and students who never worked.

5.6 Chapter Conclusion

5.6.1 The Nature and Extent of Employment Overall

From January 2020 through to April 2021, the percentage of working students continuously dropped from about 67% to 50%. Overall, nearly 10% of students stopped work during COVID-19 pandemic for a variety of reasons. The main reason for stopping work was furlough and being made redundant by an employer. Other reasons were linked to the impact of COVID on a specific industry, conflicts between study and placement and so forth. Over the three-time phases undergraduates worked on average 21.53 hours per week. From January 2020 to April 2021, the average working hours fluctuated around 20 hours, namely they were 21hrs, 23hrs, and 20hrs.

While the mean hours worked per week was 21.53, the highest weekly hours (23.79 hours) were found in Phase II. During Phase III, students worked the lowest number of hours per week at just under 20 hours per week. Overall, during COVID students working hours showed a decreasing trend, however, students overall worked 2-3 hours more per week compared with pre-COVID-19 findings.

The findings also highlighted the changes in the dominant employment sectors. The number of students working in social care jobs was higher compared to previous studies and would appear to be a reaction to the impact of COVID on the labour market. Shop and sale jobs increased slightly in Phase II and III and this may reflect the opening of essential shops during lockdown as well as changes to restrictions on opening. Employment levels in the other four job categories declined.

5.6.2 Employment Pattern and Relationship with Psychological Outcomes

This study sought to explore the impact of a naturally occurring economic impact on student employment. As such the finding reflect the dynamic nature of the student employment labour market. The fluidity of employment is demonstrated in the range of employment patterns identified. Nearly two fifths of students worked consistently, with more than one fifth not engaging with employment. As expected, more than one fifth of students had their

jobs interrupted because of the pandemic and less than one tenth either lost their job or found a new job.

The Bonferroni post hoc test indicated that consistently working students utilised significantly more emotional expression than those students who never worked. Similarly, both consistent workers and those who lost their jobs used significantly more social contact than never worked students. In addition, at the secondary subscale level, consistent workers relied significantly more on emotion focused engagement than those students who had never worked.

As indicated in the discussion a number of the issues raised by these findings would benefit from further exploration. However, it may be that an alternative methodological approach (i.e. qualitative) would be of value to address the key issues. Adopting this type of methodology may also prove beneficial in understanding student's experiences in the about market during COVID. The dynamic nature of employment meant that students had a range of different experiences during this time and that adopting a qualitative approach would allow for an exploration of their experience and provide insight into how they coped during this exceptional period.

CHAPTER 6 QUALITATIVE INVESTIGATION

This chapter presents Study 4 of the thesis using a sample of students based in the same HEI as the previous studies. Using semi-structured online interviews, this chapter reports the findings of 12 interviewees who worked or did not work during the COVID-19 pandemic. The narratives regarding changes of employment (see 6.3.1) of Study 4 partially contributed to the latter part of Aim 2, which considers changes in paid employment. The themes regarding psychological impact (see 6.3.2) and coping processes and strategies (see 6.3.3) contributed to Aim 3 and Aim 4. Aim 3 investigates the internal psychological factors in part-time employment including stress, coping and self-efficacy. Aim 4 evaluates the dynamic process adopted by students.

This chapter firstly justifies a qualitative approach and the rationale for using interviews and template analysis as described in Section 6.1. It then reports the study materials, procedure and analysis method in Section 6.2. Following this, the findings are presented in Section 6.3. After a summary of the findings, the strengths and limitations of this study are discussed, and future directions are outlined in section 6.4. Finally, a chapter conclusion is provided in Section 6.5.

6.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the final study of the mixed methods design. After two studies were conducted using a quantitative approach, this final study sought to explore students' unique experiences of employment whilst in HE. First, the decision to adopt a qualitative approach requires some consideration. Specifically, the latter part of Aim 2 focuses on changes within student employment, and it is anticipated that this will be dynamic. In addition, Aim 4 focuses on exploring the dynamic process adopted by HE students to manage their education and work roles. To explore such dynamic perspectives, it is argued that a qualitative study is more appropriate at this stage of the thesis. A qualitative approach focuses on developing our understanding of the students experience and the meaning that they ascribe to these experiences. This approach is appropriate (i) to allow us to answer the “how” and “why” questions (Edmonds & Kennedy, 2017, p.142) and (ii) “to reveal and understand phenomena within a particular context” without inferring any causation (Edmonds & Kennedy, 2017, p.143).

Second, the previous study (Study 3, Chapter 5) investigated student employment and the related psychological factors during the years 2020 to 2021 against the background of the COVID-19 pandemic. It showed the overall trend of changes within student employment including a decline in the percentage of students involved in term-time employment, increased weekly working hours and type of jobs were different compared with Study 2 conducted in 2019. It was argued that the changes identified by Study 3 were due to the COVID-19 pandemic acting as a macro economic and social influencer. However, as a quantitative study, Study 3 only provided a snapshot of such changes and was unable to disclose the process of the dynamic perspectives within student employment and its associated psychological variables.

The true stories from individual students would further explore the changes within part-time employment found in Study 3, the psychologic impact they experienced and how they coped with these. Such further exploration not only reflects the core concerns of the researcher and this thesis but also provides insights that cannot be gained by a quantitative approach. Exploring individual perspectives based on a qualitative approach could also develop and expand our current understanding in greater depth. A qualitative approach additionally functions as a triangulation, a common approach in social science (Jick, 1979).

Third, it is a practical choice rooted from the philosophic stance of pragmatism to address some of the issues raised or unanswered in the preceding Study 3 (Chapter 5). Therefore, Study 4 ought to address the practical need of answering unanswered questions. Several unanswered issues from Study 3 were identified including the need to explore why the preceding study (Study 3) found a clear trend in students' losing their jobs but for those who were working the results indicated they were increasing their working hours.

Similarly, Study 3 also found that employment patterns³³ did not signify stress and self-efficacy which contrasted with similar studies based on adult workers in pre-COVID times (e.g. Koeske & Koeske, 1989) or using samples from other countries (e.g. Gómez-Salgado et al., 2020). As a result it is worth obtaining further evidence from students themselves to see whether this is a fact that students in differing work statuses, experience similar or different levels of stress and self-efficacy, or whether an untold narrative remained to be uncovered. A qualitative approach would help to address these unanswered questions.

³³ Employment patterns refers to work status and weekly work hours within current workers, categorised as low, medium or high working hours for current, former and no workers.

As stated above, considering the research aims, from a methodological and practical perspective, a qualitative follow-up study is considered appropriate. This qualitative study (Study 4) aims to find:

- (i) What were the changes within student employment during COVID-19 pandemic?
- (ii) What was the psychological impact of student employment and its changes during COVID-19 pandemic?
- (iii) How did students use the dynamic process to cope with employment changes and the associated psychological impact?

Ecologically, there are various ways to investigate individual circumstances including case study, interview, focus group, observation and so forth (Edmonds & Kennedy, 2017; Fossey et al., 2002). The interview approach collects “first-person descriptions of experience” (Fossey et al., 2002, p.727), and can be structured, unstructured or semi-structured. This study adopted semi-structured interviews for three reasons: first, semi-structured interviews allow flexibility (Dunn, 2005), reflexivity (Mann, 2016) and diversity (Longhurst, 2003). Such advantages allow the researcher to investigate the variation within the diverse range of students who may or may not have paid employment experiences. As each students’ experiences is likely to be divergent, a semi-structure interview provides the freedom for the participants to freely tell their story during the interview.

Second, semi-structured interviews protect the privacy of participants in a one-to-one interaction (Oates, 2015). The objectives of Study 4 are to discover the possible psychological impact experienced by students as a result of the changes in employment and how they coped with these changes. Owing to the possibility that conversations have the potential of straying into sensitive areas, exposing feelings regarding presumably negative experiences, the privacy afforded by one-to-one interviews is a strength and could maximise the quality and quantity of data collected. The advantage of protecting privacy and confidentiality in the one-to-one manner of interview helps the potential agenda of intense conversions (Oates, 2015) and by allowing the participant to talk openly and avoids any potential embarrassment which may arise in a focus group.

A third reason for the selection of semi-structured interviews is to minimise the impact of language barriers on the data collection (Barriball & While, 1993). Having one interviewee in each interview, compared with a number of participants in a focus group, also benefits the researcher “whose understanding of English was limited” (Barriball & While, 1993, p.330).

For the researcher, as English is her second language, comprehension is optimised in one-to-one interviews. Thus, adopting a one-to-one semi-structured interviews was appropriate in terms of achieving the research objectives as well as managing ethical and practical considerations.

Finally, there needs to be some consideration of the analytic approach adopted when exploring the interview data. A number of alternative approaches can be considered including grounded theory, interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA), and thematic analysis (TA). The main difference among these analytical approaches is to what degree it allows the researchers' subjectivity, flexibility and reflexivity (Braun & Clarke, 2022). Some approaches are less flexible due to being bound with specific philosophic positions, such as grounded theory and IPA. In contrast, TA is a flexible method to identify, analyse and report patterns embedded in qualitative data (Braun & Clarke, 2006). This approach provides "a really useful qualitative approach" for applied science (Braun & Clarke, 2014, p.2) and well-being research (Braun & Clarke, 2013). Such flexibility is suited to fulfilling the aims of this study, which seeks to explore changes within student employment and possible related psychological variables.

However, TA as a family contains a variety of different approaches prioritising either experiential or reflective views (Braun & Clarke, 2022). The former, code reliability TA (Boyatzis, 1998), for example, considers a quantitative positivistic worldview (a small q position of philosophy to use Braun and Clarke's (2022) parlance). The latter, such as reflective TA (RTA), considers a fully qualitative approach (a Big Q philosophy position) and encourages full flexibility, subjectivity and deep reflectivity to interpret and reflect the manifest or latent meanings embedded in the data (Braun & Clarke, 2006, 2022). In the current study, the researcher has a pragmatic worldview which allows to choose any analytic method that is appropriate and facilitates answering the research questions.

As a convenient and practical choice, codebook TA (e.g. King, 2012) lies somewhere between RTA and code reliability TA. It combines the "Big Q" value of a qualitative paradigm with a structured coding approach and is thus viewed as a "Medium Q" approach according to Braun and Clarke (2022, p.242). It allows *a priori* themes which reduces the workload and provides navigation, so it is especially useful for researchers who are new to qualitative analysis (King & Brooks, 2016). This feature, moreover, fits with the reality of the current research and author.

Practically, as a new qualitative researcher, the author might not be fully confident using RTA. Its characteristics of being highly interpretative might result in a disadvantage, impeding the process of analysis.

Additionally, as a follow-up rather than initial study, the research aims of Study 4 are clear and specific. Such research aims require specific exploration of potential meaningful themes according to the research aims. To achieve the research aims an analysis is needed under the guidance of a ‘medium Q’ position rather than the other two types with either ‘small q’ or ‘big Q’ stances. Such a position is more aligned with codebook TA. Thus, considering the aims of the research and feasibility, codebook TA is appropriate within TA family.

Within codebook TA however, two sub-types hold similar views but use slightly different structures. One sub-type is template TA (or template analysis) which uses “hierarchical coding” and “a relatively high degree structure” (Brooks et al., 2015). It allows *a priori* themes to be developed under the guide of interview questions and/or research aims while being flexible to adapt and refine the priori themes during the analysis process (King, 2004, 2012; Brooks et al., 2015). Whereas the other sub-type, framework TA (e.g. Gale et al., 2013) combines qualitative analysis with the quantified indexing (“data matrix”) and requires team work to guarantee transparency (Braun & Clarke, 2022, p.245). For the current study, the author sought primarily to openly explore students’ first-hand experiences, albeit such exploration would center around research aims. Owing to having quantitative evidence from previous studies (Studies 2 and 3), this study likewise, primarily focuses on qualitative features from students without the necessity of combining it with a quantitative feature. A flexible method without quantification fits this need. Additionally, due to the study being a PhD project, this obviates the need to conduct an analysis within a team. Thus, template analysis is more suitable for this study than framework analysis.

By its very nature, template analysis matches a pragmatist’s worldview. Brooks et al. (2015) explicitly state that template analysis, being flexible, permits “a range of epistemological positions” and is “not inextricably bound to any one epistemology” (p.205). King and Brooks furthermore claim that consideration of ontology and epistemology is not always necessary (2016). This aligns with pragmatism which advocates no epistemological position. Likewise, Crabtree and Miller (1992) also advocate pragmatism. Brooks and King (2014) explicitly endorse it, stating “template analysis is a pragmatic technique which can be applied within a range of different qualitative research approaches” (p.5).

A few strengths of template analysis as a coding technique also benefit this study. First, template analysis is useful as “a cross-case rather than a within-case analysis” (King et al., 2018). It efficiently assembles segments of text about an identified topic (i.e. codes) even in a large volume of text (Waring & Wainwright, 2008). For this study, it involved three groups of students (who work continuously or intermittently or who had never worked), template analysis facilitates identifying themes across cases and three groups to generate overall features (King, 2004).

Second, template analysis clearly defines how themes are generated. *A priori* themes can be created based on theories, research questions or interview topics (King & Brooks, 2016). Based on *a priori* themes, initial and final templates are developed according to codes rooted in raw data (King, 2012). The *a priori* themes and templates facilitate efficient analysis.

Third, and most usefully, the technique provides a natural audit trail through a transparent process of generating themes that are demonstrated by the orderly proceedings of *a priori* themes, initial, updated and final templates (King & Brooks, 2016). This transparent process also provides the opportunities to reflect and check the quality of analysis throughout the whole process. This feature is useful for the author and facilitates transparency of reporting of this qualitative study.

Finally, template analysis offers its unique strengths of adaptability, efficiency, balanced the structure with openness, and transparency (King & Brooks, 2016). For this study, certainly all these benefit the analysis process.

Furthermore, the decision to adopt template analysis also considers its suitability to psychology studies. Template analysis has usually been used in a healthcare research context (Waring & Wainwright, 2008) and business and management (King et al., 2018). It is recommended for psychology research (Brooks et al., 2015). After considering the variety of qualitative analysis approaches as well as methodological variations within TA, template analysis was determined to be the most appropriate approach for this study.

6.2 Methods

This section describes the interview approach in more detail outlining the research design, participants, materials including measures, procedure, analysis method and the ethical considerations for Study 4.

6.2.1 Design

This study utilised online one-to-one semi-structured interviews as a qualitative approach. It served as the last part of the mixed methods design.

6.2.2 Participants

Twelve participants were recruited according to their work status, i.e. consistent worker, intermittent worker and no worker. The participants were drawn from the same HEI sampled in Studies 2 and 3. The reason for sampling from these three statuses was based on the findings from Study 3 (see section 5.5.3). Briefly, this approach benefited the investigation of unanswered questions related to consistent workers, those who lost their jobs (a subtype of intermittent workers) and no workers.

The age of participants ranged from 20 to 34 years (see Tables 54-55; additional details are provided in Appendix 21). The average age of the participants was 22.83 years with a standard deviation of 8.19 years. Three-quarters of participants were female (n=9, 75%) and one-quarter were male (n=3, 25%). The majority (n=9, 75%) were Scottish students, two were EU students (17%), and one was from other parts of the UK (8%).

Table 54 Participants Profile

Participant no.	Pseudonym	Gender	Work Status	Number of paid jobs	Job Information
1	Angus	Male	Consistent worker	One	Fast food
2	Brodie	Male	No worker	Zero	Seeking jobs
3	Cara	Female	Consistent worker	Two	Restaurant; retail shop
4	Daisy	Female	Intermittent worker	Four	Restaurant; supermarket; supermarket; restaurant
5	Emily	Female	Consistent worker	One	Café shop
6	Freya	Female	Intermittent worker	One	Café shop
7	Grace	Female	Intermittent worker	One	Fast food
8	Harper	Female	Consistent worker	One	Government office
9	Ivy	Female	Intermittent worker	One	English tutor
10	Jessica	Female	No worker	Zero	Avoiding jobs
11	Kayla	Female	Intermittent worker	Two	Clothes shop; GP
12	Leo	Male	Consistent worker	Two	Fast food; health care

Table 55 Participants Profiles under Each Work Status

Work Status	n	Participant No.	Mean Age (Years)	Gender (Frequency)		Year of Study (Frequency)				Student Status (Frequency)				Fundings (Frequency)		
				Female	Male	Year one	Year two	Year three	Year four	Scottish home student	Other parts of UK	EU	Only tuition fee	Only life expenditure	Tuition fee and life expenditure	No funding
Consistent worker	5	1, 3, 5, 8, 12	22.0	3	2	2	1	1	1	3	1	1	2	0	2	1
Intermittent worker	5	4, 6, 7, 9, 11	21.8	5	0	2	1	1	1	4	0	1	3	0	2	0
No worker	2	2, 10	27.5	1	1	1	0	1	0	2	0	0	1	0	1	0

6.2.3 Material

The materials for this study, namely, an interview protocol and a set of emotional touchpoints. A protocol containing semi-structured interview questions (Appendix 22) was used as a guide. It was developed based on a broad view of research questions after several discussions with the author's supervisors. Both content mapping and mining questions were designed to ensure that interview questions optimally explored the breadth and depth of interviews (Ritchie & Lewis, 2007). Questions were framed to avoid leading interviewees and at the same time allow them the freedom to answer freely, in as much as they wished. All questions were asked against a background of COVID-19 pandemic. Main questions, sub-questions and related supplementary prompts were scheduled according to three considerations. Part one focused on what happened to students' employment during COVID-19 pandemic. Part two included questions about university study, that served to explore potential relationship between work and study. Part three explored potential psychological consequences of work changes and explored students' corresponding coping experience. Under each part, a broad, ground mapping question was asked first, and then exploratory questions aiming to probe further followed (Ritchie & Lewis, 2007).

Emotional Touchpoints (Dewar et al., 2010) (see Appendix 23) were also used. These were presented to participants *via* a shared screen on Microsoft Teams™ during the interview as a probing tool to encourage students to speak about their true feelings. Students were also invited to share why they felt such emotions.

Emotional touchpoints were initially used within a medical practice area (Dewar et al., 2010). The touchpoints were used as a facility to explore patients' emotion, then they were invited to talk about why they felt in such way (Dewar et al., 2010). Afterwards, the stories which the patients described would be returned to the patients to be edited and finally would be shared with hospital staff and other patients (Dewar et al., 2010). In the current study, the researcher adopted the first two steps of the original method. This technique allowed participants to share their emotional experiences with the researcher. The last two steps were not adopted because sharing stories with other participants was not part of the design of this study and not included in the consent form and other ethic permission.

6.2.4 Procedures

6.2.4.1 Recruitment and Interview

Following ethics approval (see Section 6.2.6), approaching emails were sent to 92 potential participants who left their contact details in Study 3 survey. If students agreed to participate,

interviews were scheduled online through the HEI Microsoft Outlook Calendar. Consent forms were sent via emails to participants to be signed. After receipt of the signed consent form, each interview was conducted via Microsoft Team™. Each interview lasted between 45 minutes and 1 hour. All interviews were conducted from 26th July to 20th August 2021. Participants had the option to have their cameras switched on or off. The interviews were recorded synchronously and automatically transcribed within the Microsoft Teams™ meeting. Video clips were stored automatically within Microsoft Team™ online space secured under the researcher's account.

6.2.4.2 Data Transcription

Automatic transcriptions along with the video clips of interviews were downloaded from Microsoft Teams™ to the author's secure laptop within 48 hours of completing each interview. The names of participants were erased within 7 days from all transcripts. Transcription was further refined in two stages. First, viewing the downloaded videos to accurately capture the content of the conversations. Second, reviewing the videos to correct information and anonymise any information related that might identify participants.

6.2.5 Analysis and the Theoretical Framework

6.2.5.1 Theoretical Framework

As stated in introduction (Section 6.1), the overall philosophy of pragmatism underpinned the qualitative analysis in the current study. Concerning qualitative data, the author specifically holds an ontology and epistemology of critical realism. Critical realism stratifies reality into three layers (Bhaskar, 1979, 1998, 2008; Fletcher, 2017). The core is the 'real', where causal mechanism exists. The second layer is 'actual', a world independent from human knowledge and cannot be fully accessed. The outer layer is 'empirical', which is the world humans perceive and experience. Through the empirical layer, science and research can discover causal mechanisms in the core, the 'real' (Fletcher, 2017). This epistemology acknowledges that any research can empirically disclose a perceived reality which may not be the 'actual' reality, but such empirical knowledge can lead to the 'real' by discovering the causal mechanism. Opposing pure realism, critical realism acknowledges the power of the human mind and human experiences and their influence on knowing the empirical reality (Bhaskar, 1979). Hence, stories from student employment as an empirical layer can only be accessed by examining their reflections.

This philosophy, on the one hand, aligns with the research aims of this thesis' research to discover psychological changes underpinning student employment by accessing empirical data. The purpose of exploring the deeper causes of events offers the possibility of finding underpinning causal mechanisms of the psychological impact of student employment (Bhaskar, 1998). On the other hand, critical realism supports template analysis which combines 'Big Q' value of a qualitative paradigm with a 'Medium Q' approach (Braun & Clarks, 2022). Related to this limited realism, the analysing of data requires credible interpretation and the adoption of reflexivity (King & Brooks, 2016) (the researcher's consideration of reflexivity is discussed in Section 6.4.2.3). To reflect the researcher's philosophical stance, a top-down approach was used to inform the *a priori* themes in the analysis. Other emerging themes and sub-themes were rooted in the data; this is a bottom-up approach. To ensure the quality of such analysis, both quality control (see Section 6.2.7) and reflexivity were utilised as King and Brooks recommend (2016).

6.2.5.2 Analysis

Template analysis, a type of TA, was utilised. Template analysis identifies themes across the cases to form a hierarchical structured template using an iterative process (King, 2012). The process commonly starts from *a priori* themes and progresses through the formation of an initial template after which the templates are updated resulting in the composition of a final template (King, 2012). Usually *a priori* themes are used as a guided direction pre the coding and then modified to form the initial template and updates till achieving the final template. Themes in the template reflect "recurrent and distinctive features", "particular perceptions and/or experiences" and are highly relevant to the "research question" of the study (King & Horrocks, 2010, p.150).

Transcripts were analysed via a process of seven steps recommended by King and Brooks (2016). *Step 1* - familiarisation with the data, the author familiarises herself with the data through the transcription process and by re-reading the transcriptions several times.

Step 2 - preliminary coding, after carefully considering the research aims, the researcher generated an *a priori* theme template (see Table 56) with criteria based on the research questions. The themes comprised employment changes, psychological impact and coping. Four interview transcriptions were then coded according to the criteria under the three themes labeled with different colours (an example can be seen in Appendix 24). This step identified the data relevant to each thematic area of interest.

Step 3 - clustering, codes under the *a priori* themes were clustered into meaningful groups as sub-themes and new themes and accordingly arranged in a hierarchical order. During this time, modifications were made to insert sub-themes under the themes to transparently incorporate nuanced information.

Step 4 - reiterative coding, clustering and re-ordering were conducted on four included transcriptions until satisfaction of examining nuance in the data and exhausting the new themes and sub-themes. An initial template (Appendix 25) was then produced.

Step 5 - developing the template, the author applied the initial template to four more transcripts where steps 3 and 4 were repeated, and then amended the initial template to the first version of updated template (Appendix 26). Then four more transcripts were analysed by repeating steps 3 and 4 again, and the template was adjusted iteratively (versions of updated templates can be seen in Appendix 27) then finally reach a final template (see Figure 2).

Step 6, the author applied the final template, once again to all the interviews and the full data set was coded based on it to ensure the final template is fully supported by the original data set (an example of coding based on the final template can be seen in Appendix 28).

Step 7 - writing up, the author presented the final template and interpreted each theme in this chapter.

Table 56 *A Priori* Themes

Themes	Criteria
Employment changes	Any statement about changes in part-time employment.
Psychological impact	Any statement about how students feel about the changes of employment as well as employment per se. (Any statement about feelings to university study and general COVID-19 situation which did not link with employment were excluded/ ignored.)
Coping	Any statement about how students react/cope to the changes of employment and the related feelings.

6.2.6 Ethics

Ethics approval for this study was granted by the Education and Social Sciences School Ethics Committee on 19th July 2021. The approval number was 2021-13934-13840. (Ethics approval letter, Participant Information sheet, Consent Form and Debriefing form are attached in Appendices 29-32.)

Signed consent forms were obtained before interviews commenced. Immediately following interviews, debriefing sheets were sent to all participants as attachments using their HEI

emails. The recorded videos of each interview were stored automatically in the researcher's secure Microsoft space under the HEI staff account. The data in Microsoft Teams™ recordings were permanently deleted after this project was completed and the copies of recordings were stored within researcher's secured university laptop. Within the transcripts and any proceedings, all identification information was anonymised.

6.2.7 Quality Control

During coding, the researchers' subjectivity and reflexivity were both acknowledged. To ensure transparency and quality of the analysis, the author considered controlling the quality during the process of analysis and writing stages. Initially, the supervisory team reviewed and discussed *a priori* themes. The reliability of the template was reviewed within the supervisory team which ensured the quality of the process and the final template. This group also checked the quality of the author's interpretation and accuracy of quotes during the final writing stage.

The author also created a researcher's personal journal as a memo of reflexivity about the analysis process (see Appendix 33). The case summaries for each interview were created and samples are attached in Appendix 34. Case summary is suggested by King and Brooks (2016) as a document reflecting the overall story of a case and the dynamics of the interview. Case summaries demonstrated the immediate impression and response to interviews from the researcher's perspective (King & Brooks, 2016). By providing a holistic view of a case, the researcher's case summaries compensated for a particular shortcoming of template analysis, i.e. emphasising themes across, rather than within cases (King & Brooks, 2016).

6.3 Findings

This section presents the findings of this study. After illustrating the final template, the three main themes are introduced individually. After introducing the theme, illustrative quotes are provided and interpreted in line with the theme. Finally, the previous research related to each main theme is addressed.

The final template is illustrated in Figure 2. It suggests that employment changes under the influence of COVID-19 pandemic were characterised as disruptions to and modification of employment. Such changes resulted in psychological impacts featuring as stress and impacted well-being, less control and meaning. To cope with the changes within employment and its psychological impact, students dynamically utilised coping processes including prevention and reactive coping.

Figure 2 Final Template

6.3.1 Employment Changes

This theme represents changes to student employment as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic. Employment changes identifies what was different, alerted or modified within student employment as a result of the pandemic. The dominant changes were characterised as disruptions to and modifications of employment. This theme and its sub-themes answered the research question (i) - What were the changes within student employment during this pandemic?

6.3.1.1 *Disruption to Employment*

This sub-theme represents the overall impact of COVID on industries where students worked. It appears that student employment was interrupted as a part of the disruptive impact to the labour market by the pandemic. The first and most salient disruption was furlough. ‘Furlough’ referred to the Coronavirus Job Retention Scheme (CJRS) in which employees whose work was paused due to COVID restrictions, received 80% of their current salary or previous average salary with a maximum of £2,500 (UK Government, 2024). Furlough was

implemented originally from March to September 2020 and extended until September 2021 (UK Government, 2024). If students were employed in non-essential sectors during the CJRS implementation periods, they received furlough. As below, students who worked in food/catering jobs were furloughed when lockdown(s) occurred. Such jobs include work in fast-food stores, restaurants and café shops.

“They just shut us down and started paying us like an average wage... We were getting that weekly until they opened up again.” [Angus, p.2³⁴]

“I wasn’t in the restaurant for a while because of furlough”. [Cara, p.2]

“(I got) furloughed to start with”. [Daisy, p.1]

“I was furloughed for about 2-3 months at the stage prior to start”. [Emily, p.1]

“With the COVID you were getting furlough money for the time you weren’t working”. [Freya, p.3]

“We were furloughed that I wasn’t working sort of during that time.” [Leo, p.2]

The duration of furlough interruption varied. The industries in which students worked and the policies of their employers contributed to this variation. Most employers followed the lockdown timeline and their employees’ furlough ran accordingly. Students working in food/catering services were furloughed when the venues closed during the first and/or second lockdown. For example:

“When restrictions like tightened again I was on furlough then I was off furlough and then from January, well from late December, until mid-May, I was on furlough again until the restaurant reopened.” [Cara, p.2]

“Furlough would be from the start of the lockdown started the furlough scheme I think, and I was furloughed up until like mid-July.” [Leo, p.3]

In contrast, the furlough scheme did not apply to essential sectors such as health and social care, administration and grocery shops. None of the students who were employed in these essential jobs mentioned furlough experiences. This included Cara and Daisy who worked in a grocery store as a second job, Harper who worked in an emergency office of the government, Kayla and Leo who worked in health care jobs. Besides, Emily worked in a café

³⁴ All such page numbers in this chapter following quotes of the participants represent the page numbers in the transcripts of the according participant.

where the employer found a “loophole” [Emily, p.2] that resulted in workers being denied furlough during the second lockdown.

By way of contrast to the above, the COVID-19 pandemic also created new student job opportunities in some essential sectors. Some students regained or found new jobs. Kayla temporarily returned to her previous job in health care: *“I’ve just started working back at my old job”* [p.3]. After Daisy was furloughed and made redundant in restaurant job, she later found a new job in an ‘essential’ shop: *“I started working in a supermarket, two days after lockdown ... then I started working in another supermarket.”* [p.1]

Furlough in food catering jobs not only benefited students’ finance without having to work but additionally created new job opportunities in essential sectors. Some students seized the opportunity of furlough to find second or extra jobs. When their job in a fast-food venue was furloughed, Leo sought another job in the NHS despite still being paid 80 % of the normal salary by the first employer: *“when I was furloughed ... I was quite lucky to be able to start to get (NHS) bank shifts”* [p.2] Similarly, Cara stated furlough created an opportunity for her second job in retail sector: *“I was on furlough again until the restaurant reopened, but during that time I took a second job in [SHOP NAME].”* [p.2]

Besides furlough, and the potential for new opportunities, students’ employment was disrupted by several other changes such as lost jobs. The reason for losing jobs or job opportunities could be either voluntary or compulsory. Some students chose to voluntarily quit their job.

“It was a waitress thing so it's sort of food and beverage. I quit that job September of last year.” [Freya, p.2]

Another student chose to quit one job when their old job was available again when COVID restrictions lifted.

“I was only there for a couple of months. There were just concerns paying travel, travelling wasn't working out, and then I went back to my waitress job as the buildings opened up again.” [Daisy, p.1]

In contrast to voluntary quitting, some students lost their jobs or job opportunities. Being made redundant was an example of being forced to stop working: *“... obviously a lot of*

things happened so [I] got made redundant” [Daisy, p.1]. Similarly, Brodie lost the opportunity of job trial. “I was actually on trial for a paid job ... but then it got stopped because of COVID” [p.2]. He explained the interruption of the trial job was related to closure within the non-essential industry. “I got cancelled because literally all coaching got shut down.” [Brodie, p.2]

Based on these cases, the employment status during COVID-19 pandemic for student workers appeared changeable and unpredictable. Student workers mainly experienced furlough and job loss. Furlough however, also created new job opportunities, creating a situation of dynamic work status changes switching between employed, unemployed and holding multiple jobs. The changeable work status blurred the distinction between work statuses potentially explaining why no significant differences were found for stress, self-efficacy and some coping strategies between employment status groups as reported in Chapter 5.

In previous literature, the students’ experience of furlough shows a similarity to full-time workers. The dynamics of changing work status and interrupted work activities were also reported (e.g. Resolution Foundation, 2020; Adams-Prassl et al., 2020). First, most full-time student workers’ furlough experience was similar to full-time workers. Furlough as a part of government support to retain employment, applied to “around 4.1 million of the UK’s 27.9 million employees” (Resolution Foundation, 2020, p.3). Second, the experience of losing jobs was comparable to full-time workers. BBC news (Chan & Plummer, 2020) reported that “the number of people in work fell” and the same job loss was confirmed in empirical studies (Adams-Prassl et al., 2020). The risk of losing jobs were apt to happen to those “with the lowest incomes” (Allas et al., 2020, p.2) and atypical employees such as those who worked on temporary contracts for varied hours and those had more than one job (Resolution Foundation, 2020). The temporary nature of the latter categories of employees was similar to that of student workers.

In contrast, finding new jobs or even extra jobs was not reported in research articles based on full-time workers. It may be that, as a flexible workforce, student workers are more likely to seek new working opportunities than full-time workers because the former were more motivated by direct and immediate financial necessity (Richardson et al., 2014).

6.3.1.2 Modification of Employment

The second major change in student experience of employment during COVID was modification of employment. This sub-theme refers to the changes in the daily work experience within a single job context. This includes a change to work hours, shift/work patterns, daily routines and work activities. COVID-related restrictions created a situation where shifts varied, working hours fluctuated and work patterns changed for working students.

Following the lockdown period(s) students tended to work more shifts and were given more shifts or were asked to increase their working hours. Some students worked overtime. For example:

“So there is a lot of overtime...there was definitely a lot of overtime and extra hours”.
[Daisy, p.7]

This was supported by other interviewees who indicated that they worked additional hours due to COVID. In fast-food jobs, more shifts were available:

“I did end up picking up a lot more shifts. A lot more shifts than I would have done if COVID didn't happen.” [Angus, p.5]

Similarly, this happened in retail work:

“I'm contracted 13 and a half but you can pick up extra shifts on like a marketplace so I usually do just pick up as many shifts as I can...I'm doing about maybe about 20, 30 hours”. [Kayla, p.3]

Students explained the source of extra shifts and hours. As flexible labour, student workers covered full-time workers' annual leave as well as sick leave. Despite COVID travel restrictions, full-time staff still took their annual leave which needed to be covered by flexible student workers. As one student said *“I'm doing holiday cover at my old job now”* [Kayla, p.3] which was endorsed by another student:

“Obviously original staff still have holidays to take..... so we were covering a lot of a lot of annual leave, and a lot of them sort of get their days off”. [Daisy, p.7]

When COVID infection increased, more sick leave occurred. Infected staff had to self-isolate. This rule resulted in a shortage of staff which in turn created the opportunity of more shifts and more work hours for student workers. As Leo indicated, this happened in the health/social care sector:

“They need to cover for someone sick. So, with obviously all the staff isolations there was quite a lot of shifts going around”. [Leo, p.4]

Likewise, this was experienced by those in some other sectors. For example, Angus worked in the food/catering sector and stated:

“There was a lot more shifts available cause people were getting COVID. Or they just like wanted shifts covered anyway”. [Angus, p.5]

Covering both normal annual leave and sick leave for full-time workers may explain the previous findings of increased weekly working hours in Chapter 5. The findings here support one suggestion discussed in Section 5.5.1.2 to explain that the increase in working hours identified in the survey data was the result of sickness cover and annual leave of full-time workers.

Additionally, the number of working hours were described as fluctuating along with the opening times of the venues in non-essential sectors under COVID-19 restrictions. When venues were first closed and later were staged to return to normal, working hours changed accordingly. Consequently, the working hours and shift/work pattern (i.e. when workers start and finish work) changed due to the varied opening times of the venues. As Cara described, working hours were down to zero during venue closure, “... *in September there was like a three- or four-week period where the restaurants closed again*” [p.3], and later increased with shop open time being staged back to normal.

“When we reopen then we were only allowed to open to six. So, our working hours were shortened ... I went back in May, obviously the opening hours extended again so we're back open till 10”. [Cara, p.3]

Some pattern alterations were due to social distancing leading to swapping shifts. Swapping shifts retained the same total work hours but resulted in start and finish times being altered. Angus for example, stated he worked “*the same hours*” for each the shift, but his start time changed to early hours: “*I started doing different times, like I’ve been starting five, six a.m.*” [p.5] Likewise, the same alteration of work pattern was reported by another student who explicitly said it was a shift swap.

“...they've been more likely to shift swap. Yeah, so like you would need to start earlier and finish earlier just to do with seating because there's less desks now obviously so they can't have so many people in ... So, you're still working like 9 hours but it's just instead half 8 you would start at half 7...”. [Harper, p.3]

The other alteration of the shift/work pattern was extending original shifts, which added more hours as well as altered the start and finish times: “...you end up doing like 8 or 8-9 hour shifts instead and like you’re five you’re meant to do that day.” [Daisy, p.7]

These examples demonstrate the reasons for fluctuating working hours, altered shifts and varied work patterns but they were all associated with COVID including COVID isolation, staged opening time and social distancing. These changes however, created a problem. As changes to hours worked and shift/work patterns were mostly temporary, student workers were usually asked to change such work arrangement at short notice via staff social groups such as Facebook, mobile Apps or text messages. For example:

“We've got a Facebook group chat and everyday it's the manager asking ‘can anyone come in today cause we're running really low on staff?’ Uh it happens a lot.” [Angus, p.5]
“You get a text like the night before being like ‘hi, I know you might start at four, can you come in at two instead?’” [Daisy, p.7]

Arranging such working pattern changes at short notice was especially relevant to a flexible and instantly available work force (Kaykisiz & Akpinar, 2021). Being flexible, student workers contributed valuable labour to comply with temporary arrangements in terms of work hours, shifts and work patterns. This has also been reported in pre-COVID times (Canny, 2002) but gained salience during it. Using instant, informal channels to communicate and organise work shifts might compel student workers to comply with industry needs. Short

notice requests are known to require good time management, requiring students to organise extra work around their study needs (Hammes & Haller, 1983).

Finally, work duties and activities were altered due to COVID protection procedures such as PPE. PPE was intended to provide safety in the workplace. However, work routines correspondingly changed. To comply with regulations, daily work routines had to be altered to accommodate extra duties/tasks regarding PPE and other COVID-related restrictions. Extra duties such as policing social distancing, checking trace and track, limiting the sale of products and using PPE correctly were mentioned (see following paragraphs).

The implementation of PPE plus the related extra duties/tasks resulted in sometimes unpleasant burdens for student workers. Duties in one job suddenly doubled. As a shop manager, extra duties were passed onto Emily- *“...the only difference is that they expected staff to police their social distancing” [p.4]* and *“then track and trace started...we had to make sure that everybody does it.” [p.5]*

For non-managerial staff normal duties doubled: *“...you're adding to list of tasks you need to do- ten times on to that, you're adding double onto that.” [Freya, p.11]* Besides cleaning, she was assigned to control customers as well: *“we suddenly got the job of having to control customers, where we can regulate people” [p.3]*. Overall Freya experienced doubled responsibility: *“I felt like my responsibilities that can grow and grow and like twice...” [p.15]*. Similarly, properly worn PPE in health care contexts became an extra task: *“We are given all of the PPE that we need and it's your responsibility to use it correctly.” [Leo, p.11]*

Working in a grocery shop, Daisy faced panic buying customers. She had to limit the amount of essential food to be sold per customer. This led to unpleasant extra duties which did not normally happen in pre-COVID times:

“Because we're getting told by staff from head office and then we can [tell] half the story to the customers... it was really stressful, trying to tell people, you know, you can only have, you know, X amount of bread, X amount of milk”. [Daisy, p.4]

Extra duties and tasks were in addition to the normal workload and absorbed into ordinary work routines, creating difficulty and even chaos for workers. In this study, this happened to students who worked in restaurant and catering, retail shops, admin offices and social/health care venues. These findings support the results of full-time workers reported in the literature using quantitative methods. For instance, Moyo (2020) found the pandemic resulted in

“longer working hours, increased workload, irregular work shifts” (p.323) in adult workers. Moyo also found the shortage of PPE to be a particular issue (which is not supported by this study) possibly due to Moyo’s study being conducted at an early stage of COVID breakout. Among previous studies, only a few acknowledged the increased workload. Hoedl et al. (2022, p.2496) interviewed nursing staff who stated the extra requirement to “perform additional tasks” increased the qualitative workload. Hoedl et al.’s (2002) findings align with similar concerns found in the current study, that the implementation of PPE and restrictions created chaos in the workplace and increased work burden.

In summary, working under COVID conditions for students changed from being steady to unsteady during this pandemic. The dynamic changes happened first in industry as disruption was created by furlough and other changes such as lost jobs and new opportunities. This made work status rather changeable, blurred and unsteady. The blurred work status might explain the unanswered question regarding why the main effect of employment status relating to some of the psychological factors was not statistically significant in Study 3 (Chapter 5). However, such non-significant psychological factors (i.e. stress, self-efficacy and some of the coping strategies) also need to be examined before confirming this possibility. Second, in each job, daily working hours, shift/work pattern, duties/routines and other work activities were also modified. Such modifications added an increased workload burden for student workers. The findings of employment changes also support the suggestion in Chapter 5 that, as a flexible labor force, student workers are the main force with which to cover absent full-time workers during COVID-19, challenging normal routines and activities. As discussed before, there were similarities between what happened to student employees and to full-time workers (e.g. Adams-Prassl et al., 2020) such as furlough, lost jobs, and interrupted job activities due to COVID impact to the whole industries.

6.3.2 Psychological Impact

This theme identifies the psychological impact that resulted from changes within student employment during the COVID-19 pandemic. This impact is primarily on students’ psychological state. Students’ sense of stress and decreased well-being, along with their sense of control were adversely impacted. However, students’ sense of work-related meaning improved as did their sense of self. This theme and its sub-themes answered research questions (ii) - What was the psychological impact of student employment and its changes during this pandemic?

6.3.2.1 Stress and Impacted Well-being

The first psychological impact was on stress and impacted well-being. Negative emotions and reduced well-being were rooted in employment changes during the COVID pandemic. Stress adversely impacted overall well-being to varying degrees.

At a severe level, a couple of students were diagnosed as suffering stress-induced symptoms during COVID period. Such a severe situation was so intense that it required medication:

“From about the August, I really started to notice my mood dipping. I did just feel a bit low and it [was] not really going away. Um, book to my doctor about it, got some medication.” [Leo, p.11]

Similarly, Angus had to take medication to manage his emotions: *“...my anxiety is gone through the roof. You know my doctor is recommending like some anti-depressions.” [p.19]*

For those without a formal diagnosis, stress was high enough to cause them to quit their jobs or describe a severe impact on their general well-being. Such stress was significant. For Freya, stress from COVID changes within work was strong enough to make her quit:

“I quit that job... it was the added pressure of the COVID restrictions and that kind of COVID environment that probably made it just kind of like double more stress inducing.” [Freya, p.2]

Daisy, a supermarket worker described working during COVID as full of stress undermining her well-being.

“It was just quite stressful that people were talking to us, to act and like we were kind of looking enemy and we weren't trying help from the war...definitely a dead effect for well-being and so sort of especially mentally”. [Daisy, p.5, p.11]

In contrast, mild levels of stress were perceived as manageable. Cara explicitly said overall she *“wasn't under stress” [p.2]* and she became *“used to” [p.3]* the changes in work pattern. In daily work however, she admitted her job was *“busy and it can be stressful” [p.5]* and *“the distress comes from busyness” [p.5]*.

Like her, other students also commented on the source of their stress. First, stress impacting well-being was due to job changes during the COVID pandemic. Experiencing shift/work pattern changes, Angus admitted *“I’ve been starting 5.00 a.m., 6:00 a.m. which was different for me, and that took its toll”* [p.5]. Ivy worked as an English tutor whose teaching was delivered online. The COVID pandemic nevertheless stopped her going into the office frequently while she was work from home. This made her feel depressed- *“I feel like it’s a bit depressing staying at home to work and to study”* [p.4].

For Freya, added work duties and a changeable daily routine resulted in confusion around responsibility which increased worries and caused her to quit the job. Changes to routine and duties were the stressors for her:

“It was probably why I left, I kinda confuse and kind of worry going into shifts... it maybe probably because I couldn’t balance that, couldn’t feel comfortable where I was working.”
[Freya, p.6]

For Daisy, stress came from social interactions with customers. Panic-buying customers transferred their fear to shop assistants and abusive interactions became a significant stressor: *“just for that abuse what we’re getting every day... get screamed at and called all these names”* [Daisy, p.11] Likewise, other students experienced abusive customer interactions that seldom happened pre-COVID.

“Pre COVID, I never had any issues...during COVID, generally most customers were really rude and really abrupt, and they’re blaming you for everything... There was a lot of screaming at me and my staff, a lot of cursing...honestly all of it was just because of asking them to follow the government rules.” [Emily, p.15, p.5]

This stress, caused by extra duties (asking customers obey government rules) came directly from abusive interactions with panic-buying customers. In Emily’s food venue job, waitresses and the manager were both treated as scapegoats just like what happened to Daisy who experienced the same in a grocery shop:

“The language that they were using, the way they were acting...it was just the way they were sort of releasing those feelings and it was like we were the punching bags.” [Daisy, p.14]

For other students, stress from both workload and customers' abuse occurred concurrently, or as sometimes happened, the former induced the latter. "*With tons of the people*" [Grace, p.7] waiting for the food service. Grace experienced such abuse:

"...it's drunk people shouting abuse you cause you can't give them what they want... they're shouting about food not coming in." [pp.6-7]

Second, some stress was rooted in workload. For Cara, when suddenly "*so many people walk in the door*", she felt she was "*running about daft*" [p.5]. Her experience demonstrated that too many customers contributed to the increase in quantitative workload and that busyness resulted in feelings of stress.

"You can have quite a lot of customers and so that's where the stress comes from in my work. Um it's about how many customers we've got in... It comes from the busyness or how busy we can be." [Cara, p.5]

After COVID-19 restrictions lifted, work became busier. More customers meant more work:

"It's just a lot more work for us, because we are having to deal with more people like there was a cap on how many people were allowed in the store, and now there's not, so we could have 400 people in the store at any time". [Grace, p.6]

Work pace or service speed also contributed to qualitative workload and resulted in stress from daily work. For Angus who worked in a fast-food job, the fast work pace induced high stress: "*it's high stress...you need to go fast.*" [Angus, p.5].

Similarly, in the case of Leo as a manager, the stress came from both the fast pace and the workload challenging the capacity of staff: "*it can be hard going ...it's just [FAST-FOOD SERVICE], it's busy and you have to be quick*" [p.23]. "*when you've got less staff in with more customers to service, it could be quite difficult*" [p.4].

Additionally, during COVID, stress also came from concerns around safety in work and the related responsibility for family members. Work was not safe anymore. Even with all the protective restrictions: "*the problem is that they're breathing on us.*" [Grace, p.5] because

“we have to stay safe for them, they don't have to stay safe for us” [p.6]. Nearly every working student who lived with family worried about the safety issue in work: “what if I take something home from work. But if I give it to her [her mum], what if she ends up ill. So lot of personal stress.” [Daisy, p.5]. Freya expressed the same concerns “I felt very anxious before going back...I'm not feeling completely comfortable with going back into this” [p.4].

Facing customers and *“any of them could have COVID”, Angus worried “I could get it [virus] from them [customers], I could bring it back home” [p.22]. This meant work is risky for student workers’ family:*

“I think the big thing that changed me personally was to worry, you know, my mom was vulnerable...every time I leave this house, I could be bringing this [virus] back, I could be responsible for her [his mum] getting seriously ill.” [Angus, p.21]

Students’ feelings of stress ranged from severe to mild, meaning the emotional and well-being impact from changes of employment could vary. In fact, stress *per se* is a compound and ‘elusive’ concept rather than a simple one (Blaug et al., 2007). In the work environment, “work-related stress occurs when there is a mismatch between the demands of the job, and the resources and capabilities of the individual worker” (Blaug et al., 2007, p.4).

Theoretically, this supports the notion that employment changes and workload act as stressors for student workers as current study indicates.

The stress from changes in employment during COVID was reported in a few articles from other countries, confirming that students’ anxiety and depression were affected (Cao et al., 2020; Li et al., 2020). Wang et al. (2020, as cited in Ho et al., 2020) found the psychological consequences included stress, anxiety and depression and the threats of negative emotions led to low mental resilience. The above results endorsed that current finding of stress and impacted well-being as one consequence of employment changes.

Another study also identified fear of COVID within restaurant frontline employees in the US “was positively associated with both job insecurity and emotional exhaustion” (Chen & Eyoun, 2021, p.1). This result supported the current project’s finding that safety concerns in work during COVID time resulted in increased stress in the current study sample.

Additionally, the current study also provides new evidence of stress from employment changes and the social interaction with customers. The abusive behaviours from customers were provoked by the implementation of goods limitations, extra restrictions, and panicked

mood during the pandemic. The current findings regarding stress and well-being supplement the results relating to stress reported in Study 3 (Chapter 5) and identify related stressors including workload (increased activity and faster work pace), employment changes, abuse from customers and safety concerns.

6.3.2.2 *Less Control*

The second psychological impact was that students felt less control in work as an impact of COVID related changes. With pandemic-related employment changes, students felt disempowered in work. Less control was related to when or where students worked.

First, when work arrangements changed, student workers felt less control over when and where they worked. After lockdown lifted, Freya felt forced to return to work after furlough, *“feeling you have to go back into (work)”* [p.4]. Kayla felt less control over which job she should keep. She said, *“[I] definitely never felt in control”* [p.11]. No matter how much she liked her NHS job, she did not *“have the chance to keep [it]”* [p.17], because *“they’re like looking for someone full time and I can’t give them that”* [p.17]. *“If I had the chance, I would take that in a heartbeat. Yeah, I don’t have that choice.”* [p.17] Her choice was to keep her low-paid, clothes shop job to *“have a bit more stability when I’m back at Uni. Just a bit more money to live on and go on”* [p.17].

Second, students felt they had limited power over what they could do in work. What made Emily very angry was that she could do nothing to improve work safety. Customers were out of her control, *“...we weren’t allowed to say anything...you couldn’t even ask them [customers] politely to wear one [face mask].”* [p.14] For Leo, as a shift manager, he felt powerless in terms of safety concerns for his staff. He was aware of his *“responsibility to make sure they felt safe at work”* [p.17] but he admitted that he could only do what was in his power.

“There was only sort of certain things that we could do. There’s only so much that I can do as I am a middle level shift manager, but that we can’t facilitate sort of thing it’s out of my hands. So that was like [a] frustrating time” [Leo, p.17]

Finally, for a few student workers, work was changed from being in control to having less control in terms of shifting in locus of control from internal to external due to employment changes. For instance, Freya had only one shift in work which was not an issue pre-COVID time: *“I only had one shift a week so it wasn’t too much to balance between that”* [p.22].

During COVID however, “*doing the kind of those part-time jobs today, they have their own kinda stress and anxiety*” [p.3]. One shift became a source of stress that was beyond her ability to bear: “*...but I think it was during the COVID-19 lockdown because there was that anxiety about working.*” [p.22]

The feeling of less control within student workers has been investigated as external or internal locus (Rotter, 1966). External locus is defined as “beyond” control, whereas internal locus relates to what is “within” the reach of a person (Alias et al., 2012, p.185). Accordingly, external locus of control increases stress, whereas internal locus of control may reduce stress. For instance, Anderson (1977) found internal locus of control to be associated with less stress. In the current study, what participants narrated was mainly external locus, i.e. they believed the outcomes were largely out their reach.

Locus of control was previously demonstrated not only as a way of dealing with stress (e.g. Anderson, 1977) but also was associated with general self-efficacy as a trait. Repeated experiences of having internal locus of control contributed to improved self-efficacy but more experience of having external locus decreased self-efficacy (e.g. Shelton, 1990). In contrast, investigating adult workers, Rothmann (2001) found that both internal and external control did not significantly correlate with self-efficacy. Sampling full-time adult workers, one study found employees “who operate from an internal locus of control and who demonstrate high levels of self-efficacy reported lower levels of perceived stress” (Howatt, 2012, Abstract). This result hinted that both locus of control and self-efficacy are associated with stress. This could be one explanation for the stress and decreased well-being identified as the first sub-theme in Section 6.3.2.1. This hints that stress and decreased well-being might link with the locus changes from internal to external and hence relates with self-efficacy as a trait in a long run.

6.3.2.3 Meaning

The third psychological impact of COVID-linked employment changes, ‘sense of meaning’, was described as a positive impact. Students reflected that whether their jobs mattered to themselves or others was an important factor determining their perception of ‘self’. Expressions such as “respected”, “meaning” and “purpose of work” and other positive descriptions were used. Such expressions represent the meaning of job *per se* and/or the expanded meaning orienting to self-aspects.

Student workers felt their jobs were meaningful if they contributed to people's life. The sense of meaning in their jobs led to positive evaluations of self. Such positivity was particularly prevalent in health sector workers as they had important responsibilities: "...in the hospital you have a lot more responsibility." [Leo, p.22] This job was deemed worthy as Leo was "...able to contribute something..." [p.3] by his small deeds but "enough to just help them [patients] through a little bit." [p.20] Similarly working in a health care job, Kayla felt positive by helping others: "Satisfied in NHS job. Some days when you feel like you've done a good job of helping someone" [p.11] "you feel like is purposeful and you feel like you're doing a good job and genuinely helping people." [p.10]

Helping others and related positive feelings were also experienced in other sectors such as essential shops. Daisy worked in a grocery shop. Engaging in conversation with customers not only made customers happy but also made herself feel positive:

"Because you are helping a lot of people without knowing it by having that wee 5-minute conversation because going for the shop might be the time leave the house to see someone, especially the older generation... they always still call you [saying] '[you]made my day', '[you]made my week', 'thank you for talking to me' and you do kind of feel sort of weirdly happy and satisfied in yourself." [Daisy, p.11]

Harper felt positive working in a meaningful job, which helped others and made a difference. She worked in an essential industry- an emergency helpline office. The importance and meaning of this job added positive self-evaluation.

"The smallest things can really turn it around and then like if you're able to like make this small a bit difference, like that's obviously really the positive thing that you have helped someone." [Harper, p.13]

This additionally happened in food/catering jobs during COVID time. Though fast-food jobs are common for students (Lucas & Ralston, 1996), during the pandemic, Grace felt a sense of meaning in their work routine: "...putting burgers and the toasters helped" [p.3]. All these added positively to value and self-evaluation: "I like feeling useful...I feel like I'm doing my best work" [Grace, pp.2-3].

Second, when student workers sensed being respected and having purpose in their employment, it boosted their feelings of self-confidence. For Leo, his fast-food job was

described as “*definitely helps me in confidence level*” [p.18]. For Angus, his sense of confidence was associated with an offer of promotion that rewarded him with respect in work:

“We're going through the promotions that makes me feel confident in my ability and myself as a person. It also makes me feel respected.” [Angus, p.13]

When the problem of a lack of training for new staff in the kitchen occurred during COVID, Grace offered help, “*helping them out, making sure that they're doing things right*” [p.3]. In doing so, she was in the process of “*[going] up like a team leader sort of role*” [p.3]. This boosted her self-confidence.

This sub-theme revealed a positive impact on students because jobs brought meaning, respect and purpose. Such jobs added positive feelings and mattered to students’ sense of self. The meaning of work was “overall value or worth of the job” (Wrzesniewski et al., 2003, p.96). It reflected workers’ understandings of work and “the significance” of work (p.99). It comprises three components, i.e. “the meaning of one’s job, one’s role, and the self at work” (p.99). A person usually interpreted “the job and its tasks/activities” as job meaning, “the role(s) at work” as role meaning and “self in the job” as self-meaning (p.100). Self-meaning represented identical “qualities” of oneself and “elaborated self-narratives” within social interactions of work (p.102). In other words, how others in work interacted with the employees decided what they feel about their self-meaning. In the cases of this interview, students stated both job meaning (e.g. when they mentioned meaningful job *per se* or its tasks/duties) and role meaning (e.g. when they mentioned being promoted to a leader role) and linked both with self-meaning. Meaning of work as a positive impact might importantly balance negatives in the overall psychological well-being of student workers (Steger, 2016).

In summary, the psychological impact of employment changes includes feelings of stress and an adverse impact on general well-being, of less control and increased sense of meaning. This theme reveals stress and reduced well-being result from employment changes (which includes social abuse from customers), increased workload and increased safety concerns related to COVID. A second impact was feelings of less control in respect of when and where to work and daily work experiences. These aspects of work were possibly perceived as external locus of control. Sense of control in other published studies has been shown to be associated with stress and self-efficacy (e.g. Anderson, 1977; Shelton, 1990). Opposing the

negative impact, the last impact, a positive one, was that students sensed an increased meaning of work during the pandemic. Meaning of work was also perceived by students to relate with meaning of self and might serve as a positive anchor to balance the negatives.

6.3.3 Coping Process

This theme illustrates how student workers cope with the stress of employment changes and its impact to their personal well-being. This theme addresses research question (iii) - How did students use the dynamic process to cope with employment changes and the associated psychological impact?

As the preceding theme indicated, facing changes in the workplace, students felt stressed, had reduced general well-being and less control. To manage these changes students employed coping strategies. Coping strategies are a way of “how people actually react to stress” (Rabenu & Yaniv, 2017, p.8). Coping was defined “as constantly changing cognitive and behavioral efforts to manage specific external and/or internal demands that are appraised as taxing or exceeding the resources of the person” (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984, p.141). The strategies advanced by interviewees in this study, represent a dynamic process which comprises two parts, i.e. prevention as preventive coping and using active behaviours, rationalisation, releasing emotions in supportive social circle as reactive coping.

6.3.3.1 Prevention

As a student worker, the risks in work as well as conflicts between work and study posed equal threats to their well-being (Dakas, 2011; McNall & Michel, 2011). Students addressed how to prevent or avoid compelling scenarios and emotions aroused by work *per se* or conflicts between work and study, such as being stressed by abuse from customers or time constraints due to work and study. Foreseeing such consequences, students adopted preventative measures to avoid future stress through two approaches. They developed awareness and set priorities. Preventative coping was implemented before negative consequences became a reality with the aim of avoiding difficulties (Schwarzer, 2000).

6.3.3.1.1 Having Awareness

Prevention started with having awareness. Awareness of well-being in the workplace were utilised by non-workers and workers. Working with patients in the health care sector, Leo was acutely aware of the need to fully appreciate his role and responsibility from patients' needs:

“...it was you have to remember that the person that you're being presented with isn't always that person...you're the person is stopping them from doing what they want to do, because we're not like the patients” [Leo, p.5]

As a non-worker, Jessica was aware of stress and well-being and coped by avoiding paid employment despite experiencing financial pressure. Without income from employment, she found herself “...*spend[ing] my savings...*” [p.10]. Due to protecting her vulnerable ex-husband, however she had to remain unemployed because every day was a risk for them during the COVID pandemic. Her awareness was rooted in her need to be cautious as a carer to a vulnerable person during the pandemic:

“So for my mentality was more about keeping him safe...I live on edge like I edged like...anything can go wrong any minute...” [p.10] “... been in care and having that awareness, now I know don't do too much, so I'm happy with my choice...so I rather be happy and eat macaroni than stress myself out” [Jessica, p.2]

6.3.3.1.2 Setting Priorities

Students also set priorities to avoid conflict between work and study and its related future stress events. This approach counters the ‘less control’ issue. Students tried to retain and if necessary, re-gain control by setting priorities. The methods of prioritising included switching full-time to part-time employment, reducing shifts or working hours during term-time, not working completely or even quitting existing job(s) if necessary.

Setting priorities as a strategy meant term-time employment ideally ought to be part-time, so some students switched from full-time work to part-time once HE started. Harper, worked full-time before commencing HE studies said: *“when I had decided to go back to Uni....I needed a part-time job...it just was more ideal for me going to Uni” [p.4]* Similarly, Leo chose to *“go part-time” [p.6]* in work when entering HE.

Both Harper and Leo are exemplars of school returner students. Some of them might choose strategically to avoid working during their first term. Kayla is one of them:

“At the time of joining Uni, I didn't think I would have been able to cope having a job...So the thought of having a job is just so overwhelming. I don't think I would have managed” [Kayla, p.2]

She then started to work during summertime. When term recommenced, however, extant circumstances determined whether she coped or not. Kayla's arrangements suggest a strategic mindset:

"I started working at the end of May this year. Just to, you know, like a kind summer part-time position... I just picked up the job to give me money to last through, but hopefully I will be able to keep that on while I'm studying this year." [Kayla, p.2]

Likewise, students also strategically scheduled fewer working hours during term-time and more during summertime. Such as, *"I'm doing more hours over summer, but they know once I go back then I'll drop back down and maybe just like two days."* [Cara, p.3] Another example was Leo who reduce shifts: *"I had to reduce my shift of [FAST FOOD SERVICE]."* [p.6]

However, during COVID interruption, the employment changed (6.3.1) and the short-notice arrangement both made prevention rather difficult. For instance, it was problematic to rearrange time around study timetable due to changeable shifts. Such as this example:

"...it's just annoying that you don't really know how many shifts are doing during the week ...So she was giving me five shifts and I was just trying to give them away...I do actually have an exam this day and she gave me a shift." [Grace, p.6]

Difficulties of rescheduling timetables and extreme stress might trigger an extreme option such as quitting a job to prioritise study. Quitting a job was a last resort for students. Freya decided to *"quit that job"* to facilitate studying: *"I prioritised my study over my work"* [p.6]. Furthermore, this decision was also to prioritise well-being or prevent foreseeing stressful impact from employment: *"I would be in a much worse well-being state...it was a choice between mental well-being and income"* [Freya, p.8].

In summary, the first coping process that student adopted was to prevent future stress by using preventive coping strategies. In the case of student workers (as opposed to full-time workers), students attempted to predict risks associated with the new work environment as well as potential conflicts between work and study.

Overall, these preventative coping approaches were no different to pre-COVID times (e.g. Hammes & Haller, 1983; Richardson et al., 2014). For instance, as early as 1983, Hammes

and Haller interviewed student workers who showed awareness by “choos[ing] carefully the semesters” in which to work (p.531) and set priorities by reducing working hours and even quitting their jobs during periods of high academic stress (e.g. exam, start/end of semester). During COVID, this interview study demonstrated preventative coping might not always be effective.

6.3.3.2 Reactive Coping

Where preventative coping strategies failed, another coping process was used to manage stress in employment and its impact on students during the COVID pandemic. Students adopted active behaviours, rationalising and releasing emotions in supportive social circle to cope the present or past stress.

6.3.3.2.1 Active Behaviours

Reactive coping represents what students do to react to stress. Such coping utilises active actions and behaviours in interacting with the environment stressors such as employment changes. Interview data indicates two main active actions and behaviours as reactive coping. One is problem-solving and the other is time management.

First, students reacted actively to solve problems arising both in their everyday lives and in their working environments due to the pandemic. They took conscious, active actions to solve both sets of problems. Problem-solving involved employment as an important regulator in students’ life to react and tackle specific problems due to changes.

The pandemic impacted students’ lives including their employment (see section 6.3.1), study and personal lives (e.g. Khan, 2021). Facing such changes, engaging in employment or not was an important decision. To cope, students reacted in different ways. Some students utilised engaging in employment to solve psychological problems arising from the COVID situation. This coping involves employment as a regulator to restore balance. For them, ‘work’ was a means of maintaining well-being during the pandemic. When Cara, for example, was “*fed up*” going nowhere, her retail shop job varied her daily activities by allowing her to go “*out of the house*”:

“[job] just to get me out and be doing something else and maybe get me away from studying a wee bit and take my mind off exams...I actually did take more employment during COVID for my well-being” [Cara, p.2]

For Cara and a few others, employment during the pandemic provided a way of easing anxiety of social isolation and hence helps their general well-being which in return facilitated their studies. An extreme example of problems-solving was using employment as an escape or break from the impacted HE study during pandemic (e.g. Khan, 2021) to maintain psychological health. Angus participated in employment to escape study. He used work as an escape or buffer to restore life balance. The psychological function of employment as an escape endorsed his decision to work during the pandemic was correct.

“I couldn't keep up [with study], so I was using work as an escape and it made me happier to be in work... I felt like the extra hours was like positive psychologically to me. It definitely helps mentally, and it was probably a bad way to cope with it. But it did help.”
[p.5]

In contrast, other students remained unemployed to cope with psychological problems involving work issues, personal life and the pandemic situation. One mature student willingly decided to ‘not work’ and stated such decision was necessary for maintaining well-being:

“I know my own mental health and I think it [work] would be too much of a strain on me personally”; “although I'm not financially well off, I'm mentally better off for no working” [Jessica, p.2, p.10].

Above examples demonstrate that participating in employment or not during pandemic is one way of problem-solving which involves decision-making processes in considering possible benefits (e.g. easing social isolation) and disadvantages (e.g. stress) of employment. It appears students engage or disengage with employment to maintain their general well-being. Employment thus acts as regulator, buffering between work and study and elevating their psychological well-being.

Once the decision around working or not was made, students took actions to tackle problems happening in work. A few active actions/behaviours were adopted accordingly. One example was to use effective language to communicate and solve problems. Abusive interactions from customers were stressful in the workplace during the pandemic. When customers were abusive, Emily used explanation attempting to solve the problem: *“Just generally try to just explain that it doesn't come from me. It comes from above. That's the government rules. I'm just doing what I'm told.”* [p.5]

Another example was proactively taking actions. When the kitchen was lack of staff due to a lack of training, Grace solved the problem by volunteering to work in the kitchen and helped training others.

“So I got frustrated and I thought instead of getting annoyed, I can do kitchen and why don't I put my name forward.....then I thought, do you know I can help fix this rather than just getting annoyed when I can help fix the system rather than just getting annoyed about it.” [Grace, p.16]

By *“helping them out, making sure that they're doing things right” [Grace, p.3]* in the kitchen, she faced the problem and actively solved it. These problem-focused actions assuaged her frustration.

Another example was for job seekers to actively search for jobs during the pandemic to solve the problem of being unemployed causing financial difficulties. Some students actively searched and applied for jobs: *“it's just like apply everything I could apply to... it was just a case of just applying to like 10 different jobs a night” [Daisy, p.3]* Freya did likewise: *“I've spent last summer sending job applications to people...just keep sending a few job applications” [p.14]* After waiting for some time, Brodie started to search jobs to solve his problem: *“I'm actively going to search for something [jobs] myself.” [p.8]*

Problem-solving is defined as “the problem-solver navigates through the search space from the problem state to the goal state.” (Newell & Simon, 1972, as cited in Middleton, 2002). Interviews indicate students adopted problem-solving to resolve an unpleasant state of well-being and so reached a better state of well-being. They actively solved the problems by first making a decision to work or not and then took actions to keep that decision valid, by dealing with the problems.

Second, time management was the other active action as coping. For student workers, time management actively focused on solving the problems of time conflict between work and study. As students are learners in HE and an employee in the workplace, time conflict arises and causes stress, especially when preventive coping failed. Working students managed their time by creating weekly routines. For example, Grace stated she needed to change her work shifts pattern after updating her timetable in HE. She managed the time conflict by schedule work and study accordingly in the according term period. *“I'm going to have to re-enrol*

today so I'm getting my timetable tomorrow so I'm gonna have to change it [shift pattern]"
[Grace, p.7]

Daisy planned her week: she *"attempts to break sort of like your day up"* [p.10]. And such plan creates a routine, afterwards she just needs to simply *"stick to this routine"* [p.9]. This routine helps her feel balanced and less stressed:

"It gives me like a routine...I've got like university this day and work in this day...it helps me a lot with like, right, I've got something to do every day. So it's kinda I'm not stressed out...so it kinda helps. It just helps balance me out." [Daisy, pp.2-3]

Similarly, Cara used a *"white board"* to map out a routine to manage time between work and study.

"...on my white board I would have like do this at this time, this at this time I would always kind of take the same break for lunch um I tried to get myself in a routine" [Cara, p.8]

Having two jobs, Leo had to manage time especially carefully; he created his own routine:

"I just sort of felt like every weekend I went to work through the week. I tried to do uni. At the weekend I went to work, through the week I tried to [do] the Uni." [p.8]

The above examples demonstrate that the adoption of effective time management is an active coping mechanism, that was used to resolve time conflicts. Unlike other students who used time management as an active coping process, Brodie allocated time to his various tasks and needs: *"So it would be like 65% university and then 25 percent volunteering and then the rest would be just jam packed with everything else I would do"* [Brodie, p.21]. Brodie stated how he apportioned time to study, unpaid work and personal life. This suggests that as an active coping mechanism, the primary objective is to ensure that all tasks are optimally accommodated. Such strategies have been reported in previous studies (e.g. Greene & Maggs, 2015) but have not been characterised as coping processes.

The above-stated two coping strategies (i.e. problem-solving and time management) represent problem-focused active/engagement coping (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984; Tobin et al., 1984a). Such coping requires actively managing external demands consequent on stressful situations

by voluntarily and consciously controlling one's behaviour and cognition (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984; Gaudreau, 2018).

Previous literature suggests that problem-solving and time management are common strategies used by student workers who target problems or time resource (e.g. Hammes & Haller, 1983; Nonis & Hudson, 2006). For example, Hammes and Haller (1983) through interviews showed that students used rescheduling work timetables to manage time apportioned to work and study. Problem-solving and time management are both claimed as skills developed within part-time employment (e.g. Curtis, 2007; Jacobson & Shuyler, 2013). They are usually treated as separate coping strategies. Considering a wider concept of problem-solving rather than problem-treatment as a specific coping approach, the author argues that time management could be part of a wider problem-solving strategy, a means of managing time conflicts between work and study.

6.3.3.2.2 Rationalising

While stress existed in employment, students sought to minimise its impact to their internal psychological balance and overall well-being by adopting cognitive thinking. This sub-theme represented how students cognitively reacted to avoid or minimise personal harm.

Rationalising is a normal process of cognition of humans. It *per se* is not a coping mechanism. Only when students use rationalising to justify their decision to work (or not work), such rationalisation is reactive coping. Working students cognitively restructured and rationalised what had happened in their workplaces in a positive way. Such rationalising usually justified their made decision to work (or not) by either comparison to others or by positive thinking.

One way of rationalising is comparing oneself to others. Students first made rational comparisons with family members or close friends. Angus justified his participation in paid employment by comparing his own situation with his girlfriend who had lost her job. With such a comparison, he felt having a job was a privilege which endorsed the correct decision of involving in employment:

“My girlfriend lost her job because of COVID, and seeing her struggle for six or seven months with no job was constant rejection.....it made me really like appreciate it [employment]” [Angus, p.13]

He also compared his own situation with his father. Such comparison concluded that to be employed was a privilege and advanced his life by providing financial security.

“I compare my life to my dad's life. My dad was, he was down the mine when he was 16 and he didn't really leave them until he got an injury. Having an anchor like that to compare your life to...you're growing as a person. You're gaining in financial wealth. You're enjoying yourself..... I am privileged.” [Angus, p.13]

A few students compared themselves with a more distant social circle such as colleagues. Harper justified feeling privileged to work by comparing to her colleagues who had lost their jobs: *“I've seen like a lot of staff, especially during COVID of people like losing their jobs. and I didn't experience that. I was very privileged in that sense” [p.9]*. Similarly, Grace compared with other colleagues who are prone to use negative reactions. Making such a comparison, she realised a deeper meaning of doing her job of making burgers.

“I like feeling useful and seeing like everybody [her colleagues] screaming, but I feel like I'm doing my best work when everything is just going wrong” [Grace, p.3]

Students also made comparisons with others in the general public. For example, Daisy compared herself with others who lost their jobs and were without income. She mentioned the financial and social value of working during the pandemic: *“...there were a lot of people last year got made redundant, don't have any money coming in at all, but I could still go to work and make money and get out the house” [p.11]*.

In the above examples, students compared themselves with others, such as who lost jobs. After comparing themselves with those who were less fortunate than them, student workers tended to have positive views of working which endorsed their decision to engage in employment even during a global pandemic.

Thinking positively was another cognitive rationalisation. Nearly every student stated they thought positively. By simply thinking in an optimistic way, students adjusted their thinking to match their reality of working or not working. A few typical examples are illustrated below.

Facing all the possible risks for her vulnerable family, foreseeing financial poverty without paid job, Jessica stayed positive to keep balanced: *“So to me...things can always be worse than sorta my outlook, so it's just taken the positive”* [p.9]

Ivy articulated the same, referencing her optimism as a “mindset”: *“it's just like [the] mindset that I developed after medicines...I mean, it helps me cope with everything...being optimistic really help uh working out everything in life.”* [Ivy, p.5]

Leo endorsed working in health care by acknowledging its emotional impact and accepting it rather than ignoring it.

“I think it's OK to say no, you know what that has upset me, that's I think it's something especially in healthcare, you have to learn to be able to say ‘no, that one has affected me’ like ‘that one’s got to me’. And I'm not ashamed or embarrassed to do it, I don't think so. I think it's a good thing.” [p.21]

Similarly, when Grace faced stress, she assessed her situation as being useful to test her resilience rather than focusing on its negative effect:

“...in the summer months, um, it's been tough. But I do like my job. I like being stressed. I do my best work when someone screaming at me. So, I've been stressed out the last year, but it's been good to test.” [Grace, p.2]

Thus, thinking positively provides the stressed person a way to adjust their thoughts to align with their decisions – to either work or not work during the pandemic. By simply thinking positively, adverse impact of negative emotions is decreased or even obviated.

As illustrated, rationalisation was achieved by both comparison and thinking positively. The purpose of such rationalising was to gain or regain consonance between their thinking and their reality. In the published literature, social comparison was found to link to positive affect (Adler & Fagley, 2005) and self-esteem (Wheeler & Miyake, 1992). The former study identified interviewees using social comparisons to reduce stress and cope with the internal impact from stressors in the workplace; the current study supports these findings within a student worker population. The latter study found those with high self-esteem “were more likely to make downward comparisons” (Wheeler & Miyake, 1992, p.765). This study also suggests that downward comparisons enhance overall well-being, while upward comparison

decreased it (Wheeler & Miyake, 1992). This result supports the notion that cognitive comparisons help in addressing work-related stress. Another study also found that downward comparisons might benefit improving self-evaluations of people with low self-esteem (Aspinwall & Taylor, 1993). In either case, social comparison is associated with self-aspects. In the current study students also used downward rather than upward comparisons. They all compared their own situation with more unfortunate others. As presented earlier, Angus compared himself with his girlfriend who lost her job and his father who had to work in a mine.

6.3.3.2.3 Dealing with Emotions

When negative emotions accumulate, they break the balance and demonstrate the decision of working is wrong. To avoid this, such emotions must be released to keep or regain consonance. Students dealt with their emotions by releasing negative emotions and seeking social support from their family, friends and co-workers. Facing abusive customers, Emily used a joke or ranting with co-workers to achieve catharsis:

“Everybody tried to make a joke out of it and just say, you know people are stupid, they still don't understand and just ignore it after a while. Just kind of have a bit of a rant and complain about them and then just move on” [p.5].

Daisy screamed with her friends or towards her partner: *“we just kind of stood in the back and screamed for five minutes to each other and then went back, like nothing happened.” [p.14]* In those few minutes she felt liberated from her accumulated negative emotions. Emotions could be released quietly and invisibly: *“I just stand there, well, with the mask as well, so I swear back at them without them noticing.” [Daisy, p.14]* But there were *“...definitely a few occasions where they made me cry before I could say anything.” [p.14]* In such circumstances, she cried then *“could go sort of calm [down]”* and *“collect”* herself [p.14]. She used different emotion releasing strategies when facing different social groups. She used passive and covert emotion releasing when facing customers. In contrast, she openly shared her tears and anger with her co-workers, friends or family.

Grace liberated herself by *“laugh[ing]”*, making *“joke[s]”*, *“rant[ing]”* or, *“cry[ing]”* [p.10]. She knew *“it's good to get out the negative emotions you have a joke and you have a laugh...I went on this rant.” [p.10]* In work, releasing emotions bonded workers into a community:

“...there's a joke going on, like the whole stores laughing about it and there is really just a sense of community there.” [Grace, p.10]

The release of emotions usually happened within groups of co-workers, family members or friends. Social interactions in safe social spaces provided the best context or environment for the expression of adverse emotions. Thus, dealing with emotions was usually combined with seeking social support or emotions were released in a context of social support. One platform of support was the inner social circle of family or friends. The father of Daisy provided social support by engaging in conversations with her whenever she needed: *“where you're going, I will speak to you when you wanna be spoken to” [p.24]*. Friends having a similar experience were also important support:

“One of my closest friends used to work with me before COVID, so it did help, cause she had the same kind of situation. I would stop by her shop on a way and just at least talk to her for a little bit. So that was the biggest help.” [Emily, p.13]

Extra support from managers in work was sought as a solution for customer abuse: *“...they were making you cry and all that, you would get management involved independently.” [Daisy, p.15]* Leo as a manager gave staff supportive advice:

“You need to speak to someone about it and it was plenty of, like, support through the other staff and everything...just an impromptu a wee chat in the corner.” [p.20]

External authorities (excepting managers) were occasionally involved to escalated abuse: *“...we get the police involved because obviously that's abuse.” [Daisy, p.15]* As a store manager, Emily sought support from police under extreme circumstances: *“...you had a very extreme situation of having to ask people to leave or phone police.” [Emily, p.15]*

By letting out the emotion and through social involvement with whoever was supportive, students managed to effectively deal with their emotions. These are emotion-focused coping strategies. A recent study sampled adult social workers in western Asia and investigated the association between the coping strategies and distress during COVID pandemic (Ben-Ezra & Hamama-Raz, 2021). It found especially emotion-focused coping such as releasing emotions mediated between the positive associated of psychological distress and job demands.

In summary, in some instances prevention may be unsuccessful and students have to react to the current or past stress. These reactions, as forms of reactive coping are aimed to minimise the impact on students' internal balance to alleviate the adverse impact on general well-being. Students used reactive coping to keep or regain a state of consonance with decision of working or not. Consonance achieved from adjusting cognitive, behavioural and emotional dissonance to remain (or avoid) working during the pandemic. Support systems as platforms for safely releasing emotions, are vital for students' coping.

Reactive coping mechanisms tackle the past or present stressful events aiming to neutralise, alleviate or accept their negative impact (Schwarzer & Knoll, 2003). Recent research also indicates that reactive coping is especially important as it is a direct and instant reaction to address psychological strains from job insecurity (Langerak et al., 2022).

Overall, the theme of 'coping process' indicates students used various coping strategies via two processes which can be classified under different strategies. The first process prevented anticipated stress through preventative coping strategies. Students used well-being awareness and setting priorities to prevent negative consequences. When prevention is not successful especially in circumstance of pandemic, second process of reactive coping is adopted. On one hand, students actively took actions of problem-solving and time management. These active actions/behaviours seek to solve the identified issues, so they represent problem-focused coping. On the other hand, students adjusted their thinking by rationalising and dealing with negative emotions by releasing them with appropriate support networks. As both deal with emotions, so they reflect emotion-focused, engagement coping (Gaudreau, 2018; Tobin et al., 1984a). Such strategies focus on dealing with personal emotions rather than trying to solve problems. Both coping processes were mainly to deal with psychologically negative impacts. Obtaining a sense of meaning from working as a positive impact however, might play a covert role that was not explicitly investigated in this project.

Both preventative and reactive coping processes additionally indicate there is possibly decision-making regarding work or not during the pandemic. The benefits or values of working might support students' decision to take jobs. The risks for family and safety concerns in work coupled with disruptions to personal well-being, however, might weigh against students' decision to work. This notion is supported by previous studies focusing on reason for work or motivations of work (see Section 1.2.2, Chapter 1) which indicate students classified employment's advantages and disadvantages (e.g. McGregor, 2015). However,

these studies haven't considered the dynamic decision-making process. In the cases of this study, Jessica deliberately chose not to work as a decision-making basing on having well-being awareness. Other students all chose engaging in work or seeking jobs.

Once a decision to work or not is made, students tend to maintain and justify their decision by adopting two coping mechanisms. Such coping processes permitted students to maintain their overall consonance to remain working (or not) during the pandemic like majority of the students in this study did. This consonance effort is an antidote against dissonance, which was initially proposed by Festinger (1962). Festinger's cognitive dissonance emphasises changing cognitive thinking, behaviour and emotions to justify or maintain a chosen decision that has more benefits than harm (1962). For student workers, working while in HE especially under circumstances of COVID-19 pandemic, benefitted them in some respects such as finance (e.g. Brennan et al., 2005; McGregor, 2015), increasing meaning of self and balancing psychological well-being. Once the decision to work (even during a pandemic) or not work was made, students deployed coping strategies to validate their decision as the right decision. This explains why students made efforts to address dissonance i.e. to keep or regain consonance among behavioural, cognitive and emotional reactions whether working or not. Although there are cases in this study who cannot manage to cope the dissonance. This led to quitting jobs as the last coping resort such as Freya who cannot balance herself facing job changes and Daisy of whom travelling to the supermarket job did not work out.

Overall students not only coped to employment changes but also used employment as a way of coping to study and personal lives as part of students' lives especially during the pandemic. Participation in employment as an overall coping provides students financial safety and balanced psychological well-being in students' lives.

6.4 Chapter Discussion

6.4.1 Summary of Findings

This section summarises the findings of Study 4 and discusses the strengths of this qualitative study in the context of a mixed methods design. Finally, the author discusses how the findings in Study 4 partially explain unanswered questions from Study 3 (Chapter 5).

Through semi-structured, online interviews and template analysis, this study found that COVID restrictions resulted in working changes in terms of disruption to and modification of employment. This study first reveals what happened to students' employment during the COVID pandemic. The student workforce was disrupted through furlough and shifting job

status including losing jobs, finding new jobs or securing additional jobs. Students also accepted different and extra shifts or varied work patterns, altered everyday routines, tasks and duties. Overall, student workers' jobs became uncertain like those of full-time workers.

Secondly, owing to such changes in employment, the current study found that students were psychologically, adversely impacted. The various stressors to which students were exposed, caused stress although to different degrees in different individuals. Students also felt their overall well-being was impacted. Stress and the resulting adverse impact on students' general well-being is a negative consequence of employment changes, abusive social interactions from customers, increased workload and safety concerns. Students felt a reduced sense of control in work. This sense of having less control, possibly rooted in an external locus of control, might be related to induced stress and associated with self-efficacy. In contrast to these negative impacts, students found meaning in their employment. A sense of meaning in their job and its roles, drove a sense of meaning of self through self-evaluation and improved self-confidence. The meaning of work and self might act as a positive anchor against negative impacts.

Thirdly, students' dynamic coping was processed in two ways. Students utilised preventative coping by having awareness and setting priorities to avoid future stressful scenarios.

Meanwhile, to react to current or past stress, they used both problem-focused and emotion-focused engagement coping to react to external stressors embedded in employment changes to minimise the personal impact from those job changes. One approach was using problem-solving and time management to actively manage stress and well-being via actions/behaviours. The other way was to adopt cognitive rationalising and to deal with emotions in order to manage the personal impact of stress. Overall, the reactive coping of actions/behaviour, rationalising and emotions is to maintain the consonance with the decision to work or not work during the pandemic. These coping strategies and processes provide a comprehensive understanding of how students manage working or not working when in HE.

Finally, this study also partially answered the unanswered questions in Study 3 (Chapter 5). One such question is, why fewer students are working but those who are, work more weekly hours? The answer provided by this study is working students acquired more shifts to cover full-time workers' sick leave and annual leave. This possibly explains the increased weekly working hours in Study 3. Some students lost their jobs although others found different jobs. These findings indicate that essential industries during the pandemic were boosted thus

avoiding temporary closure. Non-essential industries were closed and workers were consequently furloughed or made redundant.

Second, another unanswered question from Study 3 (Chapter 5) is why employment status did not influence stress, self-efficacy and coping strategies. This study also found that work status was dynamic and not clearly defined during the pandemic. Contrastingly, students' experiences regarding stress and self-efficacy were universal but slightly different individually. The individual effect is possibly counterbalanced within a group as well as across work groups in a statistical analysis. Another possibility is that the COVID pandemic universally impacted everyone, including workers and unemployed. It universally impacted the overall labour force rather than specific work status.

Just as this study has strengths it has limitations, meaning that the above conclusions and interpretations should be treated with a degree of caution.

6.4.2 Strengths

6.4.2.1 Empirical Strength

Overall, this study created valuable empirical knowledge regarding employment changes, their psychological impact and coping processes of student workers during the COVID pandemic, expanding on previously published studies. This study thus fills a knowledge gap in this area.

6.4.2.2 Using Template Analysis

This section details the advantages of using template analysis which is a methodological strength of this study. TA is a family of qualitative analyses including reflexive thematic analysis, codebook analysis and code reliability analysis underpinned by various philosophical frameworks (Braun & Clarke, 2022). Template analysis was chosen due to its fit with research aims, a pragmatist's epistemology and the benefits it confers in facilitating qualitative data analysis (see Section 6.1).

First, the use of *a priori* themes, centred around three research questions, guided the analysis. Second, the output from an initial template, updated templates and a final template provided transparent trails for the analysis and acted as a quality check. Third, the hierarchical structure allowed the author to add rich features and maintain transparency of the process (King & Brooks, 2016). Overall, template analysis fitted a pragmatist's worldview and the practical needs of this study.

6.4.2.3 *Quality Control and Reflexivity*

The last strength of this study was that the author has prudently considered the quality control and reflexivity throughout the analysis. Quality is important for template analysis. The author appraises the quality control in this study by addressing potential biases before stating what reflexivity is and why it is important for this form of analysis. It briefly states the author's own reflections.

Reflecting the quality of analysis was vital to making the findings rigorous in conveying and achieving the aims of this study. The quality of template analysis was inspected in three ways (King, 2012; University of Huddersfield, 2023). Using feedback from participants was not possible due to anonymisation after interviews. This study therefore adopted the other two approaches. One was independent scrutiny of the process of analysis and interpretation in the report (University of Huddersfield, 2023). In this study, experts, comprising three academic supervisors, reviewed and gave feedback on *a priori* themes and versions of templates as well as interpretation of findings that featured in the author's writing. The other was creating an audit trail (University of Huddersfield, 2023). This study reproduces the successive versions of the templates and examples of preliminary and final coding as seen in appendices while other audit trails are documented in coded transcripts. However, the potential risks of unconscious bias to the data could still exist due to the author's personal views, existing knowledge and experiences.

Reflexivity, as a vital quality of the researcher, shaped the research process directly and its outcomes indirectly (King, 2012; University of Huddersfield, 2023). The author kept a personal, research journal to reflect her experiences of the process of analysis. Furthermore, case summaries were created as suggested by King and Brooks (2016). As a new qualitative researcher however, her reflection might be limited by a mostly quantitative background and previous knowledge.

6.4.3 Limitations

6.4.3.1 *Overall Limitations*

This study was executed during the COVID pandemic. The background against which this study was conducted limited the generalisation of its findings to normal typical term-time employment. First, the employment changes were specifically under impact of the COVID pandemic. Thus, students' psychological reactions and coping with changes within employment may be different in pre- and post-COVID times.

Another limitation was the difficulty in disentangling and deconstructing students' holistic coping strategies that were interwoven with their response to managing work during the COVID pandemic. Just as the pandemic influenced employment, it changed students' HE studies, personal life and overall well-being (e.g. Khan, 2021; Defeyter et al., 2021). There were many occasions during interviews when students talked about the general impact of the pandemic and its effect on their university study and personal lives. They addressed the combined topics of feelings, emotions and coping. To focus on the purpose of this study, data were separated from students' holistic views which might fail to consider the full context of their narratives. However, to be prudent, it is possible that some forms of coping are responses to both the period of COVID and work experience during it.

6.4.3.2 Limitations of Template Analysis

There are issues of template analysis that need to be considered. On the one hand, the analysis in this study emphasised “develop[ing] themes more extensively where the richest data” (p.203) existed. This raises a possible issue regarding template analysis - themes represent recurrent opinions or experiences of interviewees rather than reiterating ideographical, individual views (King & Brooks, 2016). To do so might result in fragmentising individual experiences, forming cross-cases themes (King & Brooks, 2016). Thus, it is possible that some opinions that are not reported here, are valuable for a few individuals but not sufficiently salient across most cases.

The other potential problem arises from an initial template. It might result neglecting valuable material which did not encompassed in it (King & Brooks, 2016). To minimise this bias, the author used quality control from experts and kept an open mind in updating the template for further versions before constructing a final template.

6.4.4 Future Studies

Sense of control was discussed insofar as it appeared to underpin the psychological impact of working and students' coping mechanisms (see Section 6.3.3). Previously, sense of control was reported to be a core factor related to coping, stress and self-efficacy in the population of workers (e.g. Skinner, 1996). Sense of control could be a central concept related to various categories of coping strategies as well as stress and self-efficacy. Given this, the author proposed a further study to investigate sense of control and its relationship to stress, self-efficacy and coping in the context of student employment.

6.5 Conclusion

Study 4 used semi-structured, online interviews and template analysis to provide ecological, in-depth findings of student employment and the related psychological factors in the same HEI. Students stated they experienced changes of employment as either disruption or modification of employment. During the COVID pandemic, student employment was disrupted by furlough that paused work when workplaces were closed. Students also experienced lost jobs and found new jobs. Their employment was modified in terms of weekly working hours, work shifts/patterns, work duties and other work activities.

All such changes resulted in students feeling stressed as their well-being was negatively impacted. They also experienced less, and loss of, control. They nonetheless, found a sense of meaning in their employment which promoted their sense of self. Sense of meaning of work and sense of self were linked to self-aspects and acted as anchors, giving students psychological resources to cope with the negative aspects of working under difficult circumstances.

To cope with employment changes and their negative psychological impact, students adopted both preventative coping and reactive coping. The former, manifesting as avoidance of future stress and issues, was executed by having awareness and setting priorities. The latter, targeting current or past stress and issues, was used to address either external stressors in students' work surroundings or internal personal impact. To tackle the stress rooted in employment changes, workload and safety issues, students tried to actively solve work-related problems and manage their time between work and study. This coping was sometimes suboptimal during the COVID pandemic. In addressing the personal impact, students cognitively rationalised and used positive thinking to manage difficult situations and release their negative emotions in supportive social circles of family, friends and co-workers. Coping also emphasised that appropriate support systems are vital for full and successful execution of coping strategies and the maintenance of balance. Overall, copings demonstrate an effort to keep consonance against dissonance among cognition, behaviour and emotions of a person after decision of working or not is made. Students not only coped to employment changes, but also utilised employment to cope and balance students' lives. Participation in employment as a overall coping provides students financial safety and balanced psychological well-being in students' lives.

Future research should consider the role of sense of control in student employment.

CHAPTER 7 GENERAL DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This chapter integrates the results and findings from the four studies in this thesis to consider the contribution of this project to the field of HE student employment research, the practical implications arising from the findings and to provide an overall conclusion. The chapter is presented in five sections. The first considers the contribution of each study in addressing the research objectives (Section 7.1). The subsequent two sections (7.2 and 7.3) consider the contribution to existing knowledge and the practical implications for stakeholders, while the fourth (7.4) considers the strengths and limitations of the whole project and the author's personal reflections. The fifth Section (7.5) addresses potential directions for future research in this area. The chapter concludes with an overall conclusion in Section 7.6.

7.1 Objectives Achieved

Previous literature in this area neglected the impact of student employment on a range of psychological variables. This gap in knowledge stimulated this project and its focus on the relationship between student employment and psychological outcomes. In addition, the research project sought to update understanding of the nature and extent of student employment within a Scottish HE context and identify any potential changes in student employment over time. The research focused on one post-92 university in Scotland based in the central and western area of Scotland. The following sections consider how the four studies, as part of a multi-stage mixed methods design, contributed to the four aims of this thesis.

7.1.1 Aim 1: provide a systematic review of the psychological variables that have been linked to HE student employment and consider the potential relationship between psychological variables and student employment.

This objective was primarily addressed in the systematic literature review, Study 1. The review focused on identifying the psychological factors that had been investigated in the context of research considering the psychological impact of student employment. To the researcher's knowledge this is the first systematic review to consider this issue. Previous literature reviews focused mainly on the nature and extent of student employment or treated psychological factors as side products of academic and career outcomes of employment. This

systematic review focused on what factors previous research had studied and which methodology had been used. The review process produced a synthesis of the methods, aims and key psychological variables of previous studies. This process identified gaps within the methods previously adopted and led to methodical recommendations for the next stage of the research reported in this thesis, regarding research design, measurement and sampling.

The systematic review showed that longitudinal designs and the use of mixed methods are rare in this research field, yet such approaches would be useful in investigating complex phenomena or changes over time. The review also highlighted the dominance of *ad hoc* measures that had been used in this area. This may be acceptable when exploring the nature and extent of student employment, however the use of *ad hoc* measures is less useful when considering psychological outcomes. In the latter case, robust psychometric scales should be used. The review showed that psychological outcomes had been neglected when considering the impact of student employment. More specifically, the synthesis of the reviewed literature identified a wide range of potential psychological variables that could be usefully explored. However, the review concluded that three key psychological factors (i.e., stress, self-efficacy and coping strategies) should be the focus of this project.

The systematic review contributes to the existing literature in this area by being the first to specifically focus on psychological factors within the context of student employment.

Previous literature reviews either did not specifically focus on psychological elements within student employment (Astin, 1984; Perozzi et al., 2003) or displayed it as a minor issue in respect of HE students' work (Riggert et al., 2006). The reviews carried out for this thesis not only provides a rigorous review of the literature but also fills a key gap by identifying the limited consideration of psychological factors within student employment. While the review was rigorous, by its very nature it did exclude a number of articles and it is possible that some of these may include some potentially useful information. Overall Study 1 achieved its goal for the project by providing a comprehensive understanding of the psychological variables which should be considered in the context of student employment and hence contributed to the existing knowledge in the area of student employment.

7.1.2 Aim 2: Establish contemporary information on the nature and extent to part-time employment amongst HE students.

Establishing contemporary information on the part-time employment of HE students within a Scottish context was an important primary goal of this project. This goal was addressed by the two online survey studies (Studies 2 and 3). The first survey was carried out in 2019 and

the second took place in 2021. The latter survey was completed against the background of the COVID-19 pandemic that impacted on the original research plan for this project and resulted in the need to adapt the research plan (Study 3, Chapter 5). The findings of the qualitative study into the changes in employment during COVID (Study 4, Chapter 6, Section 6.3.1) also contributed to achieving this aim. Regarding this aim, two aspects were targeted.

7.1.2.1 Contemporary Information regarding Nature and Extent

This objective was achieved by the two surveys conducted in 2019 and 2021. The surveys' results provided the profile of the nature and extent of student employment within this specific HEI. The percentages of those employed, their weekly working hours, type of jobs and pay rates were identified.

With respect to the number of students working, the findings suggest that student, part-time employment is a dominant phenomenon in Scotland that aligns with previous literature in this field (e.g. Brennan et al., 2005; Mercer et al., 2016). The findings demonstrated that in 2019 approximately 70% of current students had worked or were still working. This figure dropped to approximately 60% in the 2021 survey. Even allowing for the impact of COVID in the second survey, the findings support the view that combining work and study is a common experience for HE students.

The survey findings showed that, on average, students worked 19.54 hours per week at the time of the 2019 survey, but against the background of COVID the findings indicated students working nearly 22 hours per week in 2021. Other variations in employment were associated with COVID. For example, in 2019, 'shop work and sale' (30.34%), 'social care' (23.71%) and 'other' work (21.08%) were the top three work sectors. In contrast 'hotel and catering' (12.03%), 'admin and finance' (7.39%) and 'bar work' (5.47%) were the three lowest work sectors. In 2021, against the background of the COVID-19 pandemic, the proportion of employment in the different job categories changed to 'social care' (34.63%), 'shop work and sales' (28%), 'other' (14.37%), 'hotel and catering' (12.03%), 'admin and finance' (7.20%) and 'bar work' (3.57%). This suggests that employment in 'social care' jobs became a more dominant employment sector for students at this time. Finally, the hourly pay rates were shown to be £8.62 in 2019 and £9.64 in 2021. In both instances students' pay rates were slightly higher than extant national minimum wage.

The findings regarding the nature and extent of student employment, though sampled in one HEI, were found to be consistent with previous studies which were based on samples in

Scotland and England (e.g. Josiam et al., 2010). The percentages of working students in the sampled population in this thesis are comparable with those found in other studies (e.g. McGregor, 2015). The findings in this study regarding the types of jobs in which students work, while not exactly the same as in previous studies, largely echoed previous research (e.g. Robotham, 2009). A similar conclusion emerged when considering weekly working hours and pay rates as these were found to match other studies (e.g. Carney et al., 2005) and government NMW regulations (Open government, 2011).

7.1.2.2 Potential Changes of Employment

In the context of Aim 2, potential changes in employment levels amongst HE students had been anticipated. In fact, changes in the level of employment were detected by both the quantitative surveys and the qualitative interview study. First, the comparison between the 2019 survey findings (Study 2 Chapter 4) and the older 1998 survey (McKechnie et al., 1998) showed the extent of the changes over two decades. The percentage of working students increased from 54% in 1998 to 70% in 2019. Weekly working hours increased from 14.30 hours to 19.54 hours for current workers. Hourly pay rates in 1998 of £3.72, when NMW was being launched, increased to £8.62 in 2019. This trend reflects the application of the NMW Act 1998 since its introduction. The findings show that after two decades, student workers are still paid at the basic rate prescribed by the NMW legislation.

Second, the comparison between the 2021 survey (Study 3 Chapter 5) and its 2019 counterpart (Study 2 Chapter 4) demonstrated the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. The findings showed that the average percentage of working students dropped, weekly working hours increased and there were notable changes in employment sectors for students. In the latter case there was a higher proportion of students working in social care, however, the numbers in shop and sale jobs, while fluctuating slightly across the three-time periods in the second survey, showed a very slight decrease. In contrast, the other job types all experienced a decrease in terms of employment levels with bar work showing the most dramatic drop. The comparisons between the three studies (1998 study of McKechnie et al., Studies 2 and 3 in this thesis) and previous studies demonstrate the dynamic phenomenon of student employment. The changes within the nature and extent of student employment are supported by other studies conducted pre- and during the COVID pandemic (e.g. BBC News, 2020b).

Additionally, the qualitative interviews (Study 4) shows that student employment was impacted by the COVID pandemic. Students reported several changes including disruption to and modification of their employment. As with full-time workers, students were placed in

furlough or lost their jobs and experienced changes in their working hours, shifts/pattern, work duties and other work activities. In many cases students showed that they were proactive during this time to find new or extra job(s) and their work changes they experienced were typically arranged at short notice. These qualitative findings provide additional support for the need to understand the dynamic nature of student employment.

Overall, the pattern of findings supports the view that student labour, like the full-time adult labour market, responds to and reflects wider socio-economic changes. This is reflected in the changes in student employment over two decades which reflect natural economic changes, employment law(s) and external influencer(s) such as government policy. The latter is demonstrated by the response to the COVID- 19 pandemic.

Based on its research findings this thesis has achieved Aim 2 of the overall thesis. Studies 2, 3 and 4 provide contemporary information on the nature and extent to part-time employment amongst HE students and demonstrate the changes in student part-time employment.

Such findings signify that participation in paid, term-time employment is the new normal for undergraduate students. This trend will more than likely last for another few decades if there are no significant changes in relevant policies within HE (e.g. fees and funding) and employment in Scotland. This establishes this group of students (i.e. working students) as an important cohort who are not fully recognised within HEIs.

The above findings also suggest that student labour makes a notable contribution to the economy in terms of the number of hours worked and their contribution to specific job sectors.

Based on these findings it can be argued that there is a need for additional research on the impact of students working on their academic achievement and the psychological consequences of working whilst studying.

7.1.3 Aim 3: Investigate the internal psychological factors that are related to part-time employment including the potential consequences (i.e., stress) and related psychological factors (i.e., coping and self-efficacy).

Three empirical studies demonstrated associations of stress, self-efficacy and coping strategies with student employment.

The potential relationship between stress and aspects of student employment status was confirmed by the findings from the quantitative surveys. Stress, which was measured by the

Student Stress Inventory (SSI), indicated that total stress in students who were current workers was at a mild level ($M=79.66$, $SD= 17.62$) in 2019 and at a moderate level ($M=83.18$, $SD=18.48$) in 2021. In 2019, the findings indicated that total stress and interpersonal stress varied significantly between job types. Bar workers had significantly higher total and interpersonal stress than social care workers. However, stress scores across employment status were statistically non-significant. In 2021, stress across employment patterns was non-significant.

While employment status was not linked to stress scores, it was found that for those students who were working, their weekly working hours were significantly and positively correlated with overall stress, physical stress and academic stress. Overall, the findings indicated that total stress and academic stress were predicted by weekly working hours, self-efficacy and some of the coping strategies. Physical stress was predicted by weekly working hours and some of the coping strategies.

The qualitative studies supported the link between work and stress as interviewees indicated that their perceived stress undermined well-being and resulted in them having less control. The perceived stress was linked to workload, employment changes and safety concerns during the pandemic. It can be argued that the loss of control over their jobs resulted in employees feeling their work was influenced by others (i.e. an external locus of control) and this resulted in stress.

The self-efficacy of student workers was measured by the Student Self Efficacy scale (SEE). In 2019, student workers self-efficacy score was 30.48 with a standard deviation of 5.71. Self-efficacy was not found to be significantly related to employment status but was significantly associated with job type. For example, social care workers had a significantly higher self-efficacy than shop/sales workers. In the 2021 survey, student workers were found to have a mean self-efficacy score of 29.38 with a standard deviation of 6.35. However, self-efficacy did not vary significantly between the employment pattern categories.

However, the findings from the qualitative study (Study 4) suggested that employment may be linked with some aspects of self-efficacy with respect to the meaning of their job or work. Students expressed meaning related to aspects of their sense of self which could be interpreted as positive self-evaluation and self-confidence.

The final psychological variable considered was the coping strategies of student workers. This variable was measured by the Coping Strategy Inventory (CSI-32). The findings from

both surveys (2019 and 2021) indicated slightly higher engagement than disengagement coping, but overall coping in 2021 was stronger than 2019. In 2019, the average of engagement ($M=49.92$, $SD=12.77$) was higher than disengagement ($M=45.08$, $SD=12.82$) scores. Comparisons between students based on their employment status found significant differences for problem-solving, social contact and cognitive restructuring strategy. In the case of job type comparisons, significant differences were found for problem-solving, problem avoidance, problem focused disengagement and disengagement.

For the 2021 survey, average scores for engagement ($M=50.05$, $SD=13.13$) were higher than those for disengagement ($M=47.02$, $SD=13.90$) coping strategies. Comparisons between the five employment patterns found significant differences in terms of emotional expression, social contact and emotion focused engagement coping.

In the qualitative interviews it was evident that students coped with stress that arose from employment changes, workload and safety concerns via two dynamic coping processes (see Aim 4). It was evident that stress, decreased well-being and a reduced sense of control were the psychological consequence for students when facing employment changes during the pandemic. On the positive side, however, the findings suggest that students found meaning in their work and that in turn was linked to their sense of self.

Overall, these three studies demonstrate a close association between employment, stress, and coping strategies. This pattern of associations is consistent with findings from studies using full-time employees as participants (e.g. Conway & MacNeela, 2012) and those researchers who only studied one or two factors in the student population pre or during COVID pandemic (e.g. Cao et al., 2020; Swanson et al., 2006).

7.1.4 Aim 4: Evaluate the dynamic process adopted by HE students to manage their education and work roles.

This aim was primarily addressed by the findings from the interview data from Study 4 along with the supplementary snapshot information of coping strategies from Studies 2 and 3. In contrast to Studies 2 and 3, Study 4 adopted a qualitative approach. Semi-structured interviews showed that students experienced employment changes and that these experiences had a psychological impact which students managed using different coping strategies.

Faced with various changes in their employment because of the COVID pandemic, students adopted both preventative and reactive coping strategies via two dynamic processes. From the preventative perspective students used coping strategies to prevent future stress. For

example, students relied on awareness of their well-being and priority setting to prevent conflict, or stress, arising from combining paid employment along with full-time HE study. However, during the pandemic, when preventative coping was not successful, students reacted to current and past stress by relying on other coping processes. On the one hand, they took active actions/behaviours which included problem-solving and time management. On the other hand, they adopted rationalisation and the release of emotions within their supportive social circles. In the latter case students released their emotions in supportive social environments such as family, friends and co-workers. The key aim behind such coping was to manage the external stressors arising from employment and any changes in employment, or to minimise the personal impact to overall well-being and the dissonance created by deciding to work during a pandemic. The aim of all the reactive coping strategies is to support the decision of working or not working during the pandemic. Overall, employment was found to be a way to survive HE in terms of financial and psychological pressures.

The suggestion that students display dynamic coping are supported by various coping frameworks (Schwarzer & Knoll, 2003) along with sense of control theory (Anderson, 1977; Cummings et al., 1991). These findings are also supported by studies with full-time workers during the COVID pandemic (Adisa et al., 2022; Sharour et al., 2022).

7.2 Contributions

7.2.1 Empirical Contributions

The research conducted in this thesis extends previous research and contributes empirical evidence of student employment, linking employment and psychological factors. In the subsequent subsections the author demonstrates this original contribution in relation to the nature and extent of student employment and the associations between work factors and psychological factors of stress, self-efficacy and coping strategies.

With respect to the findings from this study on the nature and extent of student employment, the research provides a contemporary update on student employment and a unique insight into the impact of a major socio-economic incident (i.e. COVID pandemic) on students' employment experiences. The latter provides a non-repeatable opportunity to study macro social and economic influences on student employment. As such it provides a unique set of findings. Other researchers have considered COVID's impact. These however, focused on

full-time workers or HE students without exploring employment (e.g. Cao et al., 2020; Li et al., 2020). This thesis fills this specific knowledge gap.

A second contribution is that this thesis demonstrated that stress is significant factor in life of student workers. This confirms some previous literature which noted that stress and its related negative emotions such as anxiety are an adverse psychological impact associated with student employment (e.g. Dakas, 2011).

The third contribution is that this thesis identified additional psychological factors, namely, self-efficacy and coping strategies. The results provide empirical evidence of their statistical and real-world significant associations with overall stress, certain subtypes of stress and certain indicators of student employment (e.g. type of jobs, weekly working hours).

The above contributions expand our knowledge of the psychological factors associated with student employment. This thesis provides a holistic understanding of these three psychological factors in student employment, namely, stress is a primary consequence of taking part-time employment for full-time HE students and it is related to students' self-efficacy and coping strategies. The latter two factors are both associated with the type of job but only some coping strategies are associated with other employment indicators. This thesis demonstrates that associations between psychological outcomes and HE student workers are important and echo findings that have been previously found amongst full-time adult workers (Anand, 2019). As such, this thesis makes a unique contribution to knowledge.

7.2.2 Theoretical Contributions

This thesis has made a number of theoretical contributions to existing theoretical frameworks. Chapter 1 identified five theories in the domain of student employment (Chapter 1 section 1.3). Although this project was not based on any specific theoretical framework the results and findings provide support for some of the existing theories.

The three empirical studies (Studies 2, 3 & 4) showed that students utilised 'various' coping strategies. Such strategies could be classified under different typology such as engagement and disengagement (Skinner et al., 2003), problem-focused or emotion-focused (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984), preventative or reactive (Schwarzer, 2000), active or passive (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984) coping strategies. The former two typologies were adopted in CSI-32 (Tobin et al., 1984a) psychometric scales in Studies 2 and 3. Some were used to interpret the results of Study 4.

Regardless of typology system, coping strategies shared a common aim in that they sought to achieve a balanced state of life while maintaining full-time study in HE. According to balance theory, the goal is to achieve or maintain balance between time constraints and the demands made on that time by jobs and studies. This thesis supports this theory by identifying that balance was a state students try to achieve by utilising a range of coping strategies. In dealing with the negative impact of stress students identified balance as an ideal state between work, study and general positive well-being. To achieve such a psychological state while experiencing changeable circumstances students used a dynamic coping process via two process including preventative coping and reactive coping to deal with external stressors and personal impact. This suggests that if balance theory is to be supported then it must embrace a dynamic coping process. At present this would appear to be out with what balance theory currently advocates (Richardson et al., 2014).

If a student's life is treated as a holistic process of development, the period spent in HE is viewed as development. Developmental theory was originally applied in the context of discussions relating to younger children's participation in the labour (Nagengast et al., 2014). In that context some researchers argued that working while young may result in the development of skills and ability from their employment experience (Simpson, 2014). In this thesis, students acknowledged using some problem-solving coping. If this is considered a skill, there is no direct evidence showing such skills are developed during HE or at a younger age. Thus, there is no direction evidence to support developmental theory based on the empirical evidence from this thesis.

Warren's primary orientation model (2002) was developed from research involving high school students. His theory suggests that paid employment is a student's choice, reflecting their own orientation to school and work. However, this position is questionable based on the findings from this thesis' two survey studies (Studies 2 and 3) that show that paid employment is a necessity for students to pay tuition fees and/or cover everyday expenses. It could be argued that being able to afford HE without paid work is an option only available to a minority HE students. Additionally, the findings from Study 4 indicate that students' orientation is not static. For example, a student (participant Angus, Study 4) while interested in studying was unable to continue due in part to the COVID pandemic and the impact it had on the delivery and quality of teaching. Against this background students used their employment as an escape from issues within HE, effectively changing from a study to a work orientation. The evidence in this thesis supports the view that Warren's orientations in fact

are dynamic, changing according to context, rather than fixed. Changes in orientation can be viewed as a necessity to survive HE without financial risk and psychological damage.

There is some evidence to support the concept of role facilitation which is found within role theory. Role facilitation emerges when the skills required for work tasks facilitate other roles (e.g. Swanson et al., 2006). In the interviews some students indicated their use of employment to cope with study. The findings from the interviews suggested that the extent of facilitation between the two roles of worker and student may be more extensive than suggested by role theory. Findings from the interviews indicate a psychological facilitation, i.e. employment acted as an alleviating factor to maintain students' psychological health and so facilitated full-time study. There was also evidence of financial facilitation as employment income provided financial security which was essential for students remaining in HE. In addition, the application of role theory in student employment was supported by the interviewees indicating the existence of role conflict when setting priorities between work and study and their reliance on time management coping strategies.

Zero-sum theory (Greene & Maggs, 2015) has been a dominant model within the student employment literature. Aspects of this theory emerged when students discussed their time management and the creation of routines to accommodate their employment and study schedules. The pressures of using limited time to achieve multiple goals reflects the zero-sum concept. However, for many students the issue was less about allocating time resources but rather one of focusing on how to survive rather than emphasising time as a sum.

Overall, this thesis provides evidence which both supports and challenges the above theories. As such the findings from this project are not sufficient to fully support the entire theories (Hammersley, 1992).

7.2.3 Methodological Contributions

While this thesis adopted a mixed methods approach this is not the first time that such an approach has been used in this field. Previous researchers (e.g. Hammes & Haller, 1983) used mixed methods to provide holistic findings. However, this thesis introduced a short-term longitudinal study into the mixed methods design which, to the authors knowledge, has not before been used in this context.

A second innovation of this thesis is the emphasis placed on the use of robust psychometric measures to assess psychological variables. The use of psychometric tools was combined with an *ad hoc* survey, providing a model for future related research. Previously, studies had

used either *ad hoc* surveys or psychometric measurements alone (e.g. McGregor, 2015; Teng, 2008).

The third notable aspect of this thesis is the use of Template Analysis in student employment. Previously, Template Analysis has been used in the domains of management and business psychology (King & Brooks, 2016). Applying this approach to student employment not only supported the work of a new qualitative researcher but, more importantly, was shown to be a tool that facilitated meaningful analysis.

7.3 Implications

As this thesis' research was based on a data from one specific Scottish HEI, it is worth considering existing support systems within the subject HEI. This HEI has a Careers Affair Office, a well-being support service supported via a student app, a web-based psychological support system and a one-to-one psychological counselling service (UWS, 2024a). Except for instant access to web-based support system, other support measures all need to be pre-booked. During the time frame of this thesis, this HEI also provided a newly added direct helpline for psychological support via telephone as well as through the HEI student app on mobile phones. Such improvements have shortened the time and procedure for students to reach professional help. These services aim to help students with mental health issues. It may be however, that students are hesitant to seek professional help when they feel their issues are trivial rather than major. The systems that are in use are designed for general undergraduates and does not consider the particular and psychological needs of working students. Working students are not specifically offered any support.

This thesis' research implies that specialised support from the HEI could be improved to provide peer support specifically for working students. The author has then discussed the implications which might usefully help inform policy debates about pay rates, training and safety of student workers.

7.3.1 Support for Working Students

The three empirical studies in this project (Studies 2, 3 and 4) indicate that working students experience certain levels of stress created by combining full-time study with part-time work. The results show that many students manage to cope, however, they still experienced negative emotions. Moreover, Study 4 showed that support from family, friends and co-workers was most helpful when it came to managing the personal impact and consequences of employment and workload. The findings suggest that support from the peers who have

experience of these dual roles of worker and student was most helpful and effective. This would suggest that facilitating the sharing of students' experiences would be of value and could be a practical form of support that this HEI could adopt.

Since the host HEI has launched a student app, this function could be improved through the creation of a social group or community, specifically for working students or those intending to work. This social group could be created via social media such as a HEI Facebook. 'Peer-to-peer support' is distinct from 'expert' support (Repper & Carter, 2011, p.395) which the HEI currently adopts. It is defined as "a system of giving and receiving help founded on key principles of respect, shared responsibility and mutual agreement of what is helpful" (Mead, 2003, as cited in Repper & Carter, 2011, p.394). Peer support is an important platform for engaging with emotional self-disclosure in students who work as paramedics (Lowery & Stokes, 2005). It helps sharing coping strategies and social support to increase psychological resilience (Agarwal et al., 2020), to reduce feelings of isolation and to increased students' sense of control (Prescott et al., 2020). Hence this thesis suggests provision of peer support at work and in HEI, which might be both helpful and effective for student workers.

During their studies many students turn to the Students Union to resolve their problems (Islam et al., 2021). Given this, it could be argued it would be helpful if the Union provided employment advice and support. Currently student union is staffed by four paid roles including one president and three vice-presidents who oversee education, well-being and development of students (UWS, 2024b). At present none of these roles focus on or include responsibility for working students or job seekers. With 70% of the sampled students in this project having or had work experiences it could be argued that the Students Union should reflect this reality. Within the existing system a post of student representatives could be created to give a voice to students who must combine work and study.

7.3.2 Useful Information for Policy Debates

7.3.2.1 *Pay Rate*

This thesis' research demonstrates that student employment is a normal and important part of contemporary student life. Term-time employment is necessary to allow students to obtain financial security, mental balance and self-meaning. As Studies 2 and 3 indicate, students' pay rate is around the NMW. To survive financially, students must work more hours as interviewees in Study 4 (Chapter 6) intimated.

The intention of the NMW³⁵ was to protect low pay workers. Despite being in force for nearly two decades and despite the economic progress over that time, student workers are paid less than full-time workers and this requires revisiting and revision. Sargeant (2010, p.351) questions “whether the lower rates paid to 18-21-year-olds and 16-17-year-olds can be objectively justified”. Considering student workers provide the same quality of work as full-time workers, such age-based pay rate may represent a form of age discrimination and exploitation of young workers. Equal pay that is not based on age but on work *per se* would benefit by reducing weekly working hours with the aim of achieving financial needs as necessity. The author argues that the pay rate of working students should not establish upon their age alone. The right of an undergraduate as an employee should also be protected in line with full-time employees. This thesis suggests pay parity with full-time workers rather than pay based on a student’s age (Blackham, 2019; Gargouri & Guaman, 2017; O’Loughlin et al., 2017).

Therefore, to solve the issue for working student in HE a solution may be to apply equal pay to student workers and full-time adult workers. Part-time student workers under the age of 21 years might also be paid at the same rate if they work the same hours and work to the same standard. Scottish government should consider further research to gather evidence in justification of effecting appropriate changes to the relevant regulations or laws of general labour with a particular emphasis on equal pay.

7.3.2.2 Training and Safety

This thesis’ three empirical studies suggest that for certain jobs (e.g. bar, shop/sales and restaurants) the job sector should provide help to support workers when dealing with stress that can be caused by dealing with customers and clients.

The findings from Study 4 highlight the fact that the COVID pandemic resulted in staff experiencing levels of abuse in service sector jobs and that this abuse created external stress. Most student workers report a so-called ‘one-off clash’ with customers (e.g. Einarsen et al. 2020). In reaction to similar incidents a new law may be passed in England and Wales, tackling increased violence and abuse against shop workers (Whannel, 2024). Offenders in shops will be charged. The thesis suggests that similar regulation in Scotland could be useful.

³⁵ The NMW was for age under 25-year-olds and only one aged 25-year-old or above can get the National Living Wage (NLW) (UK government, 2019). In 2021, this age was revised to 23 years (UK government, 2022). It was recently updated again to apply to those age 21 years and above on 2nd April 2024 (Espiner & Hooker, 2024; UK government, 2024).

Data from this thesis recommends that HEIs update lists of risky jobs and shift patterns (e.g. night shift) and advise student workers accordingly. This could then be uploaded to a student app or website.

7.4 Strengths and Limitations and Reflection

7.4.1 Strengths

This thesis has several strengths. It offers a certain degree of innovation, makes theoretical contributions, tests methods, and has practical implications.

This thesis is innovative insofar as its primary focus is on exploring the relationship between student employment and the psychological consequences of combining work and study. The project, unlike many previous studies in this area, sought to capture the dynamic nature of employment by exploring changes over time. It innovatively compared one study (Study 2) with McKechnie et al.'s 1998 study. Such a comparison has not previously been reported.

This thesis has made several contributions to existing theoretical knowledge. This is evident in four areas. The project raised awareness of the psychological aspect of student employment. Second, it provides a baseline for the nature and extent of student employment in contemporary Scotland. Third, it contributes to existing knowledge regarding the impact of the COVID pandemic on students' employment changes and its psychological impact. Fourth, it suggests future directions for research.

In addition, this thesis has tested and used methods innovatively within the student employment domain (Section 7.2.3). The project adopted a new approach by combining a short-term longitudinal timeline within a mixed methods design. It also combined an *ad hoc* questionnaire with standardised psychometric scales, and in doing so filled a significant knowledge gap.

Finally, this thesis' project has several practical implications. One suggestion is to replace pay based on age by a more equitable system that recognises the utility student workers bring. The other is to consider issuing new law to protect workers from abusive behaviours in service sectors such as in shops. It additionally evidences specific measures for HEIs to help student workers.

7.4.2 Limitations

There are several limitations that should be noted. One major limitation is that the thesis' project relied on data from a single Scottish HEI. As this HEI is a post-92 institution and thus

may not represent all HEIs, or even all the post-92 HEIs in Scotland. As such the generalisability of the findings is likely to be limited.

The project also experienced disruption caused by the COVID pandemic. This affected the original aims and timeline for the project and particularly affected Studies 3 and 4. The latter studies took place at a unique time and set of social circumstances; it is difficult to know how this affected participants.

From a methodological approach it might be argued that a longitudinal design or a life-long trace study would allow a more effective exploration of a complex phenomenon.

Unfortunately, such a project would fall outside the resources available for the present study. However, the goal of being able to investigate student employment from school to HE and into adult careers would allow full exploration of the dynamics of student employment.

Finally, the issue of effect size must be considered. In both surveys most of the significant results of the ANOVA and the Welsh test produced small effect sizes varying from .005 to .038. Effect size is “the degree to which the phenomenon exists in the population or the degree to which the null hypothesis is false” (Cohen, 1988, pp.9-10). A statistically significant result means the effect degree is “some specific non-zero value in the population” (p.10). It implies that “the larger this value, the greater the degree to which the phenomenon under study is manifested” (p.10). The effect size represents the practical power of the IVs to DVs in real life (Morris, 2020). Cohen (1988) has categorised effect size as ranging from small, medium and large for different statistics³⁶. According to Cohen’s category (1988), most statistically significant results in this thesis would be categorised as being small effect sizes.

This suggests that the variation sourced from work variables accounts for only a small portion of variance in a real-life context. This demonstrates that the psychological stress, self-efficacy and coping results for working students may be influenced by a range of factors beyond the current focus (i.e. the work variable). A wider consideration beyond the work variables is necessary to explore students’ key psychological states of stress, self-efficacy and coping. In this regard, employment may be but one of the many contributors to the reported psychological consequences of working. As findings in the interview study indicate, participants freely related their feelings about employment, study and family life. Similarly,

³⁶ For *F* test based on means which ANOVA utilised, the small power is with $f=.10$ and equals to $\eta^2=.0099$ (Cohen, 1988, p.286), the medium power is with $f=.25$ and equals to $\eta^2=.0588$ and the large power size is $f=.40$ and equals to $\eta^2=.1379$ (p.287).

in interviews, stress in interpersonal relationships, physical environment and academic context readily emerged. Thus, it would not be ecologically valid to separate employment from a student's academic and family life. This may demand further study using more creative methods and ensuring that ecological validity is incorporated.

7.4.3 Reflection of the Researcher

In this section, I first consider my growth as a mixed methods researcher and then review the impact of COVID in terms of the way the pandemic interrupted research plans as well as creating research opportunities.

Prior to this project, I was a confirmed, quantitative researcher holding a view of positivism. This may unconsciously have led to adopting unhelpful approaches in seeking the 'truth'. For example, by allowing interviewees to use 0 to 10 Likert scale to judge how strong their feelings were during the interviews reflected that part of my instinct as a researcher anchored and habituated to quantitative approaches.

Overall, within what may be my last experience as a 'student', I witnessed a growth of my own attitudes, spirit of accuracy and critique towards research methods used in this thesis' project. I acknowledge the impact of COVID on this project. When the pandemic arrived in March 2020, there was a need to revise the plans for this thesis to avoid any delay in the whole PhD process. While COVID created research problems that I had to resolve, it also offered a unique opportunity to collect unique data. I have therefore commented on the influence of previous economic changes on student employment, such as the economic crisis in 2008, when I first proposed this research in 2017. COVID-19 provided a unique opportunity to understand the impact on student employment of such an economic influence in an extreme circumstance.

7.5 Directions of Future Research

Based on this body of work, several follow-up studies are suggested. Future research could develop coping strategies research by focusing on sense of control rather than categories of coping strategies (Section 6.4.4). Studies 3 and 4 demonstrated that significant macro events (in this case COVID-19) impact student employment. If student employment is as dynamic as this project suggests, then it could be affected, positively or negatively by other economic changes post-COVID. It would therefore be beneficial to fully understand the dynamics of student employment and its relationship to wider macro social-economic influences. Another proposal is to expand this thesis' studies to provide evidence for replacing age-based pay with

equal pay (see Section 7.3.2.1) and the implementation of laws to eradicate abuse in shops in Scotland (see Section 7.3.2.2).

7.6 Thesis Conclusion

Overall, this thesis provides contemporary information on the nature and extent of part-time employment amongst HE students based on one HEI data using a mixed methods design. It adds to knowledge in this area that there are potential changes in terms of prevalence of paid part-time employment, weekly working hours, type of job, pay rate and more. The dynamic changes of employment, especially the influence of the COVID-19 pandemic is also highlighted. This thesis research shows that increased stress is a primary internal psychological impact of working part-time while studying full-time in HE. It also found a close association between stress, self-efficacy and various coping strategies in part-time employment which also supports both quantitative and qualitative findings. The dynamic coping processes adopted by HE students to manage their education and work roles during COVID-19 pandemic supports a holistic observation that employment *per se* is a way of coping to satisfy financial needs and psychological well-being under pandemic conditions.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: PICOC Framework (Study 1)

Based on review questions, a PICOC framework has been utilized as a formal structure of definition the research scope and an explicit criterion of inclusion and exclusion (Petticrew & Roberts, 2006, cited in Booth et al., 2012, pp.55-56; Boland et al., 2013, p.49). The PICOC form of the current project is referred in Table A1.1.

Table A1.1 Screening Tool (Review Question+ Inclusion criteria)

Review Question: Psychological Drivers and Impact of Part time Employment of undergraduates in Scotland		
Inclusion Criteria (Based on PICOC):		
Population= undergraduates or students in higher education		
Intervention/exposure= doing part time employment or term time work (Job)		
Comparator= None		
Outcomes= Internal/ Psychological drivers, and Internal/Psychological impact.		
Context= Primary focus is on the Scotland, but national and international studies will be considered. No limit of country.		
Undergraduates + Part time Employment + Psychological Elements of Drivers and Impact Screening and Selection Tool		
Reviewer Name:		Date:
Item No.:	Year:	
Title		
	Include	Exclude
Patient Population	Must include	<input type="checkbox"/> Children (EX 1)
	<input type="checkbox"/> Full time traditional Undergraduates	<input type="checkbox"/> Post graduates/ graduates (EX 4)
	May include	<input type="checkbox"/> Non-traditional/mature students/ part time students (EX 2)
	<input type="checkbox"/> High school students (IN 0)	
	<input type="checkbox"/> International students	
Intervention/exposure	<input type="checkbox"/> Taking part in part time employment	<input type="checkbox"/> Students with full time employment (EX 2)
		<input type="checkbox"/> Students without any employment experience (EX 0)
		<input type="checkbox"/> Students in placement or career training/ education programme (EX 3)
Comparators	None	None
Outcomes	Must include	Exclude

	<input type="checkbox"/> Internal/ Psychological drivers Alternative Option <input type="checkbox"/> Internal/Psychological impact May include (Alternative) <input type="checkbox"/> General Drivers <input type="checkbox"/> External Drivers <input type="checkbox"/> General Impact	<input type="checkbox"/> Nature extent <input type="checkbox"/> Impact of Academic achievement
Context	Must include <input type="checkbox"/> Higher education of UK Scotland May include <input type="checkbox"/> Higher education of other countries <input type="checkbox"/> High School education of UK Scotland <input type="checkbox"/> High School education of other countries	Exclude <input type="checkbox"/> Primary School Education (EX 1) <input type="checkbox"/> Post graduate Education (EX 4) <input type="checkbox"/> Other types of Education (EX 0)
Overall Decision	<input type="checkbox"/> INCLUDED	<input type="checkbox"/> EXCLUDED
Notes		

Appendix 2: Data Base of Searching Strategies Applied and Inclusion / Exclusion Criteria (Study 1)

Table A2.1 Items Included after Screen I and Deduplication I

Database Type and No.	Title of Database	Included Items
Online database 1	EBSCOhost*	168
Online database 2	Web of Science	76
Online database 3	Sage	27
Online database 4	Springer Link	25
Online database 5	Science Direct	8
Online database 6	ERIC	68
Online database 7	Taylor & Francis	85
Online database 8	Ingenta Connect	30
Online database 9	Proquest	9
Online database 10	Google	38
Online database 11	Google Scholar	240
Online database 12	Emerlad	24
Grey literature database 1	Opengrey	15
Grey literature database 2	EThoS	2
Grey literature database 3	American Doctoral Dissertation	3
Grey literature database 4	Zetoc	12
Alert and Updated	All database	42
Total	17	884

Note: *EBSCOhost includes source of Education Source, PsycBOOKS, Psychology and Behavioural Science Collection and PsycINFO.

Table A2.2 Criteria of Screen III (Continued details for EXS1 EX)

Code of Screen III	Exclusion Type	Screen II	Exclusion Criteria
EXS2 EX0	Any irrelevant or partial relevant literature	EX0	Any literature is irrelevant. Any literature concerns background information of students or employment. Any literature not contains both study and part time work, including general children, adolescences (age 11-18),

Code of Screen III	Exclusion Type	Screen II	Exclusion Criteria
			<p>Youth (young adult) (age 18-21) and adults/ staff/ part time workers, who are not students. Any literature only concerns work only.</p> <p>Any literature addresses the various aspects of students except for part time working.</p> <p>This criteria is set for any literature missed filtering out at stage of Screen I.</p>
EXS2 EX1	Young Children (age 5-10)	EX1	Any literature concerns children's part time work or work who are from 5 to 10 years old.
EXS2 EX2	Part time students	EX2	Any literature concerns certain students who study part time in higher education, including mature students, or mother (maternal) students and adult students.
EXS2 EX3	Organised training or placement /instruction /intervention	EX3	Any literature concerns project or programmes conducted by institution or staff as a purpose for intervention, work-study training (placement), and other kinds of educational procedures.
EXS2 EX4	Graduates, postgraduates	EX4	Any literature concerns relevant theme of students who have graduated or study in postgraduate level including PhD or Doctorate.

Appendix 3: Crowe Critical Appraisal Tool (CCAT) Form (Study 1)

Crowe Critical Appraisal Tool (CCAT) Form (v1.4)

Reference

Reviewer

This form must be used in conjunction with the CCAT User Guide (v1.4); otherwise validity and reliability may be severely compromised.

Citation

	Year

Research design (add if not listed)

<input type="checkbox"/> Not research	Article Editorial Report Opinion Guideline Pamphlet ...
<input type="checkbox"/> Historical	...
<input type="checkbox"/> Qualitative	Narrative Phenomenology Ethnography Grounded theory Narrative case study ...
<input type="checkbox"/> Descriptive, Exploratory, Observational	A. Cross-sectional Longitudinal Retrospective Prospective Correlational Predictive ... B. Cohort Case-control Survey Developmental Normative Case study ...
<input type="checkbox"/> Experimental experiment	<input type="checkbox"/> True Pre-test/post-test control group Solomon four-group Post-test only control group Randomised two-factor experiment Placebo controlled trial ... <input type="checkbox"/> Quasi- Post-test only Non-equivalent control group Counter balanced (<i>cross-over</i>) Multiple time series Separate sample pre-test post-test [no Control] [Control] ... <input type="checkbox"/> Single One-shot experimental (<i>case study</i>) Simple time series One group pre-test/post-test Interactive Multiple baseline system Within subjects (<i>Equivalent time, repeated measures, multiple treatment</i>) ...
<input type="checkbox"/> Mixed Methods	Action research Sequential Concurrent Transformative ...
<input type="checkbox"/> Synthesis	Systematic review Critical review Thematic synthesis Meta-ethnography Narrative synthesis ...
<input type="checkbox"/> Other	...

Variables and analysis

Intervention(s), Treatment(s), Exposure(s)	Outcome(s), Output(s), Predictor(s), Measure(s)	Data analysis method(s)

Sampling

Total size	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Control
Population, sample, setting					

Data collection (add if not listed)

a) Primary Secondary ... Audit/Review b) Authoritative Partisan Antagonist ... c) Literature Systematic ... (historical)	a) Formal Informal ... Interview b) Structured Semi-structured Unstructured ... c) One-on-one Group Multiple Self-administered ...
a) Participant Non-participant ... Observation b) Structured Semi-structured Unstructured ... c) Covert Candid ...	a) Standardised Norm-ref Criterion-ref Ipsative ... Testing b) Objective Subjective ... c) One-on-one Group Self-administered ...

Scores

Preliminaries	Design	Data Collection	Results	Total [/40]
Introduction	Sampling	Ethical Matters	Discussion	Total [%]

General notes

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Category Item	Item descriptors [YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/>] [Not Applicable]	Description [Important information]	Score [0-5]
1. Preliminaries			
Title	Does the title Include study aims and design? YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/> NA <input type="checkbox"/>		
Abstract (assess last)	Is the abstract informative? YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/> NA <input type="checkbox"/>		
Text (assess last)	Is there sufficient details so that others could reproduce this study? YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/> NA <input type="checkbox"/>		
	Is the text Clear/concise (about writing, table(s), diagram(s), figure(s))? YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/> NA <input type="checkbox"/>		
Preliminaries [4]			
2. Introduction			
Background	Does it state Summary of current knowledge and provide context for the study? YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/> NA <input type="checkbox"/>		
	Does it state specific problems and why? YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/> NA <input type="checkbox"/>		
	Is it linked current knowledge with this study (objectives aims)? YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/> NA <input type="checkbox"/>		
Objective	Does it state Primary objective(s), hypothesis(es), or aim(s) YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/> NA <input type="checkbox"/>		
Is it worth continuing?			Introduction [4]
3. Design			
Research design	Does it state Research design(s) YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/> NA <input type="checkbox"/>		
	Is it appropriate? YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/> NA <input type="checkbox"/>		
Intervention, Treatment, Exposure	Is the Intervention(s)/treatment(s)/exposure(s) appropriate? YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/> NA <input type="checkbox"/>		
	Is it valid and reliable? YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/> NA <input type="checkbox"/>		
Outcome, Output, Predictor, Measure	Is there at least one Outcome(s)/output(s)/predictor(s)/measure(s) YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/> NA <input type="checkbox"/>		
	Is (Are) it (they) appropriate? YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/> NA <input type="checkbox"/>		
	Is (Are) it (they) valid and reliable YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/> NA <input type="checkbox"/>		
Bias, etc	Does it state Potential bias? YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/> NA <input type="checkbox"/>		
Is it worth continuing?			Design [8]
4. Sampling			
Sampling method	Does it state Sampling method(s) YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/> NA <input type="checkbox"/>		
	Is (Are) it (They) appropriate? YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/> NA <input type="checkbox"/>		
Sample size	Does it state Sample size YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/> NA <input type="checkbox"/>		
	Is (Are) it (They) appropriate? YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/> NA <input type="checkbox"/>		
Is it worth continuing?			Sampling [5]

5. Data collection	
Collection method	Does it state Collection method(s) YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/> NA <input type="checkbox"/> Is (Are) it (They) appropriate? YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/> NA <input type="checkbox"/>
Is it worth continuing?	
Data collection [/4]	
6. Ethical matters	
ethics	Does it state ethical matters? YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/> NA <input type="checkbox"/>
Is it worth continuing?	
Ethical matters [/2]	
7. Results	
Analysis, Integration, Interpretation method	Does it state A.I.I. method(s) for primary outcome(s)/output(s)/predictor(s) YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/> NA <input type="checkbox"/> Is (Are) it (They) appropriate? YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/> NA <input type="checkbox"/> (A.I.I is congruent with objectives, design etc.. Unadjusted data (raw data) should be analysed. Stating withdrawal/incomplete data.)
Essential analysis	Does it present demographic and other characteristics of participants/cases/groups? YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/> NA <input type="checkbox"/>
Outcome, Output, Predictor analysis	Does it summarize of results and precision for each outcome/output/predictor/measure YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/> NA <input type="checkbox"/> (Summarized with Effect size, description of any adjusted/categorised data) Are the results present correctly and roundly? YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/> NA <input type="checkbox"/> (Describe all outcomes and differences between planned and actual results) Are there any description of outlying data (e.g. diverse cases, adverse effects etc.) YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/> NA <input type="checkbox"/>
Results [/6]	
8. Discussion	
Interpretation	Does it interpret results in the context of current evidence and objectives YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/> NA <input type="checkbox"/> Is the interpretation appropriate? YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/> NA <input type="checkbox"/> (Summarise key results in relation to background and objective; Compares others' findings) Does it draw inferences consistent with the strength of the data or consideration of alternative explanations for observed results? YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/> NA <input type="checkbox"/> (Explore reasons for difference between observed and expected) Is (Are) the inference and alternative explanation(s) appropriate? YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/> NA <input type="checkbox"/> (Draw inference based on the entirety of available evidence; not over/under represent data)
Generalisation	Does it consider the overall practical usefulness of the study? YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/> NA <input type="checkbox"/> (Discuss practical/ theoretical usefulness) Does it describe generalisability (external validity) of the study? YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/> NA <input type="checkbox"/>
Concluding remarks	Does it highlight study's particular strengths and limitations? YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> NOT SURE <input type="checkbox"/> NA <input type="checkbox"/>
Discussion [/7]	

Appendix 4: Scores of CCAT (90 Items Appraised) (Study 1)

Table A4.1 Descriptive Statistics of CCAT Detailed under Nine Sections (90 Items List)

Sections Article no.	Preliminaries	Introduction	Design	Sampling	Data collection	Ethic Matters	Results	Discussion	Total score	Percentage score
No.016	4	3	7	3	2	0	6	6	31	78%
No.049	4	4	7	3	2	1	4	7	32	80%
No.052	4	4	6	1	4	2	5	5	31	78%
No.058	3	4	6	4	3	0	4	4	28	70%
No.059	4	4	7	4	3	0	6	5	33	83%
No.060	3	4	4	3	3	0	4	6	27	68%
No.061	3	4	5	2	3	2	4	5	28	70%
No.062	3	4	6	1	3	0	5	2	24	60%
No.063	3	2	6	1	4	2	6	4	28	70%
No.065	2	4	5	5	0	2	5	3	26	65%
No.081	3	4	7	3	4	0	6	5	32	80%
No.098	4	4	8	5	4	2	6	2	35	88%
No.102	3	4	7	2	4	2	3	6	31	78%
No.104	4	4	8	3	4	2	3	6	34	85%
No.105	2	3	6	4	2	0	4	4	25	68%
No.107	4	4	7	5	4	0	5	5	34	85%
No.109***	3	2	3	2	3	0	3	1	17	53%
No.110**	2	3	3	3	1	0	3	NA	15	48%
No.114*	3	4	4	3	2	0	5	5	26	68%
No.125	2	2	4	3	0	0	3	3	17	48%
No.137*	3	4	4	3	4	0	4	2	24	65%
No.152	4	4	5	2	0	0	6	6	27	68%
No.157	3	4	6	3	3	0	5	7	31	78%
No.161	4	4	7	4	4	1	5	6	35	88%
No.164	3	4	6	5	4	2	5	7	36	90%
No.167	4	4	8	3	2	0	4	4	29	73%
No.171	4	4	7	3	4	2	6	6	36	90%
No.173	4	4	7	3	4	0	5	5	32	80%
No.186	4	3	7	2	4	2	5	7	34	85%
No.197	4	4	7	4	3	0	5	4	31	78%
No.216	4	4	7	5	4	0	6	6	36	90%
No.224	4	4	7	3	4	2	4	4	32	80%
No.228	3	4	7	3	3	1	6	5	32	80%
No.231	2	4	6	2	2	0	6	3	25	63%
No.234	3	4	5	2	2	0	5	2	23	58%
No.252	3	4	6	2	2	0	6	6	29	73%
No.254	3	4	6	2	2	2	5	5	29	73%
No.257	4	4	6	3	0	2	6	7	32	80%
No.267	2	3	4	3	1	0	3	6	22	55%
No.282	4	2	7	3	2	2	5	4	29	73%
No.295*	3	3	2	4	2	0	3	6	23	63%
No.328*	3	4	3	4	3	0	5	4	26	68%
No.331	3	4	6	4	4	2	3	4	30	75%
No.347	3	4	6	5	0	0	4	6	28	70%
No.348	3	4	8	2	4	0	4	5	30	75%
No.352	3	4	6	2	0	0	4	3	22	55%
No.354	3	4	6	3	4	0	6	4	30	75%
No.370*	2	4	4	5	2	0	3	6	26	70%
No.391	3	4	7	5	2	2	6	7	36	90%
No.435	2	3	6	5	4	2	5	6	33	83%
No.438**	3	3	4	3	2	0	3	NA	18	58%
No.439	3	4	5	2	2	0	5	4	25	63%
No.461*	3	4	4	3	0	1	6	7	28	75%
No.480***	2	3	3	3	2	0	1	5	19	50%
*										
No.499	3	4	4	2	0	0	6	4	23	58%
No.513**	2	3	2	4	2	2	1	NA	18	58%
No.534	3	4	8	2	1	0	6	6	30	75%
No.554	3	4	8	2	3	0	5	5	30	75%
No.575	3	4	5	2	1	0	3	5	23	58%

Sections Article no.	Preliminaries	Introduction	Design	Sampling	Data collection	Ethic Matters	Results	Discussion	Total score	Percentage score
No.587*	2	3	2	2	1	0	5	3	18	50%
No.588***	3	3	3	1	0	0	4	1	15	47%
No.612	3	4	4	3	2	1	5	6	28	70%
No.614*	3	2	3	3	0	0	3	3	17	48%
No.622	4	4	5	5	3	0	5	7	33	83%
No.656	4	3	7	3	2	0	5	4	28	70%
No.659*	3	3	2	3	3	2	4	5	25	65%
No.696	4	4	5	3	2	0	5	1	24	60%
No.697*	3	4	4	2	2	1	4	5	25	65%
No.713*	3	3	5	3	4	0	4	7	29	76%
No.722**	3	3	6	2	2	0	5	NA	21	68%
No.732	3	3	6	2	4	2	4	6	30	75%
No.734	3	4	7	4	0	0	3	2	23	58%
No.760	3	4	4	2	4	2	4	3	26	65%
No.770	2	3	5	1	1	0	2	4	18	50%
No.784	3	4	6	4	3	0	5	4	29	73%
No.790	4	3	7	3	2	0	6	7	32	80%
No.791*	3	4	3	2	0	1	5	3	21	53%
No.800	4	4	3	4	0	2	5	3	25	63%
No.803	3	4	5	2	2	2	3	3	24	60%
No.805	4	4	6	3	3	0	6	4	30	75%
No.806	3	4	6	2	3	0	5	4	27	68%
No.812	3	3	6	2	3	0	5	2	24	60%
No.825	3	4	6	3	4	0	4	4	28	70%
No.842	3	3	4	2	2	0	5	4	23	58%
No.843	4	3	8	2	3	0	5	6	31	78%
No.844*	4	2	6	2	2	2	5	4	27	73%
No.860	4	4	3	4	0	0	4	5	24	60%
No.862	3	4	7	2	3	2	6	4	31	78%
No.867	3	4	5	2	3	2	6	6	31	78%
No.869*	2	3	4	2	2	2	3	2	21	55%
Average	3.16	3.61	5.47	2.90	2.36	0.68	4.57	4.59	27.16	70%

*Note: These items has non-applicable section, thus dividend is full score 40 minus 2 accordingly when percentage calculates.

**Note: These items has non-applicable section, thus dividend is full score 40 minus 9 accordingly when percentage calculates.

***Note: These items has non-applicable section, thus dividend is full score 40 minus 8 accordingly when percentage calculates.

****Note: These items has non-applicable section, thus dividend is full score 40 minus 3 accordingly when percentage calculates.

Appendix 5: A Sample of Data Extraction Form (Study 1)

NO.016	Short Title	Title	Time 09:45-11:39 18/09/2018	CCAT
	Nonis & Hudson, 2006	Academic performance of college students: Influence of time spent studying and working.		78%
Method	<u>Survey by Questionnaire</u>	Title of Questionnaire		
	Interview	<u>No title</u>		
	Focus group	Question type		
	Mixed method	Closed-ended: Likert Interval Y/N		
	Case study	Open-ended: fact feel/attitude cognition/judgement		
	Qualitative mixed method	<u>Mixed closed + open ended</u>		
	Quantitative mixed method	Not provide		
	Other	(Details from original articles)		
	Ad hoc	Survey: The survey consisted of two parts. The first part required students to maintain a journal during a 1-week period, documenting how much time they spent on various activities each day of the week (there were over 25 activities listed under three broad categories: academics, personal, and work related).The second part of the survey contained demographic information, such as gender, age, and race, as well as measures of several other constructs including motivation (only motivation was used in this study)		
	Psychometric scales	<u>We used the social security numbers provided by the respondents to collect university data for the variable grade point average for the semester (SGPA), semester course load, number of hours completed to date, and ACT composite score.(secondary data)</u>		
<u>Not described</u>	Data collection occurred during the 9th week of a 15-week semester. <u>We distributed surveys</u> and explained them to those students who participated in the study. For accuracy purposes, we asked students to complete their journal each morning, recording the previous day's activities.			
Primary data	Demographic Variables Students reported demographic information, such as gender, age, and racial or ethnic group membership, in their journals.			
Secondary data	We used six items from a Spence et al. (1987) <u>Likert-type 1-5-point scale</u> , to measure students' achievement striving, which we used as a surrogate for motivation. In several prior studies, researchers have used this variable as a measure of motivation (Barling & Charbonneau, 1992; Barling, Kelloway, & Cheung, 1996). The reported <u>coefficient alpha for this scale is high (0.87)</u> , and this scale has been used in several other similar studies			
<u>Mixed</u>				
Conductor				
<u>Author</u>				
Assistant				
Third party				
Online				
Unclear				
Reliability & validity coefficient				
Provide completely				
<u>Provide partially</u>				
Not provide				
Not applicable				

		<p>(Carlson, Bozeman, Kacmar, Wright, & McMahan, 2000; Nonis & Wright, 2003).</p> <p>Behavior Variables</p> <p>We also used <u>student journal data</u> to determine the time spent outside of class on academic activities like reading the text and lecture notes for class preparation, going over the text and lecture notes to prepare for exams, and completing assignments and homework. The researcher added these items for the week to derive the total amount of time students spent outside of class on academic activities during the week (TSA). Students also reported the time they spent working, as well as the time it took for them to travel to and from work each day, during the given week. These two items were also added to derive the total amount of time students spent working during a given week (TSW).</p>		
Sample	Country	US	<u>Convenience</u>	(Sampling information & Participants characters)
	Scotland UK		Purposive	Sample consisted of 276,449 students at 413 of the nation's 4-year colleges and universities (over one fourth of entering freshmen in the United States), We secured the data for this study from a sample of undergraduate students attending a medium-sized (10,000+), Association to Advance Collegiate Schools of Business (AACSB)-accredited, public university in the mid-south United States. To obtain a representative sample of all students, <u>we selected classes from a variety of business courses (e.g., management, accounting, MIS, finance) ,offered at various levels (freshmen, sophomore, junior, and senior) and at different times (day or night), for the study.</u>
	England UK		Stratified	
	Other place UK		Random	
	UK nationwide		Other	
	Europe (not UK)		Not sure	
	Asia			
	Africa			
	<u>North America</u>			
	South America			
Oceania				
Inst number		Programme	We administered 440 surveys, and 288 were returned. Two hundred and sixty-four of the returned surveys were usable, yielding an effective response rate of 60.0%. Male 44.2%, female 55.8%; white 85% African American 12% other 2.5%. average age = 23.8 years; majors = 16% accounting, 13.1% business administration, 12.3% finance, 13.5% management, 14.5% marketing, 14.5% MIS, and the remainder "other" business majors. university US	
<u>One</u>		Not specific		
Two		One		
More		Two		
		<u>Multiple</u>		
		No limits		
<u>University</u>		Initial number		
College		440		
Mixed		Returned 288		
		60%		
		Valid 264		

Main aims of study	<p>Three hypothesis are proposed:H1: There is a relationship between time spent studying outside of class and academic performance.H2: There is a relationship between time spent working and academic performance.H3: Behaviour (time spent studying outside of class) will significantly interact with ability in that the influence that ability has on academic performance will be higher for students who spend more time studying outside of class than for students who spend less time studying. H4: Behaviour (more time spent studying outside of class) will significantly interact with motivation in that the influence that motivation has on academic performance will be higher for students who spend more time studying outside of class compared with students who spend less time studying outside of class.</p>																																				
Results	<p>The partial correlation coefficient between TSA and SGPA, controlling for the variables gender, age, race, and academic load ($r = .10, p = .19$), was in the expected direction, but not significant. Therefore, H1 was not supported. The partial correlation coefficient between TSW and SGPA ($r = -.08, p = .28$) was also statistically insignificant, failing to support H2.</p> <p>Moderated Multiple Regression (MMR), controlling for gender, age, race, and academic load, provided the statistics required to test the remaining two hypotheses. For H3, the R^2 for the control variables was statistically significant ($R^2 = .06, p < .05$). In the second step, the increment to R^2 was statistically significant for the addition of the main effects of ACT composite and TSA ($\Delta R^2 = .19, p < .05$). In fact, the main effects of both ACT composite and TSA were also significant ($p < .05$).</p> <div data-bbox="347 981 887 1361" style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; margin: 10px 0;"> <p>TABLE 1. Demographic Characteristics of the Sample Compared With the Population, in Percentages</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="text-align: left;">Demographic characteristic</th> <th style="text-align: center;">Population^a</th> <th style="text-align: center;">Sample</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td colspan="3"><u>Gender</u></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Male</td> <td style="text-align: center;">43.6</td> <td style="text-align: center;">44.2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Female</td> <td style="text-align: center;">56.3</td> <td style="text-align: center;">55.8</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="3"><u>Racial/Ethnic Group</u></td> </tr> <tr> <td>White</td> <td style="text-align: center;">77</td> <td style="text-align: center;">85</td> </tr> <tr> <td>African American</td> <td style="text-align: center;">12.1</td> <td style="text-align: center;">12</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Other</td> <td style="text-align: center;">11</td> <td style="text-align: center;">2.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="3"><u>Employment Status</u></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Do not work</td> <td style="text-align: center;">35.6</td> <td style="text-align: center;">34</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Work part time</td> <td style="text-align: center;">30.3</td> <td style="text-align: center;">28</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Work full time</td> <td style="text-align: center;">34.1</td> <td style="text-align: center;">37</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p><small>Note. The sample consisted of undergraduate students enrolled in business courses at a medium-sized, Association to Advance Collegiate Schools of Business-accredited public university in the mid-south. ^aBased on Statistical Abstract of the United States (2002).</small></p> </div> <p>From Step 2 to Step 3, the increment of R^2 was also significant for the addition of the interaction term ($\Delta R^2 = .03, p < .05$); this supported H3, which stated that TSA would interact with ability (see Table 3). Predicted values generated from the regression equation that were one standard deviation above and below the mean for ACT composite score and TSA indicated that students who were high in ACT composite and TSA most likely had a very high semester GPA (\hat{y} or predicted value = 3.95), relative to students high in ACT composite score with low TSA ($\hat{y} = 3.1$) and relative to students low in ACT composite with either high ($\hat{y} = 2.5$) or low ($\hat{y} = 2.7$) TSA. This is the appropriate technique to interpret interaction terms when moderated multiple regression is implemented (Cleary &</p>	Demographic characteristic	Population ^a	Sample	<u>Gender</u>			Male	43.6	44.2	Female	56.3	55.8	<u>Racial/Ethnic Group</u>			White	77	85	African American	12.1	12	Other	11	2.5	<u>Employment Status</u>			Do not work	35.6	34	Work part time	30.3	28	Work full time	34.1	37
Demographic characteristic	Population ^a	Sample																																			
<u>Gender</u>																																					
Male	43.6	44.2																																			
Female	56.3	55.8																																			
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White	77	85																																			
African American	12.1	12																																			
Other	11	2.5																																			
<u>Employment Status</u>																																					
Do not work	35.6	34																																			
Work part time	30.3	28																																			
Work full time	34.1	37																																			

Kessler, 1982; Cohen & Cohen, 1983). Results are shown in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1. Time spent studying (TSA) and ACT composite score (ACT) interaction on semester grade point average (SGPA). Graph is based on predicted values (y-hat) generated from the regression equation for individuals 1 standard deviation above and below the mean for TSA and ACT.

TABLE 2. Descriptive Statistics and Pearson Product-Moment Correlations for Study Variables

Variable	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1. Gender	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
2. Age	23.76	6.29	-0.04	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
3. Race	—	—	0.04	-0.07	—	—	—	—	—	—
4. ACT composite (ACT)	22.00	3.91	-0.01	-0.24*	0.31*	—	—	—	—	—
5. Achievement striving (AST)*	3.53	0.71	-0.17*	0.21*	-0.09	-0.02	—	—	—	—
6. Time spent outside of class on academic activities (TSA) vs. academic load	12.94	8.57	-0.07	0.34*	-0.16	-0.18*	0.29*	—	—	—
7. Time spent working (TSW) vs. academic load	16.84	14.55	0.03	-0.03	0.06	-0.03	-0.16*	-0.06	—	—
8. Semester grade point average (SGPA)	2.97	0.76	-0.11	-0.09	0.27*	0.45*	0.35*	0.05	-0.10	—

*reliability coefficient = 0.77.
*p < .05 (one-tailed).

For H4, the R2 for the control variables was once again statistically significant ($R^2 = .10$, $p < .05$). In the second step, the increment to R2 was statistically significant ($\Delta R^2 = .14$, $p < .05$) for the addition of the main effects of achievement striving and TSA. However, the main effect of TSA was not statistically significant. From Step 2 to Step 3, the increment of R2 was also not statistically significant ($\Delta R^2 = .01$, $p > .05$) for the addition of the interaction term. These results did not provide support for H4, which stated that time spent studying outside of class would interact with motivation (see Table 4). Therefore, H4 was not supported.

TABLE 3. Results of Moderated Multiple Regression Analysis of Time Spent Outside of Class on Academic Activities (TSA), ACT Composite Score (ACT), and Semester Grade Point Average (SGPA)

Independent variable	Slope	SE	t	p	R ²
Control (Step 1)					.06*
Gender	-0.12	0.13	-0.90	.36	
Age	0.03	0.10	0.26	.78	
Race	0.70	0.22	3.22	.00*	
Academic load	0.05	0.07	0.74	.46	
Predictor (Step 2)					.25*
ACT composite (ACT)	0.43	0.07	6.60	.00*	
Time studying (TSA)	0.17	0.07	2.54	.01*	
Moderator (Interaction) (Step 3)					.28*
ACT × TSA	0.18	0.07	2.69	.01*	

*p < .05.

TABLE 4. Results of Moderated Multiple Regression Analysis of Time Spent Outside of Class on Academic Activities (TSA), Achievement Striving (AST), and Semester Grade Point Average (SGPA)

Independent variable	Slope	SE	t	p	R ²
Control (Step 1)					.10*
Gender	-0.23	0.13	-1.81	.07	
Age	-0.07	0.07	-1.08	.28	
Race	0.87	0.28	4.42	.00*	
Academic load	0.06	0.06	0.98	.33	
Predictor (Step 2)					.24*
Achievement striving (AST)	0.40	0.07	6.36	.00*	
Time studying (TSA)	0.01	0.06	0.18	.85	
Moderator (Interaction) (Step 3)					.24
AST × TSA	0.04	0.06	0.58	.57	

*p = .05.

Appendix 6: Methodical Information of Final Inclusion (Study 1)

Table A6.1 Methodical Information of Final Inclusion

Short Title (Author and Year)	Code No.	Quality Assessment (by CCAT)	CCAT Score	Design & method	Questionnaire nature	Question Type	Reliability and validity	Sample country	No. of HEI sampled	Program Limit	Sample institution types	Initial number of samples	Return rate	Valid number of samples	Level of data	conductor	Sampling method
Nonis & Hudson, 2006	016	High	78%	Survey by questionnaire (cross section)	--	Open+closed ended	Partially provide	US	1	Multiple	university	440	288 64%	264	Primary + secondary	author	convenience
Cheng & Alcántara, 2007	049	High	80%	Focus group (cross section)	Ad hoc	Open ended	--	US	1	--	college	5354	2683 49%	14	Primary	author	convenience
Josiam et al., 2010	052	High	78%	Survey by questionnaire (cross section)	Ad hoc	Closed ended	--	UK	--	1	--	--	--	362	Primary	--	convenience
Jogarathnam & Buchanan, 2004	059	High	83%	Survey by questionnaire (cross section)	Ad hoc	Closed ended	Completely provide	US	Multiple	4	university	300	138 46%	138	Primary	--	convenience
Jackson & Wilton, 2016	081	High	80%	Survey by questionnaire (cross section)	Ad hoc	Closed ended	--	UK Australia	2	1	university	--	--	372	Primary	online	convenience
Cheung & Tang, 2012	098	High	88%	Survey by questionnaire (cross section)	Ad hoc	Mixed ended	Partially provide	China	more	No limits	university	600	439 82.17%	341	Primary	assistant	convenience
Butler et al., 2010	102	High	78%	Survey by questionnaire (cross section)	--	Mixed ended	Partially provide	US	1	--	university	--	--	106	Primary	online	convenience

Short Title (Author and Year)	Code No.	Quality Assessment (by CCAT)	CA T Score	Design & method	Questionnaire nature	Question Type	Reliability and validity	Sample country	No. of HEI sampled	Program Limit	Sample institution types	Initial number of samples	Return rate	Valid number of samples	Level of data	conductor	Sampling method
Vaughn et al., 2016	104	High	85%	Survey by questionnaire (cross section)	Ad hoc	Closed ended	Partially provide	US	1	1	university	--	170 76%	170	Primary	online	convenience
Bouchard & Nauta, 2017	107	High	85%	Survey by questionnaire (cross section)	Ad hoc	Mixed ended	Partially provide	US	1	1	university	--	--	393	Primary	online	convenience
Tessema et al., 2014	157	High	78%	Survey by questionnaire (cross section)	Ad hoc	Closed ended	--	US	1	No limits	university	--	--	5223	Secondary	online	cohort
Pascarella et al., 1998	161	High	88%	Survey by questionnaire (longitudinal design)	Ad hoc	Closed ended	--	US	23	No limits	mixed	3840	2685 69.92%	1054	Primary	--	Purposive ?
Bono et al., 2017	164	High	90%	Survey by questionnaire (cross section)	Ad hoc + psychometric scales	Mixed ended	Partially provide	US	1	No limits	university	3623	2054 57%	1559	Primary	online	
Swanson et al., 2006	171	High	90%	Survey by questionnaire (cross section)	Ad hoc	Closed ended	Partially provide	Scotland	1	No limits	university	4600	1166	625	Primary	--	Cohort?
Ho & Huang, 2013	173	High	80%	Survey by questionnaire (cross section)	Ad hoc	Closed ended	--	China	1	No limits	college	250	159	137	Primary	--	Purposive
Manthei & Gilmore, 2005	186	High	85%	Survey by questionnaire (cross section)	Ad hoc	Open ended	--	New Zealand	1	1	university	132	83 63%	83	Primary	--	convenience

Short Title (Author and Year)	Code No.	Quality Assessment (by CCAT)	CCA T Score	Design & method	Questionnaire nature	Question Type	Reliability and validity	Sample country	No. of HEI sampled	Program Limit	Sample institution types	Initial number of samples	Return rate	Valid number of samples	Level of data	conductor	Sampling method
Bednarska & Olszewski, 2016	197	High	78%	Survey by questionnaire (cross section)	Ad hoc	Closed ended	--	Poland	1	2	university	--	348 66.3%	338	Primary	author	Cluster
Teng, 2008	216	High	90%	Survey by questionnaire (cross section)	Ad hoc + psychometric scales	Closed ended	--	China	14	3	mixed	980	508 51.84% calculated	483	Primary + secondary	author	Cluster
Hall et al., 2015	224	High	80%	Survey by questionnaire (cross section)	Ad hoc	Closed ended	Partially provide	Northern Ireland	1	1	university	529	318 60.1%	318	Primary	online	convenience
Gbadamosi, 2015	228	High	80%	Survey by questionnaire (cross section)	Ad hoc	Mixed ended	Partially provide	England	2	1	university	--	140 39.2% 217 60.8%	357	Primary	online	--
Beauchamp et al., 2016	257	High	80%	Survey by questionnaire (cross section)	Ad hoc + psychometric scales	Closed ended	Partially provide	Canada	1	1	college	--	--	378	Primary	--	convenience
McGregor, 2015	331	High	75%	Mixed methods (cross section)	Ad hoc	-	-	Scotland	1	1	university	-	-	186; 10	Primary	-	convenience
Hsiao, 2015	348	High	75%	Survey by questionnaire (cross section)	Ad hoc + psychometric scales	Closed ended	Partially provide	China	1	1	university	580	544 90.5%	525	Primary	Trained instructor	convenience
Carney et al., 2005	354	High	75%	Survey by questionnaire (cross section)	Ad hoc	--	--	Scotland	1	No limits	university	1600	756 47%	756	Primary	online	random

Short Title (Author and Year)	Cod e No.	Quality Assessme nt (by CCAT)	CCA T Scor e	Design & method	Questionna ire nature	Questi on Type	Reliabilit y and validity	Sample countr y	No. of HEI sampl ed	Program me Limit	Sample instituti on types	Initial numb er of sampl es	Return rate	Valid numb er of sampl es	Level of data	conduct or	Sampling method
Butler, 2007	391	High	90%	Survey by questionna ire (cross section)	Ad hoc	Closed ended	--	US	1	--	universi ty	--	--	253	Primary + seconda ry	online	conveni ence
Hammes & Haller, 1983	435	High	83%	Mixed method	--	Mixed ended	--	US	1	No limits	universi ty	300	159 53%	159 29	Primary	--	random
Gbadamosi et al., 2016	461	High	75%	Survey by questionna ire (cross section)	Ad hoc	Mixed ended	--	Nigeria	1	2	universi ty	900	324 36%	324	Primary	--	conveni ence
Sekiguchi, 20 12	534	High	75%	Survey by questionna ire (cross section)	Ad hoc	Closed ended	Partially provide	Japan	2	2	universi ty	210	190 90%	123	Primary	--	conveni ence
Jackson & Wilton, 2017	554	High	75%	Survey by questionna ire (cross section)	Ad hoc	Closed ended	Partially provide	Englan d Australi a	2	1	universi ty	--	--	480	Primary	online	conveni ence
Greene & Maggs, 2015	622	High	83%	Diary record (longitudin al design)	Ad hoc	Closed- ended	Not applicabl e	US	1	No limits	universi ty	744	726 84%	726	Seconda ry	online	Stratified
Winkler, 2008	713	High	76%	Survey by interview	Ad hoc	Open- ended	--	Germa ny	1	--	universi ty	--	--	26	Primary	author	conveni ence
Lee et al., 1999	732	High	75%	Survey by questionna ire (cross section)	Ad hoc	Mixed ended	--	Englan d	1	1	universi ty	120	120 100%	120	Primary	--	conveni ence
Earl & Bright, 2003	790	High	80%	Survey by questionna ire (cross section)	Ad hoc	Mixed ended	Partially provide	Wales	1	multiple	universi ty	--	--	1157	Primary	--	conveni ence

Short Title (Author and Year)	Cod e No.	Quality Assessme nt (by CCAT)	CCA T Scor e	Design & method	Questionna ire nature	Questi on Type	Reliabilit y and validity	Sample countr y	No. of HEI sampl ed	Program me Limit	Sample instituti on types	Initial numb er of sampl es	Return rate	Valid numb er of sampl es	Level of data	conduct or	Sampling method
Park & Sprung, 2015	805	High	75%	Survey by weekly diary (longitudin al design)	Ad hoc	Closed ended	Partially provide	US	1	No limits	universi ty	476	121 25%	74	Primary	--	conveni ence
Koeske & Koeske, 198 9	843	High	78%	Survey by questionna ire (cross section)	Ad hoc + psychomet ric scales	Closed ended	Partially provide	US	1	1	universi ty	--	-- 49%	142	Primary	--	conveni ence
Creed et al., 2015	862	High	78%	Survey by questionna ire (cross section)	Ad hoc + psychomet ric scales	Closed ended	Comple tely provide	Australi a	1	1	universi ty	--	--	185	Primary	--	conveni ence
Dakas, 2011	867	High	78%	Survey by questionna ire (cross section)	Ad hoc	Closed ended	Partially provide	US	1	No limits	universi ty	430	87 20%	79	Primary	online	random

Appendix 7: Example of Execution of Content Analysis on Psychological Variables (Study 1)

NO.016	Short Title Nonis & Hudson, 2006	Free view time: 09:30-09:37 14/03/2019	Code time: 16:13-16:18 14/03/2019	CCAT 78%
		Viewing psychological variable		
		Academic performance of college students: Influence of time spent studying and working.		
Main aims of study	Three hypothesis are proposed: H1: There is a relationship between time spent studying outside of class and academic performance.H2: There is a relationship between time spent working and academic performance.H3: Behaviour (time spent studying outside of class) will significantly interact with ability in that the influence that ability has on academic performance will be higher for students who spend more time studying outside of class than for students who spend less time studying. H4: Behaviour (more time spent studying outside of class) will significantly interact with motivation in that the influence that motivation has on academic performance will be higher for students who spend more time studying outside of class compared with students who spend less time studying outside of class.			
Results	<p>The partial correlation coefficient between TSA and SGPA, controlling for the variables gender, age, race, and academic load ($r = .10, p = .19$), was in the expected direction, but not significant. Therefore, H1 was not supported. The partial correlation coefficient between TSW (PB2)* and SGPA ($r = -.08, p = .28$) was also statistically insignificant, failing to support H2.</p> <p>Moderated Multiple Regression (MMR), controlling for gender, age, race, and academic load, provided the statistics required to test the remaining two hypotheses. For H3, the R2 for the control variables was statistically significant ($R^2 = .06, p < .05$). In the second step, the increment to R2 was statistically significant for the addition of the main effects of ACT composite and TSA (10F) (PB2) ($\Delta R^2 = .19, p < .05$). In fact, the main effects of both ACT composite and TSA were also significant ($p < .05$).</p> <p>From Step 2 to Step 3, the increment of R2 was also significant for the addition of the interaction term ($\Delta R^2 = .03, p < .05$); this supported H3, which stated that TSA would interact with ability (3F) (PI6) (see Table 3). Predicted values generated from the regression equation that were one standard deviation above and below the mean for ACT composite score and TSA indicated that students who were high in ACT composite and TSA most likely had a very high semester GPA (\hat{y} or predicted value = 3.95), relative to students high in ACT composite score with low TSA ($\hat{y} = 3.1$) and relative to students low in ACT composite with either high ($\hat{y} = 2.5$) or low ($\hat{y} = 2.7$) TSA. This is the appropriate technique to interpret interaction terms when moderated multiple regression is implemented (Cleary & Kessler, 1982; Cohen & Cohen, 1983). Results are shown in Figure 1.</p> <p>For H4, the R2 for the control variables was once again statistically significant ($R^2 = .10, p < .05$). In the second step, the increment to R2 was statistically significant ($\Delta R^2 = .14, p < .05$) for the addition of the main effects of achievement striving and TSA. However, the main effect of TSA was not statistically significant. From Step 2 to Step 3, the increment of R2 was also not statistically significant ($\Delta R^2 = .01, p > .05$) for the addition of the interaction term. These results did not provide support for H4, which stated that time spent (6F) (PB2) studying outside of class would interact with motivation (3F) (PM1) (see Table 4). Therefore, H4 was not supported.</p>			

*Note: Psychological factors were coloured with green background and frequency of words occurrence was presented in brackets. The code of each psychological factor was then followed in red colour words in brackets.

Appendix 8: Summary of Relevant Information of Final Inclusion (Study 1)

Table A8.1 Description of Aims, Methods and Findings in Final Inclusion Items

Short Title (Author, Year)	Aims of study (Shorted in summary)	Method	Sample size	Variables	Key Findings in Summary (Psychological factor and relationship with other factors)
Hammes & Haller, 1983 (No. 435)	It aimed to study both academic and non-academic consequences of holding a part time job while attending school and the strategies used by students to balance academic, non-academic, and employment responsibilities.	Mixed method (Survey and Interview)	159 (survey) 25 (interview)	Nature of jobs Effects of employment on academic performance; Balance strategy: How students cope with work and school; Costs and benefits of jobs.	College students used different ways to cope with work and school including selectively working in some terms and not in others, modifying work hours according to course demands such as cutting back on hours (or not working at all) (12.4% stopped working in survey) during times of academic stress. They reduce academic pressures by dropping courses as a relatively unpopular strategy (10% in survey) There are 68% had reduced leisure time and 48% had done less socializing. Of those interviewed, 18 (72%) claimed they became efficient in studying. They are more confidence, concentration and diligence as the consequences of working.
Koeske & Koeske, 1989 (No. 843)	It aimed to study social work students and their self-reported physical and psychological symptoms across status as students (part-time, full-time) and workers (no job, part-time, full-time); and the social support buffer function of combined student/work role on symptoms.	Quantitative	142	Demands by student/work status; Physical and psychological symptoms; Social support buffer effect	Full-time students with part-time jobs reported significant more distress symptoms than full-time students with no jobs. Only for the FT Student/PT Job group social support was associated with a reduction in Symptoms. Regression analysis indicated student/work Status accounted for a significant increment in symptom variability.
Pascarella et al., 1998 (No. 161)	It aimed to study the cognitive effects of on- and off-campus work during college.	Quantitative	3739	Impact to cognitive development; Group effect between two and four year students.	In the second year of college, on-campus work had small negative total and direct influences on science reasoning, but neither form of work inhibited students' writing skills. Both forms of work had a significant curvilinear relationship with a composite measure of end-of-third-year cognitive development consisting of reading comprehension and critical thinking.

Short Title (Author, Year)	Aims of study (Shorted in summary)	Method	Sample size	Variables	Key Findings in Summary (Psychological factor and relationship with other factors)
					Part-time on- or off-campus work had a positive influence, but on-campus work in excess of 15 hours per week or off-campus work in excess of 20 hours per week had a negative impact. Finally, across all years of the study, the cognitive impacts of work appear to be essentially the same, irrespective of student characteristics (e.g., ethnicity, gender, age, precollege ability, full- or part-time enrolment) and whether or not the student attended a two-year or a four-year college.
Lee et al., 1999 (No. 752)	It aimed to study the students' engagement in paid part-time work and the effects of this work on student major in nursing.	Quantitative	120	Nature & extent; Motivation of work; Impact; Course adjustment.	The effects of work on personal and social life: The positive impact: The major category related to having the finances to improve personal life. The second largest category was related to increased social life. The third category related to personal development. Improvements were identified in confidence, social and communication skills and time management. Comments on personally rewarding. The negative impact: The first category related to having restricted time for themselves, partners, family and socializing generally. The second category related to the physical and mental stress of combining both work and study. The combined demands of the course and employment resulted in considerable physical and psychosocial strain for many students. Despite these reported strains the majority of students did not acknowledge any negative effects on their studies. In fact, the number of reported positive and negative effects were similar.
Nonis & Hudson, 2 006 (No. 016)	It aimed to study the relationship between time spent studying outside of class, time spent working and academic performance. Interaction between time spent behaviour outside of class and the ability, motivation on academic performance.	Quantitative	264	Time spent in studying and academic performance; Time spent working and academic performance; Group difference of academic performance and motivation of low/high time spent in studying groups.	The partial correlation coefficient between Time Spent on employment and semester GPA ($r = -.08$, $p = .28$) was statistically insignificant.

Short Title (Author, Year)	Aims of study (Shorted in summary)	Method	Sample size	Variables	Key Findings in Summary (Psychological factor and relationship with other factors)
Cheng & Alcántara, 2007 (No. 049)	It aimed to study working students' college experience, academically and socially including students' perceptions of work in the context of their overall out-of-class experience.	Qualitative (Focus group)	14	Type of job; Motivation; Impact; Perception of work.	Impact: Competing with academic schedules. Students believed that work had helped shape their academic interests and career choices upon graduation. Gain insight into the job market, real world experiences, and inside track information on their selected professions. The impact of work on their social life is agreed, i.e., the highest cost of work is free time, sleep time, and time for socializing with friends. One student said that she considered working as a means to insert structure into her daily schedule. They had to make their life more focused and structured, and they learned how to manage time. More importantly, work experience helps enhance students' self-confidence in working with people.
Jogaratnam & Buchanan, 2004 (No. 059)	It aimed to study the stressors as a result between the educational and work environments and examine their impact on college students currently employed in the hospitality industry.	Quantitative	138	Stressor; Stressors' impact to employment.	There was no significant differences in stress rating across hours worked per week, GPA or the number of jobs held. Female, freshmen and full time students work in hospitality reported a greater degree of exposure to stressors. Full-time student status and found that there were significant in three stressors including higher developmental challenges, academic alienation, and romantic problems than part-time student (t test). Female indicated great stress on time pressure stressor than male. Years of study significantly differ in four stressors including social mistreatment; friendship problems, romantic problems and assorted annoyance. The freshmen had greater stress than the sophomore, junior and senior.
Swanson et al., 2006 (No. 171)	It aimed to study the impact of perceived congruence of role demands of term time employment and university life on full-time undergraduate students' satisfaction and adjustment to university life.	Quantitative	625	Role congruence of study and work relation with satisfaction and adjustment to university life; Personality and perceived stress as mediators/moderators; Work and non-work comparison.	Students generally perceived employment and university roles to be in balance, and there was no difference in adjustment for students whether currently in term-time employment or not. Correlation: Greater congruence (between term-time employment and university life in academic, career and self/social development factors) was related to more positive outcomes (including adaptation to university and satisfaction with university life). More role congruence was also associated with more positive affectivity, and lowered role congruence with more perceived stress. Regression: Academic role and self-social development were significant individual predictors of satisfaction, whereas only academic role congruence individually predicted adjustment to university life.

Short Title (Author, Year)	Aims of study (Shorted in summary)	Method	Sample size	Variables	Key Findings in Summary (Psychological factor and relationship with other factors)
					Mediation: psychological factors, particularly positive affectivity and stress were important mediators of the relationship between role congruence and adjustment.
Manthei & Gilmore, 2005 (No. 186)	It aimed to study the impact of this paid employment on their study time and other aspects of their lives (sport and recreational/leisure activities; the overall balance among activities).	Quantitative	83	Extent of work; Study workload; Impact to student life (i.e. Recreational activities and balance)	Working left less time than desired for social activities, study and recreation. There was no statistically significant relationship between the numbers of hours per week spent in any pair of activities of work, study and recreational/leisure.
Teng, 2008 (No. 216)	It aimed to study the effects of personality traits and attitudinal factors on hospitality employment aspirations in post-internship undergraduate hospitality seniors in Taiwan.	Quantitative	483	Personality, attitudes and the relation with employment aspiration.	The results show that the personality trait of extroversion is a significant predictor of students' attitudes to aspirations regarding hospitality jobs. Industry-person congruency is a key attitudinal factor mediating the effect of extroversion on hospitality employment aspirations. Several implications for both hospitality educators and practitioners are also discussed.
Carney et al., 2005 (No. 354)	It aimed to study the relationship between part time working, mental and physical health and academic performance.	Quantitative	756	Work; Debt; Relation of above two with physical and mental wellbeing; Relation of above three with perceived academic performance.	Student workers' health was compared to the sex- and age-related norms for the general population, it showed that seven of the eight areas of health measured were significantly poorer than those of the general population. Results also showed that being in debt and part time working both have a very slight (though significant), detrimental effect on both mental and physical health of students.
Butler, 2007 (No. 391)	It aimed to study job characteristics, school performance and satisfaction. It examined from two role theory perspectives, one of which emphasized resource scarcity and the other resource expansion.	Quantitative	253	Resource scarcity/expansion as role theory; Work, study and satisfaction.	Model tests using structural equation modeling showed that 2 resource-enriching job characteristics, job-school congruence and job control, were positively related to work-school facilitation (WSF). Two resource-depleting job characteristics, job demands and work hours, were positively related to work-school conflict (WSC), and job control was negatively related to WSC. In turn, WSF was positively related to school performance and satisfaction, and WSC was negatively related to school performance. Both WSF and WSC mediated the relationship between the

Short Title (Author, Year)	Aims of study (Shorted in summary)	Method	Sample size	Variables	Key Findings in Summary (Psychological factor and relationship with other factors)
					job characteristics and school outcomes. There was no evidence of interactive effects between enriching and depleting job characteristics on inter-role processes.
Winkler, 2008 (No. 713)	It aimed to study students' perceptions of Human Resource-aspects of non-standard employment, such as work task, training opportunities, students' relations to the supervisor and co-workers, and social integration.	Qualitative (semi-structured interview)	26	Quality of work (task, training); Social impact of work (social integration and relation to supervisors and co-workers)	The study revealed various perceptions of students working as flexible employees and related this picture to current empirical and theoretical research in the field of non-standard employment. The results indicated that students are satisfied doing the low-skilled job, the experienced social relations seem to be the main reason for having fun at work despite being employed in a low-skilled job, they can have negotiated work schedules, they are getting instructions but hardly any training, they are feeling integrated and mostly accepted.
Earl & Bright, 2003 (No. 790)	It aimed to study the comfort and decidedness in relation to career decisions and examine their own capabilities in relation to career goals. It also aimed to study whether the work experience promote greater understanding of self and work proposed in a positive relationship between hours and career decision status.	Quantitative	1157	Work, comfort, decidedness and relation with career decisions; Above with career goal; Work (hours), self-understanding with career decisions.	The results indicated that age was a better predictor of career decision status, although students across the two undergraduate levels identified different reasons underlying their status. Volume of work rather than pattern of work determined variability in scores on the career measures. Breadth of work experience measured by number of jobs and employers did not influence career decision status.
Josiam et al., 2010 (No. 052)	It aimed to study the attitudes to work of GEN Y hospitality management college students in the UK (England, Scotland, and Northern Ireland).	Quantitative	362	Attitude (positive, negative, work value and ethic) and the relation to work; Motivation (economic and social) for work;	Correlation: Across the UK, those with stronger positive attitudes to work significantly correlates with less work Cynicism and promotion Cynicism. Work Ethic was found to be positively correlated to Positive Attitudes. In England and Scotland, significant positive correlation was found between Positive Attitudes (to Work) and Work Value and social motivation.

Short Title (Author, Year)	Aims of study (Shorted in summary)	Method	Sample size	Variables	Key Findings in Summary (Psychological factor and relationship with other factors)
				Demographics and relations with attitudes; Relation between work and attitudes (type and amount of prior and current work, lay off) Parental factor (demographics and job) and relation with students' attitudes.	Non-significance: no significant correlations between Positive Attitudes to Work and Work Involvement, between Positive Attitudes to Work and Work Involvement scores, between positive work attitudes and economic motivations. Correlation analyses with students Negative Attitude show that students in England and Scotland with greater involvement in work are less likely to have negative attitudes. Similarly, students in Scotland and Northern Ireland with stronger work ethic have lower negative attitudes also. Impact of job factors on attitudinal variables: Increasing work experience has a significant negative correlation with Negative Work Attitude in England; It is found that in England, increasing work experience is associated with decrease in Work Value; whereas in Northern Ireland, as work experience increases, Work Value goes up
Jackson & Wilton, 2016 (No. 081)	It aimed to study career attitudes among Business undergraduates and the relationship of employment status and career attitudes.	Quantitative	372	Protean career attitudes (self-direction, values-driven); Boundaryless career attitudes (boundaryless mindset, physical mobility); Age main effect on career attitudes; Gender main effect on career attitudes; Degree specialisation main effect on career attitudes; Employment status and relation with boundaryless career attitude.	The results indicated that the students score more highly, on average, in the self-direction and boundaryless mindset dimensions. Relatively lower mean scores for physical mobility and values-driven suggest a 'one high, one low' pattern among the two items that constitute protean and boundaryless career attitudes. Employment status (part time or full time) and Business degree specialisation were found to significantly predict career attitudes.
Cheung & Tang, 2012 (No. 098)	It aimed to study parental job insecurity, their actual layoffs, the young workers' own working	Quantitative	341	Parental factor (perceived job insecurity and layoff) and relation with motivation and	The results of correlation and regression indicated that work values were strongly related to students' part-time work satisfaction and work quality. In particular, regression analyses showed that high job satisfaction and low role conflict in the part-time job were significantly related to high

Short Title (Author, Year)	Aims of study (Shorted in summary)	Method	Sample size	Variables	Key Findings in Summary (Psychological factor and relationship with other factors)
	experience, and their work values among Chinese undergraduates in Hong Kong.			work cynicism of children's work; Quality of work (skill, job autonomy, satisfaction, low role conflict of study and work) and the relation with greater motivation to do good work; Quality of work and relation with lower work cynicism.	motivation to do good work but low work cynicism, even after demographic information was considered.
Butler et al., 2010 (No. 102)	It aimed to study three characteristics of work and the relationship with daily drinking behaviour in college students.	Quantitative	106	Work factor (daily hours worked, workload, work-school conflict) and relation with daily alcohol consumption; Expectation of alcohol tension reducing mediated between work and alcohol consumption; Gender effect of work factor on daily alcohol consumption.	The results indicated that hours worked were positively related to number of drinks consumed. Workload was unrelated to alcohol consumption, and work-school conflict was negatively related to consumption, particularly when students expressed strong beliefs in the tension reducing properties of alcohol. There was no evidence that the effects of work stressors were moderated by gender. The results illustrate that employment during the academic year plays a significant role in college student drinking and suggest that the employment context may be an appropriate intervention site to address the problem of student drinking.
Vaughn et al., 2016 (No. 104)	It aimed to study the positive, negative, and ambivalent relationships and their prediction of mental health variables within the context of college students' workplace relationships.	Quantitative	170	Positive relationship (supportive); Negative relationship (aversive); Ambivalent relationship; Workplace relationship (supervisors and co-workers).	Students who reported having workplace relationships with co-occurring positivity and negativity had worse self-reported mental health outcomes than students reporting having wholly positive relationships. Positive and negative relationship together predict mental health; Positive relationship did not predict mental health. The relationship between workplace relationship quality and mental health was mediated by negative work-related variables. Conclusions: Workplace relationships—even in part-time employment settings—influence college students' mental health.

Short Title (Author, Year)	Aims of study (Shorted in summary)	Method	Sample size	Variables	Key Findings in Summary (Psychological factor and relationship with other factors)
Bouchard & Nauta, 2017 (No. 107)	It aimed to study the relationship of perceptions of unhealthy, work volition and career outcomes.	Quantitative	393	Unhealthy (in last 30 days); work volition; career outcomes (major satisfaction, leadership aspirations, educational persistence intentions, real or ideal career aspiration discrepancy).	The result indicated that the number of the last 30 days that were deemed unhealthy was significantly related to work volition, and work volition was associated with major satisfaction, leadership aspirations, educational persistence intentions, and real versus ideal career aspiration discrepancy. Path analysis results were consistent with a model specifying work volition as a mediator of the associations between unhealthy days and the career variables.
Tessema et al., 2014 (No. 157)	It aimed to study the effect of work on college students' satisfaction and GPA.	Quantitative	5223	working and non-working; number of working hours (0, 1-10, 11-20, 21-30, and above 30 hours).	The results indicated that work has positive effect on both satisfaction and GPA, when students did work fewer than 10 hours. Thus, part-job may not always be detrimental to students' satisfaction. However, when students work for more than 11 hours a week, students' satisfaction and GPA were found to decline for each additional category of work, although the change is very small. Regression: Working hours negatively impact study satisfaction and GPA. The results of regression analysis show that working hours had a negative impact on students' satisfaction ($\beta = -.05$). Working hours explains .2% of variation in the students' satisfaction ($R^2 = .002$). Working hours explains 1.7% of variation in the student GPA ($R^2 = .017$), which suggests that 98.3 percent of GPA is influenced by other factors. Regression analysis results further indicate that as hours worked increases, students' satisfaction and GPA fall.
Bono et al., 2017 (No. 164)	It aimed to study the relationship of college student employment and alcohol and tobacco use after accounting for the influences of students' social environment,	Quantitative	1457	Work, and relationship with alcohol / tobacco use (control social environment, personality and family history)	The results indicated that working 10 more hours and earning \$50 more per week as a freshman had modest positive associations with higher smoking frequency and with moderate drinking frequency and quantity prior to adjustment. After adjustment, work hours remained modestly associated with moderate drinking frequency and quantity. No adjusted associations were found among employment measures and smoking or between weekly earnings and drinking frequency. Different relationships

Short Title (Author, Year)	Aims of study (Shorted in summary)	Method	Sample size	Variables	Key Findings in Summary (Psychological factor and relationship with other factors)
	personality, and family history.				emerged for moderate versus heavy alcohol use frequency and quantity. Conclusion: Employment may yet play a role in college student substance use, but work hours and earnings are likely only small parts of a larger web of influences on drinking and smoking.
Ho & Huang, 2013 (No. 173)	It aimed to study the major determinants perceived by students for term-time employment selection and the major benefits and detriments of different types of term-time employment.	Quantitative	137	Perceived determinants (and the degree) of work; Benefits and detriments of type of work.	The results indicated that the determinant factors and employment types roughly form into four groups. The map shows that On-campus RA and TA, On-campus Administrative Job, Cooperative Educational Work, and Off-campus Tutoring had the highest rating on Employment Preparation and Learning Practical Skills. The Off campus Labor had the most bearing on Health Detriment, Safety Detriment, and Academic Detriment. Off-campus Administrative Job, On-Campus Labor were closer to Activity Detriment. Community Service was very different from all the other jobs, and was highly rated for Expanding Relationships with People in the Workplace. Finally, On Campus Laboring Jobs, and Off-Campus Administrative Jobs did not show strong relationships with any of the eight determinants.
Bednarska & Olszewski, 2016 (No. 197)	It aimed to study the role of work experience both inside and outside the hospitality industry in shaping hospitality career attractiveness perceptions and job pursuit intentions.	Quantitative	338	Type of work and relations with preferred, perceived job/organization attributes and career attractiveness; Type of work and relation to intention to apply for a job.	Correlation coefficients indicate that both perceptions of hospitality career attractiveness and intentions to apply for a job in the industry display the strongest relationship with perceived job content and development opportunities. ANOVA: Students who experienced working life, regardless of the industry, have notably higher expectations. Students with working experience in the hospitality industry rate job content higher both as expected and as perceived attribute, particularly job that matches individual interests and tasks that are challenging. Post hoc tests also revealed that type of work experience is related to perceptions of hospitality career attractiveness both in the long and in the short run.
Hall et al., 2015 (No. 224)	It aimed to study the factors affecting the empathetic ability of undergraduate pharmacy students.	Quantitative	318	Empathy and the gender /level main effect; Work status and empathy; Chronic medical condition and empathy.	There were no significant differences in scores of empathy for respondents who had a part-time job, a chronic condition, or took regular medication in comparison to those who did not. Conclusion: A reasonable level of empathy was found relative to other studies; this could be further enhanced at lower levels of the degree pathway.

Short Title (Author, Year)	Aims of study (Shorted in summary)	Method	Sample size	Variables	Key Findings in Summary (Psychological factor and relationship with other factors)
Gbadamosi et al., 2015 (No. 228)	It aimed to study the perception of students regarding their part-time working, future career aspirations and self-efficacy.	Quantitative	357	Work and relation to career aspiration; Self-efficacy and relation with work and career aspiration; Fixed self-theory and relation to work and career aspiration; Malleable self-theory and relation to work and career aspiration; Gender main effect of work, career aspiration, self-efficacy and self-theories.	The results indicated that a positive and significant relationship between part-time work and career aspiration. Students who work part-time, and value this opportunity, are likely to have a high career aspiration and strive to enhance their employability agenda. Self-efficacy (students' belief in their ability to succeed) is significantly associated with career aspiration. Finally, students' level of study and malleable self-theories (the belief that people are changeable and with effort can achieve more) were found to be the strongest predictors of part-time work, while self-efficacy is the strongest predictor of career aspiration. These findings confirm the importance of individual self-efficacy in the value attached to part-time working among students in higher education.
Beauchamp et al., 2016 (No. 257)	It aimed to study the relationship between employment status and academic achievement in the context of students' adult attachment styles, in order to better nuance the complex dynamics of employment in higher education.	Quantitative	378	Attachment style; work status; Academic achievement.	Attachment style, work status predicts academic achievement; Work negatively affect 1 st semester average to dismissing type compared to secure type, and secure type compared to preoccupied type. The results indicated that the dismissing students entering postsecondary education who also have employment are at greater risk of academic difficulties than students with a secure attachment style.
Hsiao, 2015 (No. 348)	It aimed to study attitude, subjective norm towards cheating perceived behavioural control, anticipated positive affect, anticipated negative affect, unethical professional beliefs and their intention to cheat. It also aimed to	Quantitative	525	Job status (no job, part-time, full time job) main effect) on attitude, subjective norm, perceived behavioural control and anticipated positive effect, unethical to cheating and unethical	The results indicated that perceived behavioral control has the strongest effect on cheating intention among students with no jobs and with full-time jobs, unethical beliefs in the workplace have a significant effect on cheating for students with full-time jobs, but not for students with part-time jobs and with no jobs. It should be noted that most significant determinants of cheating intention are quite different in the part-time job and full-time job student groups.

Short Title (Author, Year)	Aims of study (Shorted in summary)	Method	Sample size	Variables	Key Findings in Summary (Psychological factor and relationship with other factors)
	study student job status and the cheating behaviour.			professional beliefs positively affect intention to cheat; Anticipated negative effect to cheating negatively affect intention to cheat.	
Gbadamos i et al., 2016 (No. 461)	It aimed to study the extent of part-time working, self-development and career prospects. It aimed to study the self-efficacy of students and the influences to their part-time work activity.	Quantitative	324	Extent of work; Income from work importance; Impact to developing skills, and used for self-development and career prospect; Self-efficacy and the influence to work activity.	The results indicated that self-efficacy and being female is a significant predictor in understanding part-time work and career aspirations. Self-efficacy emerged as a statistically significant predictor of beneficial work ($\beta = 2.370$, $p < .05$). Moreover, gender ($\beta = 2.194$, $p < .05$) and self-efficacy ($\beta = 2.172$, $p < .05$) emerged as the significant predictors to career aspiration.
Sekiguchi, 2012 (No. 534)	It aimed to study the level of career development of university students through part-time work and other student activities including "employment commitment, "proactive career behavior.", skill development, proactive networking, seeking consultation, career planning, career exploration, and self-efficacy in careers.	Quantitative	123	Employment commitment (prioritize professions by organization or of choice), proactive career behaviour, and focus of career exploration (narrow down type of work, target organization); Job autonomy; Job crafting (task crafting, cognitive crafting, and relational crafting); Skill variety; Self-efficacy in careers. (in team member	Students being proactive in part-time employment have higher levels of career development. The number of hours worked per week and the level of career development appeared as an inverted U-shaped relationship. Even short working hours in part-time work still requires a diverse range of skills. Skill variety have a significantly and positively impact on career exploration and job search self-efficacy. Work hours significantly and negatively relate to proactive career behaviour and self-efficacy in team member proficiency.

Short Title (Author, Year)	Aims of study (Shorted in summary)	Method	Sample size	Variables	Key Findings in Summary (Psychological factor and relationship with other factors)
				proficiency; in job search).	
Jackson & Wilton, 2017 (No. 554)	It aimed to study perceptions of employability among undergraduates and the associated influence of career management competencies, work experience and background characteristics.	Quantitative	480	Decision making, opportunity awareness, transition learning, self-awareness, WIL and positive relation with perceived employability (PE); Work status and PE; Gender no relation with PE; Age, year of study and negatively relation with PE.	The results indicated that undergraduates demonstrated reasonably high levels of perceived Employability (PE). There were variations in the influence of career management competencies on PE across the two settings. Positive associations were reported for decision making and transition learning in Australia and only opportunity awareness in the UK. There was no support in either sample for H4 which asserted a positive association between self-awareness and PE. The influence of employment status on PE was evident in both samples (H6).
Greene & Maggs, 2015 (No. 622)	It aimed to study the college students' time use by exploring demographic correlates of employment, organized activities, and academics as well as testing the time trade-off.	Quantitative	726	Demographic correlates with work time, activity time and study time; Time trade off theory (less study time, more work and activity time).	Beginning with Model 1, on days and in semesters when students spent more time on employment, they spent less time on academics, supporting Hypothesis 2a. These associations were documented for both weekdays and weekends. However, in line with Hypothesis 2c, the association was stronger for weekdays than weekends at both the daily ($z = -9.56$, $p < .001$) and semester ($z = 4.17$, $p < .001$) levels. On weekdays, spending an hour more than average on employment on a given day was associated with spending 10 minutes less (-.16 hours) on academics whereas spending an hour more than average on employment on weekends was only associated with a 2 minute decrease in academic time. At the person level, students who averaged more time on employment on weekends averaged less time on academics. Model 2 presents associations between organized activity time and academic time. These results supported Hypothesis 2b and demonstrated that on days when students spent more time on organized activities, they spent less time on academics. However, in contrast to predictions (Hypothesis 2c), this association was similar for both weekdays and

Short Title (Author, Year)	Aims of study (Shorted in summary)	Method	Sample size	Variables	Key Findings in Summary (Psychological factor and relationship with other factors)
					weekends ($z = -.85$, n.s.). In addition, organized activity time did not predict the amount of time spent on academics at the semester level. Model 3 presents a combined model in which both employment and organized activities predict academic time. The substantive results are quite similar to the information presented in Models 1 and 2. On days when students spent more time on employment and organized activities, they spent less time on academics. Likewise, on semesters when they spent more time than average on employment, they spent less time on academics. However, it is worth mentioning that the strength of the coefficients at the daily level differed for the two activities on weekdays. On weekdays, but not weekends, the association between employment and academics was stronger than the association between organized activities and academics ($B = -.16$ vs. $-.05$, $z = -10.7$, $p < .001$).
McGregor, 2015 (No. 331)	It aimed to study term time and its effect on their confidence, extracurricular activities, study, physical health and mental health and social activities.	Mixed method (questionnaire + interview)	186 for questionnaire 10 for interview	Questionnaire: Confidence; Study (attendance, marks, extracurricular activities); Employability; Health (physical and mental health); Social activities. Interview: academic support.	Working during term has a perceived positive effect on graduate employability as well as a negative effect on attendance, social activities and studies. Working students also believe that the University could provide additional academic support for working students through pre-recorded lectures, live lectures, drop-in video tutorials and lecturer drop-in sessions. Mental health was negatively affected by working for 46% of students: 23% rarely, 19% occasionally and 4% often (see Figure 2). The biggest issue was stress (39%), followed by depression (2%). Students reported that stress was caused by issues at work as well as not having sufficient time to prepare coursework, both of which were aggravated by lack of sleep.

Short Title (Author, Year)	Aims of study (Shorted in summary)	Method	Sample size	Variables	Key Findings in Summary (Psychological factor and relationship with other factors)
Park & Sprung, 2015 (No. 805)	It aimed to study a weekly diary method among a sample of 74 Midwestern college student workers in order to examine the within-person relationships between work-school conflict, sleep quality, and fatigue over five weeks. It also aimed to study recovery self-efficacy a cross-level moderator of the relation between sleep quality and fatigue.	Quantitative	74	Work-school conflict, sleep quality and fatigue; Self-efficacy as moderator between sleep quality and fatigue.	The results indicated that weekly work-school conflict was negatively related to weekly sleep quality and positively related to end-of-week fatigue, with sleep quality partially mediating the relation between work-school conflict and fatigue. These findings enhance understanding of the process by which work-school conflict contributes to college student workers' strain on a weekly basis. Additionally, student workers with low recovery self-efficacy demonstrated a negative relation between sleep quality and fatigue; however, this relation did not exist for student workers with high recovery self-efficacy. This finding suggests recovery self-efficacy as an important resource that may reduce the association between poor sleep quality (as a result of work-school conflict) and fatigue.
Creed et al., 2015 (No. 862)	It aimed to study the antecedents and consequences of role-conflict and role-facilitation.	Quantitative	185	Role conflict and role facilitation mediated between Work benefits/ demands and academic engagement and wellbeing; Relationship between work and university.	The results indicated that work-based benefits (enabling resources, rewards, and involvement) were associated with higher work-university facilitation; more time demands and fewer psychological rewards were associated with more work-university conflict; facilitation was associated with more engagement (dedication) and general well-being; and conflict was associated with more negative feelings towards the university. There were no mediation effects. Working while studying is related to students' engagement and well-being, although modest effects were explained by role-conflict theory.
Dakas, 2011 (No. 867)	It aimed to study on and off campus job, the negative and positive spillover between the work role and the school role.	Quantitative	79	Working hours per week; Off / on campus job; work-school conflict (WSC); work school enrichment (WSE); job satisfaction.	The results indicated that work hours were positively correlated with Work-Study Conflict (WSC), and students who worked off-campus reported higher levels of WSC than those who worked on-campus. Furthermore, job satisfaction was negatively correlated with WSC and positively correlated with work-to-school enrichment.

Appendix 9: Findings of Review on Psychological Variables (Study 1)

Table A9.1 presents the list of psychological factors as primary coded phrases, sub-categories and categories. The sub-categories and categories were summarised in Table 14 in the thesis. One phrase if it described a psychological factor was identified in an according article, then was listed with green background following with the frequency of the word occurrence. For example, ‘1F’ means the frequency of ‘TWS’ occur once, ‘F’ is short for ‘frequency’. If it was an abbreviation, then full form was provided first. (e.g. full version ‘Time spend on working’ of ‘TSW’ was provided before the one frequency of the word ‘TSW’). This phrase then was classified to upper level as sub-categories. One sub-category then was classified under a category. According code matching the sub-category was listed accordingly in the last column.

Table A9.1 Content Analysis of Psychological Variables of Final Inclusions (N=36)

	Short title	Article No.	Quality	CCAT Score	Primary phrases (identified in Section of Result)	Sub-categories	Categories	Sub-category Code
1	Nonis & Hudson, 2006	016	High	78%	TSW (Time spend on working 1F) TSA (10F) ability (3F) time spent (6F) studying outside of class would interact with motivation (3F)	Time spend Time spend Ability Time spend Motivation	Behaviour Behaviour Individual difference Behaviour Motivation	PB2 PB2 PI6 PB2 PM1
2	Chen g Alcántara, 2007	049	High	80%	Work experience (2F) Perception(3F) Motivation(2F) perceive (2F) reasons for wanting longer working hours(3F) sense of fulfilment (1F) down-time periods to complete their homework (1F) motivated to work (1F) the academic pressure (1F) career choices (1F) a more advantageous position (1F) gain insight into the job market (1F) real world experiences (1F) social life free time (1F), sleep time (1F) and time for socializing with friends. (1F)	Career Perception Motivation Perception Motivation Sense Involve Motivation Pressure Career -- insight Experience Social life Time Socialization	Development Cognition Motivation Cognition Motivation Cognition Behaviour Motivation Emotion Development Development Development Social Behaviour Social	PD3 PC1 PM1 PC1 PM1 PC6 PB6b PM1 PE6 PD1 PD PD4 PD3 PS5 PB2 PS5

Short title	Article No.	Quality	CCAT Score	Primary phrases (identified in Section of Result)	Sub-categories	Categories	Sub-category Code
				a means to insert structure into her daily schedule. (1F) enhance students' self-confidence (1F) quality of social life (1F)	Time spend Self-Cognition Social life	Management Social Social	MMC2 PS3 PS5
3	Josiam, et al., 2010	High	78%	work attitudes (11F) Positive Work Attitude (2F) Negative Work Attitude (2F) Positive Attitudes (7F) to Work Negative Attitudes to Work Work Ethic (6F) Work Value(5F) Work Involvement (3F) economic motivations(4F) Work Motivation (2F) Social Motivation (3F) Work Cynicism (2F)	Attitude Attitude Attitude Attitude Ethic Value Involvement Motivation Motivation Motivation Attitude	Individual Difference(ID) ID ID ID ID ID Behaviour Motivation Motivation Motivation ID	PI3 PI3 PI3 PI3 PI5 PI4 PB6a PM1 PM1 PM1 PI3
4	Jogaratnam & Buchanan, 2004	High	83%	stress (5F) time pressure social mistreatment (4F) friendship problems (2F) developmental challenges (2F) romantic problems(3F) assorted annoyance (2F) 'conflicts with friends' (1F)	Stress Pressure Interpersonal Relationship Interpersonal Relationship Challenges Interpersonal Relationship Annoyance Interpersonal Relationship	Emotion Emotion Social Social Development Social Emotion Social	PE1 PE6 PS4 PS4 PD5 PS4 PE7 PS4
5	Jackson & Wilton, 2016	High	80%	Career attitudes (23F) self-direction (13F) values-driven (12F) boundaryless mindset (13F)	Attitude Self-direction Value Personality	Individual difference (ID) Management ID ID	PI3 MMC1 PI4 PI1

	Short title	Article No.	Quality	CCAT Score	Primary phrases (identified in Section of Result)	Sub-categories	Categories	Sub-category Code
6	Cheung & Tang, 2012	098	High	88%	work values (7F) part-time work experience (3F) motivation (8F) to do good work work cynicism (2F) job satisfaction (6F) a role conflict (9F) with part-time work the perceived(4F) job insecurity of the father job autonomy (5F) part-time work quality (2F) skill variety (3F)	Value Experience Motivation Attitude Satisfaction Role conflict Perception Autonomy Work Quality Skill	Individual difference (ID) Development Motivation ID Emotion Role theory Cognition Control Zero Sum Development	PI4 PD3 PM2 PI3 PE2 TH2 PC1 MMC4 TH4 PD2
7	Butler et al., 2010	102	High	78%	alcohol consumption (18F) follows a weekly pattern drinking (5F) tension (15F) reduction alcohol expectancies (22F) work stressors (5F) work-school conflict (8F) daily coping attributable to trait-level coping (2F)	Drink Drink Tension Expectation Stress Role conflict Coping	Behaviour Behaviour Emotion Cognition Emotion Role conflict Coping	PB1 PB1 PE6 PC2 PE1 TH2 MMC3
8	Vaughan et al., 2016	104	High	85%	work relationships (1F) mental health (29F) relationship (11F overlap with others) supportive ties (6F) somatic symptoms (2F) decreased depression (14F) decreased anxiety (13F) increased life satisfaction (5F) aversive ties (6F) ambivalent ties (7F) negative relationships (2F) somatic stress symptoms (7F)	Interpersonal Relationship (IR) Mental health (MH) IP IP MH Depression Anxiety Satisfaction IP IP IP Stress Satisfaction	Social Aspects Emotion Social Social Emotion Emotion Emotion Emotion Social Social Social Social Emotion	PS4 PE4a PS4 PS4 PE4b PE5 PE5 PE2 PS4 PS4 PS4 PS4 PE1

Short title	Article No.	Quality	CCAT Score	Primary phrases (identified in Section of Result)	Sub-categories	Categories	Sub-category Code	
				satisfaction with life (4F) physical manifestations of stress(1F) turnover intentions (3F) burnout (3F) the relationship quality (11F)	Stress Intention Burnout IP	Emotion Emotion Cognition Emotion Social	PE2 PE1 PC3 PE4 PS4	
9	Boucard & Nauta, 2017	107	High	85%	work volition (16F) health-related challenges(1F) the perceived career-choice (2F) real versus ideal career aspiration (3F) major satisfaction (5F) educational persistence intentions (4F) leadership aspirations (4F)	Control Challenge Perception Career aspiration Satisfaction Intention Skill	Management Development Cognition Development Emotion Cognition Development	MMC4 PD5 PC1 PD1 PE2 PC3 PD2
10	Tesemma et al., 2014	157	High	78%	the average satisfaction (2F) the effect of work on satisfaction (2F) the effect of work on satisfaction and GPA(28F has overlap with other) students' satisfaction (8F) overall college satisfaction (4F) student satisfaction (4F) the highest satisfaction(1F) the lowest satisfaction(1F)	Satisfaction Satisfaction Satisfaction Satisfaction Satisfaction Satisfaction Satisfaction	Emotion Emotion Emotion Emotion Emotion Emotion Emotion	PE2 PE2 PE2 PE2 PE2 PE2 PE2
11	Pascarella et al., 1998	161	High	88%	end-of-first-year composite cognitive development (9F) students' cognitive development (2F) end-of-first-year cognitive development (24F has overlap with others) precollege cognitive ability (3F) end-of-first-year science reasoning (8F) end-of-second-year writing skills (6F)	Cognition Cognition Cognition Cognition Cognition Skill	Development Development Development Development Development Development	PD4 PD4 PD4 PD4 PD4 PD2
12	Bono et al., 2017	164	High	90%	smoking frequency (4F) drinking frequency (6F) smoking (11F has overlaps with others) alcohol use frequency and quantity (1F) substance use (6F has overlaps with other)	Smoke Drink Smoke Drink Substance use (SU)	Behaviour Behaviour Behaviour Behaviour Behaviour	PB1 PB1 PB1 PB1 PB1

Short title	Article No.	Quality	CCAT Score	Primary phrases (identified in Section of Result)	Sub-categories	Categories	Sub-category Code	
				drinking (23F has overlaps with others)	Drink			
				had used any alcohol (1F)	Drink	Behaviour	PB1	
				behaviour (1F)	Behaviour	Behaviour	PB1	
				tobacco use (2F)	Smoke	Behaviour	PB1	
				substance use behaviors (2F)	SU	Behaviour	PB1	
				personality (6F)	Personality	Behaviour	PB1	
						Individual	PI1	
				consuming alcohol (2F)	Drink	Difference(ID)		
				smoking cigarettes	Smoke	Behaviour	PB1	
				smoking status (2F)	Smoke	Behaviour	PB1	
13	Swanson et al., 2006	171	High	90%	overall satisfaction (19F) with university life	Satisfaction	Emotion	PE2
					academic role congruence (3F)	Role	Role theory	TH2
					social role congruence (2F)	Role	Role theory	TH2
					adjustment to university (20F)	Adjustment	Management	MMC5
					psychological state (stress(15F has overlap with others))	Stress	Emotion	PE1
					trait (4F)	Personality	Individual difference (ID)	PI1
					positive affectivity (PA) (7F)	Personality	ID	PI1
					negative affectivity (NA) (9F)	Personality	ID	PI1
					adaptation to university (5F)	Adaption	Management	MMC5
					perceived stress (10F)	Stress	Emotion	PE1
					Role congruence (19F)	Role	Role theory	TH2
					role conflict	Role	Role theory	TH2
					role balance (3F)	Role	Role theory	TH2
					role enhancement (3F)	Role	Role theory	TH2
					missing lectures(1F), poorer concentration(1F)	Other	Behaviour	PB6b
					meeting academic deadlines (1F)	Other	Behaviour	PB6b
					career/experience (1F) factor	Experience	Development	PD3
					future job and career prospects (1F)	Career	Development	PD1
					self/social development factor (2F)	Self/Social	Development	PD6
					academic role factor (2F)	Role	Role theory	TH2
					Academic role (6F has overlap with others)	Role	Role theory	TH2

Short title	Article No.	Quality	CCAT Score	Primary phrases (identified in Section of Result)	Sub-categories	Categories	Sub-category Code	
				affectivity(1F)	Personality	ID	PI1	
14	Ho & Huan g, 2013	173	High	80%	determinant of job selection (1F)	Motivation	Motivation	PM1
				dimension of Benefits Pursuit (1F)	Motivation	Motivation	PM1	
				dimension of Risk Avoidance (1F)	Motivation	Motivation	PM1	
				Knowledge and Skills (2F)	Skill	Development	PD2	
				Beneficial to Future Employment (2F)	Career	Development	PD1	
				Avoiding Health Detriment (2F)	Health	Emotion	PE4b	
				Building Good Relationships (3F)	Relationship	Social	PS4	
				Avoiding Safety Detriment (2F)	Safety	Cognition	PC6	
				Avoiding Leisure Time (1F)	Leisure time	Behaviour	PB3	
				Detriment (6F)	Stress	Emotion	PE1	
				working experience (3F)	Experience	Development	PD3	
				extracurricular activities (1F)	Activities	Behaviour	PB3	
				paid less attention (1F)	Attention	Cognition	PC6	
				work-related safety concerns (1F)	Concerns	Cognition	PC6	
				Employment Preparation (1F)	Career	Development	PD1	
				Learning Practical Skills (1F)	Skill	Development	PD2	
15	Mant hei & Gilmore, 2005	186	High	85%	manage multiple roles and responsibilities (1F)	Role	Management	MMC1
				Too much pressure (2F)	Role	Role Theory	TH2	
				can't handle it. (1F)	Pressure	Emotion	PE6	
					Coping	Management	MMC3	
				always exhausted (1F)	Exhaust	Emotion	PE7	
				extra stress (4F)	Stress	Emotion	PE1	
				time spent (3F) in class	Time spend	Behaviour	PB2	
				hours spent studying outside of class	Time spend Time	Behaviour	PB2	
				had extra time in which to work in paid employment	spend	Behaviour	PB2	
				activities (21F)	Activities	Behaviour	PB7	
				the time (46F has overlaps with others)	Time (spend)	Behaviour	PB2	
				expense (4F has overlaps with others)	Expenditure	Behaviour	PB4	
				other inefficiencies involved in getting to and from each "work" site (classes, study place, employment) (1F)	Time spend	Behaviour	PB2	
				perception of feeling (1F)	Perception	Cognition	PC1	
				overloaded and stretched (1F)	Stress	Emotion	PE1	

Short title	Article No.	Quality	CCAT Score	Primary phrases (identified in Section of Result)	Sub-categories	Categories	Sub-category Code
				adaptation to the whole programme (1F)	Adaption	Management	MMC5
				loneliness (1F)	Loneliness	Cognition	PC6
				six areas of expenditure (4F)	Expenditure	Behaviour	PB4
				essential living expenses(2F)	Expenditure	Behaviour	PB4
				more spare time to spend (1F)with friends, family, do things they did like to	Time spend	Behaviour	PB2
				have a balanced lifestyle (3F)	Balance	Balance theory (BT)	TH1
				I would spend more time on my studies. (1F)	Time spend	Behaviour	PB2
				It would be nice not to have to worry about it (1F)	Worry	Emotion	PE7
				people contact (1F)	Socialization	Social	PS5
				the enjoyment they gained from the work (1F)	Enjoyment	Emotion	PE3
				want the job more for CV [curriculum vitae] purposes. (1F)	Career	Development	PD1
				Learn very useful skills (4F)	Skill	Development	PD2
				time management (1F)	Time management (TM)	Management	MMC2
				people skills (1F)	Socialization	Development	PD2
				socialisation with workmates and general public (1F)	Socialization	Social	PS5
				Meet new people, a sense of knowing you can support yourself. (1F)		Social	PS5
				Sport and recreational/leisure activities (3F)	Activities		
				sport and recreational activities (1F)	Activities	Behaviour	PB3
				give up a lot of entertainment/recreation activities for work (1F)	Management	Behaviour	PB3
				Would prefer to concentrate efforts on getting good grades (1F)		Management	MMC1
				having a little more leisure time (1F)	Involvement		
				Balance among activities (8F)		Behaviour	PB6b
					Time spend		
					Balance	Behaviour	PB2
					Balance	Management	MMC1
				they spent in various activities (1F)	Activities	BT	TH1
				spend more hours in study and leisure activities and fewer in paid work (1F)	Time spend	Behaviour	PB7
				out of balance.	TM	Behaviour	PB2
						Management	MMC2

Short title	Article No.	Quality	CCAT Score	Primary phrases (identified in Section of Result)	Sub-categories	Categories	Sub-category Code	
				balance between social life and studying (1F)	Balance			
				It would be great to have spare time (2F)	Balance	BT	TH1	
				spend more time on work. (1F)	TM	Management	MMC1	
				the relative ideal balance among all three categories of activities (study, work and leisure) (1F)	Time spend	Management	MMC2	
				spend more time on study (2F)	Balance	Behaviour	PB2	
				(spend more time on) recreation/leisure (1F)		BT	TH1	
				less time in paid work (1F)	Time spend	Behaviour	PB2	
				reduce the time spent in paid work or socialising (1F)	Time spend	Behaviour	PB2	
				social activities (2F)	TM	Behaviour	PB2	
				less time for recreation/leisure (1F)	Social activities	Management	MMC2	
				less time for social, leisure and extra-curricular activities (1F)	Time spend	Behaviour	PB3	
				regular attendance at lectures (1F)	Time spend	Behaviour	PB2	
				time management skills (1F)		Behaviour	PB2	
				their ability to manage stress (1F)	Involvement			
				some perceived benefits to working (1F)	TM	Behaviour	PB6b	
				experience of learning life skills (1F)	Management	Management	MMC2	
				getting more organised (1F)	Perception	Management	MMC1	
				have to delegate time to all tasks. (1F)	Skill	Cognition	PC1	
				Must take into account not just work and study but household duties (1F)	Management	Development	PD2	
				stresses of their life situation (1F)	TM	Management	MMC1	
				family commitments (e.g., child minding, children's activities) (1F)	Management	Management	MMC2	
				a "lack of motivation"(3F)	Stress			
				Of least concern was poor health (1F)	Management	Emotion	PE1	
						Management	MMC1	
					Motivation			
					Health	Motivation	PM1	
						Physical health	PE4b	
16	Bednarska & Olsze	197	High	78%	work experience (17F)	Experience	Development	PD3
					perceived job and organization attributes (3F)	Perception	Cognition	PC1
					perceptions of hospitality career attractiveness (8F)	Perception	Cognition	PC1
					intentions to apply for a job after graduation (4F)	Intention	Cognition	PC3

Short title	Article No.	Quality	CCAT Score	Primary phrases (identified in Section of Result)	Sub-categories	Categories	Sub-category Code
wski, 2016				work experience (1F)	Experience	Development	PD3
				it can influence future career decisions. (1F)	Career	Development	PD1
				career expectations (1F)	Career	Development	PD1
				social relations (3F)	Social relation	Social	PS4
				career needs (1F)	Need	Motivation	PM1
				study expectations (1F)	Expectation	Cognition	PC2
				pessimistic about social relations in the workplace (1F)	Attitude	Individual difference	PI3
				relative optimism about reputation. (1F)	Attitude	(ID)	PI3
				hospitality employment moderately attractive (1F)	Attitude	ID	PI3
				less positive toward the industry (1F)	Attitude	ID	PI3
				perceptions of hospitality career attractiveness (1F)	Perception	Cognition	PC1
				development opportunities (3F)	Development	Development	PD6
				expected and as perceived attribute (1F)	Perception	Cognition	PC1/PC2
				job that matches individual interests (1F)	Interest	ID	PI4
				tasks that are challenging (1F)	Challenge	Development	PD5
				useful experience for future employment (1F)	Experience	Development	PD3
direct experience in hospitality (1F)	Experience	Development	PD3				
more favorable attitudes (2F)	Attitude	ID	PI3				
job pursuit intentions (2F)	Intention	Cognition	PC3				
17 Teng, 2008	216	High	90%	Personality traits (5F)	Personality	Individual Difference	PI1
				the personality scale (2F)	Personality	(ID)	PI1
				the Big Five (9F)	Personality	ID	PI1
				Attitudes toward hospitality jobs (7F)	Attitude	ID	PI3
				interpersonal relationships (4F)	Interpersonal relationship	Social aspect	PS4
				Hospitality employment aspirations (12F)	Career Aspiration	Development	PD1
				Attitudinal factors (5F)	Attitude	ID	PI3
				Extroversion (5F)	Personality	ID	PI1
				Agreeableness (3F)	Personality	ID	PI1
				Neuroticism (1F)	Personality	ID	PI1
18 Hall, et	224	High	80%	empathy (21F) score	Empathy	Emotion	PE3
				a chronic condition (1F)	Health	Emotion	PE4b
				took regular medication (3F)	Take medicine	Behaviour	PB7

Short title	Article No.	Quality	CCAT Score	Primary phrases (identified in Section of Result)	Sub-categories	Categories	Sub-category Code
al., 2015				health status (1F)	Health	Emotion	PE4b
				had a chronic medical condition (2F)	Health	Emotion	PE4b
19 Gbadamosi, et al., 2015	228	High	80%	the self-theories (15F) (fixedness (3F) and malleable(7F))	Self-theory	Social aspects	PS3
				career aspiration (25F)	Career aspiration	Development	PD1
				career choice (1F)	Career	Development	PD1
				the ability of students to maximise the opportunities (1F)	Ability/Skill	Development	PD2
				value added by parttime work (3F)	Value	Individual Difference (ID)	PI4
				their ability to utilise this to inform their future career (1F)	Ability/Skill	Development	PD2
				have a high career drive (1F)	Motivation	Motivation	PM2
				strive to enhance their employability. (1F)	Motivation	Motivation	PM2
				students' self-efficacy (12F)	Self-efficacy	Social aspects	PS2
				self-confident (1F)	Self	Social aspects	PS3
have a higher drive (1F)	Motivation	Motivation	PM2				
20 Beauchamp et al., 2016	257	High	80%	attachment style (19F)	Attachment	Social aspects	PI2
				the pooled fearful and preoccupied group (1F)	Attachment	Social aspects	PI2
				Pooled secure and dismissing students (3F)	Attachment	Social aspects	PI2
				pooled preoccupied and fearful students (1F)	Attachment	Social aspects	PI2
				global amotivation scores (5F)	Motivation	Motivation	PM1
				the secure attachment style (14F)	Attachment	Social aspects	PI2
				the dismissing (10F)	Attachment	Social aspects	PI2
				the preoccupied (7F)	Attachment	Social aspects	PI2
				the fearful attachment groups (3F)	Attachment	Social aspects	PI2
				attachment style (secure vs. insecure)	Attachment	Social aspects	PI2
21 McGeogor, 2015	333	High	75%	with independence (1F)	Sense	Other emotions	PE3
				motivation (2F)	Motivation	Motivation	PM1
				time management (1F)	Time management (TM)	TM	MMC2
					Social		
				social aspects (1F)	Socialization	Social aspects	PS5
				making contacts (1F)	Time pressure	Social aspects	PS5
				lack of time (2F)	Physical health	Emotion	PE6
				followed by tiredness (3F)	Stress	Emotion	PE4b

Short title	Article No.	Quality	CCAT Score	Primary phrases (identified in Section of Result)	Sub-categories	Categories	Sub-category Code	
				stress (6F)	Social life	Emotion	PE1	
				anti-social hours (2F)	Confidence	Social aspects	PS4	
				confidence (3F)	Activities	Emotion	PE3	
				Extracurricular activities (2F)	Physical health	Behaviour	PB7	
				work-associated illness (1F)	Physical health	Emotion	PE4b	
				Physical health (1F)	Physical health	Emotion	PE4b	
				lack of sleep (2F)	Physical health	Emotion	PE4b	
				general illness (1F)	Panic	Emotion	PE4b	
				panic attacks (1F)	Mental health	Emotion	PE7	
				Mental health (3F)	Depression	Emotion	PE4a	
				depression (2F)	Social life	Emotion	PE5	
				deal with abusive and violent people	Social life	Social aspects	PS5	
				bullying at work	Social life	Social aspects	PS5	
				social life	Pressure	Social aspects	PS5	
				Lack of time	Socialisation	Emotion	PE6	
				socialise with friends	Support	Social aspects	PS5	
				support (20F)	Social life	Social aspects	PS6	
				social activities		Social aspects	PS5	
22	Hsiao, 2015	348	High	75%	students' cheating intention (12F)	Intention	Cognition	PC3
					attitude (6F)	Attitude	Individual Difference (ID)	PI3
					subjective norm (4F)	Norms/belief	ID	PI4
					perceived behavioral control (4F)	Control	Management	MMC4
					cheating (20F has overlaps with others)	Cheat	Behaviour	PB5
					anticipated positive affect (4F)	Affect	Emotion	PE8
					Unethical beliefs in the workplace (1F)	Ethics	ID	PI5
					intention to cheat (7F)	Intention	Cognition	PC3
					anticipated negative affect (3F)	Affect	Emotion	PE8
					unethical professional beliefs (3F)	Ethics	ID	PI5
					negative affect (4F has overlaps with others)	Affect	Emotion	PE8
					the theory of planned behavior (1F)	TPB	Other Theory	TH6

Short title	Article No.	Quality	CCAT Score	Primary phrases (identified in Section of Result)	Sub-categories	Categories	Sub-category Code
23 Carney et al., 2005	354	High	75%	reasons for working (1F)	Reason	Motivation	PM1
				physical and mental well-being (4F)	Well-being	Emotion/Health	PE4
				the students' physical and psychological well-being (1F)	Well-being	Emotion/Health	PE4
				Physical functioning (7F)	Physical health	Emotion/Health	PE4b
				Role limitation due to physical problems (2F)	Physical health	Emotion/Health	PE4b
				Role limitation due to emotional problems (4F)	Emotional health	Emotion/Health	PE4a
				Social function (1F)	Social	Social aspects	PS5
				Mental health (5F)	Mental health	Emotion/Health	PE4a
				Energy/vitality (1F)	Energy- Physical health	Emotion/Health	PE4
				Pain (2F)	Physical health	Emotion/Health	PE4b
				General health perception (2F)	Health	Emotion/Health	PE4
				energy and vitality (2F)	Energy-PH	Emotion/Health	PE4
				role-physical (1F)	Physical health	Emotion/Health	PE4b
				vitality (1F)	Vitality-PH	Emotion/Health	PE4
				social functioning (3F)	Social	Social aspects	PS5
				role emotional (1F)	Emotion	Emotion/Health	PE4a
				perceived academic performance (3F)	Perception	Cognition	PC1
a student perceives an effect on studying (1F)	Perception	Cognition	PC1				
a good mental state (2F)	Mental health	Emotion/Health	PE4a				
cope with more work (1F)	Coping	Coping	MMC3				
the student's perception (1F)	Perception	Cognition	PC1				
24 Butler, 2007	391	High	90%	school satisfaction (7F)	Satisfaction	Emotion	PE2
				job-school congruence (3F)	Role congruence	Role theory	TH2
				the work-school interface (2F)	Role	Role theory	TH2
25 Hammes & Haller, 1983	435	High	83%	how students cope with work and school (1F)	Coping	Management	MMC3
				requiring highly esoteric skills (2F)	Skill	Development	PD2
				mentioned as positive qualities (jobs) (1F)	Perception	Cognition	PC1
				meeting and dealing with new people (1F)	Socialization	Social aspects	PS5
				tediousness (1F)	Emotion	Emotion	PE7
				mental (40%) or physical stress (1F)	Health	Emotion/Health	PE4
				working students achieve at least as well as non-workers (1F)	Achievement	Development	PD6
Coping with work and school							

Short title	Article No.	Quality	CCAT Score	Primary phrases (identified in Section of Result)	Sub-categories	Categories	Sub-category Code
				choose carefully the semesters in which to take employment (1F)	Coping	Management	MMC3
				why they had worked during some term (1F)	Control	Management	MMC4
				the reasons most often given for not working involved (1F)			
				adjusting (2F) to college in the freshman year	Reason	Motivation	PM1
				worry about grades (1F)	Reason	Motivation	PM1
				worried about my grades (1F)	Adjustment	Management	MMC5
				a strategy available only to some students (1F)	Worry	Emotion	PE7
				modify work hours during a semester (1F)	Worry	Emotion	PE7
				handling the intermittent pressures (9F) of examinations	Strategy	Management	MMC6
				During the pressure times (1F)	Strategy	Management	MMC6
				another common strategy (3F)	Pressure	Emotion	PE6
				cutting back on hours (or not working at all) (1F)	Pressure	Emotion	PE6
				during times of academic stress (1F)	Strategy	Management	MMC6
				time commitments were reduced (1F)	Control	Management	MMC4
				when academic pressures (2F) are heaviest	Stress	Emotion	PE1
				Adjusting work hours	Time spend	Behaviour	PB2
				simply to quit (7F)	Pressure	Emotion	PE6
				they feared their grades were going to suffer (1F)	Adjustment	Management	MMC5
				quit to lessen pressures (1F)	Control	Management	MMC4
				quit courses as well as a job (1F)	Fear	Emotion	PE7
				reduce academic pressures by dropping courses (2F)	Pressure	Emotion	PE6
				impossible to handle both work and school (1F)	Control	Management	MMC4
				dropped their jobs rather than their courses (1F)	Coping	Management	MMC3
				The heavier the course load, the less I could justify working. (1F)	Balance	Balance theory	TH1
				Time becomes more valuable. (1F)	Strategy	Management	MMC6
				Dropping courses or quitting a job (1F)	Perception	Cognition	PC1
				extreme strategies (5F)	Zero Sum	Zero sum theory	TH4
				for balancing the demands of each (1F)	Judgement	Cognition	PC4
				reduced leisure time (1F)	Control	Management	MMC4
				done less socializing (1F)	Strategy	Management	MMC6
				taken any time from studying (1F)	Management	Management	MMC1
					Balance	Balance theory	TH1

Short title	Article No.	Quality	CCAT Score	Primary phrases (identified in Section of Result)	Sub-categories	Categories	Sub-category Code
				Workers reported studying a mean of 3.58 hours during an average weekday (1F)	Time spend	Behaviour	PB2
				whereas nonworkers reported studying 4.52 hours (1F)	Time spend	Behaviour	PB2
				this reduction in study time (1F)	Time spend	Behaviour	PB2
				more efficient (4F) by taking better advantage of small amounts of free time (1F)	Time spend	Behaviour	PB2
					Time spend	Behaviour	PB2
					Efficiency	Emotion	
				the activities (8F)	Time management	Management	MMC5
				the most popular activities were non-academic: visiting friend, reading the newspaper, having a beer, running errand, snacking, or getting some exercise. (1F)	Activities		
				Going to the library or studying (1F)	Involvement	Behaviour	PB7
				socializing(1F)	Social activities	Behaviour	PB7
				leisure(1F)		Behaviour	PB3
				extracurricular activities (and sleeping for the unemployed). (1F)	Study		
				value potential study time (1F)	Social activities	Behaviour	PB6b
				the fewer hours spent preparing for classes are used more effectively. (1F)	Other activities	Behaviour	PB3
				they did better under pressure (1F)	Study	Behaviour	PB7
				they became more organized (1F)		Behaviour	PB6b
				'figuring out the system (2F),'	Judgement		
				efficiency (2F)	Strategy	Cognition	PC5
				Work makes me more confident (1F)		Management	MMC6
				encourages me to learn to allocate my time more effectively (1F)	Adaption		
				to concentrate harder on what I am studying (2F)	Adaption	Management	MMC5
				use one's time wisely (1F)	Perception	Management	MMC5
				one is more apt to not concentrate as hard, to read the same page over many times before absorbing its contents, to stop studying to chat with friend, eat snacks, and not be very careful about finding a very quiet place to study. (1F)	Efficiency	Cognition	PC1
				Confidence (1F)	Confidence	Emotion	PE3
				concentration and diligence (1F)	Skill	Emotion	PE3
				may simply expand to fill the time available (1F)		Development	PD2
					Control		
					Strategy	Management	MMC4
					Control	Management	MMC6
						Management	MMC4

Short title	Article No.	Quality	CCAT Score	Primary phrases (identified in Section of Result)	Sub-categories	Categories	Sub-category Code
				contribute to students' academic achievement (3F)	Confidence		
				learned a lot on his job(1F)	Control	Emotion	PE3
				what I am doing is at least partially meaningful (1F)	Time management	Management	MMC4
				an indirect contribution (1F)	Contribution	Management	MMC2
				job provided her with an opportunity to meet and interact with other than college-age youth (1F)	Learn (other)		
				my job provide for another kind of socializing (4F)	Judgement	Development	PD6
				meeting and dealing with people (1F) on the job	Contribution	Development	PD6
				meet other students (1F)	Socialization	Cognition	PC5
				meet people with my dining job (1F)	Socialization	Development	PD6
				keep in touch with the college students (1F)	Socialization	Social aspects	PS5
				some work may provide an alternative and valuable chance to meet and interact with faculty, students, or non-academic adults. (1F)	Socialization	Social aspects	PS5
				contribute directly to social well-being (1F)	Socialization	Social aspects	PS5
				or self-concept (1F)	Socialization	Social aspects	PS5
				It really helps my social life. (1F)	Well-being	Social aspects	PS5
				meet a lot of people (1F)	Self		
				frustrating (1F)	Social life	Social Health	PE4a
				more independent (1F)	Socialization	Social aspects	PS3
				Increased independence (1F)	Frustration	Social aspects	PS5
				the reduction in time available for leisure pursuits, peer interaction, and extracurricular activities (1F)	Independence	Social aspects	PS5
				prohibits athletic scholarships (1F)	Independence	Emotion	PE7
				It was very hard to handle studies and track and a job all at the same time. (1F)	Time management	Emotion	PE3
				I decided to drop one of them (5F has overlaps with others)	Achievement	Emotion	PE3
				If one believes that these activities are beneficial, the loss of those benefits represents another hidden cost of working (1F)	Struggle	Management	MMC2
				seriously disadvantaged—physically, mentally, (1F)	Control	Development	PD6
				and socially-by the demands of the job (1F)	Decision making	Emotion	PE7
					Zero sum		
					Health	Management	MMC4
						Cognition	PC4

Short title	Article No.	Quality	CCAT Score	Primary phrases (identified in Section of Result)	Sub-categories	Categories	Sub-category Code	
				part-time work experience (6F) career development (10F) a serious attitude (1F)	Experience Career Attitude	Development Development Individual Difference Behaviour	PD3 PD1 PI3	
				participation in university studies (1F) career formation (1F) job-seeking activities (1F) the time spent in part-time work (7F) employment commitment (5F) students engaging in part-time work (3F)	Involvement Career Activities Time spend Career Involvement	Development Behaviour Behaviour Development Behaviour	PB6b PD1 PB8 PB2 PD1 PB6a	
28	Jackson & Wilton, 2017	554	High	75%	PE (24F) (Perceived employability) securing a job (1F) demand for their experience (4F) in the labour market seeking employment (1F) decision making (1F) self-awareness (2F)	Career Securing job Experience Seeking job Decision Self	Development Behaviour Development Behaviour Cognition Social aspects	PD1 PB8 PB3 PB8 PC4 PS3
29	Greene & Maggs, 2015	622	High	83%	organized activities (14F) spent more time on employment (5F) organized activity time(6F) time spent on academics (3F) studied more (2F) Academic Time(8F) employment time (4F) spent less time on academics (4F) At the person level, students who averaged more time on employment on weekends averaged less time on academics. (1F) On days when students spent more time on employment and organized activities, they spent less time on academics. Likewise, on semesters when they spent more time than average on employment, they spent less time on academics. (1F)	Activities Time spend Activities Time spend Involvement in study Time spend Time spend Time spend Zero sum Zero sum	Behaviour Behaviour Behaviour Behaviour Behaviour Behaviour Behaviour Behaviour Zero sum theory Zero sum theory	PB7 PB2 PB7 PB2 PB6b PB2 PB2 PB2 Th4 TH4

Short title	Article No.	Quality	CCAT Score	Primary phrases (identified in Section of Result)	Sub-categories	Categories	Sub-category Code
30 Winkler, 2008	713	High	76%	perceptions of the work task (7F)	Perception	Cognition	PC1
				perceptions of social integration (1F)	Social perception	Social aspects	PS1
				relations with other employees (14F)	Social perception	Social aspects	PS1
				low-skilled job (6F)	Skill	Development	PD2
				skilled tasks (1F)	Skill	Development	PD2
				unskilled work (1F)	Skill	Development	PD2
				find their job interesting (3F)	Interested	Emotion	PE3
				have fun at work (3F)	Fun	Emotion	PE3
				contributes to their personal and work experience (1F)	Career	Development	PD1
				acquire work related knowledge and abilities. (1F)	Knowledge/ability	Development	PD6
				work experience (1F)	Experience	Development	PD3
				experience work reality (1F)	Skill	Development	PD3
				learning for example how to deal with customers, how to discuss difficult topics with the supervisor (1F)	Independent	Development	PD2
				become more independent (1F)	Skill	Emotion	PE3
				They are responsible for organizing their course of study self dependent, in terms of putting together the university timetable, meeting deadlines for term papers, or registering for exams. (1F)	Coping	Development	PD2
				do several tasks at the same level of ability or responsibility (1F)	Adaption	Management	MMC3
				adopt more skilful tasks (1F)		Management	MMC5
				customer diversity contributes to their positive job interpretation. (1F)	Skill	Development	PD2
				social relations (1F)	Skill	Development	PD2
				raise the social climate, the feeling of belonging together, or their good relations to fellow employees (1F)	Relationship	Social aspects	PS4
				job satisfaction. (1F)	Social Perception		
				satisfaction (1F)	Satisfaction	Social aspects	PS1
				broader social aspects (e.g. friendly people, relaxed atmosphere) (1F)	Satisfaction	Emotion	PE2
	Socialization	Emotion	PE2				
the work schedule according to their needs. (1F)		Social aspects	PS5				
balance (1F)	Perception						
	Balance	Cognition	PC1				

Short title	Article No.	Quality	CCAT Score	Primary phrases (identified in Section of Result)	Sub-categories	Categories	Sub-category Code
				need (2F)		Management	MMC5
				training (20F)	Motivation	Balance Theory	TH1
				attitudes towards instruction and training	Training activities	Motivation	PM1
					Attitude	Behaviour	PB7
				cope with this situation (1F)		Individual difference	PI3
				adopting the strategy (1F)	Coping	Management	
				training activities (2F)	Strategy	Management	MMC3
				negative feelings (1F)	TA	Behaviour	MMC6
				problematic relation (1F)	Negative feel	Emotion	PB7
				perceived as a threat (1F)	Relationship	Social aspects	PE7
				hostile behaviour (2F).	Social perception	Social aspects	PS4
				less opportunities to participate (1F)	Relationship	Social aspects	PS1
				less respectful (1F)	Opportunity	Development	PS4
				social exclusion (1F)	Disrespectful	Emotion	PD5
				close contact with the full-time staff (1F)	Relationship	Social aspects	PE7
				integrated (2F) in the work team	Relationship	Social aspects	PS4
				social integration in the work team (3F)	Relationship	Social aspects	PS4
				the relation (14F)	Relationship	Social aspects	PS4
				negative experiences with supervisors (1F)	Relationship	Social aspects	PS4
				Good personal relations (1F)	Negative feel	Emotion	PS4
				getting along with the supervisor (1F)	Relationship	Social aspects	PE7
				positive ratings of their job (1F)	Relationship	Social aspects	PS4
				get on with fulltime employees(1F)	Perception	Cognition	PS4
				there are also some tensions (1F)	Relationship	Social aspects	PC1
				not experiencing any hostile behaviour from full-time staff (1F)	Tension	Emotion	PS4
				the formal and informal hierarchy. (2F)	Neutral feel	Emotion	PE6
							PE3
				Full-time staff ... demands ... subordination from the students	Social status	Social aspects	
							PS1
					Relationship	Social aspects	
							PS1

Short title	Article No.	Quality	CCAT Score	Primary phrases (identified in Section of Result)	Sub-categories	Categories	Sub-category Code
31	Lee et al., 1999	High	75%	Why students work (1F)	Motivation	Motivation	PM1
				reasons for working (3F)	Motivation	Motivation	PM1
				essential and desirable expenditure (1F)	Expenditure	Behaviour	PB4
				socializing (2F)	Socialization	Social aspects	PS5
				improving clinical skills (1F)	Skill	Development	PD2
				enhancing knowledge (2F)	Knowledge	Development	PD6
				In relation to future careers, becoming known to potential future employers was an important motivating factor. (1F)	Career	Development	PD1
					Experience	Development	PD3
					Motivation	Motivation	PM1
				the personal satisfaction (1F)	Satisfaction	Emotion	PE2
				meeting new colleagues, working with residents (1F)	Socialization	Social aspects	PS5
				enjoyment of work (1F)	Enjoyment	Emotion	PE3
				additional experience (1F)	Experience	Development	PD3
				the concept of confidence (8F)	Confidence	Emotion	PE3
				tiredness (2F)	Tiredness	Health	PE4b
				reduced time for preparation for assignments (1F)	Time spend	Behaviour	PB2
				social life (1F)	Social life	Social aspects	PS5
				social activities (1F)	Social activities	Behaviour	PB3
				personal development (2F)	Development	Development	PD
				social and communication skills (1F)	Skill	Development	PD2
time management (1F)	Skill	Development	PD2				
they found their work personally rewarding. (1F)	Rewarding	Emotion	PE3				
having restricted time for themselves, partners, family and socializing generally. (1F)	Time spend	Behaviour	PB2				
the physical and mental stress (1F)	Stress	Emotion	PE1				
a need for a more accepting attitude towards students in employment (1F)	Need	Motivation	PM1				
32	Earl & Brigh t, 2003	High	80%	Career Decision (33F)	Career decision	Cognition	PC4
				career decision-making (2F)	Career decision	Cognition	PC4
				career choice (4F)	Career choice	Cognition	PC4
				career decidedness (1F)	Career decision	Cognition	PC4
				career options (1F)	Career	Development	PD1
				need for career decision-making (1F)	Need	Motivation	PM1

Short title	Article No.	Quality	CCAT Score	Primary phrases (identified in Section of Result)	Sub-categories	Categories	Sub-category Code	
				indecision, certainty and decisiveness (1F)	Decision making	Cognition	PC4	
				self-clarity (5F)	Self	Social aspects	PS3	
				work experience (12F)	Experience	Development	PD3	
33	Park & Sprung, 2015	805	High	75%	weekly WSC (18F)	Role conflict	Role theory	TH2
					sleep quality (28F)	Sleep quality	Health/emotion	PE4
					weekly fatigue (28F)	Fatigue	Social aspects	PE4b
					Recovery self-efficacy (13F)	Self-efficacy	Role theory	PS2
					work-school conflict	Role conflict	Behaviour	TH2
					typical sleep duration (2F)	Sleep	Health	PB7
					lower-quality sleep	Poor sleep	Health	PE4
					recovery self efficacy	Self-efficacy	Social aspects	PS2
34	Koeske & Koeske, 1989	843	High	78%	Feeling tense or keyed up”	Tension	Emotion	PE6
					“feeling low in energy or slowed down”	Tiredness	Health	PE4
					symptoms (16F)	Symptom	Health	PE4
					“quite a bit” or “extreme” distress (8F)	Distress	Emotion	PE7
					well-being	Well being	Well being	PE4
					the groups did not differ on Social Support (10F)	Social support	Social aspect	PS6
					fulltime students with part-time jobs appeared to encounter greater demands and have somewhat fewer resources at their disposal to deal with them. (1F)	Less support	Social aspect	PS6
					“multiple role” sense (1F)	Role	Role	TH2
					role variables (such as marital and parent status) (1F)	Role	Role	TH2
					The buffering effect of social support (1F)	SS	Social aspect	PS6
					stress (10F)	Stress	Emotion	PE1
35	Creed et al., 2015	862	High	78%	enrichment (4F)	Positive feel	Emotion	PE3
					rewards (7F)	Positive feel	Emotion	PE3
					involvement (4F)	Involvement	Behaviour	PB6
					negative feelings about university (5F)	Negative Feel	Emotion	PE7
					perceiving (2F) more enrichment, rewards...at work	Perception	Cognition	PC1
					work-university facilitation (2F)	Role facilitation	Role theory	TH2
					work-university conflict (3F)	Role conflict	Role theory	TH2
					work university facilitation (1F)	Role Facilitation	Role theory	TH2
					engagement (dedication) (3F)	Engagement	Behaviour	PB6

Short title	Article No.	Quality	CCAT Score	Primary phrases (identified in Section of Result)	Sub-categories	Categories	Sub-category Code
				well-being (7F)	Well-being	Well-being	PE4
				positive feelings (1F)	Positive feel	Emotion	PE3
				vigour (1F)	Vigour	Well-being	PE4
36	Dakas, 2011	867	High	78%	Negative work-to-school spill over (1F)	Role conflict	TH2
					WSC (19F) (Work-School Conflict)	Role conflict	TH2
					positive work-to school spill over	Role enrichment	TH2
					WSE(16F) (Work-School Enrichment)	Role enrichment	TH2
					job satisfaction (9F)	Satisfaction	PE2

Table A9.2 presents the expanded categories of variable studied in the final 36 included articles. There are four categories of variables. They are ‘work variables’, ‘psychological variables’, ‘demographic variables’ and ‘academic and other variables’.

Table A9.2 Four Overarching Categories of Variables Studied

Short Title (Author and Year)	Article No.	CCAT Score	Research method	Category 1 Work variables	Category 2 Psychological variables	Category 3 Demographic variables	Category 4 Academic and other variables
Nonis & Hudson, 2006	016	78%	Questionnaire	TSW (total time spent on work)	TSW (total time spent on work)	gender, age, race (controlled)	SGPA (grade point average for the semester) TSA (total time spent on academic studying) ACT academic load (controlled variable)
Cheng & Alcántara, 2007	049	80%	Focus group	Work experiences (job description, average hours per work)	Perceptions (compared their experiences working on- and off-campus; peers perceive; sense of fulfilment of work) Motivation (reasons of work)	--	--

Short Title (Author and Year)	Article No.	CCAT Score	Research method	Category 1 Work variables	Category 2 Psychological variables	Category 3 Demographic variables	Category 4 Academic and other variables
					Impact of work on college life (positive and negative on academic) (on their social life)		
Josiam et al., 2010	052	78%	Questionnaire	Job Factor Profile; Years of working experience	Work Attitude (Positive /Negative /work ethic) Work Involvement Work Value Work Motivation	Gender, age, race	Academic performance
Jogaratnam & Buchanan, 2004	059	83%		Average work hours per week; Tenure in current job (months); Number of jobs held	sources of stress (Time pressure, general social mistreatment, friendship problems, developmental challenge, academic alienation, romantic problems, and assorted annoyance)	Gender, age	GPA, year in college, status (full time/ part time)
Jackson & Wilton, 2016	081	80%	questionnaire	Employment status (full time /part time working In background characteristics)	Career attitude (self-direction and values- driven; boundaryless mindset, physical mobility dimension)	Age, gender, (in background characteristics);	subjects degree (t in background characteristics : the data only partially supported the influence of business degree specialisation on protean career attitudes.) institution, location (controlled)
Cheung & Tang, 2012	098	88%	questionnaire	Part-time work quality, (job autonomy, skill	Work Value (motivation to do good work; work cynicism)	Gender, age	Family income, perceived job

Short Title (Author and Year)	Article No.	CCAT Score	Research method	Category 1 Work variables	Category 2 Psychological variables	Category 3 Demographic variables	Category 4 Academic and other variables
				variety, job conflicts with school, and role conflict)	work satisfaction		insecurity and actual layoff of both parents.
Butler et al., 2010	102	78%	questionnaire	Career orientation measures; Earnings; Hours worked; Work school conflict; Workload.	Number of drinks Tension reduction alcohol expectancy	Gender, age, ethical background	major subjects
Vaughn et al., 2016	104	85%	questionnaire	length of employment hours worked per week	(social) relationship quality (perceived supervisor and co-worker support) mental health (somatic stress symptoms, depression, anxiety, satisfaction of life) job satisfaction turnover intentions burnout	age, sex, ethnicity	class standing
Bouchard & Nauta, 2017	107	85%	questionnaire	short-term career outcome (presence of a discrepancy between a student's real versus ideal career aspirations, and their leadership aspirations)	work volition	--	their educational persistence intentions (belongs to short-term career outcome) health

Short Title (Author and Year)	Article No.	CCAT Score	Research method	Category 1 Work variables	Category 2 Psychological variables	Category 3 Demographic variables	Category 4 Academic and other variables
Tessema et al., 2014	157	78%	questionnaire	Working hours (0 hours (unemployed), 1- 10 hours, 11-15 hours, 16-20, 21-30, and 31 hours or more)	Student satisfaction	--	Academic achievement (GPA)
Pascarella et al., 1998	161	88%	questionnaire	Hours work on campus Hours work off campus	Direct effect of work on cognitive development (of end-of-first-year, end-of- second-year, end-of- third- year composite)	age, gender, ethnicity,	precollege cognitive ability, socioeconomic status
Bono et al., 2017	164	90%	questionnaire	Employment (Whether work, total work hours per week, total weekly earnings),	usage of Alcohol(frequency; quantity) usage of Tobacco(frequency)	sex, weight, height, and race/ethnicity (controlled/not controlled)	prior substance use, personality, social environment, and parental influences (controlled/not controlled)
Swanson et al., 2006	171	90%	questionnaire	service sector hours worked per week	Traits: Dispositional affect (Positive and negative affectivity, PA, NA) Role congruence Psychological state: Perceived stress Adaptation (adjustment) to university Satisfaction to university	age, sex,	students' year of study (1 to 4), country of origin, marital status and residential status (living at home with parents, in own home, student residences, rented flat or other)
Ho & Huang, 2013	173	80%	questionnaire	Work experience (on/off campus admin; on/off campus labor; off campus tutoring; community service; on campus teach assistant)	Term-Time Work Related Benefits and Detriment Perceived by Students2. Expand Relationships with People in Workplace 3. Gain Practical Knowledge and Skills 4. Beneficial to Future Employment 7.	Gender	1. Good Pay 5. Negative Impacts on Academic Outcomes 6. Negative Impacts on Extracurricular Activities major subject, family

Short Title (Author and Year)	Article No.	CCAT Score	Research method	Category 1 Work variables	Category 2 Psychological variables	Category 3 Demographic variables	Category 4 Academic and other variables
				Hours worked per week Monthly income	Negative Impacts on Health 8. Negative Impacts on Occupational Safety		economic status (disadvantage family, moderate prosperity, rich family)
Manthei & Gilmore, 2005	186	85%	questionnaire	Paid employment profile (whether they had a job or several, whether such work was related to their studies, hours worked per day in each job, average earnings per week and how such money was spent each week.)	sport, recreational and cultural activities balance between work and study effect of such work on their study time and activities	gender, age, marital status	Academic workload: credit point load, class contact hours per week, time spent studying and the grades they were expecting to receive) whether they had a student loan and its size Expenditure
Bednarska & Olszewski, 2016	197	78%	questionnaire	Work experience (hospitality related only; Hospitality unrelated; related/ unrelated; no experience)	Job Expectations Job Perceptions	Gender, age (≤ 20 , 21-22, 23-24, ≥ 25),	study degree (master/bachelor), study mode(full time/ part time), year of study
Teng, 2008	216	90%	questionnaire	--	Attitudes (driver) Personality traits (Big Five) (driver) employment aspirations	Gender	Institution (university, vocational or technological college) Location (northern, central, southern part of Taiwan) Major (hospitality management, beverage management, hotel management)
Hall et al., 2015	224	80%	questionnaire	part-time employment	empathy	gender, pharmacy year (level 1 to 4)	health status

Short Title (Author and Year)	Article No.	CCAT Score	Research method	Category 1 Work variables	Category 2 Psychological variables	Category 3 Demographic variables	Category 4 Academic and other variables
				(with/without job; types of part time job)			
Gbadamosi, 2015	228	80%	questionnaire	beneficial work career aspiration work experience (control variables)	self-efficacy in HE Fixed self-theories malleable self-theories	Gender, age (control variables)	level of study (control variable)
Beauchamp et al., 2016	257	80%	questionnaire	employment status (employment/ no employment) (weekly hours employed)	Attachment Type(secure, dismissing, preoccupied) Amotivation (covariates/controlled)	gender	First semester average (FSA) high school average (HAS) perceived financial burden (covariates/controlled)
McGregor, 2015	331	75%	questionnaire and interview	Work or not Weekly work hours Work pattern across a week Employability	Confidence Health (physical and mental health) Social activities	--	Attendance, marks, extracurricular activities Positive and negative impact of work Interview: academic support.
Hsiao, 2015	348	75%	questionnaire	Work status (no-job, part-time job, full- time job)	attitude, the Theory of Planned Behaviour (subjective norm (SN), perceived behavioural control (PBC), and behavioural intention (BI)) and perceived behavioural control; cheating intention	Gender, age	
Carney et al., 2005	354	75%	questionnaire	Employment information (hours worked per week, with or without	Reasons for working.	Gender, age (18–24, 25– 34, 35–44, 45– 54 and 55–64), ethnic background, disable or not,	Financial information Perceived on academic performance.

Short Title (Author and Year)	Article No.	CCAT Score	Research method	Category 1 Work variables	Category 2 Psychological variables	Category 3 Demographic variables	Category 4 Academic and other variables
				a job/ more than one job; per hour pay)	Health and well-being	faculty (science, art), live at home or away home	
Butler, 2007	391	90%	questionnaire	Hours worked (controlled/not) Job demands Job control Job-school congruence	Work school facilitation (WSF) Work school conflict (WSC)	age, gender, (controlled)	School performance (controlled/not ACT score /GPA) School satisfaction
Hammes & Haller, 1983	435	83%	Mixed method (interview+questionnaire)	activities at job	perceptions of life difference between work and not work terms frequency of activities engaged in during an hour class break) activities desired if having more time (alone Leisure time; socializing time; extracurricular activities) reason of work	--	--
Gbadamosi et al., 2016	461	75%	questionnaire	Work experience (full time/part time; sector; worked year)	Beneficial work career aspiration Self-efficacy reason of not work	Gender, age (<20, 21-25, 26-30, 31-40, 41-50, >50)	Study status (postgraduate/ undergraduate)
Sekiguchi, 2012	534	75%	questionnaire	experience of part- time work (number of months, hours worked in part-time job per week)	Skill variety job crafting (task crafting, relational crafting, cognitive crafting); Proactive career behaviour (skills development,	gender, age, (control variables)	difference in university school marks rate of attendance at lectures (control variable)

Short Title (Author and Year)	Article No.	CCAT Score	Research method	Category 1 Work variables	Category 2 Psychological variables	Category 3 Demographic variables	Category 4 Academic and other variables
				(also used as an independent variable in interaction analysis) type of part-time job (as control variable) employment commitment	network formation, consultation regarding future career, and career planning) Focus of career exploration Self-efficacy Job search self-efficacy job autonomy		
Jackson & Wilton, 2017	554	75%	questionnaire	WIL interventions (internships, placements) Employment status (permanent /temporary)	Perceived employability (PE) career management competency (decision-making, opportunity awareness, transition learning, self-awareness)	Gender, age, Year of study Country (Australia, UK)	--
Greene & Maggs, 2015	622	83%	Diary record	Employment time	Organized activity time	Age, gender, race/ethnicity	Semester (1-7 controlled) Academic time Parental education
Winkler, 2008	713	76%	interview	Work task Work sector Duration of employment Company	Perceptions of the work task Perceptions of flexibility Perceptions of instruction and training Perceptions of relations with other employees and social integration	Age	Course of study Number of terms studied
Lee et al., 1999	732	75%	questionnaire	Frequency of involved in work nature of the work;	Why students work The effects of work on personal and social life	Gender, age, marital status	The effects of work on course performance Accommodation (own home, with parents,

Short Title (Author and Year)	Article No.	CCAT Score	Research method	Category 1 Work variables	Category 2 Psychological variables	Category 3 Demographic variables	Category 4 Academic and other variables
Earl & Bright, 2003	790	80%	questionnaire	--	career decision-making variables on the Career Decision Profile Career Decision Scale	Gender	rented, students residence) Suggested adaptations to the course level (first and third years).
Park & Sprung, 2015	805	75%	Weekly diary	Average weekly work hours Credit hours sector	Recovery self-efficacy Weekly work–school conflict Weekly sleep quality Weekly fatigue	Gender, age, status (freshman, sophomore, junior, senior), major (science, art, education, business, others)	--
Koeske & Koeske, 1989	843	78%	questionnaire	Work status	Social support Symptoms (SCL-90)	Sex, race, Parent Status, Number of Children, and Household Income (using six categories from 1 = below \$10,000 to 6 = over \$49,000) (control variables)	Number of classroom and filed credits, number of credits of each type per term, Major, percentage of tuition paid by various source (self, employer, loan)
Creed et al., 2015	862	78%	questionnaire	Average hours worked per week Job sector	Work-based benefits (enabling resources, rewards, involvement) Work based demands (Time-based demands, strain-based demand, behaviour-based demands) Work-university facilitation Work-university conflict	Gender, educational achievement	University engagement.

Short Title (Author and Year)	Article No.	CCAT Score	Research method	Category 1 Work variables	Category 2 Psychological variables	Category 3 Demographic variables	Category 4 Academic and other variables
					Student well-being (context-specific, university wellbeing)		
Dakas, 2011	867	78%	questionnaire	Hours worked per week on/off campus job	Work school conflict work school enhancing job satisfaction	gender, age, ethnic background (control variables)	Enrolled credits year in college, marital status and whether or not they are a first- generation student getting a degree (control variables)

Appendix 10: Survey 1 (Study 2)

Online Survey of Study 2

CONFIDENTIAL

This questionnaire is to collect data regarding part-time jobs undergraduates have during Higher Education for the purpose of PhD research. The information collected will be treated strictly confidentially and will only be accessed by researcher herself. It will not be passed to any other persons.

ABOUT YOU

1. Please indicate your gender.....
2. Please indicate your age (in years).....
3. Accommodation status (choose one)
Living in own home (bought)
Living in own home (rented)
Living in student accommodation (University/halls)
Living in student accommodation (Private)
Living in parent's home
Other (please specify)
4. Who do you live with? (choose as many as appropriate)
With parent(s).....
With partner.....
With dependent(s)
With other student(s)
Other (please specify)
5. Ages of Dependents (in years; if none, please write none).....

ABOUT YOUR COURSE

6. What course are you studying? (e.g. BSc Psychology)
7. What is your year of study? (e.g. 2nd year)
8. What is your mode of study? (choose one)
Full-time
Part-time
9. Please indicate your student status (choose one)
Home student (Scotland).....
EU student.....
Student from other part of UK (England, Wales and Northern Ireland)
- Non-EU/International Student.....
10. Which part of your cost in Higher Education is supported by government funding (e.g. SAAS, SLC)? (Please tick the one category which best applies to you).
Both tuition fee and living costs are covered.....
Only tuition fee is covered.....

Only living cost is covered.....

Neither tuition fee nor living costs are covered.....

Unsure.....

11. Please indicate any other sources of funding you have (choose as many as appropriate)
- a. Personal savings
 - b. Subsistence support from family (parents, spouse, etc.)
 - c. Commercial loans (e.g. from banks, credit cards)
 - d. Loans from individuals (family, etc.)
 - e. Employment
 - f. Discretionary funds
 - g. Sponsorship (e.g. company, HM Forces)
 - h. Charitable Foundations
 - i. None
 - j. Other (please specify)

ABOUT PAID WORK

12. Do you have a paid job or jobs at present? Yes..... (Go to 13a) No..... (Go to 13b)

13. a. If **YES**, please give the following details: (If you have more than one job, give details for your main [or primary] job)

Job title.....

Total hours worked weekly (average)

Rate of pay per hour

13. b. If **NO**, do you intend to seek a job during this term?

Yes.....

No.....

Unsure.....

14. Did you have a paid job or jobs in Term 1?

Yes..... (Go to 15) No..... (Go to 16)

15. If **YES**, please give the following details: (If you have more than one job, give details for your main [or primary] job)

Job title

Total hours worked weekly (average)

Rate of pay per hour

Is this the same job as in Q13 a? Yes..... No.....

16. Did you have a paid job or jobs during the **summer 2018**?

Yes..... (Answer the question below) No..... (Go to 17)

If **YES**, please give the following details: (If you have more than one job, give details for your main [or primary] job)

Job title

Total hours worked weekly (average)

Rate of pay per hour

17. Did you have a paid job or jobs during term time of **academic year 2017/2018**?

Yes..... (Answer the question 'If YES')

No..... (Go to 18)

Was not a student during 17-18 (Go to 18)

If **YES**, please give the following details: (If you have more than one job, give details for your main [or primary] job)

Job title

Total hours worked weekly (average)

Rate of pay per hour

18. Please rank in order of importance (where 1 = the most important reason) the **THREE** most important reasons why you choose to work. You do not need to fill in an answer for each item, only the most 3 most important ones.

a. Need to provide money for basic subsistence (rent, food, etc.) for yourself
.....

b. Need to provide money for basic subsistence for dependants
.....

c. Need for extra items above basic subsistence (books, holidays, etc.)
.....

d. Providing money for tuition fees
.....

e. Personal development
.....

f. Development of career skills
.....

g. Other, please specify

.....

19. Do you believe that working during *term time* has **harmed** any of the following?

	Severely	Moderately	Somewhat	Not at all
your coursework performance				
your examination performance				
your participation in extra-curricular activities				
your private study				

20. Do you believe that working during *term time* has **helped** any of the following?

	Severely	Moderately	Somewhat	Not at all
your academic knowledge/ skills				
your academic motivation				
your career development				
your employment prospects				

21. Have you ever had to miss classes because of your work schedule? (choose one)

Very frequently (20%+ of classes)	Frequently (11%-20%)	Sometimes (1%-10%)	Never (0%)
.....

22. We are interested in finding out your typical weekly working pattern (start and finish times). Please see the example in the blue box below.

	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday	Saturday	Sunday
Morning (0500-1200)	0600-0800			0600-0800			
Afternoon (1200-1800)		1600-1900					
Evening (1800-2300)			1800-2300				
Night (2300-						1200-0800	

0500)							
--------------	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

Now thinking about your job, what is your typical weekly working pattern?
Please indicate this in the table below, using 24-hour clock.

	Mond ay	Tuesd ay	Wednesd ay	Thursd ay	Frida y	Saturd ay	Sund ay
Morning (0500- 1200)							
Afterno on (1200- 1800)							
Evening (1800- 2300)							
Night (2300- 0500)							

23. Have you ever had to switch classes (e.g. change seminar group) because of your job (or jobs)?
Yes No

STUDENT STRESS

Directions: This inventory measures the stresses you have experienced in your study and everyday life in your campus. There are no right and wrong answers. Read each statement and select the answer that best describes your experiences.

Below is a list of the ways you may have felt or behaved over this semester. Please select the option that best describe how you feel:

No.	Item	Never	Somewhat frequent	Frequent	Always
1	Headaches	1	2	3	4
2	Back pain	1	2	3	4
3	Sleep problem	1	2	3	4

4	Difficulty breathing	1	2	3	4
5	Excessive worry	1	2	3	4
6	Stomach pain/nausea	1	2	3	4
7	Constant tiredness/fatigue	1	2	3	4
8	Sweating/sweaty hands	1	2	3	4
9	Frequent cold/flu/fever	1	2	3	4
10	Drastic weight loss	1	2	3	4
11	I find difficult to meet my parent's high Expectations	1	2	3	4
12	My parents treat me as a helpless person	1	2	3	4
13	I feel guilty if I fail to fulfil my parent's hopes	1	2	3	4
14	My parents wish only for my success	1	2	3	4
15	I find it difficult to get along with groupmates in doing academic tasks	1	2	3	4
16	My friends do not care about me	1	2	3	4
17	I feel disturbed when having problems with my partner	1	2	3	4
18	My family is not supportive	1	2	3	4
19	My lecturers teachers are not supportive	1	2	3	4
20	I feel frustrated by the lack of faculty management	1	2	3	4
21	I have a financial problem because of the expenses of university	1	2	3	4
22	I find it difficult to juggle time between study and social activity	1	2	3	4
23	I feel nervous delivering a class presentation	1	2	3	4
24	I feel stressed as submission deadlines near	1	2	3	4
25	I feel stressed when sitting examinations	1	2	3	4
26	I find it difficult to juggle time between study and society involvement	1	2	3	4
27	I have lost interest towards my course	1	2	3	4
28	I feel burden of my academic workload	1	2	3	4
29	I feel stressed when dealing with difficult subjects	1	2	3	4
30	I have difficulties handling my academic problems	1	2	3	4
31	I have transportation problems	1	2	3	4

32	I feel stressed with bad living conditions	1	2	3	4
33	Surrounding noise distracts me	1	2	3	4
34	Pollution makes me uneasy	1	2	3	4
35	Hot weather makes me avoid going out	1	2	3	4
36	Messy living conditions distract me	1	2	3	4
37	I feel frustrated with inadequate campus facilities	1	2	3	4
38	Crowding makes me feel uneasy	1	2	3	4
39	Waiting in long lines makes me feel uneasy	1	2	3	4
40	I feel scared at insecure places	1	2	3	4

Student Self-Efficacy

In the context of education, self-efficacy refers to a student's confidence in his or her ability to achieve specific academic tasks. The Student Self-Efficacy Inventory is designed to measure a student's proficiency in the components of self-efficacy. Please select the appropriate response for each item below.

No.	Items	not at all true	hardly true	Moderately true	exactly true
1	I am convinced that I am able to successfully learn all relevant subject content even if it is difficult.				
2	I know that I can maintain a positive attitude toward this course even when tensions arise.				
3	When I try really hard, I am able to learn even the most difficult content.				
4	I am convinced that, as time goes by, I will continue to become more and more capable of learning the content of this course.				
5	Even if I get distracted in class, I am confident that I can continue to learn well.				
6	I am confident in my ability to learn, even if I am having a bad day.				
7	If I try hard enough, I can obtain the academic goals I desire.				
8	I am convinced that I can develop creative ways to cope with the stress that may occur while taking this course.				
9	I know that I can stay motivated to participate in the course.				
10	I know that I can finish the assigned projects and earn the grade I want, even when others think I can't.				

Coping Strategies

The purpose of this questionnaire is to find out how students deal with difficult academic situations that trouble them.

Take a few moments and think about an academic event or situation that has been particularly stressful for you during this last academic year. By stressful we mean a situation that was troubling you, either because it made you feel bad or because it took

effort to deal with it.

Take a few minutes to think about your chosen academic event or situation. As you read through the following items please answer them based on how you handled your academic event.

Please read each item below and determine the extent to which you used it in handling your chosen event. Please select the option that best describes how you feel.

No	Items	Not at all	A little	Somewh at	Much	Very much
1	I worked on solving the problems in the situation.					
2	I looked for the silver lining, so to speak; I tried to look on the bright side of things.					
3	I let out my feelings to reduce the stress.					
4	I found somebody who was a good listener.					
5	I went along as if nothing were happening.					
6	I hoped a miracle would happen.					
7	I realized that I was personally responsible for my difficulties and really lectured myself					
8	I spent more time alone.					
9	I made a plan of action and followed it.					
10	I looked at things in a different light and tried to make the best of what was available.					
11	I let my feelings out somehow.					
12	I talked to someone about how I was feeling.					
13	I tried to forget the whole thing.					
14	I wished that the situation would go away or somehow be over with.					
15	I blamed myself.					
16	I avoided my family and friends.					
17	I tackled the problem head on.					

18	I asked myself what was really important, and discovered that things weren't so bad after all.					
19	I let my emotions out.					
20	I talked to someone that I was very close to.					
21	I didn't let it get to me; I refused to think about it too much.					
22	I wished that the situation had never started.					
23	I criticized myself for what happened.					
24	I avoided being with people.					
25	I knew what had to be done, so I doubled my efforts and tried harder to make things work.					
26	I convinced myself that things aren't quite as bad as they seem.					
27	I got in touch with my feelings and just let them go.					
28	I asked a friend or relative I respect for advice.					
29	I avoided thinking or doing anything about the situation.					
30	I hoped that if I waited long enough, things would turn out OK.					
31	Since what happened was my fault I really chewed myself out.					
32	I spent some time by myself.					

FINAL QUESTIONS/NEXT STEPS

1. Would you be willing to take part in an interview as a second stage of this research?

Yes No

2. If YES, please provide your email address or other contact details:

.....

THANK YOU FOR YOUR COOPERATION

Appendix 11: Ethic Approval (Study 2)

07/03/2019

Dear Dan Xing,

Your application 7985: An investigation of HE student part-time employment and the relationship with psychological outcomes., submission reference 6442, has been approved, with conditions, by the Media Culture and Society SEC. **You may proceed with your study provided you meet the conditions outlined below, these are not optional and must be completed.**

Title	Comment
Where will the proposed research take place?	Ethics Committee needs to approve the online survey will need to be seen and approved by the Committee. The link has to be shared with the Committee at MCS.Ethics@uws.ac.uk and you must receive approval to use it before collecting data with it.
Please upload a copy of the Questionnaire or Interview Schedule	The supervisor can approve all of the following points A minor point but check use of 'trimester'. I believe UWS has now changed to 'terms' instead of 'trimesters'.
Please provide details of how you will obtain this consent and the information you will provide to potential participants to allow them to make an informed choice about whether or not to participate in your research.	Could the researcher please update the information sheet on how the participant can withdraw at any time (i.e. simply closing the browser for online / inform the researcher if doing it on paper).
Please upload a copy of the Participant Information Sheet(s)	You say participants can withdraw at any time: what if they ask for their data to be withdrawn the day before you submit your thesis? Make it clear they can withdraw whilst they are completing the study, but give an end date too.
Please upload a copy of your Consent Form(s)	This consent form is fine for paper collection, but could the researcher please also add an opportunity for the participants to give a code word for online - for anonymity purposes.
What measures will you put in place to ensure the confidentiality of personal data gathered during your study?	See above comment about a code word - the researcher needs to ensure that the participants who have completed this online have a chance to withdraw following data collection.

If you wish to make any significant changes to your study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr Christopher O'Donnell

Participant Information Sheet

An investigation of HE student part-time employment and the relationship with psychological outcomes.

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

What is the purpose of this study?

The purpose of this study is to investigate the potential psychological impact of part-time employment on undergraduate students.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen to take part in this study because you are an undergraduate student at UWS.

Do I have to take part?

No, it is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form. If you decide to take part you are still free to withdraw until your submission of the questionnaire by not completing the hard copy and returning the questionnaire to the researcher or by simply closing the browser online. After submission, individual participants cannot be identified, and it is therefore not possible to withdraw from the study following submission.

What will happen to me if I take part?

You will be asked to complete an online survey where you will be asked about your employment status, your levels of stress, typical ways of coping with your thoughts about your ability to meet challenges. The survey will take about 20minutes to complete.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

There are no obvious risks or disadvantages associated with taking part however, there is the possibility that some of the questions of the survey might highlight some issues about how well you think and feel about yourself at University. If this is the case, you will be supplied with contact details for student support where you can talk to someone about any issues that you might have.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

There are no direct advantages to taking part however, you will be providing information that may help to improve an understanding of how undergraduate student experience part-time work.

Data Protection Privacy Notice

The data controller for this project will be University of the West of Scotland (UWS). The UWS Data Protection Office provides oversight of UWS activities involving the processing of personal data, and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. UWS's Data Protection Officer is Andy Connor and he can also be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk.

Your personal data will be processed for the purposes outlined in this notice. The legal basis that would be used to process your personal data will be the provision of your consent. You can provide your consent for the use of your personal data in this project by completing the consent form that has been provided to you.

Your personal data will be processed so long as it is required for the research project. If we are able to anonymise or pseudonymise the personal data you provide we will undertake this, and will endeavour to minimise the processing of personal data wherever possible. Or we will anonymise or pseudonymise the personal data you provide by 1 week after the study and all data will be anonymised when analysed.

If you are concerned about how your personal data is being processed, please contact UWS in the first instance at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. If you remain unsatisfied, you may wish to contact the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). Contact details, and details of data subject rights, are available on the ICO website at: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights/>

What will happen to the results of the research study?

The data from the study will be published as part of a PhD thesis and may contribute to academic conference presentations and/or journal publications.

Who has reviewed the study?

MCS Research Ethics Committee

Contact for further information

If you require any further information please contact:

Researcher:

Name Dan Xing

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street,

Paisley,

PA1 2BE

UK

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

In addition you can contact Director of Studies:

Professor Jim McKechnie,

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street,

Paisley,

Renfrewshire, Scotland.

PA1 2BE,
School of Media, Culture and Society,
Division of Psychology,

E-mail: [REDACTED]
[REDACTED]

Thank you for taking part in this study.

School of Media Culture and Society

RESEARCH INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Title of Project:

Ethics Approval Number:

An investigation of HE student part-time employment and the relationship with psychological outcomes.

Investigator(s):

Dan Xing

Researcher Email:

Please read the following statements and, if you agree to participate this study, please tick the corresponding box at the end to confirm following all agreement:

I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw up the point where I submit my questionnaire either online or by hard copy.

I consent to the processing of my personal information for the purposes explained to me. I understand that such information will be handled in accordance with all applicable data protection legislation.

I understand that my data will be treated confidentially and any publication or presentation resulting from this work will report only data that does not identify me.

I freely agree to participate in this study.

Yes, I agree to participate.

No, I don't agree to participate.

Name of researcher (block capitals) DAN XING

Date

Signature: Dan Xing

Debriefing Form

An investigation of HE student part-time employment and the relationship with psychological outcomes

Thank you for taking part in this research. This study, is part of my PhD studies that I am undertaking at the University of the West of Scotland. The aim of the research is to investigate the potential psychological impact of part-time employment during term time on undergraduate students. More specifically, I am interested in whether the amount and type of part-time employment is associated with students' experience of stress, their ways of coping with stress and their beliefs about themselves in terms of their abilities to meet challenges and succeed in completing tasks.

Previous research on student employment has mainly focused on the nature and extent of part-time employment (Broadbridge & Swanson, 2006), reasons for participating in part-time employment (Gbadamosi, Evans, & Obalola, 2016) and the associated impact on academic achievement (Nonis & Hudson, 2006). However, the current study is concerned more with the psychological impact of part-time employment on students and predicts that students that work longer hours will experience more stress and have less confidence in their abilities to succeed at university compared with student that do not work or work fewer hours.

The goal of the current project, the first in a range of studies linked to this PhD, is to (i) consider potential changes in part-time work over time and (ii) explore the potential links between student employment and psychological outcomes; these are explained in more detail below:

(i) Change in part-time work over time:

This will involve replicating a 1998 study of student employment that was carried out at Paisley University (McKechnie, Hobbs and Lindsay, 1998). The original study was survey based and focused on collecting data on the nature and extent of student employment. The current replication has access to the original survey tool and data sets. This will allow for the establishment of current levels of employment amongst HE students and for some consideration of change between these two time periods. The latter type of comparison has never been reported in the literature.

(ii) Links to psychological outcomes: A systematic review of the literature has identified a number of psychological variables that may be associated with student employment. These may mediate any potential impact of employment and this study seeks to explore the relationship between employment (type of job, hours worked, patterns of employment etc.) and self efficacy, coping strategies and perceived stress. The latter will be assessed via standardised assessment tools (e.g. Student Self-efficacy Scale, Coping Strategy Inventory short form, Student Stress Inventory).

If you would like more information about this study once it is completed, please contact the researcher, Dan Xing [REDACTED], or my supervisor, Dr Jim McKechnie [REDACTED]

If you are interested in this area of research, you may wish to read the following references:

Broadbridge, A., & Swanson, V. (2006). Managing two roles: A theoretical study of students' employment whilst at university. *Community, Work and Family*, 9(2), 159-179.

Curtis, S., & Williams, J. (2002). The reluctant workforce: undergraduates' part-time employment. *Education+ training*, 44(1), 5-10.

Creed, P. A., French, J., & Hood, M. (2015). Working while studying at university: The relationship between work benefits and demands and engagement and well-being. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 86, 48-57.

McKechnie, J., Hobbs, S. & Lindsay, S. (1998). The nature and extent of student employment at the University of Paisley in P. Kelly (ed.) *Working in Two Worlds: Students and part-time employment*. Glasgow: Scottish Low Pay Unit.

Robotham, D. (2013). Students' perspectives on term-time employment: an exploratory qualitative study. *Journal of Further and Higher Education*, 37(3), 431-442.

If you have any complaints or feel that you have been affected by the study in any way, please contact:

Online resources list for students

STUDENT-SPECIFIC:

1. SilverCloud

<https://uws.silvercloudhealth.com/signup/>

An interactive resource which any UWS student can access. It is free and confidential, and will enable you to learn a range of self-help strategies. There are several programmes, including:

- Space from stress
- Space from anxiety
- Space from depression
- Space for positive body image

Each programme consists of 6-7 modules, and each module takes around 40 minutes to complete.

2. Think Positive

<https://www.thinkpositive.scot/resources/mental-health-quick-info/>

NUS Scotland's campaign website.

This link takes you to 7 topic links, and for each one you then get a thumbnail sketch of signs & symptoms, plus links to relevant websites and apps.

3. Students Against Depression

<https://www.studentsagainstdespression.org/>Very easy-to-navigate website with lots of advice about depression, anxiety, and sleep.

You can also contact hub to make a wellbeing appointment to access UWS counselling services: Hub@uws.ac.uk

If you want to complain about this study, you can contact my Direct of Study and Chair of the MCS Ethics Committee staff. The contact details are as follow:

Professor Jim McKechnie (Head of Psychology)

Telephone: [REDACTED]
[REDACTED].

Dr Christopher O'Donnell (Chair of the MCS Ethics Committee)

Telephone: [REDACTED]
[REDACTED]

Appendix 15: SPSS Outputs of Results of Survey 1 (Study 2)

Table A15.1 Correlation among Work Variables (N=429), Stress (N=445), Self-efficacy (N=426) and Coping Strategy I (N=395)

	Current Weekly Working Hours	Total Score of SSE	Problem Focused Engagement (CSI secondary subscale 1)	Emotion Focused Engagement (CSI secondary subscale 2)	Problem Focused Disengagement (CSI secondary subscale 3)	Emotion focused disengagement (CSI secondary subscale 4)	Engagement (CSI Tertiary subscale 1)	Disengagement (CSI Tertiary subscale 2)
Total Score of SSI	.106*	-.382**	-.231**	-.122*	.320**	.468**	-.197**	.454**
Physical Stress Subscale Score	.115*	-.220**	-.179**	-.093	.234**	.383**	-.151**	.357**
Academic Stress Subscale Score	.113*	-.409**	-.278**	-.144**	.283**	.374**	-.235**	.378**

Notes: **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table A15.2 Correlation among Work Variables (N=429), Stress (N=445), Self-efficacy (N=426) and Coping Strategy (N=395) I (Continued)

	Problem Solving (CSI primary subscale 1)	Cognitive Restructuring (CSI primary subscale 2)	Express Emotions (CSI primary subscale 3)	Social Contact (CSI primary subscale 4)	Problem Avoidance (CSI primary subscale 5)	Wishful Thinking (CSI primary subscale 6)	Self-Criticism (CSI primary subscale 7)	Social Withdrawal (CSI primary subscale 8)
Total Score of SSI	-.175**	-.245**	-.114*	-.112*	.154**	.392**	.338**	.477**
Physical Stress Subscale Score	-.120*	-.204**	-.101*	-.071	.101*	.297**	.250**	.418**

Academic Stress Subscale Score	-.232**	-.276**	-.113*	-.152**	.106*	.373**	.282**	.368**
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Notes: **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table A15.3 Correlation among Work Variables, Stress, Self-efficacy and Coping Strategy II

	Physical Stress Subscale Score	Interpersonal Relationship Subscale Score	Academic Stress Subscale Score	Environment Stress Subscale Score	Total Score of SSI	Total Score of SSE
Total Score of SSE	-.220**	-.325**	-.409**	-.253**	-.382**	1
Current Weekly Working Hours	.115*	.021	.113*	.070	.106*	.036

Notes: **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table A15.4 Correlation among Work Variables, Stress, Self-efficacy and Coping Strategy II (Continued)

	Problem Focused Engagement (CSI secondary subscale 1)	Emotion Focused Engagement (CSI secondary subscale 2)	Problem Focused Disengagement (CSI secondary subscale 3)	Emotion focused disengagement (CSI secondary subscale 4)	Engagement (CSI Tertiary subscale 1)	Disengagement (CSI Tertiary subscale 2)
Total Score of SSE	.589**	.271**	-.277**	-.257**	.475**	-.305**
Current Weekly Working Hours	-.027	-.134**	-.023	.033	-.104*	.007

Notes: **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table A15.5 Correlation among Work Variables, Stress, Self-efficacy and Coping Strategy II (Continued)

	Problem Solving (CSI primary subscale 1)	Cognitive Restructuring (CSI primary subscale 2)	Express Emotions (CSI primary subscale 3)	Social Contact (CSI primary subscale 4)	Problem Avoidance (CSI primary subscale 5)	Wishful Thinking (CSI primary subscale 6)	Self-Criticism (CSI primary subscale 7)	Social Withdrawal (CSI primary subscale 8)
Total Score of SSE	.540**	.538**	.262**	.239**	-.159**	-.319**	-.196**	-.252**
Current Weekly Working Hours	-.023	-.026	-.102*	-.144**	.036	-.067	-.020	.079

Notes: **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table A15.6 Significant Regression Models for Total Stress

Model number	Model	R, R ² , adjusted R ²	F value
One-1	Total score of Stress = 80.13 + 1.126 Social Withdrawal + 1.031 Wishful Thinking - .924 SSE - .862 Problem Avoidance + .699 Problem Solving + .255 Current Job Weekly Working Hours.	R = .607; R ² = .369; adjusted R ² = .352	F _(10,381) = 21.66, p < .001
One-2	Total score of Stress = 84.48 - .931 SSE + .774 Emotion-focused Disengagement + .234 Current Job Weekly Working Hours.	R = .559; R ² = .313; adjusted R ² = .302	F _(6,381) = 28.46, p < .001
One-3	Total score of Stress = 82.25 - .917 SSE + .455 Disengagement + .259 Current Job Weekly Working Hours.	R = .540; R ² = .291; adjusted R ² = .284	F _(4,381) = 38.76, p < .001

Table A15.7 Coefficients^a of Model Two Variables

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	p
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	17.070	2.030		8.408	.000
Current Weekly Working Hours	.085	.031	.127	2.724	.007*
Total Score of SSE	-.099	.057	-.101	-1.741	.083
Problem Solving	.165	.108	.104	1.527	.127
(CSI primary subscale 1)					
Cognitive Restructuring	-.121	.103	-.082	-1.174	.241
(CSI primary subscale 2)					
Express Emotions	-.174	.137	-.150	-1.275	.203
(CSI primary subscale 3)					
Problem Avoidance	-.234	.088	-.160	-2.646	.008*
(CSI primary subscale 5)					
Wishful Thinking	.251	.080	.207	3.141	.002*
(CSI primary subscale 6)					
Social Withdrawal	.315	.112	.258	2.815	.005*
(CSI primary subscale 8)					
Emotion Focused Engagement	.049	.072	.081	.682	.496
(CSI secondary subscale 2)					
Emotion focused disengagement	.062	.065	.089	.942	.347
(CSI secondary subscale 4)					

Notes: a. Dependent Variable: Physical Stress Subscale Score

Table A15.8 Coefficients^a of Model Three Variables

Model	Unstandardized		Standardized		p
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
(Constant)	30.282	2.271		13.336	.000
Current Weekly Working Hours	.108	.035	.135	3.118	.002*
Total Score of SSE	-.400	.063	-.341	-6.305	.000*
Problem Solving	.196	.121	.103	1.627	.105
(CSI primary subscale 1)					
Cognitive Restructuring	-.053	.116	-.030	-.459	.646
(CSI primary subscale 2)					
Express Emotions	.159	.153	.114	1.041	.298
(CSI primary subscale 3)					
Problem Avoidance	-.393	.099	-.223	-3.981	.000*
(CSI primary subscale 5)					
Wishful Thinking	.460	.089	.314	5.136	.000*
(CSI primary subscale 6)					
Social Withdrawal	.129	.125	.088	1.032	.303
(CSI primary subscale 8)					
Emotion Focused Engagement	-.146	.081	-.198	-1.803	.072
(CSI secondary subscale 2)					
Emotion focused disengagement	.110	.073	.132	1.501	.134
(CSI secondary subscale 4)					

Notes: a. Dependent Variable: Academic Stress Subscale Score

Figure A15.1 Normal Probability Plot of Residuals of Model One (N=382)

Figure A15.2 Standardized Residual Plotted Against Standardized Fitted Values of Model One (N=382)

Figure A15.3 Normal Probability Plot of Residuals of Model Two (N=382)

Figure A15.4 Standardized Residual Plotted Against Standardized Fitted Values of Model Two (N=382)

Figure A15.5 Normal Probability Plot of Residuals of Model Three (N=382)

Figure A15.6 Standardized Residual Plotted Against Standardized Fitted Values of Model Three (N=382)

Appendix 16: Survey 2 (Study 3)

Online Survey of Study 3

Higher Education students' part-time work and Covid-19: an investigation of the relationship between employment and psychological outcomes

Page 1 PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

Page 2 RESEARCH INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Page 3 ABOUT YOU

1. Please indicate your gender: *

Male

Female

Other

2. Please indicate your age (in years)..... *

3. Accommodation status (choose one) *

Living in own home (bought)

Living in own home (rented)

Living in student accommodation (University/halls)

Living in student accommodation (Private)

Living in parent's home

Other (please specify)

4. Who do you live with? (choose as many as appropriate) *

With parent(s).....

With partner.....

With dependent(s)

With other student(s)

Other (please specify)

5. Ages of Dependents (in years; if none, please write none)

*

Page 4 ABOUT YOUR COURSE

6. What course are you studying? (e.g. BSc Psychology) *

7. What is your year of study? (choose one) *

Undergraduate 1st Year

Undergraduate 2nd Year

Undergraduate 3rd Year

Undergraduate 4th Year

Postgraduates (go to Page 20 debriefing form)

8. What is your mode of study? (choose one) *

Full-time

Part-time

9. Please indicate your student status (choose one) *

Home student (Scotland).....

EU student.....

Student from other part of UK (England, Wales and Northern Ireland)

Non-EU/International Student.....

10. Which part of your cost in Higher Education is supported by government funding (e.g. SAAS, SLC)? (Please tick the one category which best applies to you). *

Both tuition fee and living costs are covered.....

Only tuition fee is covered.....

Only living cost is covered.....

Neither tuition fee nor living costs are covered.....

Unsure.....

11. Please indicate any other sources of funding you have (choose as many as appropriate) *

a. Personal savings

b. Subsistence support from family (parents, spouse, etc.)

c. Commercial loans (e.g. from banks, credit cards)

d. Loans from individuals (family, etc.)

e. Employment

f. Discretionary funds

g. Sponsorship (e.g. company, HM Forces)

h. Charitable Foundations

i. None

j. Other (please specify)

The following three sections are going to ask you about the jobs that you may have had while studying at University. We are interested in three specific time periods covering the last year and these are: Jan to March 2020, April to Sept 2020 and Oct 2020 to the present time.

Page 5 ABOUT PAID WORK DURING JANUARY TO MARCH 2020

12. Did you have a paid job or jobs during January 2020 to the end of March 2020? *
Yes..... (Go to page 7) No..... (Go to page 6)

Page 6 FOR THE NON-WORKERS

13. If **NO**, did you apply for any jobs during January 2020 to the end of March 2020?
Yes.... (Go to Q14 below) No..... (Go to page 8)

14. How many jobs did you apply during January 2020 to the end of March 2020?.....

Page 7 (parallel with page 6) FOR THE WORKERS

13. If **YES**, please give the following details about your job during January 2020 to end of March 2020: (If you have more than one job, give details for your main [or primary] job)

Job title.....

Total hours worked weekly (average)

Rate of pay per hour

Employer/organisation.....

What are your main work duties?

14A. Were you employed in this job during the entire time period from 1st January 2020 to 31st March 2020?*

Yes (Go to page 8) No.....(Go to Q14B below)

14B. If **NO**, please specify the time that you worked in this job during this period from/.... (Date/Month) to/.... (Date/Month) (Go to Q14C)

14C. From the list below please indicate the main reason that you stopped working (choose **one** option. If there was more than one reason, please indicate the MAIN reason.)

I stopped working because:

I was made redundant (fired) by the employer due to Covid-19.

I was furloughed due to Covid-19.

I left the job because I did not like the Covid-19 adjustments that my employer made

I was worried about my own health due to Covid-19 and stopped working.

I was worried about the health of my family members due to Covid-19.

I found the job too stressful due to Covid-19 related risks

I needed to spend more time on my academic studies

I decided to look for another job.

Other reasons, please specify.....

Page 8 ABOUT PAID WORK DURING APRIL TO SEPTEMBER 2020

15. During the period April 2020 to the end of September 2020 which statement reflects your work status:

I did not have a job. (Go to page 9)

I worked during this period. (Go to page 10)

I had a job but stopped working during this time period. (Go to page 11)

Page 9 (parallel with page 10/11) FOR THE NON-WORKERS

16A. Did you apply for any jobs during April 2020 to the end of September 2020?

Yes..... (Go to Q16B below) No..... (Go to next page) <(go to page 12)>

16B. How many jobs did you apply during 1st April 2020 to 30th Sept 2020?.....

Page 10 (parallel with page 9/11) FOR THE WORKERS

16A. Please tell us about your job during 1st April 2020 to the end of September 2020, please give the following details: (If you had more than one job, please give details for your main [or primary] job)

Job title

Total hours worked weekly (average)

Rate of pay per hour

Employer/organisation.....

What are your main work duties?

16B. Were any aspects of this job changed as a result of Covid-19 during 1st April 2020 to 30th Sept 2020?

Yes..... (go to 16C below) No..... (go to page 12)

16C. If **YES**, what were the changes? (Choose as many as appropriate)

My weekly work hours increased.

My weekly work hours decreased.

My weekly days of working decreased.

My weekly days of working increased.

My work rota changed (e.g. prior to Covid you worked on Monday and Wednesday, after Covid you were asked to work Thursday).

I was told to work from home.

I was furloughed during the time period.

Other changes, please specify

Page 11 (parallel with page 9/10) FOR THE STOPPED WORKERS

16A. Please tell us about the job you had during the period 1st April 2020 to the end of September 2020, please give the following details: (If you had more than one job, please give details for your main [or primary] job)

Job title

Total hours worked weekly (average)

Rate of pay per hour

Employer/organisation.....

What are your main work duties?

16B. With respect to this job please tell us when you started and then left your job: started the job/.... (Date/Month) Left your job/.... (Date/Month) (Go to Q16C)

16C. From the list below please indicate the main reason that you stopped working (choose **one** option. If there was more than one reason, please indicate the MAIN reason.)

I stopped working because:

I was made redundant (fired) by the employer due to Covid-19.

I was furloughed due to Covid-19.

I left the job because I did not like the Covid-19 adjustments that my employer made.

I was worried about my own health due to Covid-19 and stopped working.

I was worried about the health of my family members due to Covid-19.

I found the job too stressful due to Covid-19 related risks

I needed to spend more time on my academic studies.

I decided to look for another job.

Other reasons, please specify.....

16D. During the time that you were working in this job were any aspects of your work changed as a result of Covid-19?

Yes..... (go to 16E below) No..... (go to page 12)

16E. If **YES**, what were the changes? (Choose as many as appropriate)

My weekly work hours increased.

My weekly work hours decreased.

My weekly days of working decreased.

My weekly days of working increased.

My work rota changed (e.g. before work on Monday and Wednesday, now work on Thursday).

I was told to work from home.

I was furloughed during the time

Other changes, please specify

Page 12 ABOUT PAID WORK IN THIS ACADEMIC YEAR

17. Since October 2020 to the present time, which of the following best describes the following your work status:

I have not had a job since October 2020 (Go to page 13)

I am currently working. (Go to page 14)

I had a job but stopped working during this time period. (Go to page 15)

Page 13 (parallel with page 14/15) FOR THE NON-WORKERS

18A. Have you applied for any jobs since Oct 2020?

Yes..... (Go to Q18B below) No..... (Go to next page) (go to page 16)

18B. How many jobs have you applied for since Oct 2020?.....

Page 14 (parallel with page 13/15) FOR THE CURRENT WORKERS

18A. Please tell me about your current job: (If you have more than one job, give details for your main [or primary] job)

Job title

Total hours worked weekly (average)

Rate of pay per hour

Employer/organisation.....

What are your main work duties?

18B. We are interested in finding out your typical weekly working pattern for your current job (start and finish times). Please see the example in the blue box below.

	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday	Saturday	Sunday
Morning (0500-1200)	0600-0800			0600-0800			
Afternoon (1200-1800)		1600-1900					
Evening (1800-2300)			1800-2300				
Night (2300-0500)						1200-0800	

Now thinking about your current job, what is your typical weekly working pattern? Please indicate this in the table below, using 24-hour clock.

	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday	Saturday	Sunday
Morning (0500-1200)							
Afternoon (1200-1800)							
Evening (1800-2300)							
Night (2300-0500)							

18C. Have you been employed in this job during the entire time period from 1st Oct 2020 to current date *

Yes (Go to Q18E) No..... (Go to Q18D below)

18D. If NO, please specify the work time period(Date/Month/Year) to.....
(Date/Month/Year)

(Based on Q18C and Q18D, we can identify new workers as what Amanda's exemplified.)

18E. During the time that you have been working in this job have any aspects of your work changed as a result of Covid-19?

Yes..... (go to Q18F below) No..... (go to page 16)

18F. If **YES**, what were the changes? (Choose as many as appropriate)

My weekly work hours increased.

My weekly work hours decreased.

My weekly days of working decreased.

My weekly days of working increased.

My work rota changed (e.g. before work on Monday and Wednesday, now work on Thursday).

I was told to work from home.

I was furloughed during the time period.

Other changes, please specify

Page 15 (parallel with page 13/14) FOR THE STOPPED WORKERS

18A. Please tell us about the job that you had: (If you had more than one job, give details for your main [or primary] job)

Job title

Total hours worked weekly (average)

Rate of pay per hour

Employer/organisation.....

What are your main work duties?

18B. With respect to this job please tell us when you started and then left your job: started the job / (Date/Month/Year) Left your job / (Date/Month/Year) (Go to Q18C)

18C. As you no longer have this job please indicate the main reason for stopping work: (choose **one** option. If there was more than one reason, please indicate the MAIN reason.)

I stopped working because:

I was made redundant (fired) by the employer due to Covid-19.

I was furloughed due to Covid-19.

I left the job because I did not like the Covid-19 adjustments that my employer made.

I was worried about my own health due to Covid-19 and stopped working.

I was worried about the health of my family members due to Covid-19.

I found the job too stressful due to Covid-19 related risks

I needed to spend more time on my academic studies

I decided to look for another job.

Other reasons, please specify.....

18D. During the time that you were working in this job were any aspects of your work changed as a result of Covid-19?

Yes..... (go to 18E below) No..... (go to page 16)

18E. If **YES**, what were the changes? (Choose as many as appropriate)

My weekly work hours increased.

My weekly work hours decreased.

My weekly days of working decreased.

My weekly days of working increased.

My work rota changed (e.g. before work on Monday and Wednesday, now work on Thursday).

I was told to work from home.

I was furloughed during the time

Other changes, please specify

In the following sections you will be asked about how you have felt, coped and managed during this academic. It is important to note that there are no right or wrong to these questions, it is simply a case of how you wish to respond.

Page 16 ABOUT YOUR PERCEIVED STRESS

Directions: The following questions measure the stresses you have experienced in your study and everyday life. There are no right and wrong answers. Read each statement and select the answer that best describes your experiences.

Below is a list of the ways you may have felt or behaved over this semester. Please select the option that best describe how you feel: *

No.	Item	Never	Somewhat frequent	Frequent	Always
1	Headaches	1	2	3	4
2	Back pain	1	2	3	4
3	Sleep problem	1	2	3	4
4	Difficulty breathing	1	2	3	4
5	Excessive worry	1	2	3	4
6	Stomach pain/nausea	1	2	3	4
7	Constant tiredness/fatigue	1	2	3	4
8	Sweating/sweaty hands	1	2	3	4
9	Frequent cold/flu/fever	1	2	3	4
10	Drastic weight loss	1	2	3	4
11	I find difficult to meet my parent's high Expectations	1	2	3	4
12	My parents treat me as a helpless person	1	2	3	4
13	I feel guilty if I fail to fulfil my parent's hopes	1	2	3	4
14	My parents wish only for my success	1	2	3	4
15	I find it difficult to get along with groupmates in doing academic tasks	1	2	3	4
16	My friends do not care about me	1	2	3	4
17	I feel disturbed when having problems with my partner	1	2	3	4
18	My family is not supportive	1	2	3	4
19	My lecturers / teachers are not supportive	1	2	3	4
20	I feel frustrated by the lack of Faculty / School management	1	2	3	4
21	I have a financial problem because of the expenses of university	1	2	3	4
22	I find it difficult to juggle time between study and social activity	1	2	3	4
23	I feel nervous delivering a class presentation	1	2	3	4
24	I feel stressed as submission deadlines near	1	2	3	4
25	I feel stressed when sitting examinations	1	2	3	4

26	I find it difficult to juggle time between study and society involvement	1	2	3	4
27	I have lost interest towards my course	1	2	3	4
28	I feel burden of my academic workload	1	2	3	4
29	I feel stressed when dealing with difficult subjects	1	2	3	4
30	I have difficulties handling my academic problems	1	2	3	4
31	I have transportation problems	1	2	3	4
32	I feel stressed with bad living conditions	1	2	3	4
33	Surrounding noise distracts me	1	2	3	4
34	Pollution makes me uneasy	1	2	3	4
35	Hot or wet weather makes me avoid going out	1	2	3	4
36	Messy living conditions distract me	1	2	3	4
37	I feel frustrated with inadequate campus facilities	1	2	3	4
38	Crowding makes me feel uneasy	1	2	3	4
39	Waiting in long lines makes me feel uneasy	1	2	3	4
40	I feel scared at insecure places	1	2	3	4

Page 17 ABOUT YOUR SELF-EFFICACY

The following questions are designed to measure how confident you are in your ability to achieve specific academic tasks. Please select the appropriate response for each item below. *

No.	Items	not at all true	hardly true	Moderately true	exactly true
1	I am convinced that I am able to successfully learn all relevant subject content even if it is difficult.				
2	I know that I can maintain a positive attitude toward this course even when tensions arise.				
3	When I try really hard, I am able to learn even the most difficult content.				
4	I am convinced that, as time goes by, I will continue to become more and more capable of learning the content of this course.				

5	Even if I get distracted in class, I am confident that I can continue to learn well.				
6	I am confident in my ability to learn, even if I am having a bad day.				
7	If I try hard enough, I can obtain the academic goals I desire.				
8	I am convinced that I can develop creative ways to cope with the stress that may occur while taking this course.				
9	I know that I can stay motivated to participate in the course.				
10	I know that I can finish the assigned projects and earn the grade I want, even when others think I can't.				

Page 18 ABOUT YOUR COPING STRATEGIES

The purpose of this questionnaire is to find out how students deal with difficult academic situations that trouble them.

Take a few moments and think about an academic event or situation that has been particularly stressful for you during this last academic year. By stressful we mean a situation that was troubling you, either because it made you feel bad or because it took effort to deal with it.

Take a few minutes to think about your chosen academic event or situation. As you read through the following items please answer them based on how you handled your academic event.

Please read each item below and determine the extent to which you used it in handling your chosen event. Please select the option that best describes how you feel. *

No	Items	Not at all	A little	Somewhat	Much	Very much
1	I worked on solving the problems in the situation.					
2	I looked for the silver lining, so to speak; I tried to look on the bright side of things.					

3	I let out my feelings to reduce the stress.					
4	I found somebody who was a good listener.					
5	I went along as if nothing were happening.					
6	I hoped a miracle would happen.					
7	I realized that I was personally responsible for my difficulties and really lectured myself					
8	I spent more time alone.					
9	I made a plan of action and followed it.					
10	I looked at things in a different light and tried to make the best of what was available.					
11	I let my feelings out somehow.					
12	I talked to someone about how I was feeling.					
13	I tried to forget the whole thing.					
14	I wished that the situation would go away or somehow be over with.					
15	I blamed myself.					
16	I avoided my family and friends.					
17	I tackled the problem head on.					
18	I asked myself what was really important, and discovered that things weren't so bad after all.					
19	I let my emotions out.					
20	I talked to someone that I was very close to.					
21	I didn't let it get to me; I refused to think about it too much.					

22	I wished that the situation had never started.					
23	I criticized myself for what happened.					
24	I avoided being with people.					
25	I knew what had to be done, so I doubled my efforts and tried harder to make things work.					
26	I convinced myself that things aren't quite as bad as they seem.					
27	I got in touch with my feelings and just let them go.					
28	I asked a friend or relative I respect for advice.					
29	I avoided thinking or doing anything about the situation.					
30	I hoped that if I waited long enough, things would turn out OK.					
31	Since what happened was my fault I really chewed myself out.					
32	I spent some time by myself.					

Page 19 FINAL QUESTIONS/NEXT STEPS

1. Would you be willing to take part in an interview as next stage of this research?

Yes No

2. If YES, please provide your email address or other contact details:

THANK YOU FOR YOUR COOPERATION. BY CLICKING 'NEXT', YOU WILL BE SUBMITTING YOUR COMPLETED SURVEY.

Page 20 DEBRIEFING FORM

25/01/2021

Dear Dan Xing,

Your application [REDACTED]: Higher Education students' part-time work and Covid-19: an investigation of the relationship between employment and psychological outcomes, submission [REDACTED], has been approved by the Education and Social Sciences SEC. You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

While informed consent has been considered and addressed, the lack of critical analysis of the rationale is a concern in any analysis of the data and should be discussed with the supervisors. Also, it is unlikely that a large enough sample will be recruited from UWS, and therefore this sampling strategy may require some change.

Good luck with your research.

Dr Iain McPhee

Page 1 of 1

School of Education and Social Science

Participant Information Sheet

Higher Education students' part-time work and Covid-19: an investigation of the relationship between employment and psychological outcomes

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

What is the purpose of this study?

The purpose of this study is to investigate the potential changes to students' work experience during the Covid-19 pandemic. The study will also consider how you have coped academically and felt about any changes you have experienced.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen to take part in this study because you are a full time undergraduate in UWS.

Do I have to take part?

No, it is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part you will be given this information sheet to view and be asked to indicate your consent to participate. If you decide to take part, you are still free to withdraw without giving a reason by simply closing the browser online prior to submitting your questionnaire. After submission, individual participants cannot be identified, and it is therefore not possible to withdraw from the study following submission.

What will happen to me if I take part?

You will be asked to spend 15 to 20 minutes of your time to fill in a questionnaire. The majority of the questions are about your work status prior to and during Covid-19. We're interested in any changes you may, or may not, have experienced during this time, how you feel about your current situation, your ability to deal with academic tasks and how you have coped during the last few months.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

There are no obvious risks or disadvantages associated with taking part however, there is the possibility that some of the questions of the survey might highlight some issues about how well you think and feel about yourself. If this is the case, you will be supplied with contact details for student support where you can talk to someone about any issues that you might have.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

There are no direct advantages to taking part, however you will be providing information that may help to improve our understanding of how the COVID-19 pandemic affects undergraduate students' experience of part-time work and the associated psychological outcomes. This information could help shape potential support for student workers.

Data Protection Privacy Notice

The data controller for this project will be University of the West of Scotland (UWS). The UWS Data Protection Office provides oversight of UWS activities involving the processing of personal data, and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. UWS's Data Protection Officer is Emma Cuckow and she can also be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk.

Your personal data will be processed for the purposes outlined in this notice. The legal basis that would be used to process your personal data will be the provision of your consent. You can provide your consent for the use of your personal data in this project by completing the consent form that has been provided to you.

Your personal data will be processed so long as it is required for the research project. If we are able to anonymise the personal data you provide we will undertake this, and will endeavour to minimise the processing of personal data wherever possible. Or we will anonymise the personal data you provide within one week of the study and all data will be anonymised when analysed.

If you are concerned about how your personal data is being processed, please contact UWS in the first instance at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. If you remain unsatisfied, you may wish

to contact the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). Contact details, and details of data subject rights, are available on the ICO website at: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights/>

Detail any intended recipients of personal data if not explained elsewhere, and also advise if any personal data will be transferred outside the EEA, and if so to where.

What will happen to the results of the research study?

The data from the study will be published as part of a PhD thesis and may contribute to academic conference presentations and/or journal publications.

Who has reviewed the study?

ESS Ethics Committee-Approval Number: [REDACTED]

Contact for further information

If you require any further information please contact:

Researcher:

Name Dan Xing

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street,

Paisley,

PA1 2BE

UK

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

In addition you can contact Director of Studies:

Professor Jim McKechnie,

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street,

Paisley,

Renfrewshire, Scotland.

PA1 2BE,

School of Education and Social Sciences,

Division of Psychology,

E-mail: [REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

Thank you for taking part in this study.

School of Education and Social Science

RESEARCH INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Title of Project:

Higher Education students' part-time work and Covid-19: an investigation of the relationship between employment and psychological outcomes

Ethics Approval Number: [REDACTED]

Investigator(s): Dan Xing

Researcher Email: [REDACTED]

Please read the following statements and if you agree, select "Yes, I agree to participate" below.

I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw up the point where I submit my questionnaire online.

I consent to the processing of my personal information (*age, gender, and contact details*) for the purposes explained to me. I understand that such information will be handled in accordance with all applicable data protection legislation.

I understand that my data will be treated confidentially and any publication or presentation resulting from this work will report only data that does not identify me.

I freely agree to participate in this study. *

Yes, I agree to participate.

No, I don't agree.

If you would like a copy of this consent form to keep, please ask the researcher. If you have any complaints or concerns about this research, you can direct these, in writing, to the Chair of the ESS Ethics Committee by email at: [REDACTED] Alternatively, you can contact us by post at: Ethics Committee Chair, School of Education and Social Science, University of West of Scotland, Paisley, PA1 2BE

School of Education and Social Science

Debriefing Form

Higher Education students' part-time work and Covid-19: an investigation of the relationship between employment and psychological outcomes

Thank you for taking part in this research. This study is part of my PhD project being conducted at the University of the West of Scotland. The aim of the research is to understand how undergraduate students' part-time employment might impact on them in terms of stress, confidence in their academic abilities and preferred coping strategies within the context of the Covid-19 pandemic.

The goal of the current project, is firstly to consider potential changes in part-time work due to COVID-19 pandemic. Recent studies have found young people's jobs are more likely to be affected during COVID-19 pandemic (BBC News, 2020e) and this may be associated with mild to severe anxiety (Cao et al., 2020).

In this study, we expect to find changes in student employment resulting from the impact of responses to the COVID-19 pandemic. We also expect to find some potential consequences such as increases in perceived stress and changes to confidence and how to cope with related job changes during COVID-19 pandemic.

If you would like more information about this study once it is completed, please contact the researcher, Dan Xing (B00230186@studentmail.uws.ac.uk), or my supervisor, Professor Jim McKechnie (Jim.McKechnie@uws.ac.uk).

If you are interested in this area of research, you may wish to read the following references:

Cao, W., Fang, Z., Hou, G., Han, M., Xu, X., Dong, J., & Zheng, J. (2020). The psychological impact of the COVID-19 epidemic on college students in China. *Psychiatry research*, 287. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2020.112934>

Galea, S., Merchant, R. M., & Lurie, N. (2020). The mental health consequences of COVID-19 and physical distancing: The need for prevention and early intervention. *JAMA internal medicine*, 180(6), 817-818. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamainternmed.2020.1562>

Ho, C. S., Chee, C. Y., & Ho, R. C. (2020). Mental health strategies to combat the psychological impact of COVID-19 beyond paranoia and panic. *Academy of Medicine*, 49(1), 1-3.

If you have any concerns or feel that you have been affected by the study in any way, please access online support resources:

SilverCloud <https://uws.silvercloudhealth.com/signup/>

Think Positive <https://www.thinkpositive.scot/resources/mental-health-quick-info/>

Students Against Depression <https://www.studentsagainstdepression.org/>.

If you have any concerns about this study and the way it has been conducted, you can contact my Director of Study and/or the Chair of the School of Education and Social Sciences Ethics Committee. The contact details are as follow:

Professor Jim McKechnie (Head of Psychology) Telephone: [REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

Dr Iain McPhee (Chair of the School of Education and Social Sciences Ethics Committee)

Telephone: [REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

Thank you again for taking part in this study. You can click 'Done' to finish the survey.

Appendix 21: Participant Profile of Interviewees (Study 4)

Table A21.1 Participant Profile- Employment

Participant No. (Pseudonym)	Job pre-March 2020	Hours worked per week	Pay rate (£)	Job Apr-Sept 2020	Hours worked per week	Pay rate (£)	Job Oct 2020 to Apr 2021	Hours worked per week	Pay rate (£)	Job Apr 2021 to Aug 2021*	Hours worked per week	Pay rate (£)
Participant 1 (Angus)	Crew Member-Food and catering	16.00	7.25	Crew Member-Food and catering	24.00	7.25	Crew Member	16.00	8.72	Crew Member-Food and catering		8.72
Participant 2 (Brodie)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant 3 (Cara)	Member Representative (Cashier)-Finance	35	9.72	Member Representative (Cashier)-Finance	35	9.72	Waitress-Food Catering	18.00	8.20			
Participant 4 (Daisy)	Floor Team Member-20 Bar work		7.7	Customer Team Member-Shop and sales	32.00	9.00	Customer Assistant-Shop and sales	12.00	6.66			
Participant 5 (Emily)	Store manager-Food and catering	40.00	9.60	Store manager-Food and catering	40.00	9.60	Store manager-Food and catering	40.00	9.60			
Participant 6 (Freya)	Hospitality Assistant (Waitress)-Food and catering	12.00	6.15	Hospitality Assistant (Waitress)-Food and catering	12.00	6.15	Quit job	-	-			
Participant 7 (Grace)	No job	-	-	No job	-	-	Crew Member (Kitchen staff)-Food and catering	32.00	7.25	Crew Member (Kitchen staff)-Food and catering	32.00	7.25

Participant No. (Pseudonym)	Job pre-March 2020	Hours worked per week	Pay rate (£)	Job Apr-Sept 2020	Hours worked per week	Pay rate (£)	Job Oct 2020 to Apr 2021	Hours worked per week	Pay rate (£)	Job Apr 2021 to Aug 2021*	Hours worked per week	Pay rate (£)
Participant 8 (Harper)	Service Advisor-Other (Gov)	16.00	12.60	Service Advisor-Other (Gov)	16.00	12.60	Service Advisor-Other (Gov)	16.00	12.60	Service Advisor-Other (Gov)	16.00	12.60
Participant 9 (Ivy)	No job	-	-	No job	-	-	English tutor-Other	6.00	15.00	English tutor-Other	6.00	15.00
Participant 10 (Jessica)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant 11 (Kayla)	Phlebotomist/Medical Receptionist (Pre-university job)	37.50	9.20	Phlebotomist/Medical Receptionist (Pre-university job)	37.50	9.20	No job	-	-	Shop assistant-Shop and sales Phlebotomist/Medical Receptionist (Temporary job)-Heath and care	-	8.90 9.20
Participant 12 (Leo)	Shift manager-Food and catering	35.00	10.40	Health Care Support Worker-Health and care	30.00	-	Shift Manager-Food and catering	24.00	10.60	Shift Manager-Food and catering Health Care Support Worker-Health and care	29.70	10.40

Notes: Information of job(s) pre Apr 2021 is achieved from survey 2021 within a week after the interview; Job from Apr 2021 to Aug 2021 is achieved from interview.

Appendix 22: Interview Questions (Study 4)

Interview Questions

I would like to hear about your employment and university experience and how Covid-19 has impacted on this. The first lockdown occurred on 23rd March last year and I'd like to know how you have been managing since then and up to the present day.

Theme one - Employment experience during COVID-19

Can you tell me about your job or jobs during this time?

Potential Sub-Qs:

Can you tell me why you work/don't work while at University?

(Alternatives: Why did you lose your job? / Did you try to find a job? / How did you find a new job?)

What was it like working continuously / working off and on / not working during this time?

Were there any changes in your work that were the result of COVID?

(Supplementary: change to work patterns, what you were asked to do, the amount of time that you worked?)

How did/do you feel about those changes? (losing your job/ being furloughed/ being unable to find a job / finding a new job?)

Theme two – Interplay with HE experience during COVID-19

How has your university work been over this time period?

Potential Sub-Qs:

Are work and study two separate things for you? Or do they somehow affect each other?

(Supplementary: Any conflicts between work and study: time / energy/ skill required, any facilitation between work and study: work helps study/ study helps work)

Has combining part-time work and University been more difficult or easier during COVID crisis?

(Supplementary: Any examples?)

Why did it get easier or more difficult?

(Supplementary: Any specific reasons? Any examples?)

Did you find yourself spending less or more time on university work during this time? Why do you think this happened?

Theme three – Impact / outcomes during COVID-19

The following questions are specifically about your experience of combining work and study.

When I say work, it literally refers to work during your Higher Education under COVID-19 background.

Do you think that working during Covid-19 affected your wellbeing?

Potential Sub-Qs:

How did you feel about your work/not working during this time? / How did you feel about working and studying during this time?

(Using emotional touch point sheet. Instructions of emotional touch point: I'd like you to look at this list of words and choose whatever suits your feelings. You can choose as many as you want. Then interviewer would ask about why participants chose the words and try to get them to elaborate on their feelings including asking some supplementary questions: level of feeling: strong / mild; tough /easy? Sources of the feelings? Any examples?)

How do you deal with such feeling(s)? / How do you cope with the feeling(s)?

(Supplementary: approaches of dealing /managing your situation; time management; coping strategies)

How well do you think you have coped during this time?

(Supplementary: satisfied or dissatisfied? Examples of coping with successful/ unsuccessful result?)

Have you had any support during this time to help you manage work and study together?
(Supplementary: what for? Who from? or How helpful was that support?; Alternately (if they say no support: would you have liked some support? who from and what for?)

End question:

Is there anything else you want to share with me regarding your work and study during this time which we haven't cover in this interview?

Appendix 23: Emotional Touchpoints (Study 4)

Calm	Positive	Cheerful	Privileged
Comfortable	Protected	Confident	Proud
Fortunate	Relieved	Happy	Respected
Heard	Safe	Hopeful	Satisfied
Included	Supported	In control	Welcomed
Moved	Optimistic	Over the moon	
A bit silly	Frustrated	Alarmed	Intimidated
Anxious	Let down	Awful	Messed about
Brushed off	Nervous	Cagey	Rushed
Cut off	Scared	Defensive	Shaken
Dejected	Shocked	Disheartened	Sorry
Dismissed	Uncomfortable	Dreadful	Upset
Fed up	Flustered		

Appendix 24: Example of Preliminary Coding (Study 4)

This is an example of preliminary coding step 2 using template analysis (see Section 6.2.5.2 Analysis, Chapter 6). The coding used colour to mark three primary themes based on the criteria of Table 56 in the thesis. Blue coloured words were identified as employment change theme. Red coloured words were identified as psychological impact theme. Yellow coloured words were identified as coping (strategies/process) theme. In brackets (i.e.[]), a number of coding (e.g. C1, C presents coping, 1 presents as the first code in this transcript) and a short summary of the coded words was provided.

To keep the page number the same with the original transcript, it is presented on next page.

1 Transcript of Interview (Harper)

2 Time length: 47 minutes Date of Interview: 09-08-2021

3 Dan Xing

4 Hi.

5 Harper

6 Hi.

7 Harper

8 Hi, sorry I can't get my camera to work.

9 Dan Xing

10 That's OK, that's fine. That I'm really appreciated you can join me today and so we can just talk like this. If you feel
11 OK, is it OK?

12 Harper

13 Yeah, that's fine.

14 Dan Xing

15 That's good, so at the beginning I just want to probably go back to my survey thing- my research so I can remind you a
16 bit about my project. It is about students when they work at the same time in the university. So before this interview
17 I'd like to check couple things with you. The first is I'd like to make sure you have taken your time to read the
18 participant information sheet. And since you've already just send me the full consent signed consent form, I still need
19 to ask you again. Do you still give the full consent to proceed, this recording and interview? Do you?

20 Harper

21 Yeah.

22 Dan Xing

23 I also need to repeat about right of free withdraw and confidentiality so the interview will be last for at most an hour
24 but you are still free to withdraw at any time point during this interview without giving me any reasons. And after
25 today, it's like up to one week afterwards. All the data will be transferred further so you won't be able to withdraw
26 after one week. And all data of today will be used and stored applying the confidentiality in line with GDPR for UWS.
27 So everything here with we say is confidential. So just feel free to say anything regarding our topic.

28 Harper

29 OK.

30 Dan Xing

31 What I like to hear about is your paid employment and your university study as well. It should be actually sitting in
32 this COVID-19 and COVID 19 impact to your paid employment and impact to your university study and to yourself
33 as well. So the time period we talk about is from the first lockdown. So that's last year 23rd of March and until now,
34 so the topic will be about 3 things. One is it about your paid employment, second is about your university study and
35 3rd is about your well-being. So just feel free to say anything you want to share with me OK?

36 Harper

37 OK.

38 Dan Xing

39 Good. So part one is about your paid employment or your job experience during COVID-19. Can you tell me about
40 your job or jobs during this time?

41 Harper

42 Yeah hi so I work in / for [GOV ADMIN]. And so I take like emergency services calls basically, so it's like if you
43 need to like, report anything that would be me to answers the phone basically, but both of my brothers are high risk
44 because they have an immune deficiency, so actually had to be shielded through locked down, but I was quite good
45 because my work gave me full pay the whole time. So although I wasn't working from March through to, I think it was

46 June and I went back. Repeat paid like Maxim, which the whole time and like it was absolutely fine but um. Yeah,
47 they they they obviously because it's emergency services. It's been opened like the whole time like it's never ever
48 closed and think that and like working from home wasn't really an option because of the information like private and
49 confidential. So if somebody was to hack like my Wi-Fi type of thing, obviously it would be like official police
50 documents that would get out and stuff like that. So like working from home wasn't really an option, 'cause otherwise I
51 would have been happy to do that. Actually I was just sitting around the house for months [C1 work was stopped
52 because vulnerable family and work at home is not an option] but it was definitely really good that they they still paid
53 me the full pay, stuff like that. So I really have no struggle. [C2 financial safe because have a job]

54 Dan Xing
55 uh, are you still shielding now or you're at end of your shielding?

56 Harper
57 No, no, I'm back now I'm back at work now.

58 Dan Xing
59 When you come back to work, can I ask?

60 Harper
61 Uh, yeah. So we were shielding again from like Christmas until April [C3 stopped work because of shielding]. I think
62 it's April again, but just when the restrictions changed um we don't have to shielding anymore just from like the
63 government guidelines. But it's pretty much the same as a first time. Just go back when they said that we could. [C4 go
64 back to work when restrictions lifted]

65 Dan Xing
66 So you do work when the pandemic is going you do work for a while, so specifically is from March to beginning of
67 June and from January probably this year beginning and until April. Yeah, no. That time you're shielding so you come
68 back work from May until now. Is that right?

69 Harper
70 Yeah, yeah.

71 Dan Xing
72 Uh, can I ask what you feel when the COVID thing going on and you have to go to work?

73 Harper
74 To be honest, I feel like I'm gonna start like I wasn't really like it [C5 doesn't really like work during covid]but it
75 doesn't really bother me all that much like I think it was more like just not really paying attention to what was going
76 on. [C6 cope- ignore it/ don't pay attention to it] But like as it kind of got worse. [C7 get worse afterwards] And so
77 like by the time that I first went by like last April. And when the first lockdown lifted like there weren't really any kind
78 of safety measures in place, to be honest, like it wasn't really like social distancing wasn't really a thing in the office
79 [C8 concerns about lack of safety protection in work], there was obvious, like hand sanitizer and stuff like just like
80 around the office[C9 hand sanitizer], but like other than that, there wasn't really any restrictions [C10 concerns about
81 lack of safety protection in work], but it was maybe like that the end of summer, so maybe like August times I think.
82 Obviously there was a spike again. They cannot put restrictions in place, but then at that point it's a little bit late [C11
83 negative about belated safety protection in work]. Do you know what I mean, but now, like all the desks and stuff like
84 that are all separated, you're not allowed to sit at a table and the canteen with anybody else. And kinda you wipe your
85 desk down before and after you start um. Yeah, so like there's a lot more restrictions now set that it does seem like a
86 little bit more hygienic, [C12 restrictions / safety protection in work applied] but at the start it was a bit like, you're not
87 really doing a lot, but then I don't think really anybody knew how to handle it, [C13 chaotic in work/lack of clarity of
88 safety restrictions] But yeah, I mean now I'm not really bored like only work and stuff. Yeah, exactly like obviously
89 things are kind of going back to normal and you still need to wear face masks and that moving around the office so
90 they do have things in place [C14 safety protection in work still applied] kinda make it feel about more safe [C15 feel
91 safe after a while].

92 Dan Xing
93 So except the PPE and hygiene changes within your work, are there any changes? In terms of, for example, your
94 working hours or duties of your work, and feelings when you're doing work?

95 Harper
96 Uh, yeah, so like quite a lot of the processes change like see 'cause it's like calls and stuff we used to get call monitor
97 and you don't get that anymore. 'cause obviously can't really sit yeah, like with like your team leader and stuff like
98 that. [C16 process changed without monitor from team leader/ work alone?] And if you need to go on in it's like um
99 separate room in every things like wipe down before you go. I need to set apart um[C17 social distancing]. The hours
100 can, like they've been more likely to like shift swap. Yeah, so like you would need to start earlier and finish earlier just
101 to do with seating because there's less desks now obviously so they can't have so many people in so that that was that
102 changed like sometimes your shift will get slid to different hours[C18 work pattern changed due to limited desk to
103 social distancing], but it's like the same amount of time. It's just a different start and finish in time. So you're still
104 working like 9 hours but it's just instead half 8 you would start a half 7 something like that. [C19 work pattern
105 changed but with same sum of work time]

106 Dan Xing
107 So your total hours of work doesn't change, but the kind of from when to when changed.

108 Harper
109 Yeah, but the hours of worked haven't changed at all, no. [C20 work pattern changed but with same sum of work time]

110

111 Dan Xing
112 How about the nature of your work? You kind of dealing all the phone calls, emergency phone calls for, uh, for [GOV
113 ADMIN]. Few or more?

114 Harper
115 Uh, yeah. I mean before like obviously there were like it's more so like the like more people would obviously be [C21
116 more people phoned in], like the actual things that you were doing would be different, like you cannot incident your
117 reason and stuff like that[C22 the content of work interaction changed]. Especially like during like lock down. There
118 was always a lot of people like falling into report their neighbours. Having people in the houses and stuff like that. So
119 in that sounds like the job did change, but other than that, not really. It's kind of just the same, but it would just be
120 we're a lot busier. I would say that we have been recently just because obviously a lot of people where phone into the
121 report like breaches of codes and stuff like that. [C23 work gets busier]

122 Dan Xing
123 So it is changed to a little bit busier, you say?

124 Harper
125 Yeah, it is definitely busier now than it has been. [C24 work is busier]

126 Dan Xing
127 What you feel when this change like getting busier at work?

128 Harper
129 So to be honest, like it doesn't really bother me, just 'cause like, like I'm not gonna rush myself just because it's busy
130 do you know, I mean they can still just do what I need to do and that is what it is. [C25 control work speed- not rush]
131 But at the end of the day, like if they're wanting to report something like, they will either need to wait [C26 reason
132 why don't rush], but it was like they set up like a inbox so you could like because like it's not urgent, instead of being
133 on hold for like 40 minutes to get through, you could send an email. [C27 work provided alternative channel for
134 customers- workload diversion] So that was quite helpful [C28 positive about alternative channel-helpful], but like to
135 be honest, I wouldn't say like it made me feel more stressed [C29 not stressed thanks to control work speed] knowing
136 that it was busy no. [C30 busy] It just takes as long as it takes to do what you need to do. [C31 reason work takes as
137 long as it takes]

138 Dan Xing
139 I see you mention about this kind of inboxing. Is that a new thing during COVID? or already placed before?

140 Harper
141 Yeah, like there's there's always been like there's like you if you want to report something you can do it through email,
142 but then we set up like a separate COVID inbox for like anyone that was wanting to report every breach of COVID
143 rules. They would send that into that. That was kind of put in place to kinda I think it was to manage the calls[C32
144 email as workload diversion] because the queues were like outrageous. At one point I think people some people are
145 waiting for kinda one hour and stuff like that. [C33 long queue for customers] Just because we're so busy. [C34 busy
146 work]

147 Dan Xing
148 It is interesting you work for you know [GOV ADMIN], I mean how can you at beginning find this job?

149 Harper
150 My mom actually works for them as well, doing like a different job and just when I had decided to go back to Uni, I
151 was working in a bank before, but um just like I needed a part time job and they like the pay and stuff like that. It's
152 really good. Like four part time hours and stuff like that. So my mom working there obviously made me aware of like
153 I could get like I could then apply for it so I didn't obviously know that was really a thing beforehand but it was just it
154 just was more ideal for me going to Uni.

155 Dan Xing
156 So can I ask a little bit about your considerations except for your family connection to this job, before you enter this
157 job again, any other motivations?

158 Harper
159 No, like I don't want anything like pursue a career in the [GOV ADMIN] or anything like that. Like that's not why it
160 was. It was literally just because I was looking for a job and it became available and I got offered it so it was easy to
161 accept it. But like I don't want to, I don't want to be a [GOV ADMIN] officer or anything like that. It literally just was
162 the 'cause I was looking for part time work and it became available.

163 Dan Xing
164 Can I ask do you work for financial reasons or not?

165 Harper
166 For what sorry?

167 Dan Xing
168 Financial reason to earn money for cover your tuition fee or something like that?

169 Harper
170 Yeah yeah. Now, like I pay all my own bills and stuff like that, so I've got the car then obviously my phone bill all that
171 kind of stuff so I can take my own money, and then last year I had been to Uni before for two years, so SASS weren't
172 paying my tuition last year I was paying for it, so I need need to work in order obviously to pay things. [C35 work
173 helps pay things including tuition fee and life expense]

174 Dan Xing
175 How many hours do you work average per week, can I ask?

176 Harper
177 Uh, yeah, so like this during the summer I work full time so it's 37 hours a week. But on term time it drops down at
178 like 16. I think it has to do like for four hours shift a week during term time. [C36 cope-manage time term time less
179 hours summer time work full-time]

180 Dan Xing
181 Yeah. Yeah, I can see you work more hours in summer and less hours in the term time. Then that leads to my curious
182 question about how you deal with the relationship between your work and study?

183 Harper
184 Um Well during term time it's actually easy. 'cause I get a lot of days off. So it's just more about like planning if I've
185 got like the deadline stuff coming up. Then it's just more like kinda to do it on the days that I'm off rather than leaving
186 it to the last minute and then having to rush. Like being at work so we're working till like 9:30 at night so it's not as if
187 like I can come home and sit and do it. I'd be up all night, do you know what I mean and so it is, it's quite good to like
188 manage it because I do have a lot more time off to do it. [C37 cope- manage time plan it]So yeah, it's it's not too bad.
189 That's quite good like that that I was that I have like are really convenient. [C38 positive to flexible work-lots of time
190 off]

191 Dan Xing
192 Do you feel like it work and study actually affect each other? Or these are totally separate things for you?

193 Harper
194 I think for me it's separate, but when I first started um like my course, I was working full time for the first two weeks,
195 because they couldn't get my shifts different yet. Uh, so like I find it really, really difficult to like stay on top of things
196 because I feel like as soon as I was finished Uni had to go into work and then by the time I got home I was pure tired
197 because I've been at work all day and then that like Uni and all that and then I just felt like I was really running out of
198 time. For the first two weeks, so I think if you obviously are expected to do a lot of hours, I can see why that would be
199 like a disturbance [C39 conflict between work and study- fulltime job makes study difficult], but because I do get a lot
200 of time off, I do think for me it is separate.

201 Dan Xing
202 Yeah, interesting to know. So let's just move on to your university study during COVID-19. How has your university
203 study been over this time?

204 Harper
205 Um I think it's been definitely different. See because I know what Uni is like like already 'cause I've been before, it
206 was definitely an adjustment like I think like trying to find the motivation to do things from home was quite difficult
207 in math in courses [PROGRAMME / COURSE], so it's obviously very active course. That's all practical and stuff like
208 that. So I think having to go online and not being able to do any of the practical stuff was quite different. But I think
209 overall like it was alright 'cause I think like see when you obviously have gone on lectures or not all of them are
210 recorded. So if you want me like catch up on it or you missed something. You can always go back 'cause it's all online,
211 whereas before sometimes like I would leave, uh, lecture and be like I don't know what that was about and then it
212 wouldn't even be there to go back in like go through the whole thing again. So I think on that it was quite good like to
213 have it all there, but it definitely wasn't adjustment. I think like going from being on campus and know what that's like
214 till obviously being at home like specially when you're having to get up in the morning like you're not even leaving
215 your room type things. You know what I mean.

216 Dan Xing
217 Yeah, but this thing like you don't really need to leave your house to go to Uni to study. Do you think for you, it's
218 easier or more difficult?

219 Harper
220 I found it easier because um...do you know see sometimes like when you're like having to drive and stuff like that,
221 you get caught up in like other things like you might be running late and then if I may be more than 10 minutes late, I
222 don't really necessarily want to walk in a lecture full of people when I'm late. So then I would end up just not going
223 that kind of way. So I definitely found it easier. Like my attendance is much better. And so, like I don't mind doing it
224 from home, but I think it might be like see like they're talking about doing, like blended learning. I think that would
225 definitely be like I could in between because then that way you're not expected to be on campus all the time. And then
226 like it's costly as well. Like see like petrol wise to get to and from or like even like if you had to use public transport
227 like is it big definitely saved a lot of money in the past year, not having to drive to and from.

228 Dan Xing
229 Yeah, same feeling here.

230 Harper
231 Yeah.

232 Dan Xing
233 So if you consider combining your part time work and university together, do you think is it more difficult or easier
234 during COVID time?

235 Harper
236 I find it's easier during COVID, but I think it was just because like obviously life was put on hold. So like I didn't
237 really have any like socializing. [C40 COVID pause socialisation]So it like it wasn't this hard to juggle everything that
238 was really only Uni and work that I was doing. But yeah, I definitely think like when like lockdown lifted and stuff
239 like that, it was quite like, if I've had like other things on, it would be like my schedule was a wee bit busier, but I
240 definitely found it easier during COVID because there was less like outside things happen. It was just more so a case
241 of doing what you need to do because there's nothing else to do. [C41 paused socialisation make work and study at the
242 same easier]

243 Dan Xing
244 What do you think this, uh, studying during COVID time impact to your academic achievement?

245 Harper
246 To be honest, I think I've done a lot better this year than I have any other time I've been at Uni like most of my results
247 have been really good. Uh, so like I definitely think because you have more time to do it. You find yourself like
248 applying yourself more. So like for me like I even like doing like an essay stuff like that. Just like sitting out more
249 time to do it 'cause I wasn't ever in a rush. I definitely I think I've done better this year than any other time that I've
250 been at Uni.

251 Dan Xing
252 You've just mentioned your time, so this is what I interest as well. So did you find yourself spend less or more time on
253 your university study during COVID time?

254 Harper
255 More. Definitely more.

256 Dan Xing
257 And why?

258 Harper
259 I think it was just because I had time to spare. So instead of being bored, I would be sitting take take notes and make
260 sure I had everything like down like for one of the one of my courses like one of the assessments was like an online
261 testing and they had the math question in it and I'm not really good at math. So like I sat and actually took time to
262 practice like the the sum so that I made sure that when I was doing it I knew what I was doing. See before I would just
263 have worked like wing that like just guess my way through it but because I had the time to spare and actually take time
264 out and do it, it was a lot, a lot better I think.

265 Dan Xing
266 It's good to see you feel a little bit better during COVID time about your studying, and I'm also curious about what
267 you reckon about your paid job function. What kind of role during this time to you?

268 Harper
269 Yeah. What do you mean?

270 Dan Xing
271 Um, I want to know like any pro, any advantages and disadvantages when you think about your work at the same time
272 that when you're studying, especially during COVID time.

273 Harper
274 Oh, yeah, I mean I think for me see because I was shielding and so like I had quite a lot like it wasn't really a struggle
275 for me to juggle work and Uni at any point, so I don't really think much has changed for me. 'cause like for the
276 majority of the past year I've been at home more than I've been at work. Because I've been shielding, so like I don't
277 really think there was anything that's changed for me to be honest, like if anything. I was just I'm more so go in and do

278 the job come home [C42 shielding/ not go in work helps my study at time wise] 'cause I know that that's not the job
279 that I want to be in forever is just for right now.

280 Dan Xing
281 What about your feelings, if you're comparing comparison to pre COVID time?

282 Harper
283 Uh. I'm not really sure to be honest. I don't really feel any different to be like to be honest. I don't, I feel fine about all
284 like I think I will[C43 neutral impact]. I know a lot of people really struggled with it, but for me personally I didn't
285 find it all that bad. [C44 compare with others] Like I didn't mind it too much like obviously like it would have
286 been ideal for everything to just be normal, [C45 don't mind it] but I didn't really struggle with the thought of being at
287 home like I was fine with that[C46 neutral impact psychologically], but I have quite a big family so. It's not as if like I
288 was ever on my own or anything like that, [C47 cope- social support from family]but I would imagine like living on
289 your own stuff like that would be more difficult for me [C48 compare with others], but my feelings are like quite the
290 same[C49 neutral impact psychologically]. To be honest, just because of that like I don't think, there is a really a point
291 during that I was really struggling. [C50 neutral impact psychologically]

292 Dan Xing
293 You just mentioned you have a big family. Do you got any support from your family?

294 Harper
295 Yeah, has there ever needed anything like, I know that like they would be able to help [C51 cope- social support from
296 family]. So, yeah.

297 Dan Xing
298 Uh, I will later show you a list of emotions, negative and positive ones. So it's regarding your well-being so you can
299 pick up any words you think fit in your situation or if there's none, just say none. Alright, go, bear with me 2 seconds.
300 Can you see the blue words?

301 Harper
302 Yeah.

303 Dan Xing
304 These are positive ones. Take your time, thank you.

305 Harper
306 So do you want me just pick out the ones that I felt?

307 Dan Xing
308 Yeah.

309 Harper
310 OK.

311 Dan Xing
312 Like the dominant feeling, which one?

313 Harper
314 Um, I think comfortable, definitely. Ah fortunate. Supported, safe. Happy. Respected. Proud, uh and I suppose
315 privileged as well because obviously do have a very supportive family [C52 cope- social support from family], so
316 yeah, the ones would really stand out.

317 Dan Xing
318 So can we come together talk about this? You have picked quite lots of words here. And which one is like the
319 dominant one? Uh.

320 Harper
321 Probably, privileged because if I didn't have that kind of support system, then it wouldn't have been as easy for me so
322 that one is probably. [C53 cope- social support from family]

323 Dan Xing
324 Yeah, let's just do that in the way to give the score from one to 10. Probably easy to find out which one is dominant.
325 So if 1 is lowest and 10 is the highest level, so what score you gave to comfortable?

326 Harper
327 Oh a 7.

328 Dan Xing
329 Fortunate?

330 Harper
331 9.

332 Dan Xing
333 Supported?

334 Harper
335 About 9 or 10, maybe 10.

336 Dan Xing
337 OK, safe?

338 Harper
339 10

340 Dan Xing
341 Happy?

342 Harper
343 probably 7. So there were days when it wasn't as happy as others.

344 Dan Xing
345 Respected?

346 Harper
347 About an 8.

348 Dan Xing
349 Proud.

350 Harper
351 Eight.

352 Dan Xing
353 Privilege.

354 Harper
355 10.

356 Dan Xing
357 So according to your scores like supported and privileges 10, and fortunate is 9, and unsafe is ten as well. And I like
358 you to talk about why you gave 9 or 10 scores for these words and why, I already said why. Sorry, um. Yeah and just
359 give me some explanation.

360 Harper
361 I think just because like... like I know I've seen like a lot of stuff, especially during COVID of people like losing their
362 jobs and stuff like that. And I didn't experience that. [C54 cope- compare with others] I was very like privileged in that
363 sense, and like fortunate to have my family like they're respecting my decision to go back to Uni and going to part
364 time and stuff like that like [C55 cope- social support from family]. So all of that together make made me feel like safe

365 around it [C56 positive- safe]. So it was just more so, like my circumstances and the people that I have around me that
366 made me feel those things. [C55 assess her own situation logically/ cope- social support from family]

367 Dan Xing
368 That's good to know, so let's ask move to the negative one, the orange ones. Any idea?

369 Harper
370 Um.....I don't really know that I feel any of them.

371 Dan Xing
372 You can, you can speak if we got any dominate feeling, you could speak out your own words if you want.

373 Harper
374 I think I may be frustrated sometimes just because obviously you do. You want things to go back to normal sooner and
375 it would have been. I think we're like one of my modules. I would say specifically like it was supposed to be practical
376 so it was quite hard to understand. Uh. More just because it was all online, whereas I feel like I would have been, I
377 would have benefited from being in person, so I think maybe it frustrated with be the one that would stand out from
378 that list the most just because of that scenario like where, I think I would have understood faster or picked up more if I
379 had been face to face.

380 Dan Xing
381 If you gave one to 10 score, what kind of score you'll give to frustrated?

382 Harper
383 Maybe only about six or seven like it's not that high 'cause it was all like as it was only that one module that I feel that
384 we were.

385 Dan Xing
386 Good, any other ones?

387 Harper
388 No, I don't think so. I see maybe maybe nervous likes you just when things were going back to normal, like obviously
389 like throwing yourself any social scenarios again like maybe that, but like I think that kind of went away quite quickly
390 so.

391 Dan Xing
392 Sorry, can you say again about nervous?

393 Harper
394 Yeah, just like when everything kind of started to reopen and go back to normal like in your back in that kind of social
395 scenario that you haven't been in for a while. Like I maybe a bit nervous about that but it didn't last very long like it
396 with it like after I did it like once or twice I was fine. So it wasn't really like a big thing.

397 Dan Xing
398 Can you give me specific things like why you feel like, think about social scenario, you're nervous? What kind of
399 aspect?

400 Harper
401 It's because it covers used to not not speaking until like anyone outside my house really. So they happen to go back to,
402 like you know, they've been in like a restaurant and like talking to different people and having other people around
403 and they get being loud and stuff like that. 'cause it's also just a bit of a change. But like I say it didn't last very long. It
404 was maybe only the first, like once or twice that I went out that I was like, oh, it's a bit weird to be back out again, but
405 it wasn't like an overwhelming feeling or anything like that was just a little bit.

406 Dan Xing
407 Yeah, if from one to 10 score. What kind of score give to nervous?

408 Harper
409 About a 4.

410 Dan Xing
411 Let us stop sharing this and back to our main screen. OK, it's good. It seems like you've quite positive feeling lots of
412 positive feeling, but still we need to focus on the negative ones. Let us talk about the six to seven level frustrated. And
413 when you talk about frustrated, you talk about the module because your study's mainly practical. Uh, when you feel
414 little frustrating about Uni study, how can you cope with it?

415 Harper
416 I think it was just more like it couldn't be changed like it wasn't an option to have it face to face, so I just had to kind
417 of get on with it so it was more so like I just had to put more time in to going over like the lecture notes and really like
418 forcing myself to set time aside to understand it. Um... But it was only I think that was it was just only really
419 frustrating 'cause it was supposed to be practical. And then like every kinda attain that we're doing like the lectures
420 and stuff like that. Like the lecture I would say like obviously if this was through in person it would be like this and I
421 just find that a bit annoying. 'cause I was like. Well it's not in person. So why are we talking about it everything, but
422 there was a case of like having to just get on with it 'cause it wasn't optional like there wasn't anything that could be
423 done about it. And I wasn't the only one, that wasn't getting that. Do you know what I mean? Like there was
424 everybody in the class wasn't in person so.

425 Dan Xing
426 Yeah. Uh, let us talk about when you feel this kinda frustrated, have you received any support from anybody?

427 Harper
428 Yeah, I think maybe like even like students like the people that were in my classes and stuff just that kind of talking
429 about it with them helped about like I said, it wasn't like anything that felt like majorly angry about, or anything like
430 that. I wasn't. It didn't affect me that much, it was just like if I had something that's what would have frustrated me the
431 most about had like having to do Uni from home.

432 Dan Xing
433 Yeah, so if I want to ask you overall how COVID and during COVID you work and study in the same time, impact to
434 your well-being, what you will say in a couple of sentences?

435 Harper
436 I mean, I don't think it's really massively affected my well-being to be honest with you. I think it's as well, like I think
437 recently like lots of people of like came out and been speaking about like mental health and stuff like that. [C56 cope-
438 compared to others] But to be honest, like this not really something that I've ever experienced, so I'm obviously quite
439 lucky in that sense. That I'd just kind of get up and get on with it. [C57 neutral impact psychologically] And I know
440 that not everyone is like that, but I think like overall like although we're seeing my life did change like I kinda always
441 knew it would go back to normal at some point. [C58 cope- compared to others] So like I don't think that my well-
442 being was massively affected overall. If anything actually feel like it was less stressed. So 'cause I didn't have as much
443 to juggle. [C59 neutral impact psychologically- less stressed]

444 Dan Xing
445 If you can have a say to improve anything about your paid work, what do you want to say?

446 Harper
447 I honestly don't know if there's anything that I would change about it. To be honest. I really, really like the... the...
448 like the scenario with the have like the work life balance and stuff like that that I've got just now is really well and
449 they can have enough time to do everything that I need to do so I wouldn't, I wouldn't really change much to be
450 honest. [C60 neutral impact psychologically- achieve life balance during covid]

451 Dan Xing
452 How about your study and anything you want to change to make it better?

453 Harper
454 I would definitely like to like, do some practical, but obviously it would just be whenever that's allowed. And I know
455 that obviously the Uni will do that whenever they can, so hopefully, maybe next year you can start like kind of hands
456 on learning 'cause I think that's maybe wait that's for me, that's how I learn best like actually doing it, so hopefully that
457 that can happen sooner than later.

458 Dan Xing
459 You just before, previously you've mentioned this job isn't a career for you or the expect for future career. What's your
460 future career you are expecting?

461 Harper
462 Uh-huh, so I would like to like work in a [JOB TYPE] and do like training programs and training sessions and stuff
463 like that for players. So that's like kind of like my goal but it's obviously nothing to do with the [GOV ADMIN].

464 Dan Xing
465 And do you have any idea this work, working in the [GOV ADMIN] can help you? Any help to your future career
466 too?

467 Harper
468 I definitely think it's taught me like how to deal with people like and like communication skills and stuff like
469 that. So like on that side, yeah, but like more like, on the actual job role, it will be completely different I think, but for
470 like a social side of it then it's definitely taught me quite a lot of stuff about like communication and like how to adapt
471 to different working scenarios and stuff like that so. [C61 work improved my social skills]

472 Dan Xing
473 I think I have another question, might forgot it. Yeah, I think is from what you say. About your paid job. Yeah, in
474 [GOV ADMIN] and what kind of the benefits you have from it?

475 Harper
476 I think it's just like every day is different, like it's never the same [C62 work is different everyday in good sense]. Um
477 and it's kind of eye opening to like see what other people are going through and things like that. 'cause it's very like,
478 obviously you get like a quite serious incidents and stuff like that, so definitely shows you like that, kinda appreciate
479 you obviously don't really know what anyone has gone through and things like that, so just kind of like this showing
480 that you can't always judge a bit book by its cover type thing [C63 work widen my horizon to learn diversity of
481 people's life] like teaching like empathy and things like that. It's like, like it's nice to be nice really as well. [C64 work
482 improves my attitude to others— empathy, be nice to others]I've learned about it 'cause I think a lot of the time people
483 do have a lot of other things going on that you will never know about. [C65 work widen my horizon]

484 Dan Xing
485 How about when you receive the phone calls from kind of the citizens. Whatever they say, have anything upset you?

486 Harper
487 Um I try not to let it get to me [C66 control- not let it get to me]because there's, but I was quite a lot of things that you
488 do get, like if you have like people that are suicidal and things like that, you need to kinda talk them down so it can be
489 quite tough. But I think if you let it really affect you then... I don't know like, you, but you probably wouldn't be
490 having a very good time, so I try not let it bother me trying like kind of find the positives in it to be honest. [C67 cope-
491 find positives]

492 Dan Xing
493 And how can you find a positive and not let it get to you?

494 Harper
495 Just like we see like when you're talking to the people and things like that, you just kind of try and like talks about
496 their family or like previous holidays. Things like that. Like say, even like just the smallest things can really turn it
497 around and then like. If you're able to like make this small a bit difference like that's obviously really the positive thing
498 that you have helped someone. [C68 positive in work- help others/ small help makes difference]

499 Dan Xing
500 Has this thing happened to you in your life like some citizens talk with you, in the work and after work, you still think
501 about it or afterwards you can completely forgot the negative stuff you have heard within your work?

502 Harper
503 I think it depends on the scenario that are quite a lot of times where there are things that are quite sad, but once I leave
504 I don't think about again [C69 forget it/don't think about it again], but it depend, it like something's do really stick

505 with you and you do kinda think about it until like the next stage and stuff like [C70 negative psychological impact
506 from work- sth. stick with you], then so you start working again like it's a whole new day of other things so it's quite
507 easy to move on from [C71 use work as a cure- move on], but there will be like every so often there will be something
508 that will be... like that would stuck with me more than something else. [C72 negative psychological impact from
509 work- sth. stuck with you]

510 Dan Xing

511 Can you give me an example, things stick with you maybe longer.

512 Harper

513 I'm like especially in recent times it maybe like hidden like children are like harming themselves and stuff like that.
514 It's quite sad. Or we got like a lot of domestic abuse phone calls and things like that, and I think that could be really
515 really tough sometimes when you actually hear things are happening to other people and you kinda go home and like
516 there's children present and that's what they're growing up with and it just makes you feel quite sad for them that that's
517 the kind of life that they've started off with[C73 negative psychological impact from work- feel sad for domestic
518 violent victims], but I think the positive as well as like see like when someone's phoned in us like about it, then they're
519 doing something about it rather than nothing. [C74 make meaning/ positiveness from work- help others.] But it's
520 definitely not easy. I wouldn't say. I don't think it's not. It's not a job for... for everybody [C75 not a easy job- a job
521 with psychological impact], but I think sometimes you just have to separate it. [C76 cope- separate/quarantine
522 negativeness]

523 Dan Xing

524 And you also say this, most of the cases you can just turn around, you know, make it positive. Can you also give me
525 an example of that successfully turn around scenario?

526 Harper

527 Um... I'm trying to think now.....um...I think to just like reassuring people that like it's going to be alright, 'cause I
528 think see at the start when they like the phone you in there like... like really, really stressed out or very emotional
529 about it, so you just having a conversation with somebody just calm them down and just for them to have someone to
530 listen to, like they'll say at the end of the call, like, I really appreciated that like thank you so much for just sitting and
531 listening to me 'cause sometimes they don't. It's easier to tell a stranger than someone you know. So like that's
532 definitely kinda stand out when sometimes people do, you are on the phone for like 20 minutes or something, but at
533 the end of the day, if it makes a difference and then, it's all you can ask for. [C77 add positiveness - work is
534 appreciated and meaningful]

535 Dan Xing

536 If I liked you to use several words to describe what you are in the paid job of this job, what you will describe yourself
537 as?

538 Harper

539 I think I'm just quite level headed to be honest. [C77 cope- control, level headed]

540 Dan Xing

541 Level headed?! OK, explain it.

542 Harper

543 Like um, you know, like very calm like see if like there's like an emergency, like if someone is on the phone to me
544 having like a panic about it. I can't then be panick back because that's not we're not going to get any further so it's
545 more so like you just need to like stay calm and kinda like try and get to the bottom of what's actually going on so that
546 you can determine what kind of help they need. So like in that sense like more like level headed, like no like hyper
547 emotional in the circumstances. [C78 cope- control does not panic back and no hyper emotions]

548 Dan Xing

549 Yeah, so that's interesting to know. So you say level headed or label headed. I'm not sure whether that is right.

550 Harper

551 Yeah, level headed sorry.

552 Dan Xing
553 Yeah, that's good. So uh, it's interesting to hear about your personal story. Seems you quite coping with your work and
554 study at the same time, so this interviews is about to end and I want to ask you got anything to add on about your work
555 and your university study? Any impact to your well-being.

556 Harper
557 No, I don't think so. I think I said everything.

558 Dan Xing
559 Yeah, if we if we there could be support from University or Government or from your work employer, what kind of
560 thing / support you want?

561 Harper
562 Um, I mean, I don't think I need it, to be honest. Like I think I'm coping quite well [C79 positive impact cope well],
563 but I know that my work do have things in place like um where you can go and like speak to some do like can I like
564 therapy type things so like they do it, I have not looked into it and I know 'cause I haven't ever had to use it before but
565 like just even like things like that, like counselling and stuff like that 'cause some people, obviously do need it that that
566 would be a benefit, but I don't know if they all need got things like that in place, especially these days with like how.
567 Like how much more common like mental health issues and things like that are. I think just 'cause that's so prevalent
568 just now. They would probably benefit from having something like that, but I haven't really looked into it to be honest.
569 If they've already got or not, but I definitely think that would, that would be something that some people would benefit
570 from.

571 Dan Xing
572 That's good, so that's all our, my questions. So I will later on send you a debriefing form. Thank you very much to
573 spare your precious time for me, but I do got another question because we we have a kind of a make appointment last
574 Friday. And you say, is that you I am not sure, I'm not sure when you say you will stay to work more hours that
575 evening. Is that you?

576 Harper
577 Yeah, that was me. Yeah, that's because we were busy[C80 busy] just know that they've they kinda need to people to
578 stay. So I had stay on for like another hour and a half. [C81 extra work hours]

579 Dan Xing
580 Is that like over time?

581 Harper
582 Yeah, it's over time, so I'll get paid for it. [C82 work over time]

583 Dan Xing
584 It's a cover for other colleagues?

585 Harper
586 Yeah, 'cause there's quite a lot of people that are off and short of staff just now. [C83 short of staff] So yeah, just not.
587 And I think as well because been through COVID and stuff. It's not really been taken on any staff because it can't do
588 like the training academies and certain things. [C84 no recruitment and no training]So just like with the mount of calls
589 that we're getting and the mount of the staff that we actually have, it's not. But we just been really busy. [C85 more
590 calls less staff resulted busy]

591 Dan Xing
592 How frequent these kind of overtime happened to you?

593 Harper
594 To be honest, they are asking for people to stay like every day just now, so there's always overtime going. [C86 more
595 overtime opportunities] I don't always take it so it's op, it's optional, like I don't always do it because I think
596 sometimes like I am there like most days anyway, so I wouldn't do it all the time. But it's just sometimes like if I know
597 that they're desperate and I'm not like I don't like have other plans and I will usually take it. [C87 whether take
598 overtime work depends are there other plans- be selective to work shifts]

599 Dan Xing
600 I was glad to hear it's optional. I'm just about to ask, is do you have the right to say no?

601 Harper
602 Yeah.

603 Dan Xing
604 What do you feel about this taking over time? Are you happy with it?

605 Harper
606 Well, to be honest I get benefits major out because I'll get paid for it [C88 overtime work benefits pay], but sometimes
607 I don't think it is worthwhile if they're only looking for like half an hour. And things like that like I'm like, there's no
608 point in me staying for half an hour or start in half an hour early because it's only half an hour, so it's just I would just
609 based on whether it suits me or not. [C89 whether take overtime depends on mount of extra pay- worth it or not, be
610 selective to work shifts]

611 Dan Xing
612 Yeah, so interesting. OK, that's the end of the interview and thank you very much.

613 Harper
614 No problem, thank you.

615 Dan Xing
616 I think you will contribute lots of positive aspects to my thesis, because before I've heard lots of students complain
617 this, complain that so I'm really happy to hear some like a positive voice. Yeah OK, thank you see you bye bye.

618 --End of Transcript--

619 Based on automatic transcript of Microsoft team and was further corrected and transcribed by the researcher. Auto
620 transcription was downloaded and anonymised on the day of interview. Then it was further transcribed and
621 anonymised on 13-08-2021. Later, it was transcribed and checked again on 22nd Sept 2021. Final review for
622 correction was conducted on 9th Nov 2021.

Appendix 25: Initial Template (Study 4)

Initial template (based on four cases Participants 1, 2, 3, 4)

1. Employment changes
 - 1.1 looking for job gets difficult.
 - 1.1.1 COVID impacted the work industry
 - 1.1.2 COVID interrupted, paused or cancelled job opportunities.
 - 1.1.3 Job opportunities gets competitive.
 - 1.2 COVID impacted to existing work
 - 1.2.1 changes work routines
 - 1.2.2 Interrupted work
 - 1.2.2.1 Furlough
 - 1.2.2.2 Unable to work
 - 1.2.2.3 Work location change due to nowhere to stay
 - 1.2.3 More overtime work
 - 1.2.4 Change work pattern
 - 1.2.5 PPE
2. Psychological impact
 - 2.1 Emotionally feel negative about difficult to find job, job interruptions and lose jobs.
 - 2.2 Attitudes changes
 - 2.2.1 to work- from like the job to negative -not safe, horrible, anxious, stressed.
 - 2.3 Job helps mental health
 - 2.3.1 Job helps financial safety and it helps decrease stress
 - 2.4 Job affects time management
 - 2.4.1 Job helps structure time.
 - 2.4.2 Conflict of time between work and study
3. Coping process
 - 3.1 Adopt positive thinking
 - 3.2 Take actions in purpose
 - 3.3 Use passive strategies
 - 3.3.1 Wait
 - 3.3.2 Switch off brain
 - 3.4 Employer support
4. Others
 - 4.1 Job interplays with study
 - 4.1.1 Job difficult affected study
 - 4.1.2 Job helps balance study
 - 4.1.2.1 Switch mindset between both
 - 4.1.2.2 Escape from study
 - 4.2 Job helps career experience

Appendix 26: Updated Template Version 1 (Study 4)

Updated template v1 (based on previous four cases and another four cases Participants 5, 6, 7, 8)
(13 Feb 2024)

1. Employment changes
 - 1.1 COVID impacted the work industry and finding job.
 - 1.1.1 COVID interrupted, paused or cancelled job opportunities.
 - 1.1.2 Job opportunities gets competitive.
 - 1.2 COVID impacted to the job per se
 - 1.2.1 changes work routines, work pattern and work time.
 - 1.2.1.1 Extra routines and duties
 - 1.2.1.2 Change pattern
 - 1.2.1.3 More overtime and shifts
 - 1.2.2 Interrupted work
 - 1.2.2.1 Furlough
 - 1.2.2.2 Unable to work
 - 1.2.2.3 Work location change due to nowhere to stay
 - 1.2.3 Changes of work environment
 - 1.2.3.1 Physical environment-COVID related work requires.
 - 1.2.3.2 Psychological atmosphere within customers gets abusive or more respectful.
 - 1.2.3.3 Psychological atmosphere within co-workers gets competitive, stressed and supportive
2. Psychological impact
 - 2.1 Emotionally feel negative about difficult to find job, job interruptions and lose jobs.
 - 2.2 Attitudes changes
 - 2.2.1 for work- from liked the job to negative -not safe, horrible, anxious, stressed.
 - 2.2.2 for COVID related changes- from negative to neutral/positive
 - 2.2.3 Normal routines changed to risks of safety of work- scared about too many customers and without or less work protection.
 - 2.3 Job helps mental health
 - 2.3.1 Job helps financial safety and it helps decrease stress
 - 2.3.2 Job helps balance between work and study
 - 2.3.3 Job gives chance of social contact
 - 2.3.3.1 at the beginning of COVID, not going to work deprived the chance to any social contact
 - 2.3.3.2 Going back to work gives chance to see people
 - 2.4 Job affects time management
 - 2.4.1 Job helps structure time.
 - 2.4.2 Conflict of time between work and study
 - 2.5 Important or not
 - 2.5.1 Ignored and not heard
 - 2.5.2 Be recognised/ respected
3. Coping process
 - 3.1 Adopt logical thinking
 - 3.3.1 Compare with other people/ companies
 - 3.3.2 Hope
 - 3.2 Take proactive actions in purpose

- 3.2.1 Explain
- 3.2.2 Release emotions in safe social circle
- 3.2.3 Do work normally
- 3.2.4 Do other things / activities as distractions
- 3.3 Use passive strategies
 - 3.3.1 Wait
 - 3.3.2 Switch off brain
 - 3.3.3 Drink
 - 3.3.4 Blame others
 - 3.3.5 Passive violent
 - 3.3.6 Forget it
- 3.4 Support
 - 3.4.1 from employers
 - 3.4.2 from family (parents, partners, grandparents, other relatives)
 - 3.4.3 from friends
 - 3.4.4 from co-workers, managers and supervisors
- 4. Others
 - 4.1 Job interplays with study
 - 4.1.1 Job difficult affected study /Juggling between work and study
 - 4.1.2 Job helps balance study
 - 4.1.3 Work to meet financial needs for HE
 - 4.1.4 Work facilitated study
 - 4.2 Job helps career experience, career shaping and development

Updated template v.2 (based on all cases) (20th Feb 2024)

1. Employment changes happened to both job-seeking process and existing jobs.
 - 1.1 COVID impacted the work industry and finding job.
 - 1.1.1 COVID interrupted, paused or cancelled job opportunities.
 - 1.1.2 Job opportunities gets competitive.
 - 1.2 COVID impacted to existing work.
 - 2.2.1 Work was interrupted / stopped (including furlough and location change).
 - 2.2.2 Routines and work pattern changed.
 - 2.2.3 More hours / shifts and duties/ workload added.
 - 2.2.4 Atmosphere of work environment changed.
 - 2.2.4.1 Physical atmosphere changes were COVID-related work requires (PPE social distancing and limitations) and it brought concerns of unsafe and chaotic.
 - 2.2.4.2 Psychological atmosphere of interactions with customer changed.
 - 2.2.4.2.1 In retail and food sector changed first to unthankful, abusive, and stressful, then finally back to normal.
 - 2.2.4.2.2 In health care and admin sector changed to more respectful.
 - 2.2.4.3 Psychological atmosphere of interactions within co-workers changed to either competitive/ strained or supportive.
2. Psychological impact may result attitude change towards employment via emotional, cognitive and behavioural channels.
 - 2.1 Resulted mental fatigue (stressed, difficult and anxious) or not
 - 2.2 Brought financial safety or not
 - 2.3 Brought respect, meaning and purpose or not (job matters or not)
 - 2.4 Resulted less or more sense of control
3. Use both preventative and reactive coping process.
 - 3.1 Use preventative coping to avoid compelling scenarios and emotions beforehand.
 - 3.2 Use reactive coping to cope daily stress.
 - 3.2.1 Take proactive actions in purpose
 - 3.2.1.1 Explain
 - 3.2.1.2 Release emotions in safe social circle
 - 3.2.1.3 Do work or carry on daily routine normally
 - 3.2.1.4 Time management
 - 3.2.1.5 Control and minimize damage
 - 3.2.1.6 Use distractions- do other things
 - 3.2.2 Thinking logically and use mind power
 - 3.2.2.1 Compare with other people/ companies.
 - 3.2.2.2 Think positively.
 - 3.2.2.3 Set boundary/ stop thinking
 - 3.2.3 Seek social support from family, friends and co-workers
 - 3.2.4 Stay passive (Wait, drink or blame others).
4. Overarching theme: participate in term-time employment is a way of coping with study in HE and mental health
 - 4.1 Job helps financial safety and it helps decrease stress
 - 4.2 Job offers escape and balances between study and work
 - 4.3 Job gives chance of social contact

1. Employment changes
 - 1.1 COVID impacted the work industry and created procedure changes.
 - 1.1.1 Work was interrupted / stopped (including furlough and location change).
 - 1.1.2 COVID-related work requires change work routines <PPE social distancing and limitations>
 - 1.1.3 Work pattern changed.
 - 1.1.4 More hours / shifts and duties/ workload added.
 - 1.2 Situation of job finding is highly fluid or COVID created a cards-shuffle period for job seekers.
<COVID interrupted, paused or cancelled job opportunities as well as created new job opportunities. Job opportunities gets competitive.>
 - 1.3 Psychological atmosphere of work environment changed.
 - 1.3.1 It brought concerns of unsafe and chaotic in work.
 - 1.3.2 Social interactions within co-workers and customers changed.
2. Psychological impact
 - 2.1 Resulted mental fatigue.
 - 2.2 Brought financial safety.
 - 2.3 Brought respect, meaning and purpose (job matters).
 - 2.4 Resulted less or more sense of control.
3. Use both preventative and reactive coping process.
 - 3.1 Preventative coping to avoid compelling scenarios and emotions beforehand.
 - 3.1.1 Have awareness
 - 3.1.2 Set priority
 - 3.1.3 Plan ahead
 - 3.2 Reactive coping to deal with work environment.
 - 3.2.1 Take proactive actions in purpose. <explain, solve problems, Do work or carry on daily routine normally; tolerant >
 - 3.2.2 Time management
 - 3.2.3 Stay passive. <Wait, ironic, drink, regret, or blame others and other passive copings>
 - 3.3 Reactive coping to deal with daily personal stress
 - 3.3.1 Release emotions or stay distracted.
 - 3.3.2 Control behaviour, emotion and mind to minimize damage.
<withdraw from stress environment, set boundary, forget, don't think it>
 - 3.3.3 Thinking logically or positively.
<by comparison with other people/ companies, assessment and justification.>
 - 3.3.4 Seeking social support from family, friends and co-workers.
4. Integrative theme: participating in term-time employment is an overall way of coping with study in HE and mental health
 - 4.1 Job helps financial safety and correspondingly decreases stress.
 - 4.2 Job offers escape and balances with study in HE.
 - 4.3 Job gives chance of social contacts which provided social support partially.
(After reviewing this version, supervisors suggest that theme 4 is not integrative enough based on the data set, so it is suggested to be combined with other three themes)

1. Employment changes
 - 1.1 Disruptions to employment
 - 1.1.1 Furlough and new job opportunities.
 - 1.1.2 Job changes
 - 1.2 Modification to employment
 - 1.2.1 Hours / shifts and work pattern changed.
 - 1.2.2 Work routines and activities changes.
<PPE social distancing and limitations> <Duties/ workload added>
2. Psychological impact
 - 2.1 Changes evoked stress centred mental fatigue and difficulty.
 - 2.2 Changes resulted less sense of control.
 - 2.3 Meaning of work contributed positiveness to self.
3. Use both preventative and reactive coping process.
 - 3.1 Preventative coping to avoid compelling scenarios and emotions beforehand.
<Have awareness; Set priority; Plan ahead>
 - 3.2 Reactive coping to external stressors in work environment.
 - 3.2.1 Take proactive actions in purpose. <explain, solve problems Time management>
 - 3.2.2 Stay passive. <Do work or carry on daily routine normally; Wait, tolerant, ironic, drink, regret, blame others >
 - 3.3 Reactive coping to deal with internal daily stress
 - 3.3.1 Minimize damage by mind work
< thinking logically or positively by comparison, assessment and justification; forget >
 - 3.3.2 Minimize damage by behaviour < stay distracted, withdraw from stress environment, set boundary>
 - 3.3.3 Minimize damage by dealing emotions < seeking social support; release emotions >

(After reviewing of this version, supervisors suggest labels of themes and sub-themes should be abstract rather than detailed.)

1. Employment changes
 - 1.1 Disruptions to employment
 - 1.1.1 Furlough and new job opportunities.
 - 1.1.2 Job changes
 - 1.2 Modification to employment
 - 1.2.1 Hours / shifts and work pattern changed.
 - 1.2.2 Work routines and activities changes.

2. Psychological impact
 - 2.1 Stress and well-being
 - 2.2 Less control
 - 2.3 Meaning

3. Coping process
 - 3.1 Prevention
 - 3.2 Dealing with external stressors.
 - 3.2.1 Be active
 - 3.2.2 Tolerance and passive coping
 - 3.3 Managing personal impact
 - 3.3.1 Rationalising
 - 3.3.2 Behaviour
 - 3.3.3 Dealing emotions

(After reviewing of this version, supervisors suggest 3.2.2 is not coping, 3.3.2 is not distinguishable from 3.2.1)

Appendix 28: Final Coding Based on the Final Template (Study 4)

This is an example of final coding based on the final template of template analysis as step 6 (see Section 6.2.5.2 Analysis, Chapter 6). Based on primarily coding (see Appendix 24), final codes were provided in <> with theme hierarchy number (e.g. 1.1) in red words. Each code number represents a lowest level of sub-themes in Figure 2 final template in the thesis. For example, 1.1 represents the sub-theme 'disruption to employment', 3.1.1 represents the sub-sub-theme 'having awareness'. During this step, if a code was changed to another theme, the colour of words marked in the primarily coding did not change, but in the <>, 'change to' was added before the hierarchy number. For instance, in this transcript, Line 174 <change to 3.2.1 problem solving work as financial facilitation>, means this code was changed from other themes in primarily coding to coping process theme in the final coding.

To keep the page number the same with the original transcript, it is presented on next page.

1 Transcript of Interview (Harper)

2 Time length: 47 minutes Date of Interview: 09-08-2021

3 Dan Xing

4 Hi.

5 Harper

6 Hi.

7 Harper

8 Hi, sorry I can't get my camera to work.

9 Dan Xing

10 That's OK, that's fine. That I'm really appreciated you can join me today and so we can just talk like this. If you feel
11 OK, is it OK?

12 Harper

13 Yeah, that's fine.

14 Dan Xing

15 That's good, so at the beginning I just want to probably go back to my survey thing- my research so I can remind you a
16 bit about my project. It is about students when they work at the same time in the university. So before this interview
17 I'd like to check couple things with you. The first is I'd like to make sure you have taken your time to read the
18 participant information sheet. And since you've already just send me the full consent signed consent form, I still need
19 to ask you again. Do you still give the full consent to proceed, this recording and interview? Do you?

20 Harper

21 Yeah.

22 Dan Xing

23 I also need to repeat about right of free withdraw and confidentiality so the interview will be last for at most an hour
24 but you are still free to withdraw at any time point during this interview without giving me any reasons. And after
25 today, it's like up to one week afterwards. All the data will be transferred further so you won't be able to withdraw
26 after one week. And all data of today will be used and stored applying the confidentiality in line with GDPR for UWS.
27 So everything here with we say is confidential. So just feel free to say anything regarding our topic.

28 Harper

29 OK.

30 Dan Xing

31 What I like to hear about is your paid employment and your university study as well. It should be actually sitting in
32 this COVID-19 and COVID 19 impact to your paid employment and impact to your university study and to yourself
33 as well. So the time period we talk about is from the first lockdown. So that's last year 23rd of March and until now,
34 so the topic will be about 3 things. One is it about your paid employment, second is about your university study and
35 3rd is about your well-being. So just feel free to say anything you want to share with me OK?

36 Harper

37 OK.

38 Dan Xing

39 Good. So part one is about your paid employment or your job experience during COVID-19. Can you tell me about
40 your job or jobs during this time?

41 Harper

42 Yeah hi so I work in / for [GOV ADMIN]. And so I take like emergency services calls basically, so it's like if you
43 need to like, report anything that would be me to answers the phone basically, but both of my brothers are high risk
44 because they have an immune deficiency, so actually had to be shielded through locked down, but I was quite good
45 because my work gave me full pay the whole time. So although I wasn't working from March through to, I think it was

46 June and I went back. Repeat paid like Maxim, which the whole time and like it was absolutely fine but um. Yeah,
47 they they they obviously because it's emergency services. It's been opened like the whole time like it's never ever
48 closed and think that and like working from home wasn't really an option because of the information like private and
49 confidential. So if somebody was to hack like my Wi-Fi type of thing, obviously it would be like official police
50 documents that would get out and stuff like that. So like working from home wasn't really an option, 'cause otherwise I
51 would have been happy to do that. Actually I was just sitting around the house for months [C1 work was stopped
52 because vulnerable family and work at home is not an option]<1.1> but it was definitely really good that they they still
53 paid me the full pay, stuff like that. So I really have no struggle. [C2 financial safe because have a
54 job]<2.1neutral/mild>

55 Dan Xing

56 uh, are you still shielding now or you're at end of your shielding?

57 Harper

58 No, no, I'm back now I'm back at work now.

59 Dan Xing

60 When you come back to work, can I ask?

61 Harper

62 Uh, yeah. So we were shielding again from like Christmas until April[C3 stopped work because of shielding] <1.1>. I
63 think it's April again, but just when the restrictions changed um we don't have to shielding anymore just from like the
64 government guidelines. But it's pretty much the same as a first time. Just go back when they said that we could. [C4 go
65 back to work when restrictions lifted] <1.1>

66 Dan Xing

67 So you do work when the pandemic is going you do work for a while, so specifically is from March to beginning of
68 June and from January probably this year beginning and until April. Yeah, no. That time you're shielding so you come
69 back work from May until now. Is that right?

70 Harper

71 Yeah, yeah.

72 Dan Xing

73 Uh, can I ask what you feel when the COVID thing going on and you have to go to work?

74 Harper

75 To be honest, I feel like I'm gonna start like I wasn't really like it [C5 doesn't really like work during covid] <2.1>but
76 it doesn't really bother me all that much like I think it was more like just not really paying attention to what was going
77 on. [C6 cope- ignore it/ don't pay attention to it] <3.2.2>But like as it kind of got worse. [C7 get worse afterwards]
78 <2.2>And so like by the time that I first went by like last April. And when the first lockdown lifted like there weren't
79 really any kind of safety measures in place, to be honest, like it wasn't really like social distancing wasn't really a thing
80 in the office [C8 concerns about lack of safety protection in work]<2.1stressor>, there was obvious, like hand sanitizer
81 and stuff like just like around the office[C9 hand sanitizer]<1.2>, but like other than that, there wasn't really any
82 restrictions [C10 concerns about lack of safety protection in work] <2.1stressor>, but it was maybe like that the end of
83 summer, so maybe like August times I think. Obviously there was a spike again. They cannot put restrictions in place,
84 but then at that point it's a little bit late [C11 negative about belated safety protection in work] <2.1>. Do you know
85 what I mean, but now, like all the desks and stuff like that are all separated, you're not allowed to sit at a table and the
86 canteen with anybody else. And kinda you wipe your desk down before and after you start um. Yeah, so like there's a
87 lot more restrictions now set that it does seem like a little bit more hygienic, [C12 restrictions / safety protection in
88 work applied] <1.2>but at the start it was a bit like, you're not really doing a lot, but then I don't think really anybody
89 knew how to handle it, [C13 chaotic in work/lack of clarity of safety restrictions] <1.2>But yeah, I mean now I'm not
90 really bored like only work and stuff. Yeah, exactly like obviously things are kind of going back to normal and you
91 still need to wear face masks and that moving around the office so they do have things in place [C14 safety protection
92 in work still applied] <1.2>kinda make it feel about more safe [C15 feel safe after a while]. <2.2>

93 Dan Xing
94 So except the PPE and hygiene changes within your work, are there any changes? In terms of, for example, your
95 working hours or duties of your work, and feelings when you're doing work?

96 Harper
97 Uh, yeah, so like quite a lot of the processes change like see 'cause it's like calls and stuff we used to get call monitor
98 and you don't get that anymore. 'cause obviously can't really sit yeah, like with like your team leader and stuff like
99 that. [C16 process changed without monitor from team leader/ work alone?] <1.2>And if you need to go on in it's like
100 um separate room in every things like wipe down before you go. I need to set apart um[C17 social distancing] <1.2>.
101 The hours can, like they've been more likely to like shift swap. Yeah, so like you would need to start earlier and finish
102 earlier just to do with seating because there's less desks now obviously so they can't have so many people in so that
103 that was that changed like sometimes your shift will get slid to different hours[C18 work pattern changed due to
104 limited desk to social distancing] <1.2>, but it's like the same amount of time. It's just a different start and finish in
105 time. So you're still working like 9 hours but it's just instead half 8 you would start a half 7 something like that. [C19
106 work pattern changed but with same sum of work time] <1.2>

107 Dan Xing
108 So your total hours of work doesn't change, but the kind of from when to when changed.

109 Harper
110 Yeah, but the hours of worked haven't changed at all, no. [C20 work pattern changed but with same sum of work time]
111 <1.2>

112 Dan Xing
113 How about the nature of your work? You kind of dealing all the phone calls, emergency phone calls for, uh, for [GOV
114 ADMIN]. Few or more?

115 Harper
116 Uh, yeah. I mean before like obviously there were like it's more so like the like more people would obviously be [C21
117 more people phoned in] <1.2>, like the actual things that you were doing would be different, like you cannot incident
118 your reason and stuff like that[C22 the content of work interaction changed] <1.2>. Especially like during like lock
119 down. There was always a lot of people like falling into report their neighbours. Having people in the houses and stuff
120 like that. So in that sounds like the job did change, but other than that, not really. It's kind of just the same, but it
121 would just be we're a lot busier. I would say that we have been recently just because obviously a lot of people where
122 phone into the report like breaches of codes and stuff like that. [C23 work gets busier] <1.2>

123 Dan Xing
124 So it is changed to a little bit busier, you say?

125 Harper
126 Yeah, it is definitely busier now than it has been. [C24 work is busier] <1.2>

127 Dan Xing
128 What you feel when this change like getting busier at work?

129 Harper
130 So to be honest, like it doesn't really bother me, just 'cause like, like I'm not gonna rush myself just because it's busy
131 do you know, I mean they can still just do what I need to do and that is what it is. [C25 control work speed- not rush]
132 <3.2.1> But at the end of the day, like if they're wanting to report something like, they will either need to wait [C26
133 reason why don't rush] <3.2.2>, but it was like they set up like a inbox so you could like because like it's not urgent,
134 instead of being on hold for like 40 minutes to get through, you could send an email. [C27 work provided alternative
135 channel for customers- workload diversion] <1.2>So that was quite helpful [C28 positive about alternative channel-
136 helpful], but like to be honest, I wouldn't say like it made me feel more stressed [C29 not stressed thanks to control
137 work speed] <2.1>knowing that it was busy. [C30 busy] <1.2> It just takes as long as it takes to do what you need to
138 do. [C31 reason work takes as long as it takes] <3.2.2>

139 Dan Xing
140 I see you mention about this kind of inboxing. Is that a new thing during COVID? or already placed before?

141 Harper
142 Yeah, like there's there's always been like there's like you if you want to report something you can do it through email,
143 but then we set up like a separate COVID inbox for like anyone that was wanting to report every breach of COVID
144 rules. They would send that into that. That was kind of put in place to kinda I think it was to manage the calls[C32
145 email as workload diversion] <1.2>because the queues were like outrageous. At one point I think people some people
146 are waiting for kinda one hour and stuff like that. [C33 long queue for customers] <1.2>Just because we're so busy.
147 [C34 busy work] <1.2>

148 Dan Xing
149 It is interesting you work for you know [GOV ADMIN], I mean how can you at beginning find this job?

150 Harper
151 My mom actually works for them as well, doing like a different job and just when I had decided to go back to Uni, I
152 was working in a bank before, but um just like I needed a part time job and they like the pay and stuff like that. It's
153 really good. Like four part time hours and stuff like that. So my mom working there obviously made me aware of like
154 I could get like I could then apply for it so I didn't obviously know that was really a thing beforehand but it was just it
155 just was more ideal for me going to Uni.

156 Dan Xing
157 So can I ask a little bit about your considerations except for your family connection to this job, before you enter this
158 job again, any other motivations?

159 Harper
160 No, like I don't want anything like pursue a career in the [GOV ADMIN] or anything like that. Like that's not why it
161 was. It was literally just because I was looking for a job and it became available and I got offered it so it was easy to
162 accept it. But like I don't want to, I don't want to be a [GOV ADMIN] officer or anything like that. It literally just was
163 the 'cause I was looking for part time work and it became available.

164 Dan Xing
165 Can I ask do you work for financial reasons or not?

166 Harper
167 For what sorry?

168 Dan Xing
169 Financial reason to earn money for cover your tuition fee or something like that?

170 Harper
171 Yeah yeah. Now, like I pay all my own bills and stuff like that, so I've got the car then obviously my phone bill all that
172 kind of stuff so I can take my own money, and then last year I had been to Uni before for two years, so SASS weren't
173 paying my tuition last year I was paying for it, so I need need to work in order obviously to pay things. [C35 work
174 helps pay things including tuition fee and life expense] <change to 3.2.1 problem solving work as financial
175 facilitation>

176 Dan Xing
177 How many hours do you work average per week, can I ask?

178 Harper
179 Uh, yeah, so like this during the summer I work full time so it's 37 hours a week. But on term time it drops down at
180 like 16. I think it has to do like for four hours shift a week during term time. [C36 cope-manage time term time less
181 hours summer time work full-time] <3.2.1>

182 Dan Xing
183 Yeah. Yeah, I can see you work more hours in summer and less hours in the term time. Then that leads to my curious
184 question about how you deal with the relationship between your work and study?

185 Harper
186 Um Well during term time it's actually easy. 'cause I get a lot of days off. So it's just more about like planning if I've
187 got like the deadline stuff coming up. Then it's just more like kinda to do it on the days that I'm off rather than leaving
188 it to the last minute and then having to rush. Like being at work so we're working till like 9:30 at night so it's not as if
189 like I can come home and sit and do it. I'd be up all night, do you know what I mean and so it is, it's quite good to like
190 manage it because I do have a lot more time off to do it. [C37 cope- manage time plan it] <3.2.1> So yeah, it's it's not
191 too bad. That's quite good like that that I was that I have like are really convenient. [C38 positive to flexible work-lots
192 of time off] <change to 3.2.2>

193 Dan Xing
194 Do you feel like it work and study actually affect each other? Or these are totally separate things for you?

195 Harper
196 I think for me it's separate, but when I first started um like my course, I was working full time for the first two weeks,
197 because they couldn't get my shifts different yet. Uh, so like I find it really, really difficult to like stay on top of things
198 because I feel like as soon as I was finished Uni had to go into work and then by the time I got home I was pure tired
199 because I've been at work all day and then that like Uni and all that and then I just felt like I was really running out of
200 time. For the first two weeks, so I think if you obviously are expected to do a lot of hours, I can see why that would be
201 like a disturbance [C39 conflict between work and study- fulltime job makes study difficult] <2.1>, but because I do
202 get a lot of time off, I do think for me it is separate.

203 Dan Xing
204 Yeah, interesting to know. So let's just move on to your university study during COVID-19. How has your university
205 study been over this time?

206 Harper
207 Um I think it's been definitely different. See because I know what Uni is like like already 'cause I've been before, it
208 was definitely an adjustment like I think like trying to find the motivation to do things from home was quite difficult
209 in math in courses [PROGRAMME / COURSE], so it's obviously very active course. That's all practical and stuff like
210 that. So I think having to go online and not being able to do any of the practical stuff was quite different. But I think
211 overall like it was alright 'cause I think like see when you obviously have gone on lectures or not all of them are
212 recorded. So if you want me like catch up on it or you missed something. You can always go back 'cause it's all online,
213 whereas before sometimes like I would leave, uh, lecture and be like I don't know what that was about and then it
214 wouldn't even be there to go back in like go through the whole thing again. So I think on that it was quite good like to
215 have it all there, but it definitely wasn't adjustment. I think like going from being on campus and know what that's like
216 till obviously being at home like specially when you're having to get up in the morning like you're not even leaving
217 your room type things. You know what I mean.

218 Dan Xing
219 Yeah, but this thing like you don't really need to leave your house to go to Uni to study. Do you think for you, it's
220 easier or more difficult?

221 Harper
222 I found it easier because um...do you know see sometimes like when you're like having to drive and stuff like that,
223 you get caught up in like other things like you might be running late and then if I may be more than 10 minutes late, I
224 don't really necessarily want to walk in a lecture full of people when I'm late. So then I would end up just not going
225 that kind of way. So I definitely found it easier. Like my attendance is much better. And so, like I don't mind doing it
226 from home, but I think it might be like see like they're talking about doing, like blended learning. I think that would
227 definitely be like I could in between because then that way you're not expected to be on campus all the time. And then
228 like it's costly as well. Like see like petrol wise to get to and from or like even like if you had to use public transport
229 like is it big definitely saved a lot of money in the past year, not having to drive to and from.

230 Dan Xing
231 Yeah, same feeling here.

232 Harper
233 Yeah.

234 Dan Xing
235 So if you consider combining your part time work and university together, do you think is it more difficult or easier
236 during COVID time?

237 Harper
238 I find it's easier during COVID, but I think it was just because like obviously life was put on hold. So like I didn't
239 really have any like socializing. [C40 COVID pause socialisation] <2.1>So it like it wasn't this hard to juggle
240 everything that was really only Uni and work that I was doing. But yeah, I definitely think like when like lockdown
241 lifted and stuff like that, it was quite like, if I've had like other things on, it would be like my schedule was a wee bit
242 busier, but I definitely found it easier during COVID because there was less like outside things happen. It was just
243 more so a case of doing what you need to do because there's nothing else to do. [C41 paused socialisation make work
244 and study at the same easier] <2.1>

245 Dan Xing
246 What do you think this, uh, studying during COVID time impact to your academic achievement?

247 Harper
248 To be honest, I think I've done a lot better this year than I have any other time I've been at Uni like most of my results
249 have been really good. Uh, so like I definitely think because you have more time to do it. You find yourself like
250 applying yourself more. So like for me like I even like doing like an essay stuff like that. Just like sitting out more
251 time to do it 'cause I wasn't ever in a rush. I definitely I think I've done better this year than any other time that I've
252 been at Uni.

253 Dan Xing
254 You've just mentioned your time, so this is what I interest as well. So did you find yourself spend less or more time on
255 your university study during COVID time?

256 Harper
257 More. Definitely more.

258 Dan Xing
259 And why?

260 Harper
261 I think it was just because I had time to spare. So instead of being bored, I would sitting take take notes and make sure
262 I had everything like down like for one of the one of my courses like one of the assessments was like an online testing
263 and they had the math question in it and I'm not really good at math. So like I sat and actually took time to practice
264 like the the sum so that I made sure that when I was doing it I knew what I was doing. See before I would just have
265 worked like wing that like just guess my way through it but because I had the time to spare and actually take time out
266 and do it, it was a lot, a lot better I think.

267 Dan Xing
268 It's good to see you feel a little bit better during COVID time about your studying, and I'm also curious about what
269 you reckon about your paid job function. What kind of role during this time to you?

270 Harper
271 Yeah. What do you mean?

272 Dan Xing
273 Um, I want to know like any pro, any advantages and disadvantages when you think about your work at the same time
274 that when you're studying, especially during COVID time.

275 Harper
276 Oh, yeah, I mean I think for me see because I was shielding and so like I had quite a lot like it wasn't really a struggle
277 for me to juggle work and Uni at any point, so I don't really think much has changed for me. 'cause like for the
278 majority of the past year I've been at home more than I've been at work. Because I've been shielding, so like I don't
279 really think there was anything that's changed for me to be honest, like if anything. I was just I'm more so go in and do

280 the job come home [C42 shielding/ not go in work helps my study at time wise] <2.1> 'cause I know that that's not the
281 job that I want to be in forever is just for right now.

282 Dan Xing
283 What about your feelings, if you're comparing comparison to pre COVID time?

284 Harper
285 Uh. I'm not really sure to be honest. I don't really feel any different to be like to be honest. I don't, I feel fine about all
286 like I think I will[C43 neutral impact] <2.1>. I know a lot of people really struggled with it, but for me personally I
287 didn't find it all that bad. [C44 compare with others] <3.2.2> Like I didn't mind it too too much like obviously like it
288 would have been ideal for everything to just be normal, [C45 don't mind it] <3.2.2> but I didn't really struggle with
289 the thought of being at home like I was fine with that[C46 neutral impact psychologically] <2.1>, but I have quite a
290 big family so. It's not as if like I was ever on my own or anything like that, [C47 cope- social support from family]
291 <3.2.3>but I would imagine like living on your own stuff like that would be more difficult for me [C48 compare with
292 others] <3.2.2>, but my feelings are like quite the same[C49 neutral impact psychologically] <2.1>. To be honest, just
293 because of that like I don't think, there is a really a point during that I was really struggling. [C50 neutral impact
294 psychologically] <2.1>

295 Dan Xing
296 You just mentioned you have a big family. Do you got any support from your family?

297 Harper
298 Yeah, has there ever needed anything like, I know that like they would be able to help [C51 cope- social support from
299 family] <3.2.3>. So, yeah.

300 Dan Xing
301 Uh, I will later show you a list of emotions, negative and positive ones. So it's regarding your well-being so you can
302 pick up any words you think fit in your situation or if there's none, just say none. Alright, go, bear with me 2 seconds.
303 Can you see the blue words?

304 Harper
305 Yeah.

306 Dan Xing
307 These are positive ones. Take your time, thank you.

308 Harper
309 So do you want me just pick out the ones that I felt?

310 Dan Xing
311 Yeah.

312 Harper
313 OK.

314 Dan Xing
315 Like the dominant feeling, which one?

316 Harper
317 Um, I think comfortable, definitely. Ah fortunate. Supported, safe. Happy. Respected. Proud, uh and I suppose
318 privileged as well because obviously do have a very supportive family [C52 cope- social support from family]
319 <3.2.3>, so yeah, the ones would really stand out.

320 Dan Xing
321 So can we come together talk about this? You have picked quite lots of words here. And which one is like the
322 dominant one? Uh.

323 Harper
324 Probably, privileged because if I didn't have that kind of support system, then it wouldn't have been as easy for me so
325 that one is probably. [C53 cope- social support from family] <3.2.3>

326 Dan Xing
327 Yeah, let's just do that in the way to give the score from one to 10. Probably easy to find out which one is dominant.
328 So if 1 is lowest and 10 is the highest level, so what score you gave to comfortable?

329 Harper
330 Oh a 7.

331 Dan Xing
332 Fortunate?

333 Harper
334 9.

335 Dan Xing
336 Supported?

337 Harper
338 About 9 or 10, maybe 10.

339 Dan Xing
340 OK, safe?

341 Harper
342 10

343 Dan Xing
344 Happy?

345 Harper
346 probably 7. So there were days when it wasn't as happy as others.

347 Dan Xing
348 Respected?

349 Harper
350 About an 8.

351 Dan Xing
352 Proud.

353 Harper
354 Eight.

355 Dan Xing
356 Privilege.

357 Harper
358 10.

359 Dan Xing
360 So according to your scores like supported and privileges 10, and fortunate is 9, and unsafe is ten as well. And I like
361 you to talk about why you gave 9 or 10 scores for these words and why, I already said why. Sorry, um. Yeah and just
362 give me some explanation.

363 Harper
364 I think just because like... like I know I've seen like a lot of stuff, especially during COVID of people like losing their
365 jobs and stuff like that. And I didn't experience that. [C54 cope- compare with others] <3.2.2>I was very like

366 privileged in that sense, and like fortunate to have my family like they're respecting my decision to go back to Uni and
367 going to part time and stuff like that like [C55 cope- social support from family] <3.2.3>. So all of that together make
368 made me feel like safe around it [C56 positive- safe] <cope result>. So it was just more so, like my circumstances and
369 the people that I have around me that made me feel those things. [C55 assess her own situation logically/ cope- social
370 support from family] <3.2.2>

371 Dan Xing

372 That's good to know, so let's ask move to the negative one, the orange ones. Any idea?

373 Harper

374 Um.....I don't really know that I feel any of them.

375 Dan Xing

376 You can, you can speak if we got any dominate feeling, you could speak out your own words if you want.

377 Harper

378 I think I may be frustrated sometimes just because obviously you do. You want things to go back to normal sooner and
379 it would have been. I think we're like one of my modules. I would say specifically like it was supposed to be practical
380 so it was quite hard to understand. Uh. More just because it was all online, whereas I feel like I would have been, I
381 would have benefited from being in person, so I think maybe it frustrated with be the one that would stand out from
382 that list the most just because of that scenario like where, I think I would have understood faster or picked up more if I
383 had been face to face.

384 Dan Xing

385 If you gave one to 10 score, what kind of score you'll give to frustrated?

386 Harper

387 Maybe only about six or seven like it's not that high 'cause it was all like as it was only that one module that I feel that
388 we were.

389 Dan Xing

390 Good, any other ones?

391 Harper

392 No, I don't think so. I see maybe maybe nervous likes you just when things were going back to normal, like obviously
393 like throwing yourself any social scenarios again like maybe that, but like I think that kind of went away quite quickly
394 so.

395 Dan Xing

396 Sorry, can you say again about nervous?

397 Harper

398 Yeah, just like when everything kind of started to reopen and go back to normal like in your back in that kind of social
399 scenario that you haven't been in for a while. Like I maybe a bit nervous about that but it didn't last very long like it
400 with it like after I did it like once or twice I was fine. So it wasn't really like a big thing.

401 Dan Xing

402 Can you give me specific things like why you feel like, think about social scenario, you're nervous? What kind of
403 aspect?

404 Harper

405 It's because it covers used to not not speaking until like anyone outside my house really. So they happen to go back to,
406 like you know, they've been in like a restaurant and like talking to different people and having other people around
407 and they get being loud and stuff like that. 'cause it's also just a bit of a change. But like I say it didn't last very long. It
408 was maybe only the first, like once or twice that I went out that I was like, oh, it's a bit weird to be back out again, but
409 it wasn't like an overwhelming feeling or anything like that was just a little bit.

410 Dan Xing

411 Yeah, if from one to 10 score. What kind of score give to nervous?

412 Harper
413 About a 4.

414 Dan Xing
415 Let us stop sharing this and back to our main screen. OK, it's good. It seems like you've quite positive feeling lots of
416 positive feeling, but still we need to focus on the negative ones. Let us talk about the six to seven level frustrated. And
417 when you talk about frustrated, you talk about the module because your study's mainly practical. Uh, when you feel
418 little frustrating about Uni study, how can you cope with it?

419 Harper
420 I think it was just more like it couldn't be changed like it wasn't an option to have it face to face, so I just had to kind
421 of get on with it so it was more so like I just had to put more time in to going over like the lecture notes and really like
422 forcing myself to set time aside to understand it. Um... But it was only I think that was it was just only really
423 frustrating 'cause it was supposed to be practical. And then like every kinda attain that we're doing like the lectures
424 and stuff like that. Like the lecture I would say like obviously if this was through in person it would be like this and I
425 just find that a bit annoying. 'cause I was like. Well it's not in person. So why are we talking about it everything, but
426 there was a case of like having to just get on with it 'cause it wasn't optional like there wasn't anything that could be
427 done about it. And I wasn't the only one, that wasn't getting that. Do you know what I mean? Like there was
428 everybody in the class wasn't in person so.

429 Dan Xing
430 Yeah. Uh, let us talk about when you feel this kinda frustrated, have you received any support from anybody?

431 Harper
432 Yeah, I think maybe like even like students like the people that were in my classes and stuff just that kind of talking
433 about it with them helped about like I said, it wasn't like anything that felt like majorly angry about, or anything like
434 that. I wasn't. It didn't affect me that much, it was just like if I had something that's what would have frustrated me the
435 most about had like having to do Uni from home.

436 Dan Xing
437 Yeah, so if I want to ask you overall how COVID and during COVID you work and study in the same time, impact to
438 your well-being, what you will say in a couple of sentences?

439 Harper
440 I mean, I don't think it's really massively affected my well-being to be honest with you. I think it's as well, like I think
441 recently like lots of people of like came out and been speaking about like mental health and stuff like that. [C56 cope-
442 compared to other] <3.2.2>But to be honest, like this not really something that I've ever experienced, so I'm obviously
443 quite lucky in that sense. That I'd just kind of get up and get on with it. [C57 neutral impact psychologically] <2.1>
444 And I know that not everyone is like that, but I think like overall like although we're seeing my life did change like I
445 kinda always knew it would go back to normal at some point. [C58 cope- compared to others] <3.2.2>So like I don't
446 think that my well-being was massively affected overall. If anything actually feel like it was less stressed. So 'cause I
447 didn't have as much to juggle. [C59 neutral impact psychologically- less stressed] <2.1>

448 Dan Xing
449 If you can have a say to improve anything about your paid work, what do you want to say?

450 Harper
451 I honestly don't know if there's anything that I would change about it. To be honest. I really, really like the... the...
452 like the scenario with the have like the work life balance and stuff like that that I've got just now is really well and
453 they can have enough time to do everything that I need to do so I wouldn't, I wouldn't really change much to be
454 honest. [C60 neutral impact psychologically- achieve life balance during covid] <2.1>

455 Dan Xing
456 How about your study and anything you want to change to make it better?

457 Harper
458 I would definitely like to like, do some practical, but obviously it would just be whenever that's allowed. And I know

459 that obviously the Uni will do that whenever they can, so hopefully, maybe next year you can start like kind of hands
460 on learning 'cause I think that's maybe wait that's for me, that's how I learn best like actually doing it, so hopefully that
461 that can happen sooner than later.

462 Dan Xing
463 You just before, previously you've mentioned this job isn't a career for you or the expect for future career. What's your
464 future career you are expecting?

465 Harper
466 Uh-huh, so I would like to like work in a [JOB TYPE] and do like training programs and training sessions and stuff
467 like that for players. So that's like kind of like my goal but it's obviously nothing to do with the [GOV ADMIN].

468 Dan Xing
469 And do you have any idea this work, working in the [GOV ADMIN] can help you? Any help to your future career
470 too?

471 Harper
472 I definitely think it's taught me like how to deal with people like and like communication skills and stuff like
473 that. So like on that side, yeah, but like more like, on the actual job role, it will be completely different I think, but for
474 like a social side of it then it's definitely taught me quite a lot of stuff about like communication and like how to adapt
475 to different working scenarios and stuff like that so. [C61 work improved my social skills] <2.3>

476 Dan Xing
477 I think I have another question, might forgot it. Yeah, I think is from what you say. About your paid job. Yeah, in
478 [GOV ADMIN] and what kind of the benefits you have from it?

479 Harper
480 I think it's just like every day is different, like it's never the same [C62 work is different everyday in good sense]
481 <1.2>. Um and it's kind of eye opening to like see what other people are going through and things like that. 'cause it's
482 very like, obviously you get like a quite serious incidents and stuff like that, so definitely shows you like that, kinda
483 appreciate you obviously don't really know what anyone has gone through and things like that, so just kind of like this
484 showing that you can't always judge a bit book by its cover type thing [C63 work widen my horizon to learn diversity
485 of people's life] <2.3> like teaching like empathy and things like that. It's like, like it's nice to be nice really as well.
486 [C64 work improves my attitude to others– empathy, be nice to others] <2.3>I've learned about it 'cause I think a lot of
487 the time people do have a lot of other things going on that you will never know about. [C65 work widen my horizon]
488 <2.3>

489 Dan Xing
490 How about when you receive the phone calls from kind of the citizens. Whatever they say, have anything upset you?

491 Harper
492 Um I try not to let it get to me [C66 control- not let it get to me] <3.2.2>because there's, but I was quite a lot of things
493 that you do get, like if you have like people that are suicidal and things like that, you need to kinda talk them down so
494 it can be quite tough. But I think if you let it really affect you then... I don't know like, you, but you probably wouldn't
495 be having a very good time, so I try not let it bother me trying like kind of find the positives in it to be honest. [C67
496 cope- find positives] <3.2.2>

497 Dan Xing
498 And how can you find a positive and not let it get to you?

499 Harper
500 Just like we see like when you're talking to the people and things like that, you just kind of try and like talks about
501 their family or like previous holidays. Things like that. Like say, even like just the smallest things can really turn it
502 around and then like. If you're able to like make this small a bit difference like that's obviously really the positive thing
503 that you have helped someone. [C68 positive in work- help others/ small help makes difference] <2.3>

504 Dan Xing
505 Has this thing happened to you in your life like some citizens talk with you, in the work and after work, you still think
506 about it or afterwards you can completely forgot the negative stuff you have heard within your work?

507 Harper
508 I think it depends on the scenario that are quite a lot of times where there are things that are quite sad, but once I leave
509 I don't think about again [C69 forget it/don't think about it again] <3.2.2>, but it depend, it like something's do really
510 stick with you and you do kinda think about it until like the next stage and stuff like [C70 negative psychological
511 impact from work- sth. stick with you] <2.1>, then so you start working again like it's a whole new day of other things
512 so it's quite easy to move on from [C71 use work as a cure- move on] <3.2.1>, but there will be like every so often
513 there will be something that will be... like that would stuck with me more than something else. [C72 negative
514 psychological impact from work- sth. stuck with you] <2.1>

515 Dan Xing
516 Can you give me an example, things stick with you maybe longer.

517 Harper
518 I'm like especially in recent times it maybe like hidden like children are like harming themselves and stuff like that.
519 It's quite sad. Or we got like a lot of domestic abuse phone calls and things like that, and I think that could be really
520 really tough sometimes when you actually hear things are happening to other people and you kinda go home and like
521 there's children present and that's what they're growing up with and it just makes you feel quite sad for them that that's
522 the kind of life that they've started off with[C73 negative psychological impact from work- feel sad for domestic
523 violent victims] <2.1>, but I think the positive as well as like see like when someone's phoned in us like about it, then
524 they're doing something about it rather than nothing. [C74 make meaning/ positiveness from work- help others.] <2.3>
525 But it's definitely not easy. I wouldn't say. I don't think it's not. It's not a job for... for everybody [C75 not an easy job-
526 a job with psychological impact] <2.1>, but I think sometimes you just have to separate it. [C76 cope-
527 separate/quarantine negativeness] <3.2.2>

528 Dan Xing
529 And you also say this, most of the cases you can just turn around, you know, make it positive. Can you also give me
530 an example of that successfully turn around scenario?

531 Harper
532 Um... I'm trying to think now.....um...I think to just like reassuring people that like it's going to be alright, 'cause I
533 think see at the start when they like the phone you in there like... like really, really stressed out or very emotional
534 about it, so you just having a conversation with somebody just calm them down and just for them to have someone to
535 listen to, like they'll say at the end of the call, like, I really appreciated that like thank you so much for just sitting and
536 listening to me 'cause sometimes they don't. It's easier to tell a stranger than someone you know. So like that's
537 definitely kinda stand out when sometimes people do, you are on the phone for like 20 minutes or something, but at
538 the end of the day, if it makes a difference and then, it's all you can ask for. [C77 add positiveness - work is
539 appreciated and meaningful] <2.3>

540 Dan Xing
541 If I liked you to use several words to describe what you are in the paid job of this job, what you will describe yourself
542 as?

543 Harper
544 I think I'm just quite level headed to be honest. [C77 cope- control, levelheaded] <3.2.2>

545 Dan Xing
546 Level headed?! OK, explain it.

547 Harper
548 Like um, you know, like very calm like see if like there's like an emergency, like if someone is on the phone to me
549 having like a panic about it. I can't then be panick back because that's not we're not going to get any further so it's
550 more so like you just need to like stay calm and kinda like try and get to the bottom of what's actually going on so that

551 you can determine what kind of help they need. So like in that sense like more like level headed, like no like hyper
552 emotional in the circumstances. [C78 cope- control does not panic back and no hyper emotions] <3.2.2/3.2.3>

553 Dan Xing
554 Yeah, so that's interesting to know. So you say level headed or label headed. I'm not sure whether that is right.

555 Harper
556 Yeah, level headed sorry.

557 Dan Xing
558 Yeah, that's good. So uh, it's interesting to hear about your personal story. Seems you quite coping with your work and
559 study at the same time, so this interview is about to end and I want to ask you got anything to add on about your work
560 and your university study? Any impact to your well-being.

561 Harper
562 No, I don't think so. I think I said everything.

563 Dan Xing
564 Yeah, if we if we there could be support from University or Government or from your work employer, what kind of
565 thing / support you want?

566 Harper
567 Um, I mean, I don't think I need it, to be honest. Like I think I'm coping quite well [C79 positive impact cope well]
568 <coping result>, but I know that my work do have things in place like um where you can go and like speak to some do
569 like can I like therapy type things so like they do it, I have not looked into it and I know 'cause I haven't ever had to
570 use it before but like just even like things like that, like counselling and stuff like that 'cause some people, obviously
571 do need it that that would be a benefit, but I don't know if they all need got things like that in place, especially these
572 days with like how. Like how much more common like mental health issues and things like that are. I think just 'cause
573 that's so prevalent just now. They would probably benefit from having something like that, but I haven't really looked
574 into it to be honest. If they've already got or not, but I definitely think that would, that would be something that some
575 people would benefit from.

576 Dan Xing
577 That's good, so that's all our, my questions. So I will later on send you a debriefing form. Thank you very much to
578 spare your precious time for me, but I do got another question because we we have a kind of a make appointment last
579 Friday. And you say, is that you I am not sure, I'm not sure when you say you will stay to work more hours that
580 evening. Is that you?

581 Harper
582 Yeah, that was me. Yeah, that's because we were busy[C80 busy] <1.2> just know that they've they kinda need to
583 people to stay. So I had stay on for like another hour and a half. [C81 extra work hours] <1.2>

584 Dan Xing
585 Is that like over time?

586 Harper
587 Yeah, it's over time, so I'll get paid for it. [C82 work overtime] <1.2>

588 Dan Xing
589 It's a cover for other colleagues?

590 Harper
591 Yeah, 'cause there's quite a lot of people that are off and short of staff just now. [C83 short of staff] <1.2>So yeah, just
592 not. And I think as well because been through COVID and stuff. It's not really been taken on any staff because it can't
593 do like the training academies and certain things. [C84 no recruitment and no training] <1.2>So just like with the
594 mount of calls that we're getting and the mount of the staff that we actually have, it's not. But we just been really busy.
595 [C85 more calls less staff resulted busy] <1.2>

596 Dan Xing
597 How frequent these kind of overtime happened to you?

598 Harper
599 To be honest, they are asking for people to stay like every day just now, so there's always overtime going. [C86 more
600 overtime opportunities] <1.2> I don't always take it so it's op, it's optional, like I don't always do it because I think
601 sometimes like I am there like most days anyway, so I wouldn't do it all the time. But it's just sometimes like if I know
602 that they're desperate and I'm not like I don't like have other plans and I will usually take it. [C87 whether take
603 overtime work depends are there other plans- be selective to work shifts] <3.2.1>

604 Dan Xing
605 I was glad to hear it's optional. I'm just about to ask, is do you have the right to say no?

606 Harper
607 Yeah.

608 Dan Xing
609 What do you feel about this taking over time? Are you happy with it?

610 Harper
611 Well, to be honest I get benefits major out because I'll get paid for it [C88 overtime work benefits pay] <change to
612 3.2.2 financial justification>, but sometimes I don't think it is worthwhile if they're only looking for like half an hour.
613 And things like that like I'm like, there's no point in me staying for half an hour or start in half an hour early because
614 it's only half an hour, so it's just I would just based on whether it suits me or not. [C89 whether take overtime depends
615 on mount of extra pay- worth it or not, be selective to work shifts] <3.2.1 time management >

616 Dan Xing
617 Yeah, so interesting. OK, that's the end of the interview and thank you very much.

618 Harper
619 No problem, thank you.

620 Dan Xing
621 I think you will contribute lots of positive aspects to my thesis, because before I've heard lots of students complain
622 this, complain that so I'm really happy to hear some like a positive voice. Yeah OK, thank you see you bye bye.

623 --End of Transcript--

624 Based on automatic transcript of Microsoft team and was further corrected and transcribed by the researcher. Auto
625 transcription was downloaded and anonymised on the day of interview. Then it was further transcribed and
626 anonymised on 13-08-2021. Later, it was transcribed and checked again on 22nd Sept 2021. Final review for
627 correction was conducted on 9th Nov 2021.

Ethic Approval Letter

19/07/2021

Dear Dan Xing,

Your application [REDACTED]: Higher Education students' part-time work and Covid-19: an investigation of the relationship between employment and psychological outcomes, submission [REDACTED], has been approved by the Education and Social Sciences SEC. You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr Iain McPhee

Page 1 of 1

Participant Information Sheet

Higher Education students' part-time work and Covid-19: an investigation of the relationship between employment and psychological outcomes (Interview)

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

What is the purpose of this study?

The purpose of this study is to investigate the potential changes to students' work experience during the Covid-19 pandemic. The study will also consider how you have coped academically and felt about any changes you have experienced.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen to take part in this study because 1) you have volunteered in the survey stage of the project and have provided a contact email in the online survey; 2) you are a full time undergraduate in UWS.

Do I have to take part?

No, it is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part you will be given this information sheet to view and be asked to indicate your consent to participate. If you decide to take part, you are still free to withdraw without giving a reason at any time during the interview and up to one week after the interview.

What will happen to me if I take part?

You will be asked to spend a maximum of one hour of your time to take part in a semi-structured interview. The interview will be conducted online via Microsoft team and will be digitally recorded. Recording files will be secured and stored in line with university data protection procedure. All files will be deleted after completion of this project. The majority of the questions are about your work status prior to and during Covid-19. We are interested in any changes you may, or may not, have experienced during this time, how you feel about your current situation, your ability to deal with academic tasks and how you have coped during the last few months.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

There are no obvious risks or disadvantages associated with taking part however, there is the possibility that some of the questions of the survey might highlight some issues about how you think and feel about yourself. If this is the case, you will be supplied with contact details for student support where you can talk to someone about any issues that you might have.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

There are no direct advantages to taking part, however you will be providing information that may help to improve our understanding of how the COVID-19 pandemic affects undergraduate students' experience of part-time work and the associated psychological outcomes. This information could help shape potential support for student workers.

Data Protection Privacy Notice

The data controller for this project will be University of the West of Scotland (UWS). The UWS Data Protection Office provides oversight of UWS activities involving the processing of personal data, and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. UWS's Data Protection Officer is Emma Cuckow and she can also be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk.

Your personal data will be processed for the purposes outlined in this notice. The legal basis that would be used to process your personal data will be the provision of your consent. You can provide your consent for the use of your personal data in this project by completing the consent form that has been provided to you.

Your personal data will be processed so long as it is required for the research project. If we are able to anonymise the personal data you provide we will undertake this, and will endeavour to minimise the processing of personal data wherever possible. Or we will anonymise the personal data you provide within one week of the study and all data will be anonymised when analysed.

If you are concerned about how your personal data is being processed, please contact UWS in the first instance at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. If you remain unsatisfied, you may wish to contact the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). Contact details, and details of data subject rights, are available on the ICO website at: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights/>

Detail any intended recipients of personal data if not explained elsewhere, and also advise if any personal data will be transferred outside the EEA, and if so to where.

What will happen to the results of the research study?

The data from the study will be published as part of a PhD thesis and may contribute to academic conference presentations and/or journal publications.

Who has reviewed the study?

ESS Ethics Committee-Approval Number: [REDACTED]

Contact for further information

If you require any further information please contact:

Researcher:

Name Dan Xing

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street,

Paisley,

PA1 2BE

UK

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

In addition you can contact Director of Studies:
Professor Jim McKechnie,
University of the West of Scotland,
High Street,
Paisley,
Renfrewshire, Scotland.
PA1 2BE,
School of Education and Social Sciences,
Division of Psychology,
E- [REDACTED]
[REDACTED]

Thank you for taking part in this study.

School of Education and Social Science

RESEARCH INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Title of Project:

Higher Education students' part-time work and Covid-19: an investigation of the relationship between employment and psychological outcomes (Interview)

Ethics Approval Number: [REDACTED]

Investigator(s): Dan Xing

Researcher Email: [REDACTED]

Please read the following statements and, if you agree, initial the corresponding box to confirm your agreement:

	Initial below:
I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.	
I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time during the interview and up to one week after the interview has been completed.	
I consent to the processing of my personal information (<i>age, gender, and contact details</i>) for the purposes explained to me. I understand that such information will be handled in accordance with all applicable data protection legislation.	
I agree to have my interview digitally recorded.	
I understand that my data will be treated confidentially and any publication or presentation resulting from this work will report only data that does not identify me.	
I freely agree to participate in this study.	

Signatures:

Name of participant (block capitals):

Name of researcher (block capitals):

DAN XING

Date:

Date: (exact date) 2021

Signature:

Signature: [REDACTED]

Debriefing Form

Higher Education students' part-time work and Covid-19: an investigation of the relationship between employment and psychological outcomes

Thank you for taking part in this research. This study is part of my PhD project being conducted at the University of the West of Scotland. The aim of the research is to understand how part-time employment might impact on undergraduate students' in terms of stress, confidence in their academic abilities and preferred coping strategies within the context of the Covid-19 pandemic.

The goal of the current project is to consider potential changes in part-time work due to COVID-19 pandemic. Recent studies have found young people's jobs are more likely to be affected during COVID-19 pandemic (BBC News, 2020e) and this may be associated with mild to severe anxiety (Cao et al., 2020).

In this study, we expect to find changes in student employment resulting from the impact of responses to the COVID-19 pandemic. We also expect to find some potential consequences such as increases in perceived stress and changes to confidence and how to cope with related job changes during COVID-19 pandemic.

If you would like more information about this study once it is completed, please contact the researcher, Dan Xing [REDACTED], or my supervisor, Professor Jim McKechnie [REDACTED]

If you are interested in this area of research, you may wish to read the following references:

Cao, W., Fang, Z., Hou, G., Han, M., Xu, X., Dong, J., & Zheng, J. (2020). The psychological impact of the COVID-19 epidemic on college students in China. *Psychiatry research*, 287. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2020.112934>

Galea, S., Merchant, R. M., & Lurie, N. (2020). The mental health consequences of COVID-19 and physical distancing: The need for prevention and early intervention. *JAMA internal medicine*, 180(6), 817-818. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamainternmed.2020.1562>

Ho, C. S., Chee, C. Y., & Ho, R. C. (2020). Mental health strategies to combat the psychological impact of COVID-19 beyond paranoia and panic. *Academy of Medicine*, 49(1), 1-3.

If you have any concerns or feel that you have been affected by the study in any way, please access online support resources:

SilverCloud <https://uws.silvercloudhealth.com/signup/>

Think Positive <https://www.thinkpositive.scot/resources/mental-health-quick-info/>

Students Against Depression <https://www.studentsagainstdepression.org/>.

If you have any concerns about this study and the way it has been conducted, you can contact my Director of Study and/or the Chair of the School of Education and Social Sciences Ethics Committee. The contact details are as follow:

Professor Jim McKechnie (Head of Division of Psychology and Social Work) [REDACTED]
[REDACTED]

Dr Iain McPhee (Chair of the School of Education and Social Sciences Ethics Committee)

Telephone: [REDACTED]
[REDACTED]

Thank you again for taking part in this study.

Appendix 33: Researcher Journal of Template Analysis (Study 4)

Process of analysis

I am really familiar with the interviews by the time I use the template analysis. I have spent a couple of months to conduct transcriptions by listening to the video repeatedly. I encounter some strong local accent and slangs which challenge me.

During primarily analysis, I am excited to learn students' first-hand stories and reflections. I am satisfied with the settled a priori themes reflected the research questions. The first coding is on the document files of transcripts. According to the priori themes, I strictly marked the relevant statement with different colours. I use duck-egg blue coloured everything relevant to employment changes due to COVID-19 pandemic. During this process, I constantly encounter other information of student employment which is useful but not necessary relevant to the changes such as where they worked, why they worked there, how long they worked. To against distraction, I strictly mark the addressing to ask myself is it changes of employment, or it is simply the nature and extent of employment. I use pure red coloured content relevant to psychological impact, any psychological factors under influence of employment changes. During this process, there are psychological impact by the general pandemic, university study and its changes during this pandemic and personal circumstances which haven't involved employment. To against this distraction, I only mark the psychological impact strictly under influence of employment changes. I use pure yellow to colour statements regarding to coping strategies and process. During this process, I also encounter some addressing about coping to overall pandemic situation and university study. To concentrate on the relevant content, I ask myself is it the reactions to employment changes and its psychological impact. Anything is not mentioned involving employment such as copings to general pandemic and university study are excluded. There are some statements involved two main interested topics. Then salient theme colour is applied but in the code description, I have put two descriptions. One addresses the salient theme, the other describe less salient theme. Sometimes, one sentence contains two themes. Such as first part is about stress and latter part is about coping. These statements were segmented under different colours. I think having a priori themes help the first time of coding a lot especially for me as a new qualitative researcher.

During the process of updating templates and final templates, some codes are switched to other themes or sub-themes. This process I do not re-colour the codes, I only mark it as alternative theme or sub-themes. I do this still on digital word files manually. Maybe using NVivo could help organize codes. I have not use it to avoid my instinct of counting numbers rather than focusing on meanings within the transcripts.

Overall, I sense the raw data of the interviews are rich and in-depth. The amount of information is massive. Reflecting this, I think template analysis is useful to filter away noise within the data and do save me lots of time. I use the priori themes to guide my primarily coding.

There are codes which eventually stay un-themed. Such as some unique experience for one individual or a few individuals. Especially for coping themes, I find students used various different copings. Some codes are included to sub-themes when they are salient across cases. Some copings however are not included into sub-themes due to less salient across cases. They are still meaningful for a few individuals.

I have not used any pre-existing typology of coping strategies (not even the one used in survey studies 2 and 3) to scaffold the sub-themes of coping to avoid early interpretations during process of analysis. To do so, I try to empty my brain about the knowledge of typology of coping and focused on identifying the meaningful sub-themes based on the codes alone. It is not easy for me because after Studies 2 and 3, I am so familiar with subtypes within engagement and disengagement coping strategies. What I do is not to identify the types of coping but to focus on and follow the dynamic and meaningful facts which present the process of how students cope. During the writing process, I allow myself to link what I find to categories of coping strategies but not limiting the one I used in Studies 2 and 3, i.e. the engagement and disengagement coping strategies.

Self-reflection of analysis

The qualitative analysis of the interviews forms a challenge for me. Though I have completed a thematic analysis assignment in master's degree of Psychology, I lack a qualitative instinct and as such had to invest a lot of effort and time to transcribe, familiarize and analysis the qualitative data. To accomplish the qualitative parts in this thesis, I have attended the thematic analysis class for the Master students and recapped the essential techniques. I further practiced qualitative interviews and the analysis when conduct Study 3. Such practices may not be perfect, but it is part of my growth as a mixed method researcher. In a way, I have gained some insight into both quantitative and qualitative views, and I prefer the stance of mixed methods which provides the whole picture rather than a single side generalization based on quantitative data alone.

As a PhD student, I found I could easily identify with the students in this study whereas as a researcher I am supposed to be neutral. Even as I hold a neutral position, I recognized the students' situation because I have had similar experiences. During the analysis of the interview material, I found that I automatically took the side of interviewees, the students. It also needs to recognize that, as a student, I may not fully comprehend the difficulties faced by the University, lecturers and the government especially when reacting to Covid-19. In a way this thesis took the perspective of students rather than the staff and HEI management. This may impact on some of the practical suggestions advocated in the final discussion and may lack consideration of the applicability from the view of the staff, the HEI and the government.

Moreover, since the researcher could be a primary influencer in qualitative research it is worth considering the researcher as a potential variable. As a non-English student of Asian ethnic background, female and in my early forties, English is my second language. Due to this reason, there may be some misunderstanding within the interview due to accent and cultural differences. Some local terms and use of slang terms by the interviewees were understood later after searching or knowing the relevant information after the first or second view of the interview clips and the transcriptions. Thus, within the synchronous process of interview, some meanings described by local language could be neglected. Second, due to my ethnic background, I realize that participants mentioned the international situation of COVID, abuse to minor ethnic background people and sympathy to them. As these comments were deemed to be irrelevant to student employment these conversations were not included in analysis, but we should be aware that the gender and ethical background of the researcher may potentially change what the interviewees expressed and the wording in an unconscious way.

Finally, as the primary researcher I carried out the main analysis and transcription tasks. Thus, for the interview data, the analysis could be affected by order effect which cannot be avoided technically. During the process of coding and thematic analysis, the memory of coding and themes in first four cases, could affect analysis on the following cases. So it is possible, if I do it again by choosing different four cases for initial template, the findings could be slightly different. In addition, the researcher had a cognitive habit of seeing common points or congruence rather than divergence. This may result too many themes identified and the potential over-generalization of the interview data.

Appendix 34: Examples of Case Summaries (Study 4)

Case summary of Angus (Participant 1 Consistent worker)

Interview process: He appeared earlier than scheduled time. The surroundings at his side of camera are a bit messy and with dim light. He is honest about his study and work situation. He is relaxed but looks tired when talking with me. He is anxious, not happy about his university study related things. He is happy and proud when talking about his employment.

Summary of his circumstance:

Angus is a male who worked in fast food sector for two years and study in Year 2 by the time interview took place.

His centre of interest switched from study to employment, because university study turned as a disaster during COVID pandemic time for a few reasons. But in employment, he felt respected. He was about to be promoted and his hourly pay increased with his age. He can't cope with stress from study, and he can only use employment as an escape. He coped with work stress by switching off mind and working automatically, putting chicken nuggets in the box without thinking about it. He also compared with other persons and via this comparison he stayed positive. He had support from managers and the employer. He saw work changes due to COVID in work as being positive. He enjoys pick up more shifts and work overtimes.

With financial safe benefited from his employment, he concerned about his own safe and his family's because he oversaw grocery shopping for the family. He complained a lot about teaching online and unsupportive staff.

Case summary of Brodie (Participant 2 No worker)

Interview process: He appeared earlier than scheduled time. The surrounding at his side of camera is clean and tidy. He is honest about his study and work situation. He is nervous when talking with me.

Summary of his circumstance:

Brodie is a male who had no paid employment but has volunteer work and study in Year 3 by the time interview took place.

He needs to find a job but his interested industry was paused due to COVID. He is frustrated about online teaching. Some university staff are helpful while others are not. He used physical exercises and other activities (read, drive), socializing with friends to cope with stress from study and overall COVID anxiety. He imagined finding a paid job will benefit his balance.

Case summary of Daisy (Participant 4 Intermittent worker)

Interview process: She appeared exactly the time as scheduled time. The surroundings at his side of camera are neat and with bright light. She is joyful and giggles even when talking about very stress things. She has no issues with her study because all the things were learned before COVID time. She gives lots of details about the unpleasant interactions with customers which appeared first very serious and then getting better and eventually customers are back to normal. She talks about his study and employment neutrally.

Summary of his circumstance:

Daisy obviously experiences lots of job changes including changing jobs for four times. She actively searches for job opportunities. She likes her work and has support from work mates and her partner as well as family. She seems balanced between university study and busy jobs. She creates routine to balance his study and work. During lockdown, work benefits a lot to his mental health. She let her emotions out in safe social circles such as best friends, co-workers and family. She seeks supervisors help and uses explanations and passive violence to cope with abuse from panic buying customers. She feels useful and meaningful to talk with customers, using five-minutes talk makes somebody's day. She takes a lot of lovely overtime works.

(End of the Thesis)